

WHAT COMES NEXT? ROMA, GYPSY AND TRAVELLER STUDENTS' AGENCY,
EDUCATIONAL PROGRESSION AND CAREER DECISION-MAKING IN THE U.K.

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Declaration

I certify that this thesis has been written by me and is my own work except where explicitly stated otherwise. I further declare that it has not been submitted for any other degree or professional qualification.

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Abstract

This thesis contributes new and original knowledge to our understanding of Roma, Gypsy and Traveller students' aspirations and their experiences of education and career guidance across England, Wales and Scotland. In doing this, it adopts a grounded theory approach drawing on Hodkinson and Sparkes 'careership' theory to explore the interplay between structure and agency in learners' education and career decision-making, critical race theory, intersectionality and critical pedagogy. This approach enables a nuanced understanding of how complex and intersecting social inequalities within the educational field influence students' horizons for engagement and action. This body of work, informed by 18 months of in-depth qualitative fieldwork, addresses a key gap within the literature as no other study has explored the educational and career aspirations of young Roma, Gypsy and Traveller cross-nationally. Similarly, no other study has examined students' experiences of career education and guidance.

In order to foreground their experiences, eight focus group and four semi-structured interviews were conducted with 36 Roma, Gypsy, Traveller and Showmen young people across the three U.K nations. Learner narratives were supplemented by in-depth semi-structured interviews with four parents and 22 stakeholders including teaching staff, Career Advisers, local council and NGO employees. Findings demonstrate that students were positively disposed to education and that they expressed high aspirations. Analysis of their narratives indicates that students make pragmatically rational decisions that reflect the interaction between the following processes: individual habitus; agency; family habitus; and the institutional habitus or 'school affect'. While familial habitus plays a crucial role in students' decision-making, this research has determined that institutional habitus exerts a greater influence. The intersectional barriers that young people faced were not homogenous and experiences varied by geographical context. Their experiences reflect that they must navigate structural, political and cultural tensions intersecting with 'race', ethnicity, poverty, class gender, and language that exert power over and influence their lives.

The significance and originality of this thesis is that student voices provide a powerful counter-story to challenge master narratives within the public imaginary on what 'people like them do'. The findings also yield great utility in enabling policy makers, researchers, educators and Career Advisers to think holistically about how learners' multiple identities impact on their career decision-making and social mobility. A number of key recommendations are made in order to help inform policy and practice across the U.K regarding Roma, Gypsy and Traveller educational and career aspirations and decision-making processes.

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Abbreviations

BEMIS	Black and Ethnic Minorities Infrastructure in Scotland
DfE	Department for Education
EAL	English as an Additional Language
ERPC	European Roma Policy Commission
ERRC	European Roma Rights Centre
GRTPA	Gypsy Roma Traveller Police Association
ICT	Information and Communications Technology
MECOPP	Minority Ethnic Carers of Older People Project
MyWow	My World of Work
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
OFSTED	Office for Standards in Education
SDS	Skills Development Scotland
STEP	Scottish Traveller Education Programme
TENET	Scottish Traveller Education Network

Chapter One

Introduction

This doctoral research explores Roma, Gypsy and Traveller¹ students' aspirations² and their experiences of education and career guidance across England, Wales and Scotland. In order to elucidate their experiences, eight focus groups and four semi-structured interviews were conducted with 36 Roma, Gypsy, Traveller and Showmen young people across the three U.K. nations. Student narratives were supplemented with in-depth semi-structured interviews with four parents and 22 stakeholders including teachers, teaching staff, Career Advisers, local council and NGO employees, and underpinned by an emancipatory ethos. In doing this, it adopts a grounded theory approach by drawing on Hodgkinson and Sparkes 'careership theory' to explore the interplay between structure and agency in learners' education and career decision-making, critical race theory (Solórzano and Yosso, 2002; Bell 1980), intersectionality (Crenshaw 1991; Yuval-Davis, 2006; Hill Collins and Bilge, 2019) and critical pedagogy (Freire, 1993).

Researchers have yet to explore Roma, Gypsy and Traveller students' aspirations and their experiences of careers education and guidance across various geo-political and policy contexts. While previous research has illuminated the perspectives of stakeholders and student experiences of education (see for e.g. Bhopal, 2004, 2011; D'Arcy, 2017; Derrington and Kendall, 2003; Deuchar and Bhopal, 2013), there is a dearth of literature examining experiences of career education and guidance³ from the perspective of young Roma, Gypsy and Traveller people (Beremenyi, 2020; Greenfields, 2008; Mulcahy, 2017; Wilkin et al., 2009).

This chapter begins with a detailed overview of the research background that informed the aims and questions guiding this thesis. I then turn to the methodological and theoretical orientations adopted. An account is also given of my own positionality, history and multiple social belongings that framed the selection of research methods, interpretation and analysis of the data collected. The chapter closes by providing an outline of the structure of the thesis.

¹ See Appendix A: Terminology (p. 343) for description of Roma, Gypsy and Traveller identities and use within this thesis.

² See Appendix A: Terminology (p. 312 – 313) for a description regarding how aspirations are conceptualised within this thesis.

³ See Appendix A: Terminology (p. 343) for conceptualisation and use of career education and guidance within this thesis.

Research Background, Aims and Questions

It is well documented that young Roma, Gypsy and Traveller young people continue to fare less well than any other minority group at every age and every stage of education (Cemlyn et al., 2009; Wilkin et al., 2009; Equality and Human Rights Commission, 2015). Census data revealed that Roma, Gypsy and Traveller communities experienced significantly low educational attainment outcomes in comparison to any other ethnic or social group. Of the 58,000 Gypsy, Roma and Traveller people living in England and Wales aged 16 or over, 60 percent held no qualifications compared to the national average of 23% (ONS, 2014). While 50% of the 4200⁴ Gypsy and Traveller people living in Scotland had no qualifications compared to 27% of the national average (Scottish Government, 2015a).

A large body of literature has revealed that young Gypsy and Traveller people are less likely to transition from primary to secondary education (Derrington and Kendall, 2004; Reynolds et al., 2003; Derrington, 2005; Bhopal and Myers, 2008; STEP, 2015; Smith, 2017), more likely to be treated unfairly and be excluded from secondary school settings (Bhopal, 2004; Deuchar and Bhopal, 2013, Levinson and Sparkes, 2005) and more likely to drop out of education (Foster and Norton, 2012; Wilkin et al., 2010). These early experiences have been associated with exclusion from further and higher education (Clark, 2004), the labour market in adulthood (Kóczé, 2009) as well as having a lower economic status (Drydakís, 2012) and fewer opportunities overall (Geraghty, Erbstein, and Greenfield, 2010).

Overall, despite interventions and policy to improve attainment, Roma, Gypsy and Traveller students' school experiences continue to be marred by absenteeism, underachievement and significantly high drop-out rates compared to the national average (Harding, 2014). One such intervention that has been largely overlooked, is that of career education and guidance in increasing attendance and improving attainment for young Gypsy, Roma and Traveller people.

It has been posited that career education and guidance has never been more important due to technological advancements and increased digitization dramatically altering the nature of the labour market and the skills needed within the world of work (Taylor, 2017). The Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD, 2020, p. 12), suggests that across the globe students currently aspire to occupations that are problematic as they are '19th- and 20th- century occupations' that are outdated and fail to take into consideration the rapid acceleration

⁴ The population counts across the three home nations are considered an underestimate and do not include Roma (see Chapter two, p. 16).

of automation. This thesis also comes at a time of great political and economic change in the U.K which will directly impact on labour markets, in the wake of recent events such as the U.K leaving the European Union (McCrorry and Thomsen, 2019; Clark, 2020) and public health crises such as the COVID 19 pandemic (Blustein et al., 2020). Collectively these events are likely to deepen existing inequalities particularly amongst already marginalised communities.

Young people, then, have to acquire skills and traverse highly complex pathways within a labour market that is rapidly evolving. Career education and guidance has been proposed as a mechanism to provide young people with the necessary knowledge and skills to meet the needs of the labour market (Moote and Archer, 2018). It is thought to facilitate their understanding of both the educational and career routes available to them whilst simultaneously enhancing their understanding of their own aspirations and competences (Hooley et al., 2011). The role of career education and guidance then is critical to student aspiration formation and subsequent career development (Watson and McMahon, 2005), helping them into jobs with higher pay (Hughes et al., 2016).

Moreover, career guidance has been correlated with a number of positive outcomes such as increased motivation (Moote and Archer, 2018), broader aspirations, greater awareness of opportunities, progression (Hooley et al. 2014) and better academic achievement (Hughes et al., 2016). A number of commentators have also highlighted that career guidance serves to promote social equity (Archer et al. 2014a) and upward social mobility (Hughes, 2017; Hutchinson, 2012).

To date, however, there is a dearth of research beyond a sentence or two within the scholarly literature pertaining to Roma, Gypsy and Traveller students experiences of accessing sources of career education and guidance in the U.K and the implications for policy. Mulcahy and colleagues (2017) found that the sample of young Gypsy, Roma and Traveller people in their research had limited experiences talking to parents, teachers and other adults about university, especially if they had dropped out prior to year 11. Through discussions with young people in focus groups, Mulcahy et al. (2017) suggested that students were able to address their misconceptions by asking questions and receiving information about higher education thereby changing their perceptions.

Although there was no direct mention of Career Advisers in research conducted by Wilkin and colleagues (2010) their study briefly described one school that appeared to reduce drop-out rates by using 'counsellors' to raise Gypsy, Roma and Traveller students' awareness of the

labour market (p. 67). Finally, while research by Greenfields (2008) did not explicitly explore experiences of career guidance, it did examine Gypsy and Travellers perceptions of Health and Social Care careers in the U.K. Findings indicated that participants were more able to identify careers⁵ that family members were employed in. Participant's also demonstrated limited knowledge regarding training bursaries to support eligible health and social care staff.

Further research is needed in order to understand how students from these backgrounds develop their aspirations, how they experience career education and guidance provision, and how they access services, with consideration of the information available to their parents and the impact that services have on breaking down internalised stereotypes. It is against this background that my research aims and questions were formulated. In order to address the gaps in knowledge, this thesis aims to explore Roma, Gypsy and Traveller students' aspirations and experiences of career education and guidance within educational settings and understand the challenges and barriers that they face. This involves analysing and 'representing' (Spivak, 1988) student narratives across England, Scotland and Wales in response to the following research questions:

1. What are young Roma, Gypsy and Traveller people's aspirations and what support do they feel they need in order to realise their aspirations?
2. Do young Roma, Gypsy and Traveller people have equitable access to career education and guidance provision. If they do, what have their experiences been? If they have not had access, do they think believe that they would benefit from career guidance, and how do they think local services could best meet their needs?

Methodology, Theoretical Orientations and Methods

Working within the emancipatory paradigm, I adopted an ethnographic approach to methodology, employing a mix of qualitative methods in order to explore and understand young people's experiences. The recruitment of research participants across the three home nations was facilitated through the support of organisations such as Article 12 in Scotland (an NGO supporting Travellers), the Gypsy, Roma, and Traveller Police Association (GRTPA), and former colleagues known to the researcher who worked within local authority education departments. I also compiled 'recruitment videos' wherein I offered insights into my background, the research project and details on what I would be seeking from potential research participants. I shared these videos with various groups and across multiple social media

⁵ See Appendix A: Terminology (p. 313) for a description regarding the conceptualisation and use of the term 'career' within this thesis.

platforms, so that they could be passed along the ‘grapevine’ in order that community members could get a sense for who I am.

A mix of qualitative methods such as focus groups, semi-structured interviews and participant observation with 36 young people and 26 adults were employed to collect data. A thematic analysis was applied to the interview transcripts and field notes. The analytic process involved drawing on Braun and Clarke’s (2006), six-phase guide to thematic analysis, to identify patterns (themes), interpret multiple aspects of these patterns, and provide a rich and detailed account of the qualitative data. The coded extract examples were then further analysed in relation to the research questions, literature and theoretical orientations.

I draw on a range of theoretical orientations in a grounded practice approach to theory for the foregrounding of students’ experiences. The work of Hodkinson and Sparkes (1997) encourages the examination of the interface between structure and agency in learners’ education and career decision-making; critical race theory (Solórzano and Yosso, 2002) draws attention to the high aspirations held by Roma, Gypsy and Traveller students and their parents in order to challenge dominant master narratives that suggest that these communities do not want a career or education; and theories of intersectionality (Crenshaw, 1991; Yuval-Davis, 2006; Hills Collins and Bilge, 2019) that enable a more nuanced understanding of how complex and intersecting social inequalities within the educational field influence students’ horizons for action. These theories are thread throughout the analysis and findings chapters and are useful in elucidating how young people’s agency is constrained by structural forces within their field whilst exposing and challenging the discrimination within students’ experiences.

The focus groups and interviews were recorded and personally transcribed verbatim and young people’s voices are provided ample space throughout the analysis chapters for authenticity. With only 36 young people and four parents participating in the current research, the sample is small thereby limiting generalisability of findings (Tsang, 2014; Vasileiou et al., 2018) and I recognise that there may be many other experiences of Roma, Gypsy and Traveller community members may not be captured and represented here.

Positionality

It is important that I set out my positionality before delving further in to the research, as my history and multiple social belongings have framed the selection of research methods,

interpretation and analysis of the data collected. I am a Queer, white, migrant, gadjé, ally-identified researcher who has worked on Roma, Gypsy and Traveller related issues with Scottish Traveller community members for just over six years. While I am a migrant, I hold a British passport which confers on me privileges that other migrants do not have access to (Clark, 2020). Having grown up in apartheid South Africa, I was aware of the ‘us’ and ‘them’ binary from an early age, observing how people were discriminated against and dehumanised based on their identity, which has shaped my social and political beliefs. My history, along with my multiple identities, has allowed me to occupy various spaces during the data gathering process, oscillating between being an insider and outsider and at times transcending the dichotomy.

Contribution to knowledge

Given the lacuna of critical scholarly literature on Roma, Romani Gypsy, Scottish Traveller, Irish Traveller and Showmen students’ aspirations and experiences of career education and guidance cross-nationally, this doctoral research fills a key gap in knowledge about this area. The diverse and heterogeneous nature of the sample has also broadened our current understanding of different community group’s needs offering unique insights in to the challenges and barriers that they face based on their multiple social belongings.

Findings revealed that young people were positively disposed to education and that they expressed high aspirations (Levinson, 2015). Both parent and student narratives suggest that parents were supportive of their children’s education and career aspirations. This thesis challenges deficit assumptions that purport that Roma, Gypsy and Traveller communities are present-oriented (Lawrie, 1983; McCann, 1987; Feder et al., 1989; Jackson et al., 2016), living for the moment and not for the ‘industrial clock’ (Forster, 2018, p. 170). Young people in the current research, through the planning of their next steps in an educational context, demonstrated a future-oriented position centred on gaining employment.

This thesis also challenges deficit assumptions about Roma, Gypsy and Traveller men (see Hamilton, 2016, 2017; Poole and Adamson, 2008; Sime et al., 2018; Marcus, 2016; Levinson, 2015; D’Arcy, 2017). Similar to findings with Gypsy Travellers by Bhopal (2004) the Roma and Romani Gypsy fathers who participated in the current research were not only involved, but

were invested in their children's education and worked to support their educational and career aspirations. To this end, the use of critical race theory as a theoretical lens yielded great utility in illuminating powerful counter-stories (Delgado, 1995; Ladson-Billings and Tate, 1995) to challenge the dominant discourse that suggests that Roma, Gypsy and Traveller people do not want an education or a career (see for e.g. Bhopal, 2004 Lloyd and McCluskey, 2008; Marcus, 2016; McGarry, 2014; Peček and Munda, 2015).

Further findings suggest that students make 'pragmatically rational decisions' (Hodkinson and Sparkes, 1997, p. 33) that reflect the interaction between the following processes: individual habitus; agency; family habitus; and the institutional habitus or 'school affect' (Lanskey, 2015; Smyth and Banks, 2012). These findings concur with Smyth and Banks (2012) who explored the impact of institutional habitus on decision-making amongst students from middle and working class backgrounds across two secondary schools in Ireland. While familial habitus plays a crucial role in students' decision-making, this research has determined that institutional habitus exerts a greater influence, which either broadened or constrained learners' horizons for action (Hodkinson and Sparkes, 1997). Teachers, teaching staff and Career Advisers played a significant role in guiding and shaping students' perceptions (Foskett et al., 2008) and nurturing their aspirations (Hart, 2012).

These findings were, however, geo-politically dependant and were not replicated in the Scottish context, where the majority of staff were found to impose a narrow range of options that they deemed as 'possible' for these students. There was an over-reliance on majoritarian master narratives by a number of Scottish teaching staff and Career Advisers wherein community members' mistrust of authority, their culture, and their 'inherently mobile' lifestyle were cited as reasons to justify their exclusion.

The barriers that young people faced were not homogenous and their experiences reflect that they are caught between institutional, structural, political and cultural tensions intersecting with equality issues such as 'race', ethnicity, poverty, class gender, and language that exert power over and influence their lives. The use of an intersectional framework is a strength in the current research, allowing researchers, educators and Career Advisers to think about how learners' multiple identities impact on their career decision-making and social mobility. Overall holistic guidance and pedagogical experiences (Freire, 1993) from a range of trusted others can make a tangible difference in young people's lives, encouraging their continued engagement in education and nurturing their future aspirations.

Structure of the Thesis

This thesis is divided into eight chapters and the following outline details the structure to follow. Due to the inter-disciplinary and cross-national nature of the current thesis, a double literature review was needed in order to situate the research in relation to existing knowledge across Romani studies and the Career Education and Guidance literature and respective policy contexts.

In *Chapter two*, I outline historical information and offer nuanced considerations of Europe's largest Ethnic minority group, the conflation of terminology and the need for disaggregated data in order to understand respective community groups' needs that will allow for effective resource allocation. The chapter then considers the education of young Roma, Gypsy and Traveller people and the policy contexts across England, Scotland and Wales, before turning to explore the educational experiences of these heterogeneous communities from primary school to further and higher education. I then outline the paucity of literature detailing what is known about the educational and career aspirations of these young people before briefly touching on Roma, Gypsy and Traveller employment patterns.

In *Chapter three*, I present existing knowledge in relation to the need for career education and guidance in equipping young people with the knowledge and the skills required to traverse a rapidly evolving and precarious labour market. I then highlight the positive impact that access to such services have on young people and the potential for career guidance to support students to challenge stereotypes in relation to 'what people like them do' (Holman, 2014). The chapter then considers the various sources of career education and guidance available to young people before turning to explore career education and guidance policy developments over the years across England, Wales and Scotland. As becomes clear, the literature examining Roma, Gypsy and Traveller student experiences of career education and guidance is near non-existent thereby illuminating the need for further research in order to address this gap in knowledge.

Chapter four then details the methodological decisions I made throughout the process of conducting this empirical project, beginning with epistemological considerations and the emancipatory paradigm underpinning the current research before detailing the theoretical orientations drawn on in a grounded approach and the adoption of thematic analysis applied to the resultant data, with a justification for the use of careership theory, critical race theory and intersectionality. The methods and tools employed within the current thesis to gather and

analyse data are also explained and defended. This chapter also offers insights into the school environments in England, Scotland and Wales, whilst also detailing the unexpected fieldwork occurrences that took place, such as increasing the geographic scope of the research to include Wales, and the adoption of digital ethnography due to young people contacting me following focus groups. I then clarify my own position and methodological reflections.

In *Chapter five*, findings emerge that address the first research question: What are young Roma, Gypsy and Traveller people's aspirations and what support do they feel they need in order to realise their aspirations? Students educational and career aspirations are 'represented' (Spivak, 1988) along with the steps that they intend so that they may realise their ambitions. Overall, students make pragmatically rational decisions for their futures based on what they believe is possible. The aspirations that parents hold for their children are then explored, illuminating their calls for further support so that their children can have better lives than they themselves have had. What emerges from narratives within this chapter are powerful counter-stories to challenge master narratives within the public imaginary on what 'people like them do'.

Chapter six addresses the second research question: Do young Roma, Gypsy and Traveller people have equitable access to career education and guidance provision. If they do, what have their experiences been? If they have not had access, do they believe that they would benefit from career guidance and how do they think local services could best meet their needs? Here, I consider sources of advice within the family field and within educational settings from the perspective of students before turning to the school field from adult perspectives. What emerges is that learners approach knowledge based experts for both educational and career advice based on trust and familiarity. Education and career guidance provision in schools across England, Scotland and Wales is then considered from the perspective of adult stakeholders who detail their experiences of working with young Roma, Gypsy and Traveller children.

Chapter seven then explores the intersectional barriers that young people face within institutional settings that carry the potential to constrain their educational and career trajectories. What emerges is that their experiences reflect that they are caught between institutional, structural, political and cultural tensions intersecting with 'race', ethnicity, poverty, class gender, and language that exert power over and influence their lives. Moreover, this chapter considers how current policy fails to consider learners' multiple social belongings,

ultimately serving as an exclusionary mechanism to equitable access to education and career guidance.

In *Chapter eight*, I discuss the salient outcomes and conclusions drawn from the research findings, illuminating the significance of this research in its original contribution to knowledge. Recommendations are thread throughout the conclusion and in relation to the findings. In closing, this thesis presents the limitations of the current research and recommendations for future research.

Chapter Two

Literature Review

This literature review provides a critical analysis of the existing literature within the field that has informed my study. The purpose of this chapter is to situate this study within the broader corpus of knowledge. The first part provides a critical review of who Roma, Gypsy and Traveller communities are, issues surrounding the conflation of terminology and the erasure of identities in counting populations. There follows a short overview of current data relating to the education and qualification levels held by these communities in the U.K. The second part of this chapter contains a critical review of the respective educational policy developments across England, Scotland and Wales in relation to Roma, Gypsy and Traveller students. The third part details the literature on students' educational experiences within institutional settings before touching on the lacuna of knowledge relating to learners' aspirations.

Who are Roma, Gypsy and Traveller People?

Roma, Gypsy and Traveller communities are Europe's largest ethnic minority group, with an estimated 10-12 million (Council of Europe, 2019) individuals living across the continent, the majority of whom continue to experience severe poverty and deprivation (Poole and Adamson, 2013). According to the Council of Europe (2012, p. 4), the term 'Roma' captures 'Roma, Sinti, Kale and related group [identities] in Europe including Travellers and Eastern groups (Dom and Lom)' as well as 'persons who identify themselves as Gypsies'. Conversely, within the U.K context, the term Roma refers to community groups who arrived from Central and Eastern Europe over the last 40 years.

In tracing the lineage of Europe's present day Roma, Acton (1974, p. 1) contends that they left India over a thousand years ago, travelling 'across trade routes'. Although the out-of-India migratory theory has been contested (see for e.g. Okely, 1983; Marcus, 2015), more recent genome-wide data lends support to Acton's (*ibid*) claims. In tracing the genetic lineage of Roma people Bánfai and colleagues (2018) demonstrated Roma migration from India and through the Caucasus region before their arrival in Europe.

Romanichals are thought to have left Europe and arrived in England and Wales in the 16th century (Council of Europe, 2012). Romanichals who arrived in England are known as Romani Gypsies, while those who settled in Wales are known as Welsh Kale. The presence of Roma

across the U.K is not a new phenomenon. The collapse of the Soviet Union in 1989, saw an increasing number of Roma communities fleeing persecution in Central and Eastern Europe (Brown et al., 2013) and seeking asylum as political refugees in the U.K in the 1990's (Clark, 2014), but a large proportion of asylum applications generally failed (Ryder and Cemlyn, 2016). The expansion of the European Union to include A8 (Poland, Hungary, Slovenia, Estonia, Lithuania, Latvia, the Czech Republic and Slovakia) and A2 countries (Romania and Bulgaria) saw various national and ethnic subgroups freely migrate to the U.K (Pietarinen, 2011; Ryder and Cemlyn, 2016).

Travellers, on the other hand, are thought to be indigenous communities to their respective nations and do not share a common ancestry with Roma and Romani Gypsy communities of Indian descent (Council of Europe, 2012). Travellers include Irish Travellers and Scottish Gypsy Travellers and are ethnically distinct from Roma communities (Council of Europe, 2012). In tracing the lineage of Travellers, Williamson (1994) contends that Traveller communities are hunter – gatherers from the Mesolithic period. Clark (2001, p. 112), however argues, that their lineage can be traced to the 15th century with the ‘intermarriage between local nomadic craftsmen and Roma from France and Spain’. Due to the contested and fragmented nature regarding the origins and histories of Roma and Travelling communities, Belton (2005) asserts that there is no consistent lineage.

It is important to note that English Romani Gypsies were defined as an ethnic minority group (CRE V Dutton, 1989) by the Race Relations Act 1976⁶ and Irish Travellers were recognised as a minority ethnic group in 2000 in England (O’Leary v. Allied Domecq, 2000; Race Relations (Amendment) Act, 2000) with community members being protected from racial discrimination for the first time in legislation. Scottish Travellers were only recognised as having a separate ethnic status in Scotland in 2008 (K. MacLennan vs GTEIP, 2008) thereby being granted protection under the Race Relations Act (The Scottish Government, 2014). While, Irish Travellers were only recognised and granted protection under legislation in Ireland much later, in 2017 (Houses of the Oireachtas, 2017).

Other Traveller identities that are not protected under current legislation are Occupational Travellers (Showpeople and Bargees) and New Travellers (Bhopal and Myers, 2009; Mulcahy, et al., 2017). Occupational Travellers are commercial nomads who have a long history linked to self-employment and travelling from February to November for the fair season (Gillan, 2000

⁶ The *Race Relations Act* (1976) was repealed by the Equality Act 2010 (J. Brown 2018).

as cited in Clark, 2001). New Travellers are thought to have emerged in the late 1960s in their desire to live an alternative lifestyle on the road (Lally, 2015). Clark (2001, p. 187) asserts that this 'convoy culture' began with people travelling across the festival circuit. New Travellers are perceived by the larger Gypsy/Traveller community to be from middle-class backgrounds or as 'Travellers with bank accounts' (Clark, 2001, p. 188), who are often degree educated and are anti-materialist in their ideology.

Distinctions between various groups are important in order to illuminate the heterogeneous nature of Roma, Gypsy and Traveller communities' origins and histories. Despite what similarities may exist between community groups, Roma, Romani Gypsy and Traveller people present with different needs. For example, more recent Roma migrants will present with more English language support needs than indigenous Scottish Travellers or English and Welsh Romani Gypsies (Hay et al., 2020). Indeed, in a recent report by the Women and Equalities Committee (House of Commons, 2019), it was suggested that Roma communities experience different inequalities to those faced by Romani Gypsies and Travellers.

Conflating terms and erasing identities

Roma, Gypsy and Traveller identities are often clustered homogeneously within data sets and policy (see for e.g. Scottish Government, 2018) rendering distinctions between various communities invisible. As mentioned in the preceding section, they are Ethnic Minority communities that are protected under legislation (Equality Act, 2010) and statutory bodies including schools have a duty of care to prevent discrimination and to promote 'race' equality.

Currently there is no specific U.K-wide policy on Roma, Gypsy and Traveller people (House of Commons, 2017). Similarly, there are glaring disparities related to terminology within policy between governments in the U.K making it difficult to understand various communities' needs. For example, in a recent House of Commons Library (2017) briefing paper the terms 'Gypsy and Travellers' were used to capture Roma, Romani Gypsies, Irish Travellers, Scottish Gypsies/Travellers, and Welsh Gypsies/Travellers. While in a recent Scottish Government consultation the term 'Traveller' is used to describe Gypsy/Travellers, Roma and Showpeople (Scottish Government, 2017).

Moreover, nomenclature fails to capture the unique identities of Roma, Gypsy and Traveller people as illustrated by the terminology employed by the European Union which refers to all

nomadic and semi-nomadic people as Roma (Council of Europe, 2012). The conflation of terminology is problematic as Scottish Travellers disapprove of this categorization (Marcus, 2015), while Irish Travellers consider themselves to be a distinct group from Roma (Joyce, et al., 2017).

Levinson (2015) further stresses the pejorative nature of the terminology. Use of the terms ‘Gypsy’ and ‘Traveller’ is also an area of contested space and only acceptable to some communities, while others may find it offensive due to the way that the term has been used pejoratively by members of mainstream society (D’Arcy, 2017). For example, European Roma reject the term ‘Gypsy’ and prefer to self-identify as ‘Roma’ (Mulcahy et al., 2017), as they see the term as being a direct translation of the extremely derogatory term ‘Cigany’ (Acton, 2016). While the Council of Europe (2012, p. 8), contends that the term ‘Gypsy’ is ‘alien’ to Roma community members due to its association with ‘negative and paternalistic stereotypes’.

To this end, nuanced understanding of the origins and needs of each community is essential. This research recognises that the terms ‘Roma’ ‘Gypsy’ and ‘Traveller’ have been widely used to describe multiple heterogeneous, nomadic, semi-nomadic (Bhopal, 2011) or settled communities (Levinson, 2015). However, the use of generic terminology has been controversial (Foster and Norton, 2012) as it does not define a single homogenous group and does little to acknowledge the nuanced origins of these communities (Sime et al., 2014) nor their various needs (Hay et al., 2020). While Roma, Gypsy and Traveller communities share cultural practices such as holding the family unit in high regard; clearly defined familial and gender roles; respect for the intergenerational transfer of knowledge within families and self-employment (Lloyd and McCluskey, 2008) it must be recognised that each community is multi-layered (Mayall, 2004) and has its own unique identity, lifestyle, religion and moral belief system (Hamilton, 2016).

Counting populations

2011 saw the first attempt to include Gypsy and Traveller people in the Census data (ONS, 2014), however different ethnic classifications were used on Census questionnaire categories in England and Wales, Scotland, and Northern Ireland. In England and Wales, participants could self-ascribe as ‘Gypsy or Irish Traveller’, while in Scotland the response category included ‘Gypsy/Traveller’ and the equivalent category in Northern Ireland was ‘Irish Traveller’ (House of Commons, 2017).

The 2011 Census data identified 63,000 Gypsy and Traveller people living in the U.K. 58,000 people in England and Wales self-ascribed as ‘Gypsy or Irish Traveller’, 4200 people living in Scotland self-ascribed as ‘Gypsy/Traveller’ and 1000 people living in Northern Ireland identified as ‘Irish Traveller’ (ONS, 2013). This count is however, considered to be gross underestimate as the Council of Europe (2012) has estimated a population of between 150,000 and 300,000, while Brown and colleagues (2013) suggested that there may be between 400,000 - 500,000 Roma, Gypsy and Travellers in the U.K. Further, in Scotland, Clark (2001, p. 113) posits the number of Scottish Travellers to be 15,000 thereby signifying a gross underestimation on Census 2011 figures.

To explain this underestimation, Mulcahy and colleagues (2017) cite three factors: fear of racial prejudice and discrimination may result in a reluctance to self-identify due to historical persecution (Hay et al., 2020); low literacy rates may have resulted in community members finding census data forms inaccessible; and institutional failure to include those in mobile housing. For Clark (1998), this gross underestimation may be explained by discrimination and politics. He asserts that it is tempting for politicians to ignore communities within ethnic monitoring data as ‘they do not require grants, services or ... funding because they are invisible’ (Clark, 1998, p. 10).

Further contributing to the underestimation, is that the census excluded Roma as a response category advising participants who would self-identify as ‘Roma’ to select ‘White Other’ (Mulcahy et al., 2017). Pertaining to Roma populations, Brown et al. (2013, p. 28) estimate approximately 197,705 Roma living in the U.K. England is argued to have a Roma population estimate of 193,297 while 3030 Roma migrants reside in Scotland and 500 in Northern Ireland respectively. Matras (2015, p. 29), however, problematizes the estimations put forward by Brown and colleagues (2013) describing them as ‘abstract projections’ and a methodology that not only lacked transparency but failed to engage directly with Roma communities. To this end, population figures for the most deprived ethnic minority community groups remain contested.

Further compounding the issue is that while the large majority of community members accept the term ‘Traveller’, others feel that it overlooks ethnicity (Levinson, 2015) and runs the risk of ascribing a travelling lifestyle to those who may now be settled. Indeed, although some Roma, Gypsy, and Traveller people continue to travel, the majority of Roma (circa 80–85 percent) in Europe, Irish Travellers in Ireland (circa 80 percent) and Romani Gypsies in

England and Wales (circa 75 percent) are largely sedentary (Council of Europe, 2012; ONS, 2011) as living a nomadic lifestyle has become far too difficult due to wider socioeconomic changes (Allen, 2018). Levine-Rasky (2018, p. 314) contends that despite this forced settlement, these communities are ‘unjustly regarded as inherently mobile’.

Education and Qualifications

Census data revealed that Roma, Gypsy and Traveller communities experienced significantly low educational attainment outcomes in comparison to any other ethnic or social group. Of the 58,000 Gypsy, Roma and Traveller people living in England and Wales aged 16 or over, 60 percent held no qualifications compared to the national average of 23 percent (ONS, 2014). Data in Scotland suggested that 50 percent of the 4200 Roma, Gypsy and Traveller people living in Scotland had no qualifications compared to 27 percent of the national average (Scottish Government, 2015a).

Although the Department for Education and Skills (DfES, 2006) has consistently argued that the data show cause for concern, limited institutional action has been taken to address the glaring disparities. In 2016, data indicated that fewer than nine percent of Gypsy/Roma young people and fewer than 18 percent of Irish Travellers achieved five GCSEs graded A*- C, compared to the national average of 57 percent (House of Commons, 2017). The implication of this is that many young Roma, Gypsy and Traveller people leave school without the qualifications needed to move on to further and higher education (Mulcahy et al., 2017) and increase their employment opportunities (Kóczé, 2009). More recently, the U.K Government’s Race Disparity Audit (Cabinet Office, 2017) reaffirmed that Roma, Gypsy and Traveller learners’ had the lowest attainment outcomes of all ethnic groups. Lack of qualifications may serve as a catalyst for continued inequalities experienced later in life.

Prior to the inclusion of Gypsy and Traveller communities inclusion in the 2011 Census, the DfES in England and Wales revised ethnic monitoring categories in order to address the attainment gap in January 2003. Students were categorised under ‘Traveller of an Irish Heritage’ or ‘Gypsy/Roma’ (DfES, 2003). Such categories also appear in the Pupil Level Annual School Census Data (PLASC 2003-2008 [now known as the School Census]) thereby allowing the DfES to monitor and analyse the performance of various community groups.

Although Roma are included within school data, Mulcahy et al. (2017) recommended that school census data should include appropriate categories for young Roma, Gypsy and Traveller people to ascribe to by expanding the number of categories available so that the terms ‘Gypsy’ and ‘Roma’ are not categorised together. Disaggregated data will offer insights into the needs of various community groups thereby allowing for targeted approaches to supporting young people within educational settings.

Comparatively the educational qualification outcomes in the Welsh context also found Roma, Gypsy and Traveller learners’ to experience the worst educational attainment outcomes of any ethnic group. Data indicated that between 2014 and 2016, just 24 percent of Gypsy/Gypsy Roma students achieved five or more GCSEs at grades A*-C compared to 59 percent of the national average (National Assembly for Wales, 2017).

In Scotland, the leavers data for 2013/2014 and 2014/2015 (two year average is used due to small numbers), indicates that 42 percent of young people recorded as ‘White – Gypsy/Traveller’ left school with one or more qualifications at SCQF level five compared to the national average of 84.7 percent. For 2014/2015 and 2015/2016, the Directorate for Education Analytical Services Anna MacKinnon (personal communications, October 2017) advised that 74.6 percent of leavers recorded as ‘White – Gypsy/Traveller’ had moved in to positive follow up destinations compared to 91.7 percent of the national average. Although 74 percent may seem like a significant number of young Gypsy and Traveller people moving on to positive destinations, one must use caution as the size of the cohort was only 67 young people which makes it difficult to draw comparisons.

Issues of ethnic minority categorisation appear again in the Scottish Government’s (2016a) attainment data, wherein ‘Occupational Gypsy and Other travellers’ is included under ‘All other categories’ with no mention of Roma communities. Moreover, the term ‘Travellers’ is not capitalized within this categorization which is problematic as some Traveller community members feel that it fails to acknowledge their ethnicity (Marcus, 2016b). The lack of disaggregated categories raises concerns as it does not allow for the monitoring and analysis of different community groups’ performance thereby preventing targeted interventions. This clustering is again perpetuated in subsequent policy documents produced by the Scottish Government (2017, p. 11), wherein the term ‘Traveller’ was used to refer to European Roma, Scottish Gypsy/Travellers and Showpeople.

The education of young Roma, Gypsy and Traveller people in England, Wales and Scotland: policy and context

It is well documented that Roma, Gypsy and Traveller people have suffered historically and contemporaneously from significant disadvantage and marginalisation across a number of indicators such as education, employment, health, accommodation and societal prejudice (Equality and Human Rights Commission, 2015). Various discriminatory policies and practices have existed throughout the centuries as a means to control these communities, ranging from the death penalty in the 16th century, deportation to the colonies, ethnic cleansing, and segregated education (Dawson, 2005; Fraser, 1995; Ryder et al., 2014). The Scottish Social Attitudes Survey (Scottish Centre for Social Research, 2010, 2015d) and the Amnesty reports (2012a and 2012b) indicate that persecution persists. More recently, policies have also acted to discriminate against Roma, Gypsy and Traveller people, ranging from precarious accommodation policies to being denied access to doctor's surgeries (MECOPP, 2012).

The European Commission (2011) published 'An EU Framework for National Roma Integration studies up to 2020' calling on EU member states to adapt strategy and policy documents, in order to tackle social exclusion (Rostas and Ryder, 2012; Ryder and Cemlyn, 2016). The goals set out within the EU Integration Framework include education, employment, healthcare and housing. In response to this call, the U.K government highlighted the overwhelming and multiple disparities impacting on Gypsies and Travellers indigenous to the U.K and developed a National Roma Integration strategy (DCLG, 2012) setting out its approach to integration in a paper entitled 'Creating the Conditions for Integration' (ibid).

The European Roma Policy Commission (ERPC, 2012, p. 22) described the U.K's approach as being subsumed within 'wider social inclusion policies', in that the strategy was not explicit in promoting integration for Roma, Gypsy and Traveller communities specifically. Ryder and colleagues (2012, p. 1) criticised the strategy due to its hierarchical nature, as it failed to 'engage with or adequately promote community groups and opposes forms of positive action; as a consequence of localism it is reluctant to endorse central government interventions'. Moreover, the strategy overlooked Roma migrants arriving from Central and Eastern Europe (Brown et al., 2013).

The Welsh government on the other hand, not only produced a distinct submission to the U.K but also included Roma in their annex to the European Commission entitled 'Travelling to a better Future' (Welsh Government, 2011), along with guidance on how they planned to deliver

on the strategy (Welsh Government, 2013, 2016). To date, the Scottish Government is yet to submit its own Roma Integration Strategy to the European Commission (Community InfoSource, 2016).

Education is cited as the best possible means of addressing the multiple interlocking disparities facing community groups (Harding, 2014). As stated previously, there is no agreement between governments on Roma, Gypsy and Traveller terminology. Similarly there is no U.K-wide policy on the education of young Roma, Gypsy and Traveller people. The Government of Wales Act and Scotland Act in 1998 resulted in the devolution of powers (including education, skills and social policy) to the National Assembly for Wales and the Scottish Parliament that had previously been reserved to the U.K government (Reynolds, 2008). The devolution of powers have resulted in Scotland, England, Wales and Ireland each having their own policies and guidance regarding the educational inclusion of Roma, Gypsy and Traveller young people, as discussed below.

English Education Policy Context

The educational attainment of Roma, Gypsy and Traveller people has been a concern for decades as highlighted by the Plowden (1967) and Swann (1985) reports. In 1967, Bridget Plowden (as Chairman of the Central Advisory Council for Education in England) presented a report entitled ‘Children and their Primary Schools’ (Plowden Report) to the Department of Education and Science. The report identified Gypsies as the “most severely deprived children in the country” (p. 59). There have been a number of developments over the years to address the barriers to attainment for children from these backgrounds in England.

The Education Act 1981 extended each local authorities’ duty to include children residing permanently or temporarily in their catchment, including Traveller children (Binns, 1990). The Education Reform Act in 1988 subsequently saw the central government making educational provision grants to anyone who did not have a fixed address. This provision was again replicated in the Education Act of 1996 which supported Gypsy and Traveller young people in education in over 3000 schools (Ofsted, 1996). Further attempts to redress the imbalance saw the Department for Education (DFE) (2000), develop guidance on good practice, thereby opening up research on examining the barriers to educational inclusion for young Gypsy and Traveller people (Bhopal et al., 2000). Despite these measures, Ofsted (2001, 2003) raised concerns as these community groups continued to fare less well than their mainstream peers.

The Department for Education and Skills (DfES) subsequently released the 'Aiming high' strategy guidance (2003, 2005) which sought to raise both the attendance and attainment amongst young Gypsy and Traveller people with specific programmes of support. Echoing earlier concerns raised by the Plowden Report (1967) both of these reports argued that these children are the group most at risk of underachievement within the education system. Included in these publications, was guidance pertaining to the ways in which race equalities policy could be implemented in order to address the racism and exclusion experienced by Gypsy Travellers in schools. Further attempts to redress the imbalance included a specific focus on these marginalised young people within the Ofsted framework; reviewing the Education Act 1996; and reviewing statutory guidance so as to include young Roma, Gypsy and Traveller people (Department for Communities and Local Government, 2012).

Wilkin and colleagues (2010, p. 8) argued that these targeted interventions in the English context were 'beginning to make an impact'. However, subsequent administrations have resulted in differential provision and support. By way of illustration, funding for various initiatives to facilitate students' educational development has been withdrawn (Naldic, 2011). Local authorities in England received an Ethnic Minority Achievement Grant up until 2011, in order to support young Roma, Gypsy and Traveller people within educational settings. However, this grant was mainstreamed and there is no longer a requirement for the funding to be spent on young Ethnic Minority people (Naldic, 2011). This means that young Roma, Gypsy and Traveller people are missing out on crucial resources and targeted interventions that will ultimately impact on their life chances.

More recently, the Women and Equalities Committee launched an inquiry to explore progress in tackling the inequalities experienced by Roma, Gypsy and Traveller communities. The Committee found that little progress had been made in reducing inequalities across a range of indicators including education, health, discrimination and hate crime and gender (House of Commons, 2019a). In providing oral evidence to the Women and Equalities Committee (House of Commons, 2018), Kalwant Bhopal, Professor of Education and Social Justice at University of Birmingham, highlighted concerns related to the drastic funding cuts that have impacted on the Traveller Education Support Services (TESS) in England and Wales; lack of representation in the school curriculum; and the need for clearer guidance on how racism and discrimination is handled within educational settings. In her recommendations, Bhopal cited the need for ring-

fenced funding for TESS as a means of ameliorating the barriers that young people face within education institutions.

Overall, the Women and Equalities Committee (House of Commons, 2019a) found education provision to be severely lacking, presenting several barriers for learners. Amongst the findings, the inquiry noted that schools would off roll students who were perceived to be struggling and a tendency for educational institutions to reproduce paternalistic and negative stereotypes of communities. The Committee also noted the lack of Roma, Gypsy and Traveller visibility and cultural heritage within English school curricula. Importantly, the inquiry included Roma specific issues.

Despite the evidence gathered, however, the recommendations put forward by the Committee were found to be lacking. Recommendations included: the DfE carrying out audits of local authorities policies in relation to home education; council officers to monitor children being home educated; a pupil passport scheme to allow students to move between schools with records; placing responsibility on individual schools to enact the Equality Act (2010) so that young people are not discriminated against; guidance on sex education; and role models for young Roma, Gypsy and Traveller people to speak to. The report failed to address concerns raised by Bhopal in that there was no commitment to ring-fence funding for TESS provision. Finally, the recommendations failed to include the development of an inclusive curriculum.

Welsh Education Policy Context

The Welsh Government revised Gypsy Traveller policy in 2008 based on a number of key reports (see for e.g. Estyn, 2005; National Foundation for Education Research, 2006; National Assembly for Wales, 2003). The Estyn report (2005) on ‘The Education of Gypsy Traveller pupils’ recommended improving data collection methodologies; addressing low attendance rates; developing inclusive school policies; and developing an inclusive curriculum reflective of Gypsy Traveller heritage. The Welsh Assembly (2008) subsequently produced guidance entitled ‘Moving Forward – Gypsy Traveller Education’. The guidance indicated that it was the duty of each local authority to develop policies and strategy to support all Gypsy and Traveller learners. An emphasis was placed on the employment of a flexible and culturally relevant curriculum in order to engage students and families. Transition programmes between primary and secondary school were also identified as vital, and local authorities were encouraged to apply for funding in order to support Gypsy Traveller education initiatives. The

report also highlighted the pivotal support offered by TESS in promoting access and encouraging students' continued engagement in education.

In measuring the progress made based on the recommendations of the Estyn report (2005) and the Moving Forward guidance (National Assembly for Wales, 2008) a subsequent report entitled 'The education of Gypsy Traveller pupils' (Estyn, 2011) served as a further catalyst for improving the educational provision for Gypsy and Traveller learners. The Estyn report (2011) resulted in the Welsh Assembly producing policy and strategy documents entitled 'Travelling to a Better Future' (2011) and 'Gypsy and Traveller Framework for Action and Delivery' (2013, 2016).

Burchardt et al. (2018) argued that these coherent strategies were distinct from the English context in that they provided detailed target and monitoring mechanisms to measure progress. Roma community groups were also considered within policy and strategy. The Welsh Government also disaggregated data at this point to separate Gypsy and Roma communities, while also adding a category for Showpeople to allow for effective targeting and measurement mechanisms (Estyn, 2019). Importantly, there was also a continued dedication to funding bespoke educational provision for Roma, Gypsy and Traveller learners' and a commitment to an inclusive curriculum that reflected students' cultural heritage. Ryder and Cemlyn (2016) also found that TESS provision in Wales had been protected and continued to provide vital support for learners and their families.

In the autumn of 2014, however, the National Assembly for Wales took the decision to no longer ring-fence funding for Roma, Gypsy and Traveller learners for the 2015-2016 financial year. Instead 11 different grants⁷ were amalgamated into one overarching grant called the Education Improvement Grant (National Assembly for Wales, 2017). In scrutinising the impact of non-ring-fenced funding on pupils, the Children, Young People and Education Committee questioned whether the objectives of the original ring-fenced grant were being delivered within the Education Improvement Grant (National Assembly for Wales, 2017). In providing evidence to the committee, Dr. Jonathan Bretnall argued that the cessation of protected funding reflected a 'deprioritisation of support for these groups of learners' (Bretnall, 2016). He further argued that the impact of reductions of staff levels serves as indirect discrimination on racial grounds.

⁷ Gypsy Children and Traveller Children Education Grant; Minority Ethnic Achievement Grant; Foundation Phase Revenue Grant; School Effectiveness Grant; 14-19 Learning Pathways; Welsh in Education Grant; Lead and Emerging Practitioner Grant; Reading and Numeracy Test Support Grant; Additional Funding for Band 4 and 5 schools; Teacher Induction; and the Higher Level Teaching Assistant

In response to the Children, Young People and Education Committee's (2017) report, the Welsh Government (2018) provided a draft budget on the 2019-20 Education Main Expenditure Group. The draft budget noted the need to shield schools from the considerable impact of successive years of austerity measures. Within the budget, it was also noted that funding levels of 2018-19 would be maintained during 2019-20 seeing £8.7 million being allocated from reserves for Ethnic minority, and Roma, Gypsy and Traveller students as part of core services (Welsh Government, 2018a). These new arrangements meant that local authorities would determine how the funding would be spent based on their priorities.

Following on from the recommendations made by the Children, Young People and Education Committee's (2017), the Welsh Government requested Estyn to review the impact that changes in funding would have on learners in a progress review since Estyn's (2011) report. The Estyn (2019) report found that the majority of local authorities believed that the new funding arrangements would adversely affect Roma, Gypsy and Traveller pupils. Findings had also noted that the number of young Roma, Gypsy and Traveller people attending secondary school had increased by 35 percent with Estyn correlating this increase to support measures in place over the years. The report also reinforced the vital support offered to young people and families by TESS services. However, as TESS services are managed by local authorities, spending is determined by local authorities based on local need which may affect provision of TESS services.

Traveller Education Support Services

The Traveller Education Services (more recently Traveller Education Support Services, TESS) were established in England and Wales in the late 1980s in response to the Plowden Report (1967). TESS was developed in order to provide support for Gypsy and Traveller families within the education system (Foster and Norton, 2012). TESS works closely with a number of bodies such as local authorities, schools and Gypsy and Traveller families in order to increase levels of attendance and improve attainment. Through the work within educational settings, TESS also raised levels of understanding of Gypsy and Traveller culture amongst education authorities and schools. The support given by TESS has had a significantly positive impact on young people's educational experiences (Estyn, 2019). Data also indicates that the work of TESS over the years has increased the number of children from these backgrounds attending

primary school (OFSTED, 2003), with Fremlova et al. (2009) pointing to the role of TESS in fostering the inclusion of students by adapting services to meet the needs of communities.

One criticism of the multi-agency approach that is often raised by TESS however, is that young Gypsy and Traveller people are seen as TESS's responsibility and not the school's responsibility (Derrington and Kendall, 2004). In support of this, Bhopal and Myers (2008) suggested that resolving issues with students is often left entirely with TESS with little support from the respective school. This practice is problematic, as the designation of a key TESS named person has little effect on its own and has to be matched through school policy as well as staff attitudes (Bhopal and Myers, 2008). Moreover, Foster and Norton (2012) argued that TESS tended to become marginalised within educational systems, existing on the periphery which meant that TESS teams and the young people that they supported were not fully included.

Further compounding the issue, is that funding cuts and the loss of key staff results in the reduced capacity to address inequalities faced by young Roma, Gypsy and Traveller people. Years of austerity and funding cuts have meant that institutional skills have been eradicated with little transfer of knowledge between TESS staff and teachers (Brown et al., 2013). TESS funding was initially ring-fenced through the Ethnic Minority Achievement Grant until 2006 and subsequently through the Vulnerable Children's Grant (Bhopal, 2011) and from 2008 it was incorporated in to the Area Based Grant in England. The implication of this is that local authorities sought to reduce expenditure and integrated TESS into mainstream services resulting in depleted services and targeted support for Gypsy and Traveller communities (Foster and Norton, 2012). To this end, in order to build confident and trusted relationships with Roma, Gypsy and Traveller communities and improve attendance and achievement requires not only TESS services but also commitment from government, local authorities, Head teachers, the senior management team and teaching staff. Worryingly, with recent changes to ring-fenced funding for the provision of services in Wales (Estyn, 2019), the impact on TESS remains to be seen.

Scottish Education Policy Context

It can be argued that the Scottish Government's responses to Gypsy and Traveller communities education needs over successive years has been lacking, as with their response to the needs of Roma communities who have more recently arrived. In 1982, the Secretary of State's Advisory

Committee report included a chapter on Gypsy and Traveller education citing the urgent need to address the discrimination that these communities faced (Scottish Office, 1982). This urgent need was only, however, addressed in 1990 with the establishment of the Scottish Traveller Education Programme (STEP) within the Moray House College of Education and funded by the Scottish Government. STEP's remit was to create working groups across the country in order to promote policy and practice to support Gypsy and Traveller education within the curriculum (Clark, 2001).

Following devolution in Scotland, STEP's remit includes research exploring how community groups access the Curriculum for Excellence⁸ and their accessibility needs (STEP, 2013; Scottish Government, 2015b). STEP works in collaboration with the Scottish Traveller Education Network (TENET), a Scotland-wide professional body that supports designated staff working with Roma, Gypsy and Traveller families both in and outside of school settings (Learning and Teaching Scotland, 2011). Unlike provision in England and Wales, young people are not supported in Scottish schools by a dedicated team such as TESS to improve educational outcomes. Instead STEP aims to disseminate research to staff within educational settings. Clark (2001, p. 177), contends that the lack of an 'externally targeted 'Traveller Education Service staff for Travellers, as in England and Wales, does little to increase sporadic attendance' in the Scottish context.

Subsequent reports from the Scottish Office (1998, 2000) and the Race Equality Advisory Forum (Scottish Executive, 2001a), provided a number of recommendations to schools, teaching staff and local authorities in order to develop their practice and enhance support for Gypsy and Traveller learners. In 2001, an Equal Opportunities Committee Inquiry produced a report entitled 'Gypsy Travellers and Public Sector Policies' (Scottish Parliament, 2001) found that these communities faced discrimination and prejudice across multiple indicators including accommodation, education, health and personal social services. In response, the Scottish Executive (2001a/c) made 37 recommendations to address the needs of communities including 10 recommendations related to the education of Gypsies and Travellers - the majority of which never having been implemented or actioned.

In reviewing the progress made since 2001, the Equal Opportunities Committee (Scottish Parliament, 2005) found that the recommendations had not been implemented and little

⁸ The Curriculum for Excellence in Scotland's curricular framework – designed to support children and young people gain the knowledge, skills and attributes needed for life in a rapidly changing labour market.

progress had been made in ameliorating the barriers faced by Gypsies and Travellers. In order to address the lack of progress, a Gypsy Traveller Strategic Group was subsequently established, again producing sets of recommended actions in a report (Scottish Executive, 2005). Included within the recommendations, was for the Scottish Executive to work closely with STEP, educational institutions and the Scottish Qualifications Authority in order to develop policy for Gypsy and Traveller education.

During this time, Gypsy and Traveller students' needs were also subsumed within the 'Curriculum for Excellence' (2004), 'More Choices, More Chances' (2006) and 'Getting it Right for Every Child' (2008a) policies that promoted the need for inter-agency approaches to improve outcomes for all young people, which would have been a significant step forward if implemented. Promising developments within publications such as 'Inclusive Educational Approaches for Gypsies and Travellers in Education' (Learning and Teaching Scotland, 2003) and the quality evaluation guide 'Taking a Closer Look at: Inclusion and Equality – Meeting the Needs of Gypsies and Travellers' (HMIE, 2005) increased the visibility of the needs of children from these backgrounds both at policy and strategic levels.

Specific guidance was also developed by Learning and Teaching Scotland (2011, p. 6) that stipulated 'educators must take into consideration the rights of Travelling families to maintain their cultures' and that 'a child's rights to access education should not be affected by their family's mobility'. In the same year, a mapping study produced by BEMIS (2011) entitled 'Gypsy Travellers in Contemporary Scotland: The 2001 Inquiry into Gypsy Travellers and Public Sector Policies: Ten Years On' measured the progress toward reaching the recommendations made by Scottish Parliament (2001) by engaging with community members. The report noted that the work by Article 12 and STEP addressed three of the ten educational recommendations – albeit in a patchy and regionalised approach due to funding constraints. Despite recommendations young people continued to face discrimination within educational settings and there was an identified need for schools to increase engagement and develop anti-racism strategies. BEMIS (2011) also suggested that ingrained stereotypical perceptions influenced teacher's interpretations of students behaviour in that they failed to take into account the broader social and structural concerns that impacted on learners'. The report set out the following educational recommendations in order to reduce the barriers faced by young people:

1. An alternative and flexible educational offer extending beyond the provision within educational settings. Importantly community members should be involved in the development.
2. More comprehensive anti-racism and discrimination strategies within the school context.
3. Involving Gypsy and Traveller parents in Parental Council in order to promote and foster greater engagement with specific projects aimed at young people to encourage retention.
4. Continued Professional Development to increase cultural awareness and how to deal with racism in schools for teaching staff.
5. Lifelong learning provision for both adults and young people from Gypsy and Traveller backgrounds.

Despite recommendations made by BEMIS (2011), Marcus (2015) argues that mainstream comprehension of these marginalised communities is still underdeveloped within the Scottish context. In 2017, a report from the Scottish Government's independent Race Equality Adviser Kaliani Lyle (Scottish Government, 2017, p. 27) stated:

“Despite parliamentary enquiries and reviews of progress, various reports, strategies and initiatives, little has changed for Gypsy/Travellers in Scotland. They face much the same problems that have troubled them for decades. In their Gypsy/Travellers and Care Report, the 2012 Equal Opportunities Committee concluded that the evidence pointed to ‘repeated failures: recommendations that have not been implemented and initiatives too small scale or short term’.

The Scottish Government then opened a consultation in order to improve outcomes for young Roma, Gypsy and Traveller people (Scottish Government, 2017b). In response to the consultation, Article 12 in Scotland problematized the format taken to consult community members citing accessibility concerns for those who have literacy or language issues (Article 12, 2017). Further concerns were raised such as:

1. The use of ‘Traveller’ to capture all identities was problematic and should be avoided as Showpeople do not identify as Traveller and Roma are no longer nomadic.
2. The emphasis on a digital approach did not take into consideration that internet access is patchy, particularly in rural Scotland. Moreover, the lack of data pertaining to access to PCs, laptops and printers was highlighted.

3. An over emphasis on teaching staff educating themselves amongst competing priorities. To overcome this, training should be provided on an annual basis as part of in-service days.
4. Flexibility in the content and processes of school education.

Despite recommendations made by Article 12 (2017), the Scottish Government subsequently produced a guidance document entitled 'Improving education outcomes for children and young people from travelling cultures' (Scottish Government, 2018) where the term Traveller was used to capture all identities. The guidance went on to emphasise the need for anti-bullying policies within schools, as well as policies to support transitions and enhance attendance. However, funding provision for programmes to support transitions and promote attendance amongst community members was not alluded to within the document. Further problems included the exclusion of Roma within data gathering processes in order to measure progression and provide targeted interventions, such as language support. On a more positive note, the guidance emphasised the need of training for both non-teaching and teaching staff, including training for probationer teachers that should be on-going.

The guidance also stipulated that equity should be promoted through the use of Pupil Equity Funding which was introduced by the Scottish Government to close the attainment gap (Scottish Government, 2019a). However, this funding is spent at the discretion of the Head teacher who will also have other competing priorities. The document also states 'not everything needs to have a financial cost and school leaders should consider how using their existing resources, including premises and staff, effectively and flexibly can support Travellers' (Scottish Government, 2018, p. 29).

Across successive years, the Scottish Government has failed to provide adequate and sustainable ring-fenced funding for bespoke projects within educational institutions to increase engagement and retention amongst Roma, Gypsy and Traveller community members. As evidenced within the English and Welsh contexts, ring-fenced funding for targeted projects increased student attendance and attainment within educational settings, however, recent cuts due to austerity are impacting on the support available for students (Ryder and Cemlyn, 2016). Young people in Scotland, however, never had the opportunity to benefit from ring-fenced funding and bespoke educational provision.

Finally, in addressing Article 12's (2017) concerns regarding a digital approach and a glaring lack of evidence, the Scottish Government (2018, p. 38) contended that 'research suggests most Travellers have access to the internet'. The research that they drew on was published by STEP (2016, p. 4) entitled 'Mobile Children, Young People and Technology Project'. In exploring students use of technology, the researchers recruited 19 young people in primary schools who identified as Slovakian Roma (N=6) in Glasgow and Gypsy/Traveller (N=13) in Edinburgh, the Highlands and Ayrshire. Acknowledging low literacy rates the authors explicitly state within their methodologies section that the research design 'reflected anticipated low written literacy and communication levels and placed emphasis on oral and visual forms of participation and expression (STEP, 2016, p. 15). Digital technology use was ubiquitous amongst all young people within the aforementioned study, however, the authors noted that there may be variability in access to the internet. The small sample size raises concerns over generalisability. Moreover, the study did not include parents and therefore questions remain regarding parental literacy and digital literacy rates and finally parental language barriers.

In 2019, a joint action plan between the Scottish Government and COSLA was subsequently published entitled 'Improving the Lives of Scotland's Gypsy/Travellers: 2019-2021' (Scottish Government, 2019). It is important to note, that this action plan is not inclusive of Roma communities in Scotland. In relation to education, the joint action plan cited an additional £275,000 in funding over three years (2018-2020) to improve the delivery of education and a commitment to provide a further £500,000 of funding over three years (2020-2022) to support flexible family learning. While additional funding is much needed, it only equates to £91,000 per year between 2018 and 2020, and is a drop in the ocean in comparison to the Welsh Assembly's £8.7 million investment per year (Welsh Government, 2018a). In order to remove the barriers faced by young Roma, Gypsy and Traveller people and provide adequate support, the Scottish Government needs to meaningfully invest a substantial amount of funding.

This section has highlighted the differential provision resulting from the devolution of powers in England, Scotland and Wales, with each respective administration having their own policies and guidance regarding the educational inclusion of Roma, Gypsy and Traveller young people. The literature suggests that the support offered by TESS across England and Wales has had a significant impact on students' educational outcomes prior to austerity measures and funding cuts. While in Scotland, the impact of austerity on Roma, Gypsy and Traveller communities is a moot point, as the funding was never there to support communities to begin with.

Despite the wealth of policies and guidance, local authorities and schools continue to fail at meeting their statutory duty to protect young Roma, Gypsy and Traveller people's rights and to create a meaningful and inclusive ethos and curriculum that promotes and celebrates cultural diversity (Deuchar and Bhopal, 2013; Marcus, 2015). McCowan (2010) further argues that Ethnic minority young people are subjected to education systems that are both unresponsive as well as repressive of their cultures. The literature suggests that despite initiatives to reduce the attainment gap and educational inequality that young Roma, Gypsy and Traveller people face, the disadvantage experienced by these communities persists and learners continue to fare less well than any other minority group at every age and every stage of education (Equality and Human Rights Commission, 2015).

Roma, Gypsy and Traveller students' school experiences continue to be marred by absenteeism, underachievement and significantly high drop-out rates compared to the national average (Harding, 2014). Research indicates that these learners are more likely to be excluded (Deuchar and Bhopal, 2013), identified as having Additional Support for Learning needs (Wilkin et al., 2009), leave school without formal qualifications (ONS, 2014) and are less likely to make the transition from primary school to secondary school (Foster and Norton, 2012).

Experiences of education within institutional settings

Attendance, Mobility and Exclusion

Research indicates that disengagement from education is higher for Ethnic minority young people (Reschly and Christenson, 2012) and that Roma, Gypsy and Traveller students have the lowest attendance rates of all groups (Mulcahy et al., 2017). Wilkin and colleagues (2010) identified patterns of attendance amongst young Roma, Gypsy and Traveller people in English primary and secondary schools. The research suggests that Travellers of Irish Heritage attend both primary and secondary school less frequently than Gypsy/Roma pupils. There is a correlation between attendance and attainment as young people with the lowest rates of attendance demonstrate the highest rates of underachievement (Scottish Government, 2017). Early disengagement from secondary school and the failure to attain qualifications increases risk of unemployment, precarious working conditions and low earnings (Brunello and De Paola, 2013; Kóczé, 2009; Rosário et al., 2016; Wolbers, 2007).

The reason most commonly cited for students' low attendance and underachievement is that 'they travel all the time' (Lauritzen, 2018, p. 60), however, in the words of Liégeois (1986, p. 50), 'not all Gypsies are nomads'. As mentioned previously, the majority of Roma (circa 80–85 percent) in Europe, Irish Travellers in Ireland (circa 80 percent) and Romani Gypsies in England and Wales (circa 75 percent) are largely sedentary⁹ (Council of Europe, 2012; ONS, 2011) which call into question asserted correlations between nomadism and interrupted learning. Lauritzen (2018) argues that an essentialist narrative has been established through knowledge production wherein nomadism is associated with educational disadvantage. These master narratives are then used to explain and justify Roma, Gypsy and Traveller's exclusion from education thereby sustaining 'key tropes of antigypsyist discourses' (*ibid*, p. 59).

For the small minority of families who still live a highly mobile life, however, distance learning has been developed in order to mitigate the effects of interrupted learning and has been found to be motivating and rewarding for a number of learners. The drawbacks of distance learning, however, include young people having to be highly independent and self-motivated in the case that they come from families with low literacy and education levels (Jordan, 2001). Further limitations to distance learning approaches include: the type of electricity available on sites may not be compatible with computer use and there may be limited WIFI connection in more rural locations (Jordan, 2001; Article 12, 2017).

Successful inclusion and progression will be dependent on the school's ability to support students learning outside of institutional settings. Deuchar and Bhopal (2008), however, argue that schools often fail to support young people who are highly mobile. Jordan (2000) suggests that schools perceive mobility as a problem, despite being able to offer effective support to other students experiencing interrupted learning such as those who are chronically sick or learners in care. Schools may also be less committed to students who are highly mobile based on concerns over how long they will remain with the school. Foster and Norton (2012) argued that this results in young Roma, Gypsy and Traveller people being excluded from regular literacy and numeracy intervention programmes as the school believes that mobility will result in an intervention place being wasted – again based on essentialist notions of nomadism (Lauritzen, 2018).

⁹ For a detailed discussion regarding community members increasingly moving into bricks and mortar housing due to structural and legislative changes see Greenfields and Smith (2010).

Nonetheless, for Roma, Gypsy and Traveller people who no longer live a nomadic way of life, it has been suggested that their completion of secondary school remains unlikely (Derrington, 2007; Wilkin et al., 2010) indicating that there are other factors affecting their attendance and achievement within the education system. By way of illustration, Derrington and Kendall's (2007) longitudinal research found that more than two-thirds of students dropped out of school before the end of key stage four despite the majority of the sample no longer living a nomadic way of life. To this end, Levinson and Sparkes (2005) argued that regardless of whether young people live nomadic or settled lifestyles, they will experience radically dissimilar spatial environments in contrast to mainstream young people due to racialisation.

According to the Race Disparity Audit (2017) young Roma/Gypsy and Irish Traveller people experienced the highest rates of temporary school exclusions at 17.29 percent and 17 percent; and the highest rates of permanent exclusions at 0.45 percent and 0.36 percent. Bhopal (2004) argues that young Gypsy and Traveller people are treated less fairly than their mainstream counterparts due in part to policies and practices resulting in these students being excluded (DfES, 2006). Research has consistently demonstrated that these learners experienced punishment and disciplinary exclusion at disproportionately high rates (McCluskey et al., 2011) which only serves to damage relationships (Levinson and Sparkes, 2005).

In Deuchar and Bhopal's (2013, p. 744) research with Fairground Travellers, they found that these students experienced social exclusion from both teachers and pupils, with one participant likening their experience of racism to being treated like 'aliens'. The experience of social exclusion has implications for young Roma, Gypsy and Traveller people and their sense of identity and belonging (Deuchar, 2009) which may serve as a barrier to entering the labour market (Jordan, 2001; Traveller Movement, 2019). This feeling of not belonging may then be exacerbated by schools failing to follow up on students when they do choose to self-exclude in order to avoid racist persecution. Many commentators have argued that following up on absences by schools is patchy (Kiddle, 1999; Derrington and Kendall, 2004) and may contribute to students from these backgrounds feeling further socially excluded and psychologically isolated.

Research suggests that the most vulnerable point for both girls and boys from the Gypsy, Roma and Traveller community to be excluded from school in England was between the ages of 13 to 14 years of age (Derrington and Kendall, 2003). It is thought that young Gypsy and Traveller males are more likely to be excluded and drop out than their female counterparts. Levinson and

Sparkes (2003) contend that possible reasons for this includes the threat school may impose on traditional masculine identities amongst Gypsy and Traveller men as well as family loyalty and the need to be perceived as a full community member. Parker-Jenkins and colleagues (2007) argue that men find adaptation to secondary school more difficult due to fear of cultural dilution, while others have argued (Mulcahy et al., 2017) that disengagement from education is due to economic pragmatism.

It is important to note distinctions between communities as Foster and Norton (2012) contend that Roma girls are more likely to drop out of education than Roma boys. Wilkin and colleagues (2010) suggest that one reason for this may be due to fewer opportunities for Roma boys to assume roles within established family businesses thereby increasing the incentive to gain vocational or academic qualifications within this minority group. Research by Surdu and Surdu (2006), however, contends that Romani mothers encouraged higher levels of education amongst their sons, as they were traditionally seen as breadwinners,

Transitions

Research indicates that access to primary school education continues to improve, however, this pattern is not reflected in secondary school attendance (Reynolds et al., 2003; Derrington, 2005; Bhopal and Myers, 2008; STEP, 2015). For example, Scottish Government (2017) data reflects 812 young Gypsy/Traveller people in primary school and only 228 in secondary school. It has been well documented that the transition from primary school to secondary school is a period marked by anxiety and distress with far reaching implications on young people's well-being and educational attainment (Hung, 2014; West, Sweeting and Young, 2014). Secondary schools are largely thought of as large, impersonal institutions where racist bullying and little support from teaching staff is the 'norm' (Foster and Norton, 2012). Moreover, as Roma, Gypsy and Traveller young people make the transition from primary to secondary school, the intersectionality of culture, gender, socio-economic status and religion appear to be at odds with the stipulations placed on these students by mainstream education authorities resulting in tension and conflict (Hamilton, 2016).

As mentioned previously, not transitioning to secondary school and or dropping out early has far reaching implications and has been associated with exclusion from further and higher education (Clark, 2004), the labour market, and fewer opportunities overall (Geraghty, Erbstein, and Greenfield, 2010). Completing secondary school education allows individuals to

access diverse social areas and contributes to social inclusion thereby mitigating and limiting the aforementioned negative effects. Research has found that in order to encourage attendance and increase achievement, it is important to foster good relationships with parents (Clark, 2014; Derrington and Kendall, 2004; Wilkin et al., 2010; Smith, 2017).

Further conditions that have resulted in the effective transition to secondary school include practical assistance for students and their families (school uniform provision; assisting parents with literacy issues to complete admission forms) as well as flexible opportunities within the curriculum (Wilkin et al., 2010). Confidence and engagement in learning has been found to be influenced by the extent to which young Roma, Gypsy and Traveller people can identify with the curriculum and learning resources in relation to their culture, language, history and future vocation (Bhopal and Myers, 2008). However, it must be noted, that placing too much emphasis on vocational opportunities within the curriculum may run the risk of further homogenising Roma, Gypsy and Traveller people.

Indeed, Hamilton's (2016) study found that young English Gypsy and Irish Traveller people were trading in vocational courses and striving to achieve formal qualifications in order to broaden their career opportunities. Similarly, participants in Marcus' (2015, p. 68) study posited that the education offered at mobile schools was too simple with Traveller girls expressing a desire to pursue a 'good education'. These studies serve as an important reminder not to make assumptions about the educational aspirations of young Gypsy, Roma and Traveller people, as well as to not treat them as a homogenous group.

While the number of Roma, Gypsy and Traveller students transitioning from primary to secondary school is increasing (Reynolds et al., 2003; Derrington, 2005; Bhopal and Myers, 2008; STEP, 2015), fewer are making the transition to further and higher education. According to Danvers (2015), only three to four percent of these communities accessed higher education in 2014, with figures for 2018 suggesting that only 70 students accessed higher education (Coan, 2019). Moreover, UCAS ethnic monitoring categorisations include Gypsy/Traveller and Traveller of Irish heritage, but fail to include Roma populations (Mulcahy et al., 2017). There is also a paucity of empirical research pertaining to Roma, Gypsy and Travellers experiences of further and higher education (Clark, 2004; Traveller Movement, 2018). Mulcahy and colleagues (2017, p. 56) recently explored barriers to accessing higher education and found:

- The limited relevance of higher education curricula to Roma, Gypsy and Traveller culture
- Caution on the part of young people as to whether higher education will prepare them for paid employment
- Fears of not belonging on campus or that higher education is beyond their ability
- Concerns pertaining to a financial return on investment as well as cultural debt aversion

Further barriers were identified by a BBC podcast ‘the Next Episode’ (Coan, 2019) in discussions with Roma Traveller Lois Brookes-Jones who is studying politics at the University of Chester. Lois cited the difficulties in filling out UCAS forms as her parent’s levels of literacy meant that they could not support her in the process. She also described a number of racist attacks perpetrated against her on campus, and noted that when she attempted to report the incident to the hate-crime officer on campus there was a failure to act on the part of authorities. In support of Lois experiences, the Next Episode also found that 65 percent of universities across the U.K did not provide support for students identifying as Roma, Gypsy and Traveller (*ibid*).

Amongst universities making a positive impact for these communities is Kings College London, who have established a widening access programme for Roma, Gypsy and Traveller students called ‘Rom Belong’. The outreach programme works to support students with both structural and non-structural barriers in accessing higher education (Brown, 2019). Notably, a significant number of the staff team developing the programme, are from Traveller backgrounds. The team also run ‘Rom Belong’ taster days where young people and their families are invited to think about their future education and careers through interactive activities on campus. The importance of widening access programmes was highlighted by Harrison (2018, p. 2), where he argued that they have the power to disrupt ‘historic stratification and encourage disadvantaged individuals to transcend the structural disadvantages, that they face’. Further, the taster days may be conceived of as allowing young people to create a ‘roadmap connecting the present to the future’ (Oyserman et al., 2002, p. 132), in a space where they can envision their possible future selves (Harrison, 2018).

Roma, Gypsy and Traveller Parents

A large body of literature generally contends that Gypsy Travellers do not want their children to be educated (Acton, 2004; Lloyd and McCluskey, 2008; Wilkin et al., 2010), while others have argued that parents are more likely to value primary school education as it focuses on

basic literacy and numeracy skills and is considered a safe environment (Bhopal, 2011; Derrington and Kendall, 2004). Parents are often purported to be concerned that secondary school and exposure to mainstream culture might impact on and erode cultural values (Levinson and Hooley, 2014).

In support of this, Harding (2014) asserts that Gypsy and Traveller parents feel that secondary school reduces integration into the family and prevents young people from learning the necessary cultural and economic skills. For example boys will learn various trades from their fathers and uncles, while girls will learn to be homemakers (Clark, 2001). Marcus (2015) argues that some Travellers are concerned about drinking, drugs, and sex education thereby resulting in diminished support for secondary schooling. The narratives perpetuated and recycled within academic literature are, however, harmful and serve as a barrier to students' educational engagement and attainment. This is exemplified in the work of the Women and Equalities Committee (House of Commons, 2019a) who stated within their 2019 report:

There is no lack of aspiration from Gypsy and Traveller parents for their children, but for some, formal education is not seen as a part of those aspirations. This means that it is too easy for the education system to write off the potential of Gypsy and Traveller children, enabling prejudice to continue.

While there might be strong cultural influences at play that affect transition and retention in secondary school, too much emphasis on cultural attitudes and expectations runs the risk of pathologising Roma, Gypsy and Traveller culture and overlooking institutional barriers. Increasingly, research points to a shift in parental perceptions of schooling (see for e.g. Bhopal, 2004; Flecha and Soler, 2013) due to economical and societal factors (e.g. increased urbanisation; mechanization resulting in a decline in agricultural work; increased purchasing via the Internet; austerity slowing consumer buying pace), impacting on traditional trade activities amongst communities (Hamilton, 2016; Levinson and Sparkes, 2003; Rosário et al., 2017; Smith, 2017).

Authors such as Flecha and Soler (2013) and García-Carrón et al. (2017) have also argued that Roma parents do want their children to receive an education in order to improve their life chances. Flecha and Soler (2013) found overwhelming support from parents for their children to attend primary school and engage in education. Similarly, García-Carrón and colleagues (2017) found that Roma parents were invested in their children's education and drop-out rates were reduced through familial involvement in secondary school education. While Hamilton's,

(2016) study on English Gypsy and Irish Traveller girls found that those who had supportive mothers were more likely to engage in education.

The Roma Education Fund (2010) reports that engaging Roma parents in their children's education increases attendance and performance. Parental involvement in schools is thought to improve their skills thereby allowing them to better facilitate their children's educational development (Flecha and Soler, 2013) and resolve behavioural and academic issues more effectively (Sheldon and Epstein, 2005). It is, however, important to note that while parents are engaged with educational institutions, they are often themselves illiterate (Levinson, 2007; Clark and Cemlyn, 2005) which makes it difficult for them to extend levels of support to include helping their children with homework.

Moreover, one cannot overlook the poverty that many parents are often facing, which may serve as a barrier to being sufficiently involved in education. According to the Council of Europe (2003, p. 12) Roma families 'greatest concern [may be] finding ways to satisfy their daily needs' and may act to limit parental involvement in education or prevent young people from attending school (Burchardt et al., 2018). Indeed, in an attempt to meet their daily needs, parents may expect their children to enter the world of work at an early age, or to act as childminders for their siblings so that the parents themselves can earn a living (Mulcahy, et al., 2017). Drawing on Ciuffetelli Parker (2013), it is necessary to understand the impact of poverty on families and the often contested decision between providing food for one's family or losing an income due to a lack of money for childcare.

Ciuffetelli Parker (2013) further argues that schools have to understand how poverty affects families in order to build trust and close the attainment gap. From this perspective, successful schools and teachers do not assign blame to families when young people are underachieving but are oriented toward understanding the implications of poverty on their attainment (*ibid*). As families are often extremely poor and cannot afford books or stationary, this may also affect engagement and prevent young people from doing homework (Council of Europe, 2003). To this end, schools and teachers need to understand how the intersection of inequality and deprivation impacts on young Roma, Gypsy and Traveller people without assigning blame to families or pathologising culture if we are to successfully address achievement and attainment.

While the aforementioned research points to more positive attitudes towards education, further barriers include parental concerns relating to their children's safety within the school environment due to racism and bullying (Bhopal, 2011; Myers et al., 2010). Racist bullying is

often cited as the most common reason by parents for being reluctant to send their children to school (Foster and Norton, 2012). Recent research by D'Arcy (2017) found that Romani Gypsy and Showpeople parents were committed to their young people receiving education but withdrew them from school due to racist bullying. Other concerns raised by the parents include low teacher expectations and stereotypical attitudes (Foster and Norton, 2012); the lack of understanding on the part of the schools about students cultural heritage (Wilkin, Derrington and Foster, 2009); and curriculum relevance (Cudworth, 2008).

Stereotypes and Racism

While Roma, Romani Gypsies, Scottish Travellers and Irish Travellers are protected groups under the Equality Act (2010), they continue to face significantly high levels of racial prejudice and discrimination. Sir Trevor Phillips (the then Chair of the Commission for Racial Equality) described the prejudice and discrimination exhibited toward Gypsy and Traveller people as 'the last "respectable" form of racism' (2004, as cited in Foster and Norton, 2012, p. 87). More recently, the Traveller Movement found that 91 percent of Gypsy, Roma and Traveller people have experienced hate speech or a hate crime due to their ethnicity (The Traveller Movement, 2017).

Mainstream communities have historically and contemporaneously perceived Roma, Gypsy and Traveller as 'rogues, vagabonds and vagrants', (Mayall, 1995, p. 40), dirty thieves, who do not send their children to school, who live in caravans and outside of the law (Marcus, 2015). Clark and Taylor (2014) contend that these perceptions are linked to Roma, Gypsy and Traveller communities presumed nomadism by settled communities. They argue, that while community members are merely looking for accommodation and a means to provide for their families, settled society will perpetuate a 'well-worn accusatory list of "anti-social behaviours" – litter, tax avoidance, noise, crime, [and] welfare fraud' (*ibid*, p. 1).

These master narratives become engrained in the public imaginary and reinforce stereotypes and stigmatisation. The implications of these master narratives manifesting in behaviour may be illuminated by a recent YouGov and Traveller Movement survey (YouGov, 2017) that found 42 percent of the population would be unhappy if a close relative were to have a long-term relationship with or marry a Gypsy Traveller. While the Scottish Social Attitudes Survey (Scottish Government, 2015e) recently found that 35 percent of the Scottish population felt that a Gypsy/Traveller would be unsuitable as a primary school teacher.

Over the years, research has also consistently highlighted that Gypsy and Traveller people are subjected to racist bullying in schools (Bhopal, 2004, 2011; Derrington and Kendall, 2004; Foster and Norton, 2012). The Traveller Movement (2017) found that 70 percent of community members had experienced prejudice and discrimination within educational settings. Respondents noted that teachers often perpetuated stereotypes and overlooked racist incidents when they were reported by learners. Similarly, a third of the young people who participated in research conducted by Derrington and Kendall (2003) believed that some teachers themselves perpetuated racist attitudes towards them.

Experiencing racist bullying and discrimination may also result in young people retaliating. Lloyd et al. (1999) found that Scottish Travellers often responded to racist bullying incidents by retaliating resulting in conflict with teachers. Similarly, Derrington and Kendall, (2003) found that half of their secondary school participants had been punished by teachers for retaliating to racist name-calling and bullying resulting in a breakdown between pupil and teachers relationships. Derrington (2007) suggests that a breakdown in student-teacher relationships may increase the likelihood of learners' choosing to self-exclude and disengaging from education. In support of this, Levinson and Sparkes (2005) found that the young people in their study would simply go home if problems arose at school. The relationship breakdown between pupils and teachers has far reaching implications beyond the impact on the individual pupil and schools may underestimate the damage that breakdowns have on the community at large.

The importance placed on family ties by Roma, Gypsy and Traveller people ensures that such news spreads rapidly and one family's experience has the potential to influence broader community perceptions (Lloyd and McCluskey, 2008). By way of illustration, Jordan and Carrol's (1994) research on young Showpeople, found that when teacher/pupil conflict arose, families would stand together and move all children from one school to another. Showpeople between the ages of 14 and 15 would, however, deal with this conflict by simply dropping out of school. In order to remedy these negative implications, Wilkin et al. (2010) have argued for increased attention to be placed on psycho-social factors to reduce drop-out rates and increase attainment.

Finally, pervasive stereotypes exist that propagate the idea that Roma, Gypsy and Traveller communities are not interested in education and further contribute to the educational exclusion of these students (Wilkin et al., 2010). Stereotypes are often linked to the idea that Roma,

Gypsy and Traveller people would rather exclude themselves from mainstream education in order to preserve their own culture (Flecha and Soler, 2013). Researchers have, however, contested this and instead argued that these stereotypical stock stories are used by mainstream society in order to keep these communities marginalised (Hancock, 1988; Rose, 1983) and limit the educational opportunities available to them (D'Arcy, 2017). In the context of the cultural deficit model, teachers problematize Roma, Gypsy and Traveller culture (Lloyd and McCluskey 2008; Devarakonda, 2013) through oft heard scripts that are used to explain learners underachievement (LeBas, 2014).

Research conducted by Wilkin et al. (2010) found that teachers often attributed low attainment outcomes to parental and community attitudes. Moreover, the authors demonstrated that teachers believed these students were incapable of meeting attainment targets of five or more GCSEs at level C or above. A number of authors attribute low teacher expectations to engrained master narratives wherein young people are disadvantaged due to their culture (Zachos and Panagiotidou, 2019). The implications of negative teacher attitudes is that young Roma, Gypsy and Traveller people become more marginalised; are more reluctant to attend school (Warrington, 2007); and parents are more likely to withdraw their children from mainstream education (Riaz, 2014).

Aspirations

There is a paucity of literature on Roma, Gypsy and Traveller students' educational and career aspirations, illuminating the need for further research in order to address this gap in knowledge. D'Arcy's (2017) doctoral research considered the reasons why Showpeople and English Gypsy/Travellers were home-educated. She found that elected-home education focused on Traveller culture, with parents transmitting the knowledge and skills that they felt relevant in order for their children to earn a living in adulthood. This intergenerational knowledge transference included the blending of reading and writing opportunities with vocational learning. One of the young people who participated in her research had completed a welding course in a further education college. Another research participant who was being home educated, helped with family responsibilities in the house while providing accounting and customer service support in her parents shop. Beyond these findings, D'Arcy (2017) did not explicitly explore participants' aspirations for the future. Moreover her research only included mother's voices with young people contributing to the research 'sporadically' (*ibid*, 76). While fathers were present for the interviews, they were in the background and did not

contribute to the research or their children's education – a common finding across the literature (see for e.g. Marcus, 2016; Levinson, 2015).

Marcus' (2016) PhD thesis explored the intersecting invisible experiences of Gypsy/Traveller girls in Scotland and found that out of her sample of 13 research participants, 11 aspired to marriage and having children. Further, over half of those 11 young people did not believe that they could have both a family and a career. Some of the girls aspired to be beauticians or hairdressers when they grew up but acknowledged that they would have to stop working when they got married. Only two of the girls did not want to get married or have children because they had 'bigger ambitions for their life' (*ibid*, p. 246), with one of the participants aspiring to a career in horsemanship, while the other was attending college taking cooking and hairdressing courses. Although Marcus' work addresses significant silences in the literature, her research only focuses on Scottish Traveller girls and is not inclusive of other communities who face significant disadvantage. Moreover, a large body of the literature details accounts from Roma, Gypsy and Traveller women (Hamilton, 2017, Kiddle, 1999, Marcus, 2016, Okely, 1983), with a lacuna of research considering the experiences of men and boys (see for e.g. Okely, 1983; O'Boyle 1990; Levinson, 2015; Levinson and Sparkes, 2003).

Levinson's (2015) research with two Gypsy communities in the South West of England explored the changing aspirations of young people and the implications for future cultural identities. Levinson found that all 11 young people were positively disposed toward education and held intentions of taking their GCSE exams in Year 11 (age 16). Students also planned on entering further education through college following their GCSE's as a means of achieving their goals – despite having no immediate family members who had gone to college or university. Learners' ambitions for the future included being a hairdresser, carpenter, chef, shop-assistant, teacher, soldier and paramedic. Importantly their aspirations remained stable over a two year period. The young people, however, felt that there were limited opportunities in schools to pursue vocations such as tree surgery or mechanics and there was a general feeling that schools or career guidance would fail to support them as 'no one wanted [them]' (Levinson, 2015, p. 1160). Research participants included Gypsy/Traveller girls, boys and their mothers. Consistent with previous literature, fathers did not participate in the research (see for e.g. Marcus, 2016 and D'Arcy, 2017).

Greenfields (2008) research explored the aspirations of 38 Romani Gypsy, Irish Traveller and Showmen young people (aged between 12 and 23) and their attitudes towards careers in Health

and Social Care. Greenfields sample included 11 (eight English Romani Gypsies, one Showman and two Irish Travellers) males which revealed a clearly demarcated gender division regarding the types of occupations participants expressed an interest in due to gender norm socialisation. Female participants often cited aspirations related to childcare, working with disabled children and midwifery. It is thought that participants selected these careers as family members were often employed within the Health and Social Care sector in roles such as midwifery, nursing and care home assistant. While male participants identified aspirations related to physiotherapy or radiography they cited that occupations such as tree surgeons, mechanics or employment within the construction sector would be considered as more acceptable careers for men.

Less is known about Roma students' educational and career aspirations in the U.K, relegating the paucity of what is known to the European context. Peček and Munda (2015) explored primary school aged Roma students' attitudes toward education in Slovenia in response to majoritarian attitudes that purport that Roma do not value education. The authors found that learners demonstrated positive attitudes towards education, with students reporting that education was important for their future employment, confirming previous findings by Macura-Milovanović, (2006) and Munda and Peček (2013). It is important to note, however, that Peček and Munda (2015) advised that these results were due to safe school environments wherein students were nurtured to thrive (Joyce, 2018). The aspirations expressed by students were not homogeneous and included occupations such as doctor, lawyer, teacher, sales assistant, medical technician, caterer, mechanics, house painter, professional dancer, singer, athlete, sports coach and football player, with some of the young girls aspiring to be homemakers.

Employment

Contrary to stereotypes within the public imaginary where Roma, Gypsy and Traveller people are constructed as work-shy benefits scroungers (McGarry, 2014; Marcus, 2016), these communities work because they have to sustain themselves and their families (Liégeois, 1986). The family is seen as an economic entity where tasks are shared with members often pursuing self-employment that relies on manual skills (Levinson, 2015; Smith, 1997). Judith Okely (1979, p. 23) observed that the English Gypsies she had studied had become successful masters of their trades as they knew the 'local economy and the local people' and they had within them 'manual dexterity, mechanical ingenuity, highly developed memory, salesmanship and

bargaining skills'. Whyte (2001) provides an account on Scottish Travellers, illuminating their strong work ethic, a tradition of hard labour and self-employment as a means to survive.

According to Liégeois (1986, p. 77), Gypsies historically undertook a range of trades such as 'tinning, metalworking, basket-making, caning or stuffing chairs, regrinding, second-hand cars, and grape harvesting'. For Stewart (1997) and Clark (2001, p. 173), Gypsy and Traveller communities cited a preference for self-employment in trades such as 'scrap dealing, tarmacking, agricultural work [...] or gardening work', with some Scottish Travellers engaging in collecting whelks and pearl fishing (Neat, 1998). While women are largely responsible for home-making duties, they still contribute to the 'family purse' through trades such as 'running a market stall, selling bedding and towels and hawking' (Clark, 2001, p. 174). Many things have changed, however, since Liégeois (1986) and Clark (2001) made these observations due to the rapidly evolving world of work and draconian legislation that has 'culled' traditional Roma, Gypsy and Traveller occupations (Marcus, 2016a).

According to figures from the 2011 Census (ONS, 2014), Gypsy and Irish Travellers (circa 22 percent) were the ethnic groups that were most likely to work in elementary positions such as farm workers, process plant workers, cleaners or hospitality staff compared to the national average (circa 11 percent). They were also the ethnic groups, with the highest proportion of skilled trades (circa 19 percent) with community members working in occupations such as farmers, electrical and building positions in comparison to the national average (circa 12 percent). Community members from these backgrounds were however, the least likely to identify as being in professional occupations (circa 7 percent).

Although the literature suggests that there may be a tendency for Gypsy and Traveller community members to be self-employed, this pattern does not appear to be replicated amongst Roma populations to the same extent. O'Higgins and Ivanov (2006) contend that Roma from Bulgaria, the Czech Republic, Hungary, Romania and Slovakia are less likely to be self-employed and more likely to face discrimination when seeking employment. Research conducted by the European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights exploring Roma students transition from education to employment across nine European member states found that many were likely to be in low-skilled and hard labour jobs (FRA, 2018).

Drydakakis (2012) examined the employment of Roma women in Athenian organisations and found that younger Roma women were more likely to demonstrate higher secondary school graduation rates. Findings also suggested that Roma women who held a higher education level

faced a smaller wage gap than those with a lower education level, suggesting the importance of education in increasing economic status. Overall findings indicated that Roma women were more likely to be occupationally segregated (Bergmann, 1996), occupy low-paid blue-collar jobs, work in the service industries and more likely to face labour market discrimination than non-Roma.

Drydakis (2012) concluded that these patterns were reflective of Becker's (1957) hypothesis of prejudices and Bergmann's (1996) assumptions of occupational segregation. Nevertheless, these findings contribute to the dearth of knowledge in relation to Roma women's employment practices across Europe. Further evidence of subtle changes in Roma employment patterns across the European context were presented by Foster and Cemlyn (2012, p. 63) who pointed to the 'small but growing educated minority Roma' who were working in both non-governmental and central government positions and who were highly influential particularly within the context of the 'Decade of Roma Inclusion 2005 – 2015'.

There is however, a dearth of literature on Roma employment within the U.K highlighting the need for further knowledge in order to address this gap (see for e.g. Greenfields, 2008; Ryder and Greenfields, 2010). Foster and Norton (2012) observe that community members often engage in employment related to painting, decorating, collecting scrap metal, second hand car dealing, and selling The Big Issue. Martin et al. (2017) conducted research with 159 Roma participants across England and Scotland, and found that the majority of community members were primarily employed in occupations such as working in chicken and potato factories and in restaurants. A number of participants also illustrated the exploitative work practices they had experienced and often worked for less than minimum wage.

Clark (2018) explored the everyday experiences of Roma migrants living in Scotland through the lens of employment. Research participants often cited occupations related to being a delivery driver or potato farmer. Clark correctly pointed out that the current economic climate in light of the EU Referendum result only serves to add an extra layer of difficulty in securing decent work for Roma, with these community members often having to occupy employment positions characterised as insecure, temporary and without sick pay or holiday entitlements.

Conclusion

To conclude, this chapter has outlined and synthesised the literature relating to who Roma, Gypsy and Traveller people are, their experiences of education, qualification levels and employment practices across various policy contexts in England, Scotland and Wales. It has been shown that despite interventions and policy to improve attainment outcomes, Roma, Gypsy, and Traveller students' school experiences continue to be marred by absenteeism, underachievement and significantly high drop-out rates compared to the national average (Harding, 2014). Early disengagement from school has far reaching implications and has been associated with exclusion from further and higher education (Clark, 2004), the labour market in adulthood (Kóczé, 2009) as well as having a lower economic status (Drydakis, 2012) and fewer opportunities overall (Geraghty, Erbstein, and Greenfield, 2010).

Florian, (2016) argues that there is not a catch all solution to bridge the attainment gap, while Blanden et al., (2015) suggests that school success does not result from a single intervention. Where young people do gain the necessary qualifications to enter further and higher education, there are perceived barriers of not belonging and the threat of continued persecution based on their ethnicity (Coan, 2019). There is a need for further research into how far we are from ameliorating the barriers faced by young Gypsy, Roma and Traveller people.

One such intervention that has been largely overlooked, is that of career education and guidance in increasing attendance and improving attainment for students from these backgrounds. The need for career education and guidance has never been more vital for marginalised communities due to the rapidly evolving labour market. In the chapter that follows I present existing knowledge illuminating the need for career education and guidance in equipping young people with the knowledge and the skills required to traverse a rapidly evolving and precarious labour market. The subsequent chapter will then detail the critical role of career education and guidance in fostering students' aspirations, increasing engagement and retention in education (Hooley et al., 2011) and potentially helping them into jobs with higher pay (Hughes et al., 2016). I will also illustrate the potential for career guidance to support students to challenge stereotypes in relation to 'what people like them do' (Holman, 2014). The chapter then considers the various sources of career education and guidance available to young people and before turning to explore career education and guidance policy developments across England, Wales and Scotland.

Chapter Three

Literature Review

This second part of my double literature review provides a critical analysis of the existing literature related to the careers field that has informed my study. The purpose of this chapter is to identify the issues and debates that inform this research. The first part provides a critical review of career education and guidance literature, detailing the positive role of interventions and the likely sources of support that students will approach for guidance. There follows a short overview of the inherent power of career education and guidance in facilitating learners' to challenge stereotypes in relation to 'what people like them do'. As becomes clear, the literature examining Roma, Gypsy and Traveller experiences of career education and guidance is near non-existent thereby illuminating the need for further research in order to address this gap in knowledge. The second part of this chapter contains a critical review of the respective career guidance and skills policy developments across the three home nations. I also demonstrate examples within current policy and practice that illustrate a lack of understanding of community-specific needs regarding language barriers, digital literacy, and internet access.

Career Education and Guidance

Current transitions from education into the world of work are generally considered to be more challenging than they have been previously. Technological advancements and increased digitization is dramatically altering the nature of the labour market and the skills needed within the world of work (Taylor, 2017). According to the Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) one third of jobs within the U.K. are expected to be replaced by automation over the next ten years (Nedelkoska and Quintini, 2018). The OECD (2020, p. 12), also suggests that the occupational aspirations that young people are currently expressing are problematic as they are '19th- and 20th- century occupations' that are outdated and fail to take into consideration the rapid acceleration of automation, thereby further illustrating the need for the equitable provision of career education and guidance. Moreover, the precarious nature of the labour market is further exacerbated by recent political events such as the U.K. leaving the European Union (McCrorry and Thomsen, 2019; Clark, 2020) and public health crises such as the COVID 19 pandemic (Blustein et al., 2020). Collectively these events are likely to deepen existing inequalities.

‘Career’ then, can no longer be viewed as static and for life (Hooley et al., 2011). By way of illustration, the Centre for Social and Economic Inclusion (2014) suggests that by 2020, over nine million people who are considered to have low-skills will be competing for four million low-skilled jobs alongside regional variations. Young people, then, have to acquire skills and traverse highly complex pathways within a labour market that is rapidly evolving. Career education and guidance has been proposed as a mechanism to provide individuals with the necessary knowledge and skills to meet the needs of the labour market (Moote and Archer, 2018).

Similarly, ‘Career Management Skills’ have been increasingly promoted as a mechanism to address the precarious nature of labour markets across the European Union and within the U.K. According to Sultana (2012, p. 229), the term ‘Career Management Skills’ (CMS) refers to:

A whole range of competences which provide structured ways for individuals and groups to gather, analyse, synthesise and organise self, educational and occupational information, as well as the skills to make and implement decisions and transitions.

From this perspective, individuals are supported to develop competences and skills so that they may better plan and manage their education, training and employment decisions within an unpredictable labour market. Sultana (2012) observes that countries across the European Union are adopting CMS as a framework in order to increase employability as a means of promoting social equity and inclusion. The U.K Government as well as the devolved administrations have increasingly embedded CMS frameworks within their policies. This includes a focus on CMS both within personal guidance (Neary et al., 2016) as well as within programmes of career education across curriculums (Sultana, 2012).

There is, however, a danger in the various administrations’ emphasis on CMS within policy and practice in light of the shrinking job market (Sennett, 1998). The trend toward ‘individualisation’ inherent within the CMS approach is that those who find themselves unemployed will be portrayed as deficient, having only have themselves to blame, despite potential unemployment being linked to structural factors and not individual deficiencies. It is critical then that CMS approaches recognise the interplay between structure and agency as an individual’s success within the labour market is dependent on the economic environment and often needs structural solutions (Simon et al., 1991; Sultana, 2012).

The positive role of Career Education and Guidance

Career education and guidance works to help young people understand both the educational and career routes available to them whilst simultaneously enhancing their understanding of their own aspirations and competences (Hooley et al., 2011). The role of career education and guidance then is critical to students' aspirations and their subsequent career development (Watson and McMahon, 2005), potentially helping them into jobs with higher pay (Hughes et al., 2016). Career guidance has been correlated with a number of positive outcomes such as increased motivation (Moote and Archer, 2018) broader aspirations, greater awareness of opportunities, progression (Hooley et al. 2014) and better academic achievement (Hughes et al., 2016). Moreover, a number of commentators have highlighted that career guidance serves to promote social equity (Archer et al., 2014a) and upward social mobility (Hughes, 2017; Hutchinson, 2012).

Career education and guidance has also been found to increase engagement, retention and prevent students' disengagement from education (Andrews and Hooley, 2017; Hooley et al., 2011). Bridgeland et al. (2006) explored why individuals chose to drop out of school and the factors that might have increased their engagement and retention in the school system. 81 percent of participants indicated that their chances of completing secondary school would have been improved had they been provided the opportunity to engage in real-world and work-related learning. Similarly, Plank et al. (2005) conducted a longitudinal study and found that career education alongside core academic learning reduced the risk of dropping out.

Evans and Burck's (1992) meta-analysis illuminates the value of career education as a key component of academic achievement. The authors found a positive effect on academic achievement and a larger effect when considering certain subjects such as Maths and English. Moreover, a larger effect was also found for young people who experienced career education at a younger age. Lapan and colleagues' (2011) study on the relationships between comprehensive guidance programmes and well-being indicators amongst 22,601 young people may help explain these findings. Students attending schools that fully implemented comprehensive career guidance programmes reported feeling safer at school, better relationships with their teachers, believed that their education was more relevant to their futures, experienced fewer interpersonal problems at school and achieved higher grades. The caveat, however, is that the frequency and duration of encounters with programmes of career education and guidance was of great significance (Lapan et al., 2011).

This is evident in the case of Choi and colleagues (2015) longitudinal study exploring the relationship between participation in career education and school success amongst South Korean adolescents. Findings indicated that engaging in the programme once or twice yielded greater results. Conversely, there was no relationship between career education and school success for young people who engaged with the programme once or not at all. Similarly, a Portuguese study on the effects of two types of career interventions on young people's coping styles and career adaptability found that one-off interventions in the form of a single career information session was less effective than a six-week career education intervention (Janeiro et al., 2014). The implication of these studies suggests the need for sustained engagements and the resources necessary to support such interventions.

Janeiro and colleagues (2014) and Slack et al. (2013) argue that due to the lack of adequate funding coupled with time constraints, career education and guidance in schools is often a question of economics thereby resulting in the provision of one-off personal guidance sessions. Given the importance of sustained personal guidance engagements, recent DfE (2018), guidelines as well as the Gatsby Report (Holman, 2014) fall short. For example, both suggest that all young people should have at least one personal guidance interview by the age of 16 and access to another interview by the age of 18 (Holman, 2014; DfE, 2018). Moreover, if the most vulnerable period for dropping out of secondary school for young Roma, Gypsy and Traveller people is between the ages of 13-14 (Derrington and Kendall, 2003; Derrington, 2016) then statutory guidance needs to consider earlier access to personal guidance interviews for young from these backgrounds in primary school (Archer et al., 2014b; Hughes, & Kashefpakdel, 2019).

Sources of Career Education and Guidance

There are a broad range of factors in students social and environmental contexts that interact to influence their career development learning and ultimately shape their career aspirations and decision-making. Research indicates that socio-economic environment (Croll, 2008; Archer et al., 2014b), parents (Trice, 1991), career education and guidance (Wahl and Blackhurst, 2000) and the school environment (Lapan et al., 2007) all carry significant weight in influencing young people's aspirations and career decisions.

A large body of research has established the influence and impact of socio-economic and structural factors on young people's career aspirations (Roberts, 2009; Roberts and Atherton,

2011). Weinger (1998) highlighted that living in poverty restricts students occupational aspirations and knowledge. Conversely, Bandura and colleagues (2001) found socio-economic status to have no influence on the development of students' aspirations and instead argued that parental aspirations mediated the effects of socio-economic status.

More recently, Archer and colleagues (2014b) explored students' aspirations in science during their last year of primary school (age 10-11) as well as in their second year of secondary school (age 12-13) through a mixed methods longitudinal design. Notably, both the quantitative and qualitative data indicated that most Ethnic minority young people expressed high occupational aspirations, however, proportionally more students within the cohort were categorised as having high cultural capital compared to those with low cultural capital. The authors operationalised cultural capital based on, 'parental university attendance, leaving school before 16, number of books in the home and visits to the museum' (Archer et al., 2014b, p. 61). Within this context, research has also highlighted that while students may have high aspirations, limited economic, cultural and social capital, may serve to constrain their ambitions (Croll, 2008; Yates et al., 2011). To this end, Croll (2008, p. 255) argues that young people with high aspirations and disadvantaged backgrounds are 'less likely to be educationally equipped to realise their ambitions'. Background then, may influence what a young person perceives as achievable within their frame of reference (Hodkinson and Sparkes, 1997).

Research has suggested that parents and the wider family circle are extremely influential in their children's career learning and aspirational development. Authors have argued for decades that young people choose occupational levels that match parental expectations and occupations (Helwig 1998; Trice, 1991; Trice et al., 1995; Young and Friesen, 1992; Bandura et al., 2001). Archer et al. (2014b) found that 47 percent of young people aspired to have the same job as a family member or friend of the family. Similarly, Simon et al. (2012) highlighted the importance of family members in influencing young people's career choices. In support of this, research also points to parents being pivotal in their children's decision-making and some research contends that they are often the 'Chief Adviser' (Haynes, et al., 2013, p. 461).

Young people relying solely on parental advice may, however, be problematic and consideration must be given to parental educational levels and their knowledge of the labour market. Parents who have experienced a history of unemployment and little exposure to further or higher education coupled with limited access to career and labour market information may have limited knowledge of career progression routes (Haynes, et al., 2013). School may often

be the only source of reliable career guidance and labour market information that young people may have access to.

The influence of the school in promoting career education and aspirational development has been widely discussed with commentators arguing that career education is vital as it provides young people with realistic occupational information, challenges stereotypes and helps parents understand their own role in their children's subsequent career development (Wahl and Blackhurst, 2000). However, the school environment that career education and guidance is delivered in is of importance. McMahon et al. (2000) found that career education was a result of young people drawing from their whole school experience, with young people identifying sources of career related learning through subjects, topics and activities within the curriculum as well as learning from extra-curricular activities.

Relevant to the current study, Mulcahy and colleagues (2017) found that their sample of young Gypsy, Roma and Traveller people reported limited experiences talking to parents, teachers and other adults about university, especially if they had dropped out of education prior to Year 11. Through discussions with Gypsy, Roma and Traveller research participants' in focus groups, Mulcahy et al. (2017) suggested that respondents were able to address their misconceptions through asking questions and receiving information about higher education thereby changing their perceptions of an unfamiliar environment. These findings led the authors to recommend that both primary and secondary schools in the U.K should have discussions with Gypsy, Roma and Traveller students and their parents focusing on general information, careers and further study in order to clear up misconceptions and broaden aspirations. Likewise, in another study conducted in the U.K by Wilkin and colleagues (2010) the authors briefly allude to one school that appeared to reduce drop-out rates by using 'counsellors' to raise Roma, Gypsy and Traveller students' awareness of the labour market (p. 67). Although the researchers employ the term 'counsellors', it is thought that the reference was made in relation to 'Career Advisers'.

Research by Greenfields (2008) did not explicitly explore experiences of career guidance, however, it did examine Gypsy and Travellers perceptions of Health and Social Care careers in the U.K. Findings indicated that participants were able to identify careers such as care assistants and nurses due to family members being employed in such roles. Participants were, however, less likely to identify careers related to medicine namely radiography, physiotherapy and chiropody. Moreover, Greenfields research identified that participant's demonstrated

limited knowledge regarding training bursaries to support eligible health and social care staff. These findings point to the need for career advice and guidance related to different types of employment for community members in addition to signposting community members to relevant training bursaries in order to facilitate social mobility.

Finally, research conducted by Beremenyi (2020) in South West Hungary explored career guidance inequalities amongst 34 Roma young people (aged between 20 and 35) in the context of labour shortages. In examining how young people make school and career choices, Beremenyi found that school and career choice is largely determined by class and mediated by familial and school habitus. Overall decisions were largely driven by school settings marked by inequality that resulted in access to less competitive courses and low-paid jobs with limited social mobility. In assessing post-school support in Hungary, findings suggested that career guidance provision was discontinuous over the life-cycle, with a high degree of disconnection between service providers and delivered by non-specialists which further served to marginalise Roma community members.

Challenging Stereotypes

For young people from marginalised backgrounds, challenges exist within their day-to-day lives, wherein societal stereotypes and negative messages have the potential to be internalised (Solórzano, 1992). This internalisation may shape their future worldview and influence attitudes and behaviours. In support, Holman (2014) argues that students often internalise ideas pertaining to what ‘people like them do’. Similarly, Wong (2012) contends that if certain careers are perceived in the dominant view to be for people with certain traits and attributes such as gender, class or ethnicity, then learners who do not identify with those traits may aspire to careers that are more aligned with their self-identity. Indeed, Archer and colleagues (2014b, p. 68) found that between the ages of 12 and 13, young people began ‘situating themselves within, quite complex gendered, classed and racialized identities and inequalities, which render particular jobs as more possible’.

The context in which career guidance takes place as well as the skills and knowledge of the Career Adviser has the potential to help students overcome barriers, but only if they take into consideration their unique background and the social injustice that they may face (Sultana, 2014). Watts (2001), therefore argues that Career Advisers need to understand and have knowledge of young people’s unique frame of reference and subjective realities if interventions are going to be effective.

Similarly, Field and Baker (2004) emphasised the importance of the Career Adviser in championing equality and diversity through an ‘empowered frame of reference’. From this perspective, Career Advisers should not only advocate on behalf of students but they should also teach self-advocacy skills aimed to empower. Learners can then draw on these skills to ‘bridge future barriers, whether they be academic, emotional, social and/or environmentally based’ (Field and Baker, 2004, p.57). While these authors observe the transformative potential of career guidance, it must be noted that this emancipation can only take place if young people have equitable access to services. Research, however, appears to contend that Black and Ethnic minority communities have less opportunities to access services that may enable them to bridge structural barriers and ‘emancipate themselves’.

Archer and Moote (2016) conducted a national survey of young people in Year 11 in English secondary schools exploring their experiences of career education and work experience. This mixed methods design involved survey sampling data to 32,000 participants as well as in-depth longitudinal interviews with a tracked subsample of young people and their parents. The data revealed that less than two thirds of students in Year 11 had reported receiving career education. Moreover, the authors found career education provision to be patchy. Overall, one’s social belonging or identity group determined and reflected the in/equality of provision. Young white students were significantly more likely to have received career education than young Ethnic minority people, while boys were more likely to report receiving career education than girls. In support of these findings, Sampson and colleagues (2011) suggested that equitable access to career education and guidance is a social justice issue, as those who are often on the receiving end of social injustice are those who are furthest away from support.

The Gatsby Report (2014) observes that career guidance can play an active role in tackling assumptions based on gendered, ethnic or socio-economic assumptions, but as Watts (2001, p. 173) argues, the ‘primary role of guidance service lies in lubricating the societal structures to which inclusion is being sought’. According to Sultana (2014), the role of the Career Adviser then is to not only operate at the micro interactive level, but to make a difference on the meso or institutional, level. From this perspective, Career Advisers could work with students, empowering them to challenge internalised racism and sexism whilst simultaneously playing an advocacy role on their behalf by lobbying for the restructuring of institutional practices that reproduce injustice.

Questions remain, however, as to whether socially just career education and guidance can indeed be attained in the context of a neoliberal state. As Hooley et al. (2018, p. 17) argue, when viewed through a neoliberal and meritocratic lens, career guidance has the potential to ‘serve as a mechanism for responsabilisation and co-option’. Career Advisers increasingly have to meet target demands and ‘number crunching’ to justify their existence but this may involve an ethical trade off wherein the practitioner has less time to play an advocacy role.

Career Education and Guidance across England, Scotland and Wales

As mentioned in the preceding chapter, the Government of Wales Act and Scotland Act in 1998 resulted in the devolution of powers to the National Assembly for Wales and the Scottish Parliament that had previously been reserved to the U.K government (Bogdanor, 2001; Reynolds, 2008; Rees and Power, 2007). This saw the areas of education, skills and social policy devolved to the relevant administrations. This section details policy and practice in England and the divergence evident within Scottish and Welsh education and skills systems prior to devolution partly due to the Conservative Government’s 1979-1999 application of market principles to education and skills. The chapter also details how devolution further drove divergence between the home nations, in the form of differentiated career education and guidance delivery models (Howieson and Semple, 2006; Watts, 2006).

Career Education and Guidance in English Schools

Career guidance in English schools can be traced back to the 1920s with very few developments in the early years (Andrews, 2011). The late 1940s saw the emergence of Youth Employment Officers within local authorities focusing guidance around ‘matching’ interventions in order to support young people in their transition from school to work (Peck, 2004). The Employment and Training Act (1973) resulted in the creation of the Career Service and a stronger emphasis on provision in schools. However, this provision was limited and reactive as it only engaged young people at the point of transition (Hooley et al., 2014).

Despite initial limitations, the Career Service along with schools and colleges in England delivered career guidance services through partnership model working approaches spanning three decades between the 1970s and 1990s. Within this model, schools and colleges led on the

career education aspect, while the Career Services led on the delivery of professional career guidance as well as acting as a brokerage service between employers and schools (Hooley et al., 2014). Hooley and colleagues (2014) argue that career education and guidance provision was adequately funded during this period, ensuring that schools along with the Career Service had the resources necessary to provide meaningful services to young people.

During this time, the Conservative Government's 1979-1999 policies and its focus on applying market principles to education meant that career provision was removed from the remit of local authorities. The Trade Union Reform and Employment Rights Act (1993) amended the Employment and Training Act (1973) and resulted in the restructuring of career services (House of Commons, 1993). The implication of this is that the 'careers' marketplace slowly began opening up to market forces, leading to greater competition between providers with school's having to purchase career guidance based on tenders. Increasingly, career guidance began to be seen as a necessary mechanism that was to be used throughout an individual's life. The focus then, shifted towards career education and guidance wherein young people acquired the skills and knowledge to manage their career (Andrews, 2011). It wasn't until the Education Act of 1997, however, that career education became statutory.

2001 then saw the Labour Government create an integrated youth support service known as Connexions that had the remit of providing holistic career guidance services to young people in English schools. Criticisms pertaining to the Connexions service included a weakened career element, erosion of career professionalism, the move away from a universal service and disjointed partnership working (Hooley et al., 2014).

More recent changes ushered in under the Education Act (2011) saw funding withdrawn from the Connexions service and direct responsibility for the provision of career guidance being shifted from local authorities and being placed on schools for *all* young people from Year 8 to Year 13 (age 12-18) (DfE, 2014a; 2014b). Despite this mass restructuring, schools did not, however, receive adequate guidelines or funding to provide effective services (Chadderton, 2015). Although schools now carry the responsibility for career services, it is still within the remit of local authorities to provide targeted career guidance to young people with Additional Support for Learning needs and those who are at risk of disengaging from education (Chadderton, 2015).

Following the disbanding of the Connexions service and the shifting of responsibility back to schools, the all-age government funded National Career Service (NCS) was then subsequently

established in 2012 resulting in further fragmented provision (Watts, 2013). This provision was however, problematic as one-to-one guidance was only provided to adults while young people only had access to telephone and online services (Hooley and Watts, 2011). The remit of the NCS was subsequently expanded in 2014 to include a brokerage role between schools and employers. Alongside the developments within the NCS the U.K Government announced its intentions to establish a new Careers and Enterprise Company (CEC) with the aim of providing a brokerage service in 2014 in order to transform career education provision through acting as a conduit and bringing businesses in to schools (House of Commons, 2016). Overall, the CEC's role is that of an umbrella organisation to fill in gaps in career and enterprise provision. Akin to the problems within the school-based provision as well as the NCS, this service does not mention professional guidance (DfE, 2014c).

Watts (2014a) argues that the move toward school-based guidance disregards the plethora of evidence suggesting that career guidance has the most impact when it is part of a coherent programme of career education embedded in the curriculum and work experience opportunities related learning to support students' career choices. The implications of schools taking responsibility for career guidance services coupled with severe funding cuts are far-reaching. Evidence indicates that school-based career provision results in deterioration of services (Hooley et al., 2012; Watts, 2013). Further, within this new framework, only the non-statutory guidance documents mentioned that provision 'should include face-to-face support where needed' (DfE, 2014b, p. 20) and guidelines were vague about whether the guidance should be delivered by professional Career Advisers (Watts, 2014a; 2014b).

Alongside these developments, a rapid expansion of career provision companies flooded the unregulated career marketplace leaving schools as purchasers of career guidance services (House of Commons, 2016). Then adding another body to the confusion in January 2016, the Department for Work and Pensions (DWP) launched its Job Centre Plus schools initiative wherein local Jobcentre advisers provided young people between the ages of 12 and 18 advice and guidance on traineeships and apprenticeships (Hughes, 2017). While the CEC is meant to be an umbrella body, the DWP's schools initiative does not operate under this umbrella (House of Commons, 2016).

Career guidance provision in England has been in a state of disarray for a number of years (Roberts, 2013). The literature presented thus far has revealed that provision since 2011 has included a number of disparate and uncoordinated initiatives that only serve to confuse schools

as to which organisation or body provides relevant services. The implications of fragmented career guidance provision from 2011 to the present, is that young people have been leaving secondary school *en masse* without the skills or knowledge needed to identify how their skills fit with current and future labour market opportunities. In order to address these issues, the then Prime Minister Theresa May (HMG, 2017) announced a new industrial strategy (DfE, 2017) calling for improving education and skills through careers provision.

During this time, the Government also signalled that employer engagement and enterprise advisers were a high priority (Hughes, 2017). The Department for Education (2018) subsequently updated statutory guidance based on the aforementioned strategy to ensure that all young people in secondary school receive a programme of advice and guidance from qualified professionals and to base programmes on the Gatsby Charitable Foundation's Benchmarks (Holman, 2014). One of the benchmarks includes embedding career learning in all subjects across the curriculum which the Scottish framework has done for a number of years (Scottish Government, 2011). Statutory guidance also includes increasing the remit of the CEC to provide external support to all schools (DfE, 2018) including the provision of employer engagement support and connecting schools to enterprise advisers (CEC, 2018). In addition, all schools now have a duty to appoint a Careers Leader who carry responsibility for the leadership and management of career education and guidance across the school (Andrews and Hooley, 2017).

While current changes to statutory guidance are being implemented in English schools, the key issue is how these policy changes will influence career education and provision in English schools and the implications for practice. Worryingly, however, is that while other disadvantaged groups are considered within new statutory guidance, Black and Ethnic minority young people are not (DfE, 2018). The current thesis argues that career services policy, guidance and practice must be designed to take into consideration all marginalised groups (Howard et al., 2006).

Career Education and Guidance in Wales

As mentioned previously, the provision of career guidance services across England, Scotland and Wales was broadly similar pre-devolution. The 1973 Employment and Training Act stipulated that career guidance provision be delivered through a Career Service that was managed by local education authorities across the home nations (Watts, 2006). Consistency across the home nations continued roughly until the 1993 Trade Union Reform and

Employment Rights Act after which one can observe the beginnings of divergence in the Welsh context.

The Welsh Office initially resisted government attempts to impose market principles in education, restricting tenders to existing partnerships (Clark and Talbot, 2006). However, a year after this initial resistance published guidance appears to suggest that tenders for career services were open to external bidders (Welsh Office, 1995). Despite this apparent back-peddling, all existing contracts were re-instated following the tendering process with only one external bidder being awarded a service level agreement in 1995. Five years later, the tendering process remained restricted to existing service providers (Clark and Talbot, 2006). Watts (2006) argues that the Welsh Office's resistance to marketization policies further entrenched the differentiated direction that would be sought following devolution.

Differentiated approaches were rapidly accelerated in 1999 with the establishment of the Welsh Assembly. Matters that were once reserved to the U.K were now devolved including education, training, industry and economic development (Watts, 2006). In 1999, the Education and Training Action Group for Wales published its 'Action Plan for Wales' (Education and Training Action Group for Wales, 1999) which set out an ambitious agenda and statement of intent to establish a national bilingual, lifelong, advice and guidance service known as 'Careers Wales'. According to Rees (2004, p. 31), the ambition asserted the Welsh administration's commitment to 'deep-seated social democratic values'.

These values are further demonstrated within recommendations laid out by the Education and Training Action Group for Wales (1999) which included: bringing existing providers under the Careers Wales banner; establishing a network to provide points of access for individuals seeking support; the provision of free career guidance for those furthest away from the labour market, those in precarious and low paid work and individuals facing redundancy; and working in partnership with education institutions and employers in order to streamline services.

In relation to education, the recommendations saw the embedding of career education into the curriculum and the Welsh Baccalaureate qualification (Welsh Joint Education Committee, 2001; Welsh Assembly 2004a). Further recommendations cited the mandatory provision of career education for all 16-19 year old students in school and college. The aforementioned recommendations were all subsequently implemented (Moulson and Prail, 2004). It is important to note here, that the provision of career guidance being mandatory in Wales for 16-19 years old differentiates from the Scottish model wherein young people are only guaranteed

access to services in schools and is dependent on their risk needs assessment (Scottish Government, 2020).

As mentioned previously, the establishment of the Connexions Service in 2001 (Hooley et al., 2014) resulted in a mass re-structuring of services including the integration of various youth service providers and the funding to support them. The Welsh Assembly, however, rejected these arrangements (National Assembly for Wales Policy Unit, 2000) citing that re-structuring would result in a costly disruption to provision while yielding little benefit. Moreover, it was thought that such a move would impede service improvements, and compromise the independence of Careers Wales.

The Welsh Assembly commissioned an independent review of Careers Wales in 2004 that lauded the careers service's all age, bilingual provision and pan-Wales influence as an outstanding achievement (Moulson and Prail, 2004). The authors noted that the lifelong service delivery provision was not a common feature across OECD countries (OECD, 2004). Following these developments, the Welsh Assembly (2004b) then firmly grounded Careers Wales as a public service citing it as an example of good practice within their 'Making Connections' policy document. The document, however, acknowledged that Careers Wales faced a number of challenges such as the need to evidence rigorous outcomes to demonstrate and justify the use of resources; a need further establish Careers Wales as a brand; and the need for a standardised set of guiding principles (Clark and Talbot, 2006). Despite these challenges, Clark and Talbot (2006, p. 55) observe that the 'critical mass' that Careers Wales provide, embedded within policy processes, meant that 'career guidance had a strong voice and public visibility'.

The Welsh Assembly (2008), subsequently published its statutory framework for career education and guidance in schools entitled, "Careers and the world of work: a framework for 11 to 19-year-olds in Wales". The framework was designed to facilitate students transitions from school into the rapidly evolving labour market. Inherent within the framework were learning objective targets for key stage three, key stage four and post-16 learners. The objectives of the framework would be achieved through the blending of teaching and learning experiences within programmes of education that would draw on external partners who would provide work placement opportunities as well as the provision of individual face-to-face guidance meetings.

In 2009, the Welsh Assembly then commissioned another independent review (Welsh Assembly, 2009) to explore Career Wales provision in relation to the OECD Benchmarks (OECD, 2004). Findings demonstrated that Careers Wales met the majority of criteria as set out by the OECD benchmarks. The strengths of the body included its boundedness, lifelong provision, its professionalism and the extent to which it was embedded in both Welsh Assembly policies as well as local communities and the bilingual nature of its services. A number of weaknesses were, however, also observed. By way of illustration, despite Careers Wales being an all age service, only 15 percent of its resources were allocated to supporting adult clients. Addressing this gap would require a significant increase in resources, which the Welsh Assembly could not provide due to budgetary pressures (Webb et al., 2007). In lieu of the economic means to address this disparity, a significant re-modelling of services would be required including the need to move towards a differentiated service delivery design.

Based on these findings, the Welsh Assembly (2010) subsequently moved to re-structure Careers Wales with a focus on differentiated service delivery within their publication entitled 'Future Ambitions: Developing Careers Services in Wales'. This meant that previously semi-independent Careers Wales companies operating regionally were incorporated into the careers service. Within the report however, concerns were raised regarding re-structuring and the potential for an over-centralised organisation. From this perspective, there was a danger that local responsiveness would be lost if an element of the regional structure was not retained (Welsh Assembly, 2010). Further developments included greater integration and the use of digital technology within service provision. Whilst it was suggested that these developments aimed to increase the synergy and coherence of service provision, the report also acknowledged the economic and resource implications therein.

A report commissioned by the Welsh Assembly entitled 'Successful Futures' (Donaldson, 2015) was then conducted to examine the curriculum in Wales. Findings demonstrated that young people called for a greater emphasis on career education within the curriculum which led to substantial changes to the Welsh Baccalaureate Qualification. Further changes included removing the requirement for young people to undertake a work experience placement and replacing it with the Enterprise and Employability challenge. The Enterprise and Employability challenge was designed to facilitate students' enterprising skills development through the provision of opportunities within the school environment with the aim of enhancing their employability (Welsh Joint Education Committee, 2015).

Estyn (2017) examined the scope and effectiveness of the statutory ‘Careers and the world of work framework’ within secondary schools. Findings suggested that the majority of schools provided advice and guidance to students in Year nine when making their subject choices for key stage four. Parents were also included in these discussions with Career Advisers during open evenings. The review also indicated that most students were provided general information regarding their post-16 options. Concerns were, however, raised regarding the reduced support offered by Careers Wales which was seen to negatively impact on students access to career guidance. Schools also felt that due to the increasing demands related to delivering the key stage four curriculum, they battled to meet the demands of delivering the Careers and world of work framework (Estyn, 2017). The report also noted that the number of students engaging in work experience opportunities had reduced significantly, due in part to Careers Wales no longer having to maintain a national work experience database. Overall, schools believed that these developments had significantly impacted on learners’ career exploration.

In order to address the limitations identified by Estyn (2017), Careers Wales (2017) subsequently published its renewed strategic vision within the ‘Changing Lives: A vision for Careers Wales 2017-2020’ document, that included a stronger focus on young people and enhanced services to support their transition into employment. During this time, Careers Wales also placed an increased emphasis on the use of technology in the provision of career services for the purposes of ‘efficiency savings’ (Careers Wales, 2017, p. 20). Within its publication, Careers Wales also introduced the ‘Career Discovery Model’ that sets out the services available to students. The model posits that from Year nine, learners will have access to a workshop when selecting GCSE, where they will be sign-posted to a web chat that can be utilised to explore career routes. This direct support will be supplemented with an opportunity for employer engagement through a ‘Jobs of the Future’ event, while the Curriculum Team will provide support to the school’s Careers teacher. In Year ten, further provision includes ‘Career Management’ group work in schools and work experience placements. Under these new arrangements, students only have access to a personal career guidance interview from Year 11 followed by an employer-led workshop within educational settings. Students then have access to another final personal career guidance interview again in Year 12. All career guidance provision after Year 12 is, however, delivered through emails, SMS, and a webinar on higher education finance (Careers Wales, 2017).

The current model is problematic for a number of reasons. Firstly, evidence suggests that earlier access to career education and guidance has a number of benefits for young people (Archer et

al., 2014b; Hughes, & Kashefpakdel, 2019). Statutory guidance then needs to ensure the provision of career education and guidance from primary school, especially for young people from marginalised backgrounds. Secondly, the over-reliance on technology may negatively affect students' engagement with services. Indeed, in Scotland, Holyrood's Education and Skills Committee (2018) raised concerns related to the over-reliance on technology through Skills Development Scotland's 'My World of Work' digital platform. The Committee noted that digital provision cannot match the benefits of personal face-to-face guidance. Finally, it is also important to note that the only equality concern that the new guidance acknowledges, is that of gender, thereby omitting all other protected characteristics (Equality Act, 2010).

The Scottish Model

The Scottish Parliament and Executive were established in 1999, with both legislative and executive responsibility over devolved matters (Howieson and Semple, 2006). Prior to devolution, career guidance services were largely similar across the nations of the U.K. Statutory duty under the Employment and Training Act (1973) saw provision of career guidance in England, Scotland and Wales through a career service managed by local authorities. Despite statutory duties, the main differences between Scotland and England was that Scotland traditionally had its own education system, curriculum and qualifications framework (Watts, 2006).

Divergence between provision in Scotland and England can be traced back to the Trade Union Reform and Employment Rights Act (1993) which amended the Employment and Training Act (1973) that resulted in the restructuring of career services cross-nationally (House of Commons, 1993). Career guidance services were subsequently moved from being the remit of local authorities to the Secretary of State for Scotland (Howieson and Semple, 2006). Under the 1993 Act, duty was placed on the Scottish Office to invite tenders for the provision of career guidance services guided by the Conservative Government's 1979-1999 policies and the application of market principles to education. The implication of which meant that the Scottish Office was encouraged to adopt a competitive and more business oriented approach to the provision of career services. Further divergence arose, however, in the implementation and interpretation of the duties related to the 1993 Act in Scotland due to a difference in attitudes and values towards the application of market principles to public services.

The Scottish Executive invited tenders from local authorities and Local Enterprise Companies to deliver their career service on a partnership basis that was not subject to competitive tendering as in England. The career service was then operationalised differently in Scotland, in comparison to the English model. Despite legislative duties, all local authorities and Local Enterprise Companies remained as partners and none were privately owned (Sampson et al., 1999; Howieson and Semple, 2006).

Following the establishment of the Scottish Parliament in 1999, the Duffner Committee was set up to review the Career Service (Career Service Review Committee, 2000) resulting in the re-organisation of statutory services and the inception of Careers Scotland in 2002. This re-organisation integrated over 80 Career Service Companies, Education Business Partnerships, Adult Guidance Networks, Lifelong Learning Partnerships and Modern Apprenticeship frameworks vertically in an inclusion oriented, all-age basis within the structure of Careers Scotland. The structural re-organisation was described by Watts (2005, p. 5) as the 'largest publicly-funded organisational structure in the world that is dedicated to career planning support'. The move to integrate services was also seen to declutter the landscape of various organisations thereby providing more effective and standardised services (Howieson and Semple, 2006).

Careers Scotland was based on the publications 'A Smart Successful Scotland' (Scottish Executive, 2001b; 2004), learning and skills targets as well as performance measures. Watts (2005, p. 7) described Careers Scotland's aims as distinctive in that it linked 'economic inclusion, enterprise and employability' to career education and planning. Further setting Careers Scotland apart from cross-national services was that its service development and delivery was underpinned by Cognitive Processing theory developed at Florida State University (Sampson et al., 1999). This model sees cognitive information processing theory applied to career problem-solving and decision-making (Peterson et al., 1991), while provision is matched to an individual's identified level of need through a 'needs matrix' (Sampson et al., 1999). This meant that under Careers Scotland, service provision was based on a differentiated needs model of high, moderate and low level of needs with levels of service adapted to meet particular service-users' needs (Watts, 2005).

Watts (2005) suggests that the Scottish adoption of the Florida State University Model meets OECD (2004) recommendations in that career guidance should make greater use of self-help techniques. However, concerns are raised due to the emphasis placed on the individual as the

model does not take into consideration those who failed to make contact due to various factors, thereby further disadvantaging already marginalised people (Howieson and Semple, 2006). Despite the aforementioned limitations in provision Watts (2005) identified that the level of provision was high when compared to other OECD countries meeting four of the ‘lifelong guidance systems’ OECD Benchmarks (OECD, 2004).

In 2007 when the Scottish National Party came into power in Scotland, they announced within the first 100 days of the new administration that they would develop a Skills Strategy for Scotland. The Scottish Government (2007) then subsequently released its ‘Skills for Scotland: Lifelong skills strategy’, which laid the ground for a highly integrated skills agenda. These developments may be seen as a catalyst for a whole range of services moving out the remit of local authorities. Subsequently in 2008, Careers Scotland, the Scottish University for Industry as well as the skills and learning functions of the Highlands and Island Enterprise and Scottish Enterprise merged to form a national skills agency called Skills Development Scotland (SDS) in order to provide more streamlined services (Scottish Government, 2008b; Payne, 2009). SDS’ remit included providing information, advice and guidance to individuals and employers in order to support sustained economic development (Skills Development Scotland, 2008).

The Scottish Government, (2008b) then commissioned the Moray House School of Education to review policies, measures and delivery from SDS. Findings demonstrated that provision was working effectively but noted that there was variation in services for individuals considered to be at risk. The review also identified gaps in measurement in order to determine the impact of various programmes (Scottish Government, 2008b).

The Scottish Government (2011) then set out its vision and continued commitment to an all-age universal and impartial career guidance services in the 2011 publication ‘Career Information, Advice and Guidance in Scotland: A Framework for Service Redesign and Improvement’. Within this framework, SDS remained responsible for the delivery of career guidance in Scotland in partnership with schools, colleges, local authorities and other public bodies. The Scottish Government (2011, p. 16) also recognised the importance of one-to-one guidance delivered by qualified professionals effectively targeting those most in need and emphasised the importance of ‘equity of service for every young person’. Whilst one-to-one support for those with additional support needs in England is within the remit of local authorities, responsibility for one-to-one guidance for young people with additional support needs in Scotland is within the remit of SDS (Scottish Government, 2011, 2020).

As mentioned previously SDS works closely with schools in order to provide young people opportunities to access Curriculum for Excellence outcomes and to support teachers. Scottish provision is based on the partnership model, where the school and the external career services are responsible for the provision of career guidance and aspects of career related learning. Under these arrangements, teachers are responsible for teaching and curriculum planning while the careers service disseminates knowledge of the labour market through qualified professionals providing personalised career guidance (Andrews and Hooley, 2017). The framework also recognises that some parents may have limited experience pertaining to learning and work and suggests that SDS and schools include parents in career conversations. What further differentiates the Scottish framework from the English one is that Scotland places an emphasis on earlier access to career advice linked to the labour market (Scottish Government, 2014b/c) through opportunities for young people to participate in group work through the curriculum.

Career education was then further embedded within the Curriculum for Excellence with the publication of the Scottish Government's (2015c) 'Developing the Young Workforce (DYW): Career Education Standard' strategy. The strategy brought together local authorities, Education Scotland, SDS and employer representative organisations not only to develop a standard for career related provision within the curriculum but to strengthen the role of employer engagement within educational settings. However, Holyrood's Education and Skills Committee recently conducted a review on the progress being made in implementing the DYW strategy. Findings suggest that a number of key targets had been missed relating to embedding career education into the curriculum, personal career guidance, employer engagement and providing positive destinations for care experienced and disabled young people (The Scottish Parliament, 2018). The committee observed that there were significant funding and time constraints on teaching staff and emphasised the need to reduce teacher workloads.

Further developments included placing a greater emphasis on skills development and job sustainability alongside development in equality legislation (Scottish Government, 2008; Equality Act, 2010). However, this has not always translated to practice. For example, in response to the recession in 2008, the Scottish government invested in the development of the Modern Apprenticeship programme creating 25,000 new apprenticeship opportunities each year between 2012 and 2014 with the aim of raising the annual number to 30,000 by 2020 (Scottish Government, 2014). Despite the number of apprenticeship opportunities created by

the Scottish Government, Ethnic minority young people represent less than 2 percent of all Modern Apprenticeship entrants (Scottish Government, 2014; The Scottish Parliament, 2017).

In 2017 a report from the Scottish Government's Independent Adviser on Race Equality entitled 'Addressing Race Inequality in Scotland: The way forward'(2017) identified the need for more effective monitoring and evaluation measures to track equity of outcomes in employment for Ethnic minority communities with a particular emphasis on skills development, employment and guidance. The report further argues for the need to 'to enhance career information advice and guidance services are aligned and focused on the needs of young people of all ethnicities' (Scottish Government, 2019, p. 9).

Almost ten years after the publication 'Career Information, Advice and Guidance in Scotland: A Framework for Service Redesign and Improvement' (Scottish Government, 2011), the Scottish Government released its updated strategy entitled 'Scotland's Careers Strategy: Moving Forward' (Scottish Government, 2020). As with the framework in 2011 the new strategy renewed its support for a lifelong, pan-sectoral career system that aims to ensure citizens have 'access to the right people and services which includes employability support (Scottish Government, 2020, p. 3).

Career Education and Guidance in the Digital Age

Career guidance and the use of computer technology has a long history. As far back as the 1960s there has been interest in the use of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in career education (Watts, 2002) that saw Career Advisers using computers in their practice through interest inventories and technological profiling (Sampson and Lumsden, 2000). More recent developments in Web 2 digital technologies have been recognised as further supporting the provision of career guidance (Howieson and Semple, 2013). Digital paradigms of personalised career support paralleled philosophical developments within career guidance promoting 'self-help by clients' with differential levels of support matched to service-users individual needs (Howieson and Semple, 2013, p. 287). The U.K and devolved administrations embraced the use of digital technologies in the provision of career guidance. Online resources developed by the National Careers Service in England, Careers Wales ICT platform and SDS' My World of Work (MyWow) in Scotland aimed to provide career education and guidance to a larger audience thereby increasing accessibility.

The effectiveness of digital technologies in the provision of career guidance has however, been an area of contested space and research findings are mixed. Gore et al. (2006) explored 64,967 secondary school and 22,326 college students' online career exploratory behaviours. Results indicate that secondary school students were less likely to access the section of the system that offers guidance. Moreover, 61 percent of secondary school students were less likely to access digital career resources.

Howieson and Semple (2014) explored 250 students use of career websites in Scottish schools and examined the impact on their career management skills. Findings indicated that 63 percent of young people accessed websites for career information, 44 percent used school libraries and 66 percent had access to personal career guidance. Overall, however, the data demonstrated that the two Scottish career websites had little to no impact on students career management skills. To explain these findings, the authors suggest that while young people might be readily able to navigate digital spaces, their strategies for searching and extracting digital career information may be limited. Relevant to the current study, Ethnic minority young people were more likely to seek out personal guidance over digital services due to a lack of digital confidence amongst those whose first language was not English.

Conversely, Hooley and colleagues (2011) argue that digitised services increase access allowing more young people to engage in career education while keeping staff resources costs down. The authors further suggest that digital services can also serve to prevent disengagement and increase retention. Osborn and Reardon (2006) found that online services were a critical component within a broader intervention to promote school engagement amongst young people at risk of dropping out. However, online services were most beneficial when situated alongside personal guidance delivered by a Career Adviser and further research suggests that digital services on their own are not sufficient emphasising the need for personal career guidance used in conjunction with online services (Reile and Harris-Bowlsbey, 2000; Sampson and Lumsden, 2000; Whiston et al., 2003).

Despite Hooley and colleagues claims for increased accessibility, concerns have, however, been raised regarding inequitable accessibility to online services (Sampson et al., 2000; McGillivray et al., 2017), as those who are socially excluded are often digitally excluded (Van Dijk, 2005). With increased weight being placed on digital provision by the U.K and devolved administrations, consideration has to be given to the digital divide for those who are disadvantaged and cannot access online services. The ONS (2017) found that 90 percent of

households in the U.K. have access to the internet, with 10 percent of households being at risk of being excluded from digital spaces along gendered, ethnic, and socio-economic lines. Given these glaring disparities, Roma, Gypsy and Traveller communities' access to digital services and the digital divide also have to be taken in to consideration.

Research by Salemink (2016) explored Sinti Roma and Travellers social and digital exclusion in the Netherlands and found community members to be digitally engaged and included. It is however, thought that these results are correlated to research participants living on sites located in densely populated towns with coaxial cable connections and future plans for the implementation of fibre optics. In turning to the U.K, Ryder and Greenfields (2010) explored Roma, Gypsy and Traveller people's access to the internet. 95 participants participated in the research that indicated that 61 percent of the sample had access to the internet. 40 percent of the sample accessed the internet at home or work, while a smaller proportion of the sample (13 percent) had access to the internet at home. The authors also demonstrated that the participants had low levels of digital skills particularly amongst older participants.

More recently, Townsend et al. (2018) examined Gypsy-Traveller social and digital exclusion across Aberdeen (Scotland) and in the Netherlands. The authors found that while their participants were digitally engaged – it was not through fixed broadband structures with community members often having to rely on 3G, and 4G access. The research, however, fails to provide the number of research participants who participated in their study, raising questions regarding validity and generalisability. Research by Scadding and Sweeney (2018) also examined digital access amongst Gypsy and Traveller communities in the U.K. Findings revealed high rates of digital exclusion, with a mere 38 percent of Gypsies and Travellers having access to a household internet connection if housed, while 36 percent of Gypsy and Traveller people could not use technology and 52 percent of participants did not feel confident using technology.

Research by Hay et al. (2020) problematised the Scottish Government's Digital First approach (Scottish Government, 2018) and demonstrated examples within current policy and practice that illustrate a lack of understanding of community-specific needs regarding language barriers, digital literacy, and internet access. For example, Article 12 in Scotland, an NGO that works to support Travelling communities in Scotland responded to the Scottish Government's pre-publication consultation for their 'Improving the educational outcomes of Traveller children' strategy (Scottish Government, 2018). The organisation raised concerns regarding the Scottish

Government's heavy reliance on technology for support in working with Roma, Gypsy and Traveller young people due to issues around internet accessibility impacting on young people's ability to engage (Article 12 in Scotland, 2018). As Saleminck (2016) observes many of the sites across the U.K do not offer broadband thereby resulting in digital exclusion.

Conclusion

The current chapter has demonstrated the evidential basis of career education and guidance in schools. A considerable amount of research exists suggesting that career guidance has been correlated with a number of positive outcomes such as increased motivation (Moote and Archer, 2018) broader aspirations, greater awareness of opportunities, progression (Hooley et al. 2014) and better academic achievement (Hughes et al., 2016). Moreover, a number of commentators have highlighted that career guidance serves to promote social equity (Archer et al., 2014a) and upward social mobility (Hughes, 2017; Hutchinson, 2012).

The literature also suggests that the nature, time (chronological age of students; and duration and frequency of interventions) and manner that career education and guidance is delivered to young people is of critical importance. Research by Lapan et al. (2011), Choi et al. (2015) and Janeiro et al. (2014) all suggest that a programme of sustained engagements were more effective than one-off interventions. Further, if the most vulnerable period for dropping out of secondary school for young Roma, Gypsy and Traveller people is between the ages of 13-14 (Derrington and Kendall, 2003; Derrington, 2016) then statutory guidance needs to consider earlier access to personal guidance interviews for young from these backgrounds in primary school (Archer et al., 2014b; Hughes, & Kashefpakdel, 2019).

This chapter has also focused on policy developments across England, Wales and Scotland and the divergence in approaches post-devolution. Gaps have been identified across the three home nations. Effective monitoring and evaluation measures to track skills development, employment and access to support services have been identified as a need within the Scottish context (Scottish Government, 2014, 2017) while in England and Wales, the most recent statutory guidance fails to mention Ethnic minority communities (DfE, 2018; Careers Wales, 2017). Evidence was also presented that problematised the various administrations over-reliance on a digital approach (Hay et al., 2020; The Scottish Parliament, 2018) illustrating a lack of understanding of community-specific needs regarding language barriers, digital literacy, and internet access.

Finally, there is a dearth of research exploring Roma, Gypsy and Traveller students' experiences of accessing sources of career education and guidance (Greenfields, 2008; Wilkin, 2010; Mulcahy et al., 2017) across England, Wales and Scotland. Further research is needed to examine the impact that the differentiated models of service delivery across the home nations have on young people's aspirations and understand the multiple interlocking barriers facing students from these backgrounds. I will now turn to explore the epistemology, theoretical orientations, methodology and methods I employed in this study in order to understand how young Roma, Gypsy and Traveller people experience career education and guidance within educational settings and to identify the systemic processes that either facilitate or present barriers to equitable access.

Chapter Four

Methodology

As demonstrated in the preceding chapter, researchers have yet to explore Roma, Gypsy and Traveller students' aspirations and experiences of career education and guidance across various geo-political and policy contexts. While previous research has illuminated perspectives of young people and stakeholders within primary and secondary educational settings (see for e.g. Bhopal, 2004, 2011; D'Arcy, 2017; Derrington and Kendall, 2003; Deuchar and Bhopal, 2013), there is a paucity of literature pertaining to career education and guidance from the perspective of students themselves. It is therefore vital that this knowledge gap is addressed in order to understand student aspirations, experiences of career education and guidance as well as their perceived mechanisms of support or barriers to support that affect their transition into positive destinations. This chapter details the epistemological considerations, theoretical background to research design and the methods employed to address the following research questions:

1. What are young Roma, Gypsy and Traveller people's aspirations and what support do they feel they need in order to actualise their aspirations?
2. Do young Roma, Gypsy and Traveller people have equitable access to career education and guidance provision. If they do, what have their experiences been? If they have not had access, do they believe that they would benefit from career guidance, and how do they think local services could best meet their needs?

In order to situate the current study in relation to its methodological and theoretical framework, it is important to first consider the paradigm or worldview that informed the research design. As Denzin and Lincoln (1994, p. 13) explain, it is the 'net that contains the researcher's epistemological, ontological and methodological premises'. Second, the epistemological perspective that informed methodological choices will be illustrated before providing a rationale for the research design employed within the current research while considering the strengths and limitations thereof. The methods used to gather and analyse data will then be discussed, followed by an examination of the sampling and recruitment of research participants. Fundamental to the nature of the inquiry, ethical considerations underpinning the research process will then be highlighted, before considering the limitations of the current research. Finally, my positionality and reflexivity will be discussed in order to acknowledge the multiple social belongings that I have brought to the research process.

Epistemological Considerations

According to Steinmetz (2005), a binary is purported to exist in the social sciences between the paradigm of positivism and its 'epistemological others' such as constructionism and emancipatory paradigms. Positivism contends that the scientific method offers the best framework for investigating the social world in order to establish truth and objective reality (Crotty, 1998; Flyvbjerg, 2001). Although there are variations within the positivist paradigm such as post-positivism (Creswell and Clark, 2018) and neo-positivism (Kraft, 1953), its ontology is described as realist and its epistemological stance is rooted in rationalism.

A number of scholars have, however, critiqued the dogmatic view of positivism (see for e.g. Crotty, 1998; Steinmetz, 2005). Crotty (1998, p. 40) argues that 'research outcomes are neither totally objective, nor unquestionably certain', while Malson, (1998, p. 36) suggests that positivism is not as 'objective, value-free and apolitical' as it is purported to be. In contrast to positivist and post-positivist paradigms, constructivism places an emphasis on understanding the world based on human experience and the meanings attributed to that experience are of central importance thereby challenging positivist assumptions of a fixed external reality (Kawulich, 2012). In determining the ontology of constructionism, scholars such as Creswell (2003) and Mertens (2009) argue that there are a number of realities that are socially constructed by individuals as well as groups. Epistemologically, constructivism is based on the belief that knowledge is subjective and there are multiple truths situated within human experience and that those truths are dependent on historical and cultural norms (Kawulich, 2012).

A third paradigm – the emancipatory or transformative paradigm emerged to redress the limitations of the more dominant worldviews (Chambers, 1997; Fixico, 1998; Mihesuah, 2005). Scholars have criticised positivism/post-positivism due to its perceived failure to consider the needs of marginalised communities thereby resulting in the perpetuation of cycles of domination and repression through the production of knowledge (Kawulich, 2012). Similarly, in observing the limitations of constructivism, Creswell (2007) argued that the paradigm fails to advocate for action to help marginalised individuals.

The emancipatory paradigm has been posited to address the gaps inherent within positivist, post-positivist and constructivist orientations. The emancipatory paradigm includes, critical social science research (Neuman, 1997), critical theory (Habermas, 1973; Freire, 1993)

participatory action research (Mills, 2003) and research that aims to emancipate communities through collective action (Lather, 1992; Mertens, 2009). Ontologically, the emancipatory paradigm holds that social realities are bounded by historical, political, cultural, economic, racial, ethnic, gender, disability and power based factors (Kawulich, 2012).

The emancipatory paradigm shares tenets with positivism/post-positivism in that external reality can be discovered but diverges from the fixed reality stance and instead proposes the fluid nature of reality. Epistemologically, the emancipatory paradigm holds that truth and knowledge are collectively constructed from the meaning-making of a research participant's frame of reference. Moreover, knowledge is only true if it can be transformed into practice that empowers individuals and improves their lives (Kawulich, 2012).

To this end, the emancipatory paradigm is underpinned by a 'call to action', with considerations of social impact embedded throughout the research process in order to reform institutions based on the voices of the excluded, marginalised and oppressed. Creswell (2007) observes that the issues and concerns that marginalised groups are facing are of prime importance, in order that the researcher can provide a platform for participants' voices to be heard with the aim of improving lives. Kemmis and Wilkinson (1998) assert that the emancipatory paradigm aims to help people unshackle themselves from relationships of power and dominance in educational settings. As I am concerned with young people's experiences within educational settings, it is important to identify perceived barriers of support so as to challenge relationships of dominance within educational institutions.

Moreover, as the current paradigm emphasises that the relationship between the researcher and research participants must be symmetrical and reciprocal, I have actively worked to ensure the relationship between young people and myself was not asymmetrical (Kawulich, 2012) which has been a difficult and complex process at times. The nature of inquiry emphasises a collaborative approach conducted 'with others', viewing participants as active collaborators (Kemmis and Wilkinson, 1998), an approach that was integral in the evolution of measurement design, data collection and analysis of this research process to ensure the voices of participants are heard by those who have power to make changes in policy and practice.

Theoretical Orientations

I draw on a range of theoretical orientations in a grounded practice approach to theory for the foregrounding of students' experiences. The work of Hodkinson and Sparkes (1997) encourages the examination of the interface between structure and agency in learners'

education and career decision-making; critical race theory (Solórzano and Yosso, 2002) which elucidates the high aspirations held by Roma, Gypsy and Traveller students and their parents in order to challenge dominant master narratives that suggest that these communities do not want a career or education; and theories of intersectionality (Crenshaw, 1991; Yuval-Davis, 2006; Hills Collins and Bilge, 2019) in order to enable a more nuanced understanding of how complex and intersecting social inequalities within the educational field influence students' horizons for action. These theories are thread throughout the analysis and findings chapters and are useful in illuminating how young people's agency is constrained by structural forces within their field whilst exposing and challenging the discrimination within students' experiences.

'Careership', was developed by Hodkinson and Sparkes (1997) and later revised by Hodkinson (2008). The theoretical framework yields high analytical utility in that it allows for the examination of the interface between individual agency and structure, illustrating the role of both in influencing learners' career decision-making. The authors argue that individuals make 'pragmatically rational' career decisions that are conditioned by their 'life histories', unequal power relationships and the 'culture in which [they] are living' (Hodkinson and Sparkes, 1997, p. 37). Learners' decision-making is also situated within the familiar and known and is at times opportunistically dependent on serendipitous encounters with significant others within their field.

Drawing on Bourdieu's concepts of field, habitus and capital, careership theory has three interconnected constituent elements: horizons for action, the field and routines and turning points. Horizons for action determine what individuals see as possible within them, rendering what lies beyond them imperceptible (Hodkinson, 2008). These horizons are based on an individual's dispositions (or habitus as termed by Bourdieu) and the structural opportunities or barriers within their field. Habitus is acquired through an 'implicit or explicit learning function as a system of generative schemes ... that leads us to reproduce the social conditions of our own production' (Bourdieu, 1993, p. 76).

One's habitus then is a 'matrix of perceptions, beliefs, and attitudes that shapes an individual's expectations' that is produced and fostered by 'the family but nested and influenced by the surrounding community' (McDonough and Calderone, 2006, p. 1716). The concept of habitus is important when considering a student's career aspirations and expectations for the future as their habitus produces action that generally reflects the social context in which they are

acquired. Influenced by interactions between their habitus and the field they inhabit, young people make pragmatically rational career decisions within their horizons for action.

The field is made up of the inter-related interactions between employers, education institutions, the labour market (local, national and global) and the extensive influences of social structure (class, gender, ethnicity, age and policy contexts) wherein the individual makes career related decisions (Hodkinson, 2008). The degree to which an individual can influence their career is dependent on their position within the field and the resources that are available to them. The educational field therefore denotes the demarcated area that students' career decisions and transitions take place, with learners having differential access to economic, cultural and social capital.

Young people, due to their age generally have less resources (Lundahl, et al., 2017) and depending on their background, they will be differentially positioned in the 'economy of student worth' (Maguire et al., 2000, p. 12). The inclusionary and exclusionary practices of teachers, Career Advisers and educational institutions make up the field, institutional habitus or 'school affect' through which young people experience education and career guidance and play a significant role in the broadening or constraining of their horizons for action (Lanskey, 2015). The development of trustworthy and reciprocal relationships with students and their parents then cannot be understated if school staff aim to positively broaden what students see as possible within their worldview (Raffo and Reeves, 2000).

Drawing on Straus' (1962) notions of interrelated routines and turning points, Hodkinson and Sparkes argue that turning points are events that occur when individuals make decisions and re-orient their pathways thereby altering their habitus. From this perspective, an individual's life may be characterised as periods of routine interspersed with turning points which may be 'structural', 'enforced by others' or 'self-initiated' (Hodkinson and Sparkes, 1997, p. 39). In later reflections Hodkinson (2008), however, revised the third element of the theory. He noted the initial mistaken approach that he took along with Sparkes in attempting to classify both routines and turning points as there was no clear division between the two and he instead illuminated the central importance of learning in career development.

As Hodkinson and Sparkes (1997) 'careership' draws heavily on Bourdieu, it must be acknowledged that his work has been regarded as overly-deterministic (Jenkins, 2002). Harker and May (1993, p. 174), however, contend that while the habitus may set boundaries to action, individuals remain 'free' to respond to these boundaries through strategic practices. The effect

then serves to ‘orient rather than determine action’. Similarly, Reay (2004) argues that the framework leaves room for agency while Raffo and Reaves (2000, p. 150) assert that the concept of habitus ‘theoretically resolv[es] the dualism between agency and structure’ as it represents structural forces as manifested through human knowledge and action.

A basic tenet of careership theory is that students will make career decision-making that fits within their horizons for action or the schematic lens that is determined by their social class. Although Hodkinson and Sparkes (1997) allude to gender and ethnicity within their conceptualisation, they fail to explore the significance of each, how they interact with each other alongside social class and how they are implicated in the career decision-making process. In the same way, the careership literature is largely class focused and there is a paucity of research detailing how factors such as gender (Allin and Humberstone, 2006; Fejes and Haake, 2012; Lang, 2012), ‘race’ and ethnicity (Hodkinson and Bloomer, 2000; Smith, 2007) migration (Lindblad and Lundahl, 2020) and language impact on learners education development and career decision-making. Nor does careership theory take into consideration the intersecting and compounding effect of ‘race’, ethnicity, citizenship status, gender, and class. The current thesis concurs with Morrison (2012) and others such as Webb et al. (2017) who identified the need to expand on Bourdieusian theory by incorporating an intersectional focus within the structural analysis that will allow for a more nuanced understanding of how students’ experience intersectional barriers of inequality and how these influence their horizons for action.

In order to address these gaps and in line with the philosophical orientations of the emancipatory paradigm, the theoretical lenses of intersectionality and critical race theory were deemed to be the ‘best fit’ for the nature of the inquiry. Intersectionality attends to how racialized inequities are influenced and compounded by other dimensions of identity and social structure in order to challenge unequal and hegemonic power structures (Gillborn, 2015). According to the African American Policy Forum (2013, Intersectionality section, para. 3), intersectionality ‘enables us to recognize the fact that perceived group membership can make people vulnerable to various forms of bias’ whilst acknowledging that ‘because we are simultaneously members of many groups, our complex identities can shape the specific way we each experience that bias’.

Intersectionality may largely be attributed to Kimberlé Crenshaw (1991) who coined the term in her Stanford Law Review article ‘Mapping the Margins: Intersectionality, Identity Politics

and Violence against women of colour'. Crenshaw's fieldwork in women's shelters across Los Angeles, revealed that domestic violence was only one facet of these women's experiences that would need to be addressed. The Black and Ethnic minority women that participated in her research were not only burdened by violence but by poverty, child care responsibilities and a lack of employability skills which were thought to be a consequence of their gender and class oppression.

Crenshaw further highlighted how their experiences were compounded by discriminatory employment and housing practices due to their 'race' and ethnicity. These findings led Crenshaw (1991) to conclude that interventions that were designed by and for white women would be of little use to Black and Ethnic minority women who face multiple disadvantage. It is important to note, however, that Crenshaw (1991) and others (see for e.g. Hills Collins and Bilge, 2019) have acknowledged that her work was part of a growing collective effort amongst Black and Ethnic minority women (see for e.g. Bambara, 1970; Beal, 1969; Combahee River Collective, 1977). Hill Collins and Bilge (2019) observe that Ethnic minority women were often subordinated to men during the Civil Rights, Black Power and Red Power movements; whilst simultaneously being excluded from the second wave white feminism movement. The growing collective ultimately expanded feminism by including analyses of the simultaneity of oppressions and the interplay of factors such as 'race', class and sexuality in order to challenge inequality.

Feminist disability scholars (see for e.g. Fannon, 2016; Garland-Thomson, 2005, 2013; Hall, 2012; Naples et al., 2019) have also demonstrated how intersectionality enables a holistic understanding of the ways in which multiple disadvantages such as 'race', gender, class, sexuality and ability intersect with social, political and economic processes to create dominance hierarchies. Intersectionality has also been applied in Romani studies, with scholars urging researchers to move beyond viewing Roma, Gypsy and Traveller people through an exclusively ethnic lens so as to include intersecting social identities across gender, gender identity, sexuality and disability in order to redress multiple-disadvantage (Fremlova, 2018; Kóczé, 2009; Jovanović et al., 2015; Stewart, 2010).

As the reader will observe (see for e.g. Chapter seven, 'Intersectional Barriers', p. 203) the experiences of the young people who participated in the current study reflects that they are caught between institutional, structural, political and cultural tensions intersecting with poverty, ethnicity, 'race', gender and class that exert power over and influence their lives. As

Bhopal and Preston (2012, p. 3) argue, there is a 'need to focus on the multiplicities of identity' whilst 'acknowledging that experiences cannot be taken in isolation'. Further, it is important to illuminate the matrix of barriers that impact on young people's experiences of education and career guidance so that interventions may be designed based on their needs (Crenshaw, 1991).

Finally, an intersectional framework for analysis was also selected as it recognises within-group and between-group differences (Hancock, 2007; Bowleg 2008; Zambrana and Thornton Dill 2009). Within and between each of the community groups who participated in the current research, there will be similarities, differences and diversity. The use of an intersectional analysis will then allow for the exploration and recognition of heterogeneous identities and experiences. While intersectionality is vital to understand the multiplicities of identity, the current thesis purports that experiences of racism retains a primacy (Delgado and Stefancic, 2017) within and across the diverse community groups who participated in the current research.

Critical race theory was selected as it is concerned with 'race' as a social construct, and how racism is embedded pervasively within social, economic and historical contexts (Parker and Lynn, 2002; Delgado and Stefancic, 2001, 2017). For the purposes of this thesis, Solórzano and Yosso (2002, p. 3) define critical race theory in education as 'a framework that seeks to identify, analyse, and transform those structural and cultural aspects of education that maintain subordinate and dominant racial positions in and out of the classroom'.

A central tenet of critical race theory is the primacy of 'race' and racism in the lives of Ethnic minority community members (Russell, 1992; Delgado and Stefancic, 2017). From this perspective, racism is an 'ordinary' and 'common everyday experience' for Black and Ethnic minority people (Delgado and Stefancic, 2017, p. 8). Critical race theory also places an emphasis on the experiential knowledge of Black and Ethnic minority community members as critical to understanding racial subordination. Experiential knowledge is viewed as a strength and critical race theory employs storytelling as a methodology.

Solórzano and Yosso (2002) have argued that counter-stories from the perspective of racialized minorities can challenge majoritarian master narratives and dominant discourses that serve to oppress marginalised communities. The methodology also has the power to expose and challenge deficit-informed research and methods that have silenced the voices of the oppressed (Valencia and Solórzano, 1997).

The development of critical race theory in the U.K was pioneered by Gillborn (2005, 2008, 2010) who argues that policies in the U.K serve to marginalise and subordinate Ethnic minority

community members and have failed to address racial inequality. More recently, Bhopal (2020, p. 508) argued that policies such as Athena SWAN in higher education institutions ‘suggest the enactment of Whiteness aimed primarily (though not entirely) to advance the position of White groups’ and ‘disadvantage BME women’.

Based on my immersion within the literature, as well as experiences with institutions such as local authority Equality teams and civil servants, a prevalent discourse toward Roma, Gypsy and Traveller community members was one that served to oppress and exclude. For instance, in my role as Campaign Manager for Show Racism the Red Card Scotland, I attended a partnership meeting with a Scottish local authority’s Education and Equalities Team. At this meeting I spoke about the fieldwork I would be undertaking in my PhD, requesting that they would act as gatekeepers. In response, the Equalities Lead stated that ‘Gypsies don’t want an education’.

This contrasted with my own experiences of developing prejudice reduction education with two Scottish Travellers from Article 12 in Scotland during my time at Show Racism the Red Card. The Scottish Travellers I worked with viewed education positively and were working toward completing their own community development degrees. Based on these opposing perspectives, critical race theory provides a useful interpretive lens to explore and present counter-stories from the perspective of Roma, Gypsy and Traveller young people in order to challenge majoritarian master narratives within policy, practice and education settings that continue to oppress these marginalised communities.

Finally, a basic tenet of both intersectional and critical race theoretical approaches is the need for activism and social justice in order to challenge systems of inequality (Crenshaw et al., 2005; Gillborn, 2015; Hill Collins and Bilge, 2019). Thread throughout the subsequent chapters, I detail the steps that I took to challenge inequality when I encountered it, whilst also forming coalitions with like-minded activists and educators during the research process in order to advance equality (see for e.g. p. 127 of this chapter) in line with the emancipatory paradigm.

Methodology: A Qualitative Approach

The current paper accepts the definition of the term ‘methodology’ consistent with much of the literature (see for e.g. Mackenzie & Knipe, 2006; Schram, 2006; Walter, 2006) and defined by Somekh and Lewin (2005, p. 346) as the ‘principles, theories and values that underpin a

particular approach to research'. Approaches to research methodology in the acquisition of knowledge are classified according to two broad traditions – quantitative and qualitative.

The quantitative tradition, sometimes also referred to as the positivist or empiricist approach emphasises the 'measurement and analysis of causal relationships between variables, not processes' (Denzin and Lincoln, 2008, p. 14) in order to explain, predict and control phenomena. In contrast the qualitative tradition, sometimes referred to as the interpretive or constructivist approach places an emphasis on 'the qualities of entities and on processes and meanings that are not experimentally ... [measured]' and seeks to answer questions related to 'how experience is created and given meaning' (Denzin and Lincoln, 20018, p. 14) from the participants 'point of view' (Leedy, 1997, p. 317).

Historically within the scientific research tradition, an emphasis has been placed on quantitative approaches with a conviction that only quantitative data is valid (see for e.g. Sechrest, 1992; Denzin and Lincoln, 2008). Strong counter pressures have, however, been present throughout history that challenge conventional wisdom and point to the utility of qualitative approaches. For example, Vidich and Lyman's (2000) work outlines the presence and development of qualitative research in history ranging from early ethnography in the 17th century, to the crossing of the 'postmodern divide' in the mid-1980s (p. 60) where a crisis of representation occurred (see for e.g. Marcus & Fischer, 1986; Clifford & Marcus 1986; Clifford, 1988). During which issues of gender, class and 'race' were called into question, resulting in the qualitative researcher not only observing history but playing a part in (re)producing it (Denzin and Lincoln, 2008).

Despite past efforts to work solely within one side of a binary approach, quantitative and qualitative methodological traditions need not operate in opposition to one another. Silverman (2013, p. 9) suggests that both methodological traditions are 'complementary parts of the systematic, empirical search for knowledge'. While neither method can be considered superior or inferior, the use of a particular approach must be determined by the research problem at hand.

The selection of research methods were largely shaped by the need to understand how young Roma, Gypsy and Traveller people experience career education and guidance within educational settings and to identify the systemic processes that either facilitate or present barriers to equitable access. Detailed below are several arguments that support my preference for a qualitative approach. As this study has identified a specific gap that aims to improve

understanding based on the experiences of Roma, Gypsy and Traveller young people, I argue that a qualitative and ethnographic approach is currently more appropriate than a quantitative one. First, a qualitative approach is able to provide what Patton (1985) describes as a depth of understanding of experience as it allows the researcher to explore ‘how people interpret their experience’ as well as the ‘meaning that they attribute to their experiences’ (Merriam, 2009, p. 5).

Second, it does not limit the researcher to a predetermined research design as Creswell and Poth (2017, p. 21) observe that the ‘procedures of qualitative research are characterised as inductive, emerging and shaped by the researchers experience in collecting and analysing the data’. Third, in line with the purpose of the emancipatory paradigm which seeks to challenge dominant narratives in order to empower individuals to transform society - qualitative research was deemed an appropriate method to provide a platform for previously silenced voices to be heard and minimize the asymmetrical relationship between myself and research participants (Creswell, 2007).

Finally, it is important to note that I had considered a mixed methods approach, as the quantitative element would have increased the generalisability of the research findings (Tsang, 2014). From this perspective, data gathered during the qualitative collection phase would inform the quantitative measurement design. However, as I progressed through the qualitative element of the research process, stark inequalities emerged across geo-political contexts. As the reader will observe in subsequent chapters, learners across England and Wales would have been able to complete a quantitative measure, however, this would not be replicated within the Scottish context due to both literacy and English fluency concerns. Based on these findings and in line with the emancipatory paradigm, I felt that a mixed methods design would have introduced unequal power dynamics into the research process and raised accessibility concerns.

Methods

Focus Groups

The term ‘focus group’ was coined in Merton and colleagues (1956) paper titled ‘The focused interview: a manual of problems and procedures’ to describe a situation where after considerable research, the researcher asks very specific questions about a topic to research participants while facilitating discussions to ensure equal participation. At the broadest level,

focus groups are collective conversations. Due to the ‘social and semi-public nature’ of focus groups, they yield great utility in that they ‘elicit information that paints a portrait of combined local perspectives’ (Grudens-Schuck et al., 2002, p. 3).

There is variation in the nature and types of focus groups that a researcher may conduct as interactions during the inquiry may be facilitated amongst participants in a structured or unstructured way (Denzin and Lincoln, 2008). The use of semi-structured focus group interviewing is a flexible method of data collection that is organised around an interview guide covering themes or topics that the researcher aims to explore during the interview with a number of participants (Morgan and Krueger, 1998).

In contrast to structured focus group interviews wherein a pre-determined and structured script of questions are asked sequentially of all research participants, semi-structured interviews allow new ideas to emerge and evolve due to what the research participant says during discussions (Krueger and Casey, 2000). The approach to question ordering within the semi-structured focus group then is fluid and some questions may not be asked if deemed irrelevant to the research participant or context (Denzin and Lincoln, 2008). The third type of focus group interview style is the unstructured interview wherein there are no pre-determined script of questions and the format is open and flexible. Across the spectrum of interview styles, semi-structured focus group interviewing was considered the best approach to explore student experiences.

Madriz (2000) illuminated the use of focus groups within qualitative research as both a consciousness raising activity and a means to promote and mobilise empowerment agendas amongst Ethnic minority women. From this perspective, the approach displaces the researcher from a dominant role thereby providing a safe space for research participants to collectively share their experiences. Similarly, Morgan and Krueger (1993) state that such groups allow peers to share their perceptions and experiences whilst in the ‘safety’ of others who may be more empathetic due to shared lived experiences. In recognising researcher positionality and privilege tied to working with vulnerable groups within a research context as well as the power differential between participants and decision makers it was pivotal to create a ‘safe space’ for communities within interview settings (see ‘Interview Process’, p. 113 detailing how this was achieved) who have limited power (Morgan and Krueger, 1993).

Further, in viewing focus groups as more than a data gathering ‘instrument’, I acknowledge the unique insights into critical inquiry offered by focus groups as an approach that allows the

researcher to engage with the real-world barriers facing Roma, Gypsy and Traveller young people. Kamberelis and Dimitriadis (2008, p. 376) argue that focus groups are an appropriate method for the 'strategic purposes of teaching, challenging hegemonies and conducting research' by highlighting that as a method they have permeated overlapping domains of pedagogy, politics and qualitative research. The authors demonstrated these overlapping domains through Paulo Freire's 'Pedagogy of the Oppressed' (1993) and his use of focus groups or 'study circles' as a method for individuals to imagine beyond 'limit situations' that normalise oppression in order to transform political and educational possibilities. According to Freire (1993, p. 76),

The starting point for organising the programme content of education or political action must be the present, existential, concrete situation, reflecting the aspirations of the people.

The use of focus groups was therefore deemed an appropriate exercise in situating the research within the present and concrete lives of research participants in order to reflect their aspirations. The approach provided Roma, Gypsy and Traveller young people with a platform for their voices to be heard and for their perceptions and experiences to be visible across the backdrop of socio-political events.

Moreover, student voices are often missing from research and policy documents intended to guide practitioners in the field. For example, the Scottish Government's (2018) guidelines on 'Improving the educational outcomes for children and young people from Travelling cultures' does not include the voices of young Roma, Gypsy and Traveller people. While recent research by Marcus (2016a) which included such voices is extremely important in 'breaking the silence' for Scottish Traveller girls' experiences of education, the voices of young Roma, Romani Gypsies, and Irish Travellers were not represented. This doctoral research 'represents' (Spivak, 1988) the voices of diverse community groups including Scottish Travellers, Irish Travellers, Roma, Romani Gypsies and Showmen thereby strengthening the original contribution to knowledge made by the study.

In addition, focus groups are also a useful approach for the 'collective exploration' (Romm, 2014, p. 1) of students' aspirations. Aspirations that are not often represented within the literature. Yovovich (1991, p. 43) suggests that this format allows for 'interaction among respondents [thus stimulating] new ideas and thoughts'. While for Radway (1991, p. xix) the group process 'produc[ed] a form and level of collaboration that could not [be reproduced] in

one-to-one interviews'. Furthermore, Albrecht (1993) cites Sink (1991, p. 197) in attesting that the focus group method offers a degree of external validity, and grounds the method in the 'human tendency to discuss issues and ideas in groups'.

The eight focus group discussions and semi-structured interviews with 36 young people provided rich data in addition to findings from the 17 semi-structured interviews and one focus group with adult populations including teachers, Career Advisers, and parents. Focus groups were an appropriate method in providing peer support for young people by composing groups wherein young people could express themselves in a safe and supportive environment. Group dynamics and evolving relations amongst research participants provide an additional phenomenological dimension to the interpretation and understanding of students' experiences (Denzin and Lincoln, 2008). While the use of focus groups presented opportunities to explore themes more widely, it is important to note the limitations of the approach.

First, in observing the limitations of focus group interviews, Isenberg (1986) contends that research participants may experience pressure to conform thereby limiting opportunities for individual stories to be discussed and explored. Social norms and the potential pressure to conform led Gurdens-Schenke (2004) to question the reliability of the method. It is important to acknowledge that young people in the current study may have experienced peer pressure within the group context that limited opportunities to express their individual experiences. As will be evidenced in chapter five (p. 140) social norms led one young person to retract initial statements regarding speaking to his mother about his career aspirations. However, concerns over conformity were deemed second to ensuring that young people felt comfortable. For example, Deuchar and Bhopal's (2013, p. 740) research with young Travellers in London and Glasgow, revealed the utility in focus groups as they 'put young people at ease while encouraging their shared voices to be heard'.

Second, discerning individual voices from focus group discussion recordings was anticipated to be problematic. In order to mitigate these concerns, all young people chose a 'Super-Hero' pseudonym and interview question items were asked in a clockwise motion from left to right. Following each question, the participant question ordering 'looped' back in an anti-clockwise manner which aided the identification of research participant's individual voices. At times, however, this was not 'perfect' as young people often got excited about ideas, which would result in the whole group talking at once, or some young people 'veering off' in another direction.

When this did occur, I was mindful that I wanted the experience to include elements of ‘fun’ for students and I let their ideas flow to their natural conclusion and then I re-focused the conversation asking the last participant (by name so I could hear it on the audio) if there was anything they wanted to add to the last question. There were also times where it was advantageous for young people to ‘veer off’ and discuss ideas within the group. By way of illustration, the Romani Gypsy boys’ narratives regarding the financial costs associated with university attendance (see for e.g. Chapter seven, p. 207) allowed for rich data to be collected when they talked amongst themselves.

While acknowledging the limitations of focus groups, the research method mitigated against young people experiencing alienation through the use of familiar spaces and familiar people. Importantly, the methodological approach for the current research was informed by the nature of the data that I needed in order to understand the lived experiences of young Roma, Gypsy and Traveller people at the intersections of multiple social categories, through composing focus groups based on homogeneity of ‘race’, ethnicity, gender and age. In addition, despite the aforementioned limitations, Marcus (2016a) and Joyce (2018) validated their findings with Scottish and Irish Travellers respectively through ‘member checking’ – a process which Guba and Lincoln (1989, p. 239) claimed allows the researcher to check for ‘errors of interpretation’; produce new information; and to validate findings. Member checking was highly relevant to the current research as it allowed for more nuanced considerations between communities and across various geo-political contexts in England, Scotland and Wales – adding to the dearth of literature exploring Roma, Gypsy and Traveller experiences across the home nations. Finally, due to time and resource constraints, focus group interviews were both an efficient and cost-effective method, allowing me to speak to a large number of Roma, Gypsy, Traveller and Showmen young people in England, Scotland and Wales over an 18-month period.

Focus Group Question Format

Semi-structured interview schedules were designed within a thematic framework that took account of: attitudes, engagement and participation, relationships, practical barriers, sources of support and aspirations. Some items were pre-determined and based on previous researchers’ items that were deemed to be fit for purpose, while other items were removed making way for new questions that evolved during the course of the research process.

When asking young people what career they aspired to in the future, I employed prompts previously used by DeWitt et al. (2013) that explored the impact of ethnicity on students' science aspirations. Their sample reflected representative and comparable proportions of young Ethnic minority people in English schools. However, as there were no Roma, Gypsy and Traveller young people who identified as such within the qualitative phase of data collection, these ethnic monitoring categories were not included in the demographic data section of their survey (Louise Archer, personal communications, 28th February, 2018).

In order to effectively support Roma, Gypsy and Traveller communities within education, strategies and policies need to be grounded in comparable and reliable research. As mentioned previously, a number of instruments have attempted to measure essential data and indicators amongst Roma, Gypsy and Traveller people such as population size and educational attainment (Mulcahy et al., 2017). However, due to the differentiated design of instruments and the varying approaches to data collection and subsequent analysis, these measurements produced different outcomes.

It was therefore vital that I approached measurement design in a methodical manner and ensured that I situated research design within the literature - utilising or slightly adapting measurement items that have proven reliable with other populations in order to promote parity of participation within 'mainstream' measures (see for e.g. Haynes et al., 2013; Code et al., 2006) (see Appendix J, p. 333).

The emphasis that I placed on sourcing items from 'mainstream' measures was also thought to counter the potential for items to be constructed based on deficit assumptions. For example, Grimaldi and colleagues (2015) argued that questions can be inherently symbolically violent. During fieldwork in Italy, the authors observed how the 'seemingly innocent' question 'Do your children go to school?' (Grimaldi, et al., 2015, p. 142) visibly impacted their research participants. The authors subsequently acknowledged that through this 'symbolically violent linguistic game', they were complicit in constructing stereotypes that reinforced that Roma communities do not value education.

In constructing measurement design, I employed participatory action research methods (Vajda, 2015) whereby a member of the Scottish Traveller community Bernadette, 'piloted' and critiqued item construction on the interview guides for both parents and young people. Within this session Bernadette and I worked through the interview guide items to ensure that they were respectful of communities and not symbolically violent. Bernadette had approved all items but

one - the question pertained to asking Roma, Gypsy and Traveller parents what their occupation was (Archer et al., 2014b). Bernadette raised concerns around the item as it carried the potential to reinforce inequality in that some female research participants may feel shame due to not participating in the labour market. As such the question was removed to reduce the potential for introducing power differentials into the research relationship with participants.

Finally, considerations of sampling at the measurement design stage were important as Messing (2014) describes the challenge in constructing items for measurement that are representative of various heterogeneous Roma, Gypsy and Traveller communities. A key consideration within the current research then, was about how best to approach working with vulnerable research participants who experience marginalisation and discrimination (Bhopal and Deuchar, 2015).

Participant Observation

Participant observation commenced upon entering the field, during which time I actively participated in the lives of young people and stakeholders and wider community members. Field notes were taken in order to document contextual information and enhance data (Creswell, 2013). Field notes documented characteristics of geographic settings and demographics of the overall area (Phillippi and Lauderdale, 2018). For example, it was extremely difficult to get from the train station to where School B was located due to the only train station being location next to motorway. This meant that I could not walk from the train station to my hotel or the school which meant that I had to travel to by taxi. In documenting geographical settings information, I also spoke with locals in various locations in order to understand the surroundings that young people grew up in. In one conversation with a taxi driver, I learned that people living in the Welsh area that School B was located in were experiencing increased deprivation and poverty due to declining coal, iron and steel production.

It is important to note that all field notes were recorded following (Mulhall, 2003) focus groups and interviews as I aimed to be fully present, engaged and maintain eye contact with research participants during my time with them. Field notes (see Appendix L, p. 337) were also taken on the evening prior to focus groups with young Roma people in School A (Wales) which saw me spend the night at Mrs H's house with her and her family. During this time, I shared dinner with her family and was then invited to spend the night as Mrs H thought it would be easier for me to travel to the school in the morning. The evening spent with Mrs H was fruitful as I was offered a glimpse into her daily routines, where she would continue working and sourcing

charity goods for the young people and families in her care until 23:30pm. In entering the field, I took the position that ‘I kn[e]w nothing’ and allowed young people and stakeholders to teach me about their lives (Kawulich, 2005, p. 45).

I approached participant observations with an *ad libitum* strategy (Jorgensen, 2015), wherein I noted details that I considered important and interesting about exchanges with young people and their educational settings. I noted as many descriptive observations as possible. For example, I drew a physical map of one of the porta cabins that young Romani Gypsy people utilised as an educational space in school B. I found this set up interesting as one room looked like a beauty spa, with massage beds, tables for manicures and hairdressing stations (see Appendix M, p. 338). The TESS team had informed me that they had applied for funding to create this space over 6 years ago based on their then female students’ aspirations but the girls within the most recent cohorts were did not aspire to careers in the hair and beauty sector. The other room looked like an ordinary classroom filled with artwork and poetry created by young people (some of which I photographed see Appendix N, p. 339). I also photographed Mrs H’s classroom in addition to the field notes I recorded after my trip due to the large volume of furniture, clothes and charity goods she collected for families and stored in a corner of her classroom (see Appendix O, p. 340).

Following the initial observations regarding school settings, I moved towards a more focused observation strategy during focus group interviews (Kawulich, 2005). During focus groups with young people, I observed interactions and paid particular attention to social relationships and tensions that emerged during the interview process. For example, it struck me that the young Romani Gypsy boys in Wales had internalised demarcated gender roles and I worried for their well-being due to the pressures of being the sole bread winner in the family. The concern I felt for them led me to question their internalised norms during the interview and I documented their non-verbal responses (Phillipi and Lauderdale, 2018) (see Appendix P, 341). Following the transcription of focus group and semi-structured interviews, I employed the field notes in order to add important contextual information regarding student surroundings as well as vital non-verbal content into the transcripts (Sandelowski, 1994).

Semi-Structured Interviews

According to Holstein and Gubrium (1995, p. 1) the interview as a method of gathering data is a ‘universal mode of systematic enquiry’. As mentioned in the preceding section, focus group and individual interviews can be structured, semi-structured and unstructured. Semi-structured

individual interviewing techniques were employed with adult populations. Atkinson and Silverman (1997) contend that interviews allow us to make sense of our lives. Individual interviews then offered an appropriate method to provide further insights into some of the potential challenges facing young Roma, Gypsy and Traveller people. Focus group and individual interview participants were both viewed as epistemologically active, collectively co-constructing knowledge throughout the research process.

There are a number of challenges associated with semi-structured interviews as a method for qualitative data collection. It is generally understood that it is not possible for research to be impartial (Hammersley and Traianou, 2012) or value free (Kawulich, 2012). There were incidents where I had to take an emancipatory stance in challenging prejudicial points of view that were echoed by research participants as passivity and neutrality in the face of prejudice was not an option. To this end, interviews in the current research were not only what Kong et al. (2002, p. 254) described as a ‘methodology of friendship’ but a methodology of knowledge sharing in order to challenge stereotypical attitudes.

By way of illustration, when interviewing a Career Adviser in Scotland who blamed a lack of English fluency on the culture of young Roma students, (see Chapter seven, p. 193) my natural response was to challenge her. I did this by illuminating to the research participant that Roma as a language cannot be found on google translate and young people can often not read or write in their own language thereby necessitating further support. I also pointed out that this support was severely lacking within the respective educational institution. In addition, I felt that it was necessary to illuminate the effects of poverty on language acquisition and educational engagement through examples identified in English and Welsh schools where language acquisition support structures were cited as having a positive impact on learners and increasing attendance rates (95 percent attendance rates in school A and C), with young people completing secondary school and moving on to further and higher education (see Chapter seven, p. 235).

It is important to note that the Career Adviser espoused these deficit informed ideas within the first two minutes of the interview, and I challenged them immediately. Despite the stance I took in challenging her prejudicial ideas, she continued to express discriminatory views freely throughout the interview without considering them as problematic. This incident led me to question whether the researcher has to remain ‘neutral’ within interview settings so as to not influence the data collections outcomes (Turner, 2010) as my stance did not alter what she was willing to disclose.

Moreover, during one particular interview a visibly distressed teacher in Scotland (school D), who had been working to increase the support available to young Roma people used the interview as an opportunity to ask questions related to how best to support the children in her school. While analysis had not yet taken place, a comprehensive guide for what was appearing to work was sent to the teacher as well as e-introductions to the staff teams from secondary schools in England and Wales who participated in the current research. Research participants across the home nations have subsequently been communicating virtually and sharing best practice.

The Scottish teacher mentioned above has also travelled to school C in England to identify good practice with the aim of applying findings to her own school context. Despite her efforts, however, unless issues around language acquisition support and adequate resourcing are addressed, young people will not experience parity of access. In a personal communication (25th February, 2019) from the same teacher following the interview, she stated the need for language acquisition support in her secondary school:

Madilyn is in our school for 3 hours per week – on a Friday 9-12. It would be useful to have Madilyn, or a bilingual PSA, in 5 days per week. This staff member could not only be used to support learning in school, but also to support pastoral issues

As can be seen from the email excerpt above, and as will be evidenced in subsequent sections (see Chapter seven, p. 227), there is a need for an adequately resourced full-time bilingual support worker in educational settings so that young can access the curriculum. Full-time language acquisition support units have been found to be correlated with positive outcomes for learners (Ager and Strang, 2008).

The Sampling Process

A number of scholars have written about the difficulties in gaining access to ‘closed’ Roma, Gypsy and Traveller communities as research participants and the need for relationship building based on trust (Messing, 2014; Hamilton, 2017). Levinson and Sparkes’ (2005) ethnographic research exploring the interface between Gypsy culture and the educational system in England details the researchers’ challenges associated with negotiating access to Gypsy research participants and how they overcame reluctance from community members.

Similarly, Marcus (2016a, p. 77) speaks of the challenges associated with the ‘elusiveness of the Gypsy/Travellers’ when attempting to recruit a sample. She noted that gaining access was problematic and time-consuming - taking her just over a year to meet the first Scottish Traveller that was willing to participate in her research. Based on previous scholars’ experiences, I anticipated that gaining access to Roma, Gypsy and Traveller people would be challenging. However, the sampling process within the English and Welsh fieldwork contexts was converse to that demonstrated in previous studies.

In the original ethics application submitted for this thesis, the purposive sampling criteria stipulated:

- Roma, Gypsy and Traveller young people
- Aged 10 and above
- Living anywhere in England and Scotland
- Parents, teachers and Career Advisers

Based on support from a Romani Gypsy Police Inspector, Michael, from the Gypsy, Roma and Traveller Police Association (GRTPA), who emailed community members and stakeholders on my behalf, a number of stakeholders responded to the call for participants across England and Wales. Although the current research was initially meant to take place in England and Scotland, I felt that it was important to represent and not omit the voices of young people who ‘wanted to speak’. Therefore, amendments had to be made to my initial ethics application and approval was subsequently granted in order to extend the geographical parameters of this research to include Roma, Romani Gypsy and Irish Traveller participants living in Wales.

Access to the school in England was facilitated by Flora, a female Roma Police Constable who is a member of the GRTPA. Following a screening call at 7am regarding the aims of my research, Flora then facilitated introductions with a school in England. The school’s Vice Principal, Steve, then made contact with me regarding the success that his school had achieved with Romanian Roma young people. Before the research could proceed, however, Steve requested that I undergo a ‘screening’ phone call with the Student Progress and community liaison worker Emanuel to discuss the questions I planned on asking students as detailed below,

We have built an extremely good relationship with our community. We would want to make sure that we do not damage any reputation with them (Steve, personal communications 14th November 2018).

Both Steve and Emanuel were protective over the young learners in their care and took steps to ensure that I would not ask young people questions that could potentially damage the relationships they had built up with Roma families over the years. In addition to talking through my focus group questions, I was also requested to submit my interview schedule for screening. The school staff were satisfied with the proposed questions, and I was able to proceed with my research without any changes.

To this end, it must be acknowledged that the ease with which I accessed research participants was a direct result of the relationships that had been formed and nurtured over the years between Roma, Gypsy and Traveller police officers, schools and third sector organisations. Similarly, Forster (2018) noted that the ease with which she accessed Romani Gypsy and Irish Traveller community members, was due to the relationships built up over years by the community organisation that she approached. From this perspective, gatekeeping is viewed in a positive light and as a means to protect and care for vulnerable communities and the relationships fostered with them over time.

Gaining access to Scottish Traveller research participants in Scotland echoed Marcus' (2016) fieldwork experiences and proved to be challenging. The approach taken to sample recruitment within the Scottish context included, emailing multiple local authority education departments, schools, NGO's and Traveller site managers between August 2018 and October 2019. I also changed my approach throughout the process, by recording videos of myself where I would give an overview of who I am, where I am from, the nature of my research and why it is important to me. I shared these videos with known community members and community groups. Despite my best efforts I battled to gain access to communities.

Through the relationship I had formed with team members from Article 12 in Scotland during my role with Show Racism the Red Card Scotland, it was thought that they would act as gatekeepers to the Scottish Traveller community. Community workers from Article 12 did arrange a focus group with young people living on the site in North Cairntow for the 22nd of November 2018, however, upon arrival, the young people decided not to attend. While I was unable to access young Scottish Traveller people in educational settings, two young adults who identified as Travellers participated in the current research. Bernadette and Shera were recruited through Article 12 in Scotland and were willing to share their educational and career guidance experiences. It is also important to note at the outset, that when I arrived at interviews with adult stakeholders in Scotland, they saw the interview as a means for acquiring guidance

and support from me for working with young Roma people. At the time of submitting this thesis, I have still not accessed Scottish Traveller students in secondary schools.

Overall, I conducted eight focus groups and four semi-structured interviews with 36 young Roma, Romani Gypsy, Scottish Travellers, Irish Travellers, and Showmen research participants across England, Wales and Scotland. I also conducted a focus group with eight stakeholders from Fife Council Education Services, Skills Development Scotland and Fife Migrant's Forum in addition to 17 semi-structured interviews with six teachers and teaching staff, seven Career Advisers and four parents across England, Scotland and Wales.

The purposive sampling process continued until enough data was gathered to ensure saturation (Fusch and Ness, 2015) had been reached with fieldwork concluding in the May of 2020. I determined saturation had been attained when the data gathered reflected the heterogeneous population within the present study and no new themes emerged from discussions. To this end, the data collection process continued over 18 months until there was an excess of data and all communities identified within the purposive sampling criteria had the opportunity to have their voices heard.

The School Environments in England, Wales and Scotland

The following section provides an overview of the secondary schools and stakeholders within educational institutions across England, Scotland and Wales. It is also important to remind the reader of the varying policy and legislative contexts within which the current research took place. As detailed within the literature review, the educational systems and qualification frameworks available to young people differ depending on their geo-political context. The Government of Wales Act and Scotland Act in 1998 resulted in the devolution of powers (including education, skills and social policy) to the National Assembly for Wales and the Scottish Parliament that had previously been reserved to the U.K government (Reynolds, 2008). This devolution of powers then, has resulted in differential education and career guidance provision across the three countries, with implications for learners.

Two secondary schools were located in Wales. School A is a mixed community school that catered for the 11-18 age range. There were 1040 young people on the school roll, with staff supporting 100 young Roma people who had a 95 percent attendance rate (interview with Mrs H, a teacher in school A). The presence of multi-language teams in school A, provided vital

support that students needed to engage with the curriculum and career guidance services. The teacher in charge of Language Acquisition within school A, Mrs H, spoke five languages (Hungarian, Romanian, Slovakian, English, and Welsh) and was supported by two team members who were also multi-lingual.

School B was an English-medium school that catered for the 11-16 age range. There were over 600 pupils on the school roll, with a dedicated team of six Traveller Education Support Services staff (TESS) supporting 28 young Romani Gypsy Traveller people with an 82 percent attendance rate (interview with Liani, a TESS staff member). While the school only catered for the 11-16 age range, further support was given to young people regarding taster days at college as well as filling out college applications to complete Year 12 (ages 16-17) and Year 13 (ages 17-18) in sixth form colleges.

Moreover, within the secondary school team, a member of the Romani Gypsy community worked as a teaching support assistant (Estyn, 2019). Importantly, due to devolved educational policy within the Welsh context, schools are able to offer young people a more flexible curriculum. The programme within school B is bespoke and takes each student's needs into account. For example, 14 boys take part in a flexible school curriculum, where they work with their fathers two days a week. The TESS team also provides students the opportunity to take their GCSEs earlier in the year in order to accommodate families who travel.

School C is an academy group sponsored mainstream, co-educational school in England that caters to young people from the 11-16 age range. The 2010 Academies Act resulted in a change in provision within the English context, whereby Academies received funding directly from the government as opposed to local authority funding and are run by an academy trust (Academies Act, 2010). There were 612 learners on the school roll, with staff supporting 151 young Roma people with a 95 percent attendance rate (Steve, personal communications 14th November 2018). Moreover, 66 percent of students in school C spoke English as an additional language with a dedicated team of full-time staff members who also supported them with English language acquisition. In addition to the language and literacy support offered to young people, school C also provided language acquisition and literacy classes to Roma parents.

The numbers of Roma students that remained engaged in education from Year seven (ages 11-12) until Year 11 (ages 15-16) was unheard of in the Scottish context, as evidenced through audible gasps in the tape recording as well as from Scottish participant Vicky (education

department EAL support) (see Chapter seven, p. 233). The numbers were provided by school C's Vice Principal as below:

Table 1. Number of young Roma people attending school C per year group

	GRT		ALL	
	#	%	#	%
Year 7	31	25	124	100
Year 8	38	27	140	100
Year 9	41	35	118	100
Year 10	22	17	128	100
Year 11	19	20	95	100
ALL	151	25	605	100

The hands-on approach of the Vice Principal was again evidenced when he shared young people's destination data with me, nine months after initial data collection:

In terms of their destinations data – we have 14 going on to college, one starting an apprenticeship and the other four we have no information for (Steve, personal communications 21st August 2019)

The collection of ethnic monitoring data is vital. Encouraged by ACERT and the National Association of Teachers of Travellers + Other Professionals' (NATT+) (Foster and Cemlyn, 2012), the Department for Education and Skills (DfES, 2003) in England and Wales, revised ethnic monitoring categories in January 2003. This revision meant that Roma, Gypsy and Traveller students were categorised under 'Traveller of an Irish Heritage' or 'Gypsy/Roma' (DfES, 2003). Such categories also appear in the Pupil Level Annual School Census Data (PLASC 2003-2008 [now known as the School Census]) thereby allowing the DfES to monitor and analyse the performance of young Gypsy, Roma and Traveller people. It is pivotal that young people's destinations are monitored in order to identify needs, design targeted interventions and effectively allocate resources (Hay et al., 2020).

School D is a denominational, co-educational, comprehensive school catering for the 11-18 age range in Scotland. There was (X) number of students on the school roll, with staff supporting an unknown number of young Roma people. Due to the need for anonymity, the number of learners on the school roll cannot be disclosed. Moreover, the number of Roma students currently attending school D was unknown due to the SEEMiS¹⁰ recording system being broken. The support I observed in the Welsh and English schools was not replicated in the Scottish context in relation to college and university taster days. Nor was support available to young people in completing further and higher education application forms from Skills Development Scotland (SDS). Due to learners' lack of English fluency, focus groups were facilitated by a Roma Home Link Worker who supported students in the school once a week on Friday mornings for three hours.

Due to a distinct lack of multi-lingual support in school D, it is difficult for teachers to assist students who speak English as an additional language, who are as a result unable to communicate their needs to teaching staff. It was also communicated to me that whilst Roma students are 'geographically included', they can't 'access the curriculum' (Charlotte, teacher, school D) due to the near non-existent English language acquisition support available to young people in school D. As will be discussed in following sections, however, this lack of support is having an impact across the school resulting in staff feeling that they do not have the time or resources to support Roma students in particular (See chapter six, p. 191).

Discussions with SDS staff revealed that students 'couldn't speak English' and Career Advisers couldn't engage with them as 'they don't have translators' (see Chapter six, p. 191) As will be detailed in subsequent sections, the lack of language acquisition support for young Roma people served as a barrier to learners accessing both the curriculum and career guidance services. It is also important to note, that this lack of support was not only found within school D's local authority area but was replicated in another Scottish local authority area (Fife) where schools are relying on volunteers to support young people.

In addition to school D's SEEMiS system being broken, it is difficult to provide attendance rates for young Roma people within this Scottish school due to the lack of ethnic monitoring data categories in order to monitor attendance in Scotland (Hay et al., 2020). The Scottish Government's (2016a) attainment data only includes the response options 'Occupational

¹⁰ SEEMiS is an Education Management Information system used by Scottish local authority schools and manages all education related data.

Gypsy' and 'Other Travellers', and fails to mention of Roma communities. The inability of educational authorities to monitor and analyse destination data for young Roma people is a concern (Lane and Smith, 2019). The data is important in order to bridge the education gap based on targeted interventions through the provision of resources such as, language support delivered by dedicated, and full-time staff members.

Finally, contrary to provision evidenced in the Welsh and English schools, the Scottish context did not provide bespoke support for young Roma learners in their care. As Charlotte explained, 'so we have got nothing like that. No bespoke provision for GRT education. It's just all out of the big pot'. From this perspective, localised austerity measures appeared to be impacting on Roma students ability to access education (Ryder and Cemlyn, 2016).

The school environments across the three home nations offered unique insights into the support available to young people and how students' education, aspirations and horizons for action are facilitated and nurtured within. The institutional habitus or 'school affect' became a focus of methodological enquiry and allowed for the juxtaposition between inclusionary and exclusionary practices across educational institutions in England, Scotland and Wales (Lanskey, 2015).

Drawing on the work of Irish Traveller Sindy Joyce (2018, p. 68), who observed that young people participating in an after-school project in Galway thrived in 'safe spaces', the current research demonstrates how safe school environments facilitate and nurture students' aspirations and career development. The schools that young people attended were pivotal to their continued engagement and retention in education. The 'wrap around care and hand-holding' (Zoe, Career Adviser, England) evidenced in some schools, was critical to broadening learners' horizons.

The Participants

The data and analysis within the current research is based on fieldwork with 36 young people between the ages of 11 and 27 years old. The gender split across the sample included 22 Roma, Romani Gypsy and Scottish Traveller and Irish Traveller girls and women and 14 Roma, Romani Gypsy, Irish Traveller and Showmen boys and men across England, Wales and Scotland. From the sample, the majority of young people were interviewed in groups of four to eight in addition to four semi-structured interviews with young adults (Ana, Bernadette,

Kasey and Arthur Joskin) between November 2018 and May 2020. It is important to note, that the young adults who participated in this research have strong activist links and their experiences may not be reflective of the wider community and may impact on findings. Moreover, it is vital to consider the types of accommodation research participants currently live in. The young Romani Gypsy people in Wales as well as Kasey in England all lived in caravans on sites while the remainder of the research participants lived in publicly funded housing across the three home nations¹¹. The focus groups and semi-structured interviews took place in secondary school classrooms, mobile classrooms, families' homes, coffee shops and over Skype. Table two summarises research participant demographic data using 'Super-Hero' pseudonyms for anonymity.

Table 2. Brief profile of Interviewed Participants¹²

Participant	Ethnic Identity	Gender	Age	Grade	Country
Cat Woman	Romani Gypsy	F	13	Year 8	Wales
Super Woman	Romani Gypsy	F	13	Year 8	Wales
Poison Ivy	Romani Gypsy	F	13	Year 8	Wales
Gypsy Tony	Romani Gypsy	M	13	Year 9	Wales
Pikey Bradley	Romani Gypsy	M	14	Year 10	Wales
Big Man Wayne	Romani Gypsy	M	12	Year 8	Wales
MC Allen	Romani Gypsy	M	12	Year 8	Wales
EE	Romani Gypsy	M	13	Year 9	Wales
Smooth Move	Irish Traveller	M	12	Year 8	Wales
Big Man	Irish Traveller	M	14	Year 10	Wales
Ana	Roma	F	14	Year 10	England
Ariana	Roma	F	13	Year 9	England
Nicki Minaj	Roma	F	16	Year 11	England

¹¹ It is important to note that both housed research participants and those living on sites are largely sedentary and there will be differences in access to education for those who still live a nomadic way of life (see for e.g. Greenfields and Smith, 2010).

¹² Table 2. Profile of Interviewed Participants may also be found in Appendix Q (p. 340) for ease of access.

James	Roma	M	14	Year 9	England
Lauren	Romanian Roma	F	16	Year 11	Wales
Sonja	Romanian Roma	F	16	Year 11	Wales
Seb	Croatian Roma	M	17	Year 12	Wales
Kooper	Romanian Roma	M	16	Year 11	Wales
Mrs H	Slovakian Roma	M	13	Year 8	Wales
Katalina	Romanian Roma	F	14	Year 9	Wales
Ronaldo	Romanian Roma	M	11	Year 7	Wales
Magic woman	Italian Roma	F	13	2 nd year	Scotland
Super cat	Romanian Roma	F	12	2 nd year	Scotland
Lenka	Romanian Roma	F	12	2 nd year	Scotland
Magic Cat	Romanian Roma	F	12	2 nd year	Scotland
Participant 1	Roma	F	12	2 nd year	Scotland
Participant 2	Roma	F	12	2 nd year	Scotland
Spanja	Romanian Roma	F	13	2 nd year	Scotland
Alyssia	Romanian Roma	F	15	3 rd year	Scotland
Participant	Romanian Roma	F	15	4 th year	Scotland

London	Romanian Roma	F	15	3 rd year	Scotland
Messi	Romanian Roma	M	13	2 nd year	Scotland
Bernadette	Scottish Traveller	F	23	Final year of further education	Scotland
Shera	Scottish Traveller	F	27	No qualifications	Scotland
Kasey	Irish Traveller	F	26	Honours degree	England
Arthur Joskin	Showman ¹³	M	27	Honours Degree and postgraduate diploma	England

The table above shows research participants ethnic identity, gender, age, year of school, geographical location and current occupations for the young adults in the cohort. 32 young people within the current research were attending secondary schools across England, Wales and Scotland at the time of focus group interviews. While three young adults were in the process of completing or had completed further or higher education and only one young adult held no qualifications.

A total number of 22 stakeholders participated in the current research and four parents. An unexpected focus group also took place with eight adult research participants including staff from Fife Migrant's Forum, a staff member from Fife Council's Education and Children's Services, an SDS Career Practitioner and community volunteers supporting Roma families in Fife. I also conducted semi-structured individual interviews with 17 stakeholders including teachers, Career Practitioners, Roma and Romani Gypsy parents who all provided valuable contextual information. Participants were requested to select a pseudonym, however, a few participants chose to self-identify. Table three¹⁴ summarises the profiles of the stakeholders and parents who were interviewed in the current research.

¹³ Arthur Joskin chose to self-ascribe as a 'Showmen' as he felt that various Government administrations have started using 'Showpeople' without consulting community members before this change in terminology

¹⁴ Ethnic identities have been omitted for the all stakeholders (teachers and Career Advisers) in order to protect the anonymity of Scottish participant's in particular and ensure that they cannot be identified.

Table 3. Profile of Stakeholders and Parents¹⁵

Research Participant	Role	Country	Interview type
Wonder woman	Teacher	Wales	Semi-structured interview
Sheila	Teacher	Wales	Semi-structured interview
Lisa	Teacher	Wales	Semi-structured interview
Zoe	Career Adviser	England	Focus Group
Emi	Roma support teaching staff	England	Focus Group
Marianna	Roma Mother	England	Semi structured interview with translator present
James	Romani Gypsy Father	England	Semi-Structured interview
Mihael	Roma Father	Scotland	Semi-structured interview
Remus	Roma Father	England	Semi structured interview

¹⁵ Table 3. Profile of Stakeholders and Parents added to Appendix R (p. 343) for ease of access.

Terrence	SDS Career Adviser	Scotland	Semi-structured interview
Alison	Teacher	Scotland	Semi structured interview
Anna	SDS Career Adviser	Scotland	Semi structured interview
Chris	Fife Migrants Forum	Scotland	Focus Group
Billy	Fife Migrants Forum	Scotland	Focus Group
Suzanna	Case worker	Scotland	Focus Group
Vicky	Education department EAL support	Scotland	Focus Group
Clinton	SDS Career Practitioner	Scotland	Focus Group
Gary	Manager Fife Migrants forum	Scotland	Focus Group
Sylvia	Volunteer	Scotland	Focus Group
Michaela	Volunteer	Scotland	Focus Group
Mrs H	Teacher	Wales	Focus Group and Semi-structured interview
Sarah	SDS Scotland	Scotland	Semi-structured interview

Charlotte	Teacher	Scotland	Semi-structured interview
Falon	SDS Career Adviser	Scotland	Semi-structured interview
Richard	SDS Career Adviser	Scotland	Semi-structured interview
Sherrie	Article 12 Community Development Worker	Scotland	Focus group with Shera

The current research prioritises the data gathered from the focus group and individual interviews with young people and provides ample room for their voices to be heard throughout the data analysis. I have opted to give primacy to student voices as previous studies are often centred on the perspective of teachers and school professionals who purport that young Roma, Gypsy and Traveller people are responsible for their academic disengagement and underachievement (Peček and Munda, 2015). Further, I have prioritised the data from young people in order to address the paucity of literature on Roma, Gypsy and Traveller students' experiences of career education and guidance within educational settings. By listening to their stories, we can understand their experiences, needs and concerns. While the data from stakeholders is used, it is done so to illuminate good practice based on learners' needs or expose serious equality issues that need to be addressed to ensure equity of access.

Interview Process

Each focus group and interview began with introductions and a description of the nature of the interview. Research participants were given information sheets as well as consent forms to sign and were informed of their right to withdraw at any point (see Appendix D, p. 320 and Appendix G, p. 328). Parental consent was obtained by the schools on behalf of the researcher prior to focus groups taking place, however, young people were also given their own consent

forms to sign so that they felt that they had the freedom to choose (hooks, 2015). Translation support was required for focus groups in the Scottish context as well as for the semi-structured interview with a Roma mother Marianna in England. Madilyn in Scotland and Emanuel in England, translated the nature of my inquiry to research participants, explaining the consent forms and notifying them of their right to withdraw from the research process at any point. However, I acknowledge that the nature of what was stated may have been lost in translation (Temple and Young, 2004). Participants were then encouraged to select a ‘Super-Hero’ name to protect their identities.

Fontana and Frey (2008) problematize the traditional interview format in that it requires that the researcher be courteous and friendly but refrain from sharing their own views and are therefore expected to avoid answering direct questions asked by participants, thereby limiting reciprocity. In reaction to traditional interviewing paradigms, feminist researchers such as Oakley (1981, p.49) have noted that there is ‘no intimacy without reciprocity’. As such, it was important that I shared my own life experiences with young people during the interview process, answering their questions, expressing my feelings, and sharing in exchanges of their culture - for example, pertaining to the use of language and specific cultural terms such as *gadjé*¹⁶ or *gorjio*¹⁷ with different community groups created what Fontana and Frey (2008, p. 139) describe as a ‘sharedness of meanings’.

Interview Settings

Madriz (2000, p. 841) observed that utilising spaces that are familiar to research participants ‘further diffuse[d] the power of the researcher’ thereby ‘decreasing the possibilities of *otherization*’. Due to the historic marginalisation that Roma, Gypsy and Traveller communities have faced and continue to face it was important that research participants selected a space that was familiar to them. I met with young people in secondary school classrooms, mobile classrooms, family homes, coffee shops and over Skype.

Each focus group lasted from 60 to 90 minutes and semi-structured interviews with adults lasted from 45 to 90 minutes. In two of the focus groups in England and Wales, where students did not have class after the focus groups, they chose to remain in the focus group and continued discussions over their break time. The focus group conducted with Romani Gypsy girls in

¹⁶ The term *gadjé* (also spelled *gadze* or *gaje*) is a Roma word to describe non-Roma people or outsiders (Kuiper, 2019).

¹⁷ The term *gorjio* is an Anglo-Romani word to describe non-Romani community members or outsiders (Clark, 2001).

Wales ran over the end of the school day as we were all so immersed in discussions that their parents were standing at the school gate waiting for them and had to call them to let them know that they were there to fetch them. Young people, dependent on their community group also asked me if I was ‘Roma’ or ‘Romani’ and a number of students thought I was ‘one of them’ or that I ‘looked Roma’, or ‘looked like a Gypsy’. Perceiving me to be an insider could have potentially made them feel more comfortable around me.

Focus group discussions and semi-structured interviews were audio recorded and personally transcribed verbatim, which allowed for a deeper immersion in the data. The transcriptions, used in conjunction with audio-recordings facilitated methodical analysis of data for themes (Braun and Clarke, 2006, 2012, 2019; Braun et al., 2018). All transcripts and audio-recordings were stored as encrypted files in line with General Data Protection Regulation (European Parliament, 2016) and ethical approval conditions made by the University of the West of Scotland’s Ethics Committee.

Data Analysis

Schwandt (2007, p. 6) describes data analysis as the ‘heart’ of a research project, wherein a researcher pieces together the data collected through interpretation and theorisation. Data analysis is a process of sorting and ordering the data corpus and selecting the data set that will be used to make sense of and give meaning to participants’ experiences (Braun and Clarke, 2006; Marshall and Rossman, 1999; Mason, 1996). Data analysis is a recursive process (Ely et al., 1997) that begins at the onset of the study and develops over time. Thematic data analysis (Braun and Clarke, 2006, 2012, 2019) was employed within this thesis to identify patterns (themes), interpret multiple aspects of these patterns, and provide a rich and detailed account of the qualitative data.

The clear and concise thematic analysis approach developed by Braun and Clarke (2006, p. 78), was utilised as a foundation as it addresses the ‘anything goes’ critique levelled at qualitative research (see for e.g. Antaki et al., 2002; Laubschagne, 2003). I analysed the data according to Braun and Clarke’s (2006, p. 87) six-phase guide to performing thematic analysis:

Phase one: ‘Familiarising yourself with the data’

During this phase I personally transcribed the data of each participant, ‘reading it and re-reading it’ (Braun and Clarke, 2006, p. 87), and made notes on salient points emerging from

the transcripts. The frequency and duration of time spent familiarising myself with the data, allowed for a deeper immersion into students' experiences.

Phase two: 'Generating initial codes'

Once I had familiarised myself with the data, I then printed out the transcripts, and manually collated and coded the data in a systematic approach . I opted to do this manually as opposed to utilising qualitative data analysis software packages such as NVivo as it allowed me to make sense and observe the data over a larger space. During this phase, I focused on sorting and coding the data into 'meaningful chunks of text, such as passages [and] quotations' (Attride-Stirling, 2001, p. 391). This phase formed the foundation to the development of themes through the following identified codes:

- Educational experiences
- Career guidance experiences
- Family support
- Aspirations
- Good practice
- Equality concerns
- Barriers
- Help-seeking
- Self-regulation
- Miscellaneous

Phase three: 'Searching for themes'

During phase three I organised the aforementioned codes into initial overarching themes and sub-themes (see Appendix S, p. 345) . I then searched the data again for any codes relevant and systematically added those to related themes. In deciding on themes, Braun and Clarke (2006, p. 82) suggest that it is both a 'question of prevalence, in terms both of space within each data item and of prevalence across the entire data set' and whether the data item captures an important aspect in relation to the research question. To this end, if the data item was prevalent across the data set and if it helped address my research questions, the item was included in either the candidate theme or the sub-theme (i.e. overarching theme: aspirations; sub-themes: educational aspirations and career aspirations).

Phase four: 'Reviewing the themes'

During this phase, I reviewed and refined my candidate themes and sub-themes. As I worked through the review process, it became clear that some candidate themes could be merged (i.e. equality concerns and barriers were merged into the candidate theme ‘intersectional barriers’ which was then broken down into sub-themes). The data items within the miscellaneous pile were discarded as the items were not prevalent enough across the data corpus (Braun and Clarke, 2006). It is important to note, that two sub-themes ‘mental health’ and ‘LGBT identity’ identified under the overarching theme of ‘intersectional barriers’ had a sufficient amount of data to support them but were not included within this doctoral research due to space concerns.

Adopting a manual approach meant that I could move codes and themes and synthesise the data with ease into a thematic map which allowed for reviewing themes effectively in relation to Level one (coded data extracts) and Level two (entire data set). If a coherent pattern was identified within Level one data extracts, I moved onto Level two in order to determine if the themes corresponded to the data (Braun and Clarke, 2006).

Phase five: ‘Defining and naming themes’

During phase five, I defined and named each theme and began analysing the data in order to identify the ‘overall story’ that the data appeared to be telling (Braun and Clarke, 2006, p. 87).

Phase six: ‘Producing the report’

After defining and naming the themes, the final analysis and chapter write-up took place using vivid extract examples that were further analysed in relation to the research questions, literature and theoretical orientations. This process involved going ‘beyond [the] description of data’ in order to ‘make an argument in relation to [my] research questions’ by providing a ‘coherent, logical and interesting account of the story’ the data told ‘within and across themes’ (Braun and Clarke, 2006, p. 93).

The data analysis process took place over seven months, during which I re-visited previous analysis sessions in an iterative manner, which further shaped and influenced the writing up of the analysis chapter. Finally, thematic analysis requires that the researcher make their epistemological orientations and positionality explicit (Holloway and Todres, 2003). I now turn to consider my multiple social belongings that informed and influenced the data collection approach adopted and the subsequent analysis.

Researcher Positionality and Reflexivity

Gadamer (2004, p. 301) suggests that our histories determine the range of our 'vision that includes everything that can be seen from a particular vantage point'. Similarly, Hall (1994, p. 447) contends that the researcher 'speak[s] from a particular place and time, from a history and a culture' that is positioned in a context that is fluid and ever evolving. Positionality within the research context refers to the researcher's 'discursive situatedness in the social world' (Fremlova, 2018: 101) that must be understood in 'intersectional terms' (Grimaldi et al., 2015, p. 140) from multiple social locations and identities (Yuval-Davis, 2006).

These multiple identities include one's 'race', ethnicity, gender, gender identity, age, sexuality, ability and class, which have the potential to influence the 'contemplative eye' of the researcher (Bourdieu and Wacquant, 1992, p. 69). The researcher has to reflect on these fluid identities in relation to hierarchical structures and the relationship between the researcher and the researched. As Grimaldi et al. (2015, p.138) observe, these 'multiple social belongings' determine the researcher's attitude to the research participants and ultimately impacts on the research process and final analysis.

A large body of literature has dealt with positionality in the researcher-researched relationship through the lens of an insider-outsider dichotomy (Merton, 1972; Bhopal, 2010) with others instead suggesting that it operates along a spectrum (Breen, 2007; Trowler, 2011). Insider-research refers to the exploration of one's own cultural or community group (Naples, 2003) and is thought to confer advantages to the researcher such as easier access (Baser and Toivanen, 2018) due to shared attributes and 'perceived closeness' (Voloder, 2014). Whereas the advantages of outsider-research include the perceived objectivity and neutrality of the researcher, who is posited to become less emotionally involved as a result of exploring a cultural or community group different to one's own (Kusow, 2003; Voloder, 2014).

More critical approaches have problematized this binary approach to understanding the researcher-researched relationship (Amelina and Faist, 2012). By way of illustration, Kusow (2003) has questioned whether outsider researchers can truly understand the complexities that arise between different cultural groups. Hellowell (2006) on the other hand, suggests that a researcher can gain unique insights about a particular community group without being a member. In support, Bucarius (2013, p. 691) contends that it is possible for a researcher to be an 'outsider trusted with insider knowledge'. In working to find a middle ground between this

dichotomy that simultaneously transcends the ethno-national divide, Carling and colleagues (2014, p. 14-17) proposed five types of ‘third positions’ that are relevant to the current thesis:

1. Explicit third party: the researcher’s identity is recognisably different and neither part of the insider or the majoritarian outsider community.
2. Honorary insider: the researcher obtains honorary insider status as a result of demonstrable cultural competence, a sustained commitment to the community in question or language skills.
3. Insider by proxy: where the researcher shares some attributes with the researched such as having a migration background.
4. Hybrid insider-outsider: the researcher’s identity shares characteristics with both insider minority and outsider majority groups.
5. Apparent outsider: the traditional insider/outsider dichotomy wherein the researcher is assumed to share the same ethnic background with research participants, but ultimately becomes problematic as the relationship progresses due to other identity markers such as class.

I moved between these types of ‘third identities’. Particularly relevant to the current thesis were the ‘honorary insider’, ‘insider by proxy’, and the ‘hybrid insider-outsider’ third identities. While these identities may have resonated with how I felt, and indeed how community members made me feel, I have to acknowledge that regardless of my feelings I am an outsider, as I can never fully understand the experiences of Roma, Gypsy and Traveller community members (Kusow, 2003; Fremlova, 2018).

Reflexivity is an ongoing methodological process wherein the researcher self-consciously reflects on the relationship between themselves and research participants - always mindful of the lenses adopted to understand and represent this relationship (Fremlova, 2018). While reflexivity has sometimes been referred to as ‘narcissistic and egoistic navel gazing’ (England, 1994, p. 24), Grimaldi et al. (2015, p. 147) hold that reflexivity is an opportunity for the researcher to engage critically on the relationships between ‘research, symbolic violence, exploitation and domination’, thereby increasing the potential for a non-hierarchical relationship between the researcher and researched (Bhopal, 2010).

A number of non-Romani scholars have addressed the issue of researcher positionality and reflexivity when exploring and theorising about the lives of Roma, Gypsy and Traveller people (see for e.g. Tremlett 2009; Kóczé, 2011; Grimaldi et al., 2015; Lambrev, 2017; Fremlova,

2018). In Bhopal's (2010) research with Gypsy and Asian women, she spoke of the complexities associated with how the researcher's identity can affect the relationship with marginalised participants and particularly for researchers who belong to a dominant social group. Bhopal (2010) emphasised the need for scholars to reflect on power dynamics when conducting research with vulnerable groups so as to not perpetuate further marginalisation of Gypsy communities.

Similarly, Tremlett's (2009) research illuminated how even well-meaning scholars, in seeking to demonstrate the heterogeneous nature of Roma communities tended to recycle narratives that entrenched difference and conceptualisations that homogenise and 'other' Roma, Gypsy and Traveller identities. More recently, movements within Critical Romani Studies such as 'Nothing about us without us' (ERRC, 2015) have seen activists and academics alike placing an emphasis on the need for Roma, Gypsy and Traveller participation in the production of knowledge and policy making. Historically, these communities have been the object of study with research done on them (Vajda, 2015) instead of research for and with them (Greenfields and Ryder, 2012; Roma Research Empowerment Network, 2014; Tremlett and McGarry, 2013). Romani scholar Brooks (2015, p. 61) employs the term 'epistemological erasure/invisibility' to describe the dearth of Roma, Gypsy and Traveller individuals and communities involved in and producing 'Romani knowledge'.

Critically then, it is vital that I consider my positionality and how my multiple intersecting identities have influenced my own worldview and the steps I have taken to ensure that I conducted research with and for the young people who participated in this research. In the following section, I offer insights into the steps taken to devise research methods, ensuring that community members were central to the development of the current thesis' interview guides; the steps I took to challenge racist attitudes and institutional exclusion; and the 'Roma: Broadening Horizons' project that I collectively constructed with young Roma people as equal partners in Scotland in order to address their needs as identified within the current thesis.

Research Positionality: Acknowledging Privilege

In setting out my positionality, I am a Queer, white, migrant, gadje, ally-identified researcher who has worked on Roma, Gypsy and Traveller related issues for just over six years. While I am a migrant, I hold a British passport which confers on me privileges that other migrants do not have access to (Clark, 2020). My history along with my multiple identities have allowed

me to occupy various spaces during the data gathering process, oscillating between being an insider and outsider and at times transcending the binary. I conducted the fieldwork for the current thesis between November 2018 and May 2020. Prior to this, however, I have a long history of activism and involvement in anti-racism movements as discussed below.

Highly influential in my development was having grown up in apartheid South Africa. To this day, I can vividly recall when Nelson Mandela was released from prison. I was sitting on a swing in a play park listening to white adult conversations that suggested the end of apartheid meant that ‘Blacks were coming to kill all of the whites’. As a nine-year-old child, I could not understand this ‘racist fear’, just as prior to this I could not understand why Black people needed *dompasses*¹⁸ to travel in and out of white areas for work. For the sake of brevity, however, I cannot dwell on my early experiences, except to say that from an early age I was aware that I was part of the dominant group - the oppressors. I refer back to Delgado and Stefancic (2017) who argue that racism is a common, everyday experience for Black and Ethnic minority people and add that as a white person, I have seen racism occur incessantly over three decades. Endemic and unrelenting. When I was old enough, however, I volunteered in various grassroots movements, spending my weekends in ‘townships’ distributing food, footballs and bicycles and eventually setting up a volunteer arts club for Black children in one of South Africa’s most dangerous and deprived areas (Hillbrow).

Upon arriving in Scotland, my activism continued, and I eventually took up a post where I could combine working for equalities while also earning an income through my role at Show Racism the Red Card Scotland. Relevant to the current thesis, it was during this time that I formed relationships with two Scottish Travellers who worked for Article 12 in Scotland. Bernadette, her sister Meg along with an Education worker for Show Racism the Red Card and I worked together for over a year developing a programme of education to tackle racism perpetuated against Traveller communities. Admittedly, due to my South African origins I was a ‘tabula rasa’, ignorant of who Traveller people were prior to working with Bernadette and Meg. It was also during this time that I met Scottish Traveller Professor Colin Clark, on a cold, winter night at the Cross-Party Group for Racial Equality in Scottish Parliament. This serendipitous and ‘happenstance’ (Krumboltz, 2009) encounter ultimately resulted in this

¹⁸ An Afrikaans word (the oppressors language) that when translated means ‘stupid passes’. Black and Ethnic minority South Africans were required to carry these passes with them at all times to prove their identities and were not allowed in White areas during certain hours without risking arrest.

thesis with Colin as my lead supervisor three years after our initial meeting. These early encounters ultimately led me to associate ‘Travellers’ with ‘Educators’.

This association continued once I had embarked on the doctoral journey. I attended the Critical Romani Studies summer school at the Central European University in Budapest in 2018 followed by the Critical Romani Studies Conference in 2019. During this time I formed deep friendships with Roma scholars and activists, and it was often after the long days in seminars that my education really began, gaining further unique insights into the lived histories of my Roma friends.

I need to acknowledge that these experiences resulted in a deeply emotionally entangled network of friendships that potentially influenced how I approached research participants and ultimately how I analysed and interpreted the data (Creswell, 1998). In the same way non-Romani scholar Fremlova (2018) reported similar experiences, blurring the lines between being an insider and an outsider. Contrary to Fremlova, however, who embodied ‘neither of the two’ binaries, I felt that at times I embodied both simultaneously through my research with young people, which I discuss below, following considerations of critical whiteness.

Drawing on the work of hooks (2000), Kóczé (2011), and Vajda (2015, p. 48) I acknowledge that Roma, Gypsy and Traveller emancipation cannot progress until ‘the concept of critical whiteness is incorporated into it’. As a result of my migrant identity, I have experienced racism twice since my arrival in Scotland. The first incident occurred on a night bus heading home from work, where a random stranger upon hearing my accent told me to ‘f*** off back to my own country’. I was shocked by the incident and due to my ‘whiteness’ I hadn’t noticed I was any different before this.

The second racist incident occurred during my time as the head of anti-racism charity Show Racism the Red Card Scotland. Having condemned the sale of Golly dolls in shops in Glasgow across a number of newspapers (see for e.g. Lerche, 2015) a male individual telephoned the office and asked to speak to me. After disagreeing with the position I set out within the article, he started asking me where I was from, and when I responded, ‘South Africa’, he suggested that I ‘go back to South Africa and take the refugees with me’.

While I am a migrant, I am a white presenting migrant and ultimately these experiences do not ‘qualify’ me to speak on matters related to racism. I only highlight these experiences as they have shaped my ‘contemplative eye’ (Bourdieu and Wacquant, 1992, p. 69) and I need to acknowledge that I can never understand the persistent racism that Black and Ethnic minority

communities experience on a daily basis, and I need to take responsibility for the white privilege I receive and exercise.

As McIntosh (1999, p. 38) argues white privilege is an ‘invisible package of unearned assets, special provisions, maps, passports, codebooks, visas, clothes, tools, and blank checks’ that can be ‘cashed in at any point’ whilst ‘remain[ing] oblivious’ to them. Unchecked and ‘taken-for-granted white privilege results in white normativity’ (Fremlova, 2018, p. 105). In order to mitigate this, I engaged in a continuous process of critical reflection by trying to see my own history and identity through the eyes of Roma, Gypsy and Traveller community members (Vajda, 2015). I was reflective of my white privilege from the outset of the research process as well as the power differential within focus groups as a result of the younger age profile of participants. As such I paid close attention as to how I devised research methods (Harding, 1991; Emirbayer and Desmond, 2012) in order to reduce the potential for power hierarchies (Bhopal, 2011) and to increase young people’s comfort through the employment of focus groups (Deuchar and Bhopal, 2013).

Methodological and Ethical Reflections

The interactions during focus group and semi-structured interviews that I conducted with young people and parents may be characterised as warm and welcoming. As mentioned in the preceding section, young Romani Gypsy and Roma people often assumed that I was one of them. In all focus group settings the students would always ask if I was Romani Gypsy or Roma. At other times such as walking down school hallways, other Romani Gypsy and Roma learners’ who did not participate in the current research would stop and ask me if I was a member of the community. I was always extremely flattered to be considered a community member and let the young people know that while I was indeed flattered, I was not in fact one of them. This usually resulted in them asking where I was from due to my accent. When I told them that I was from South Africa, excitement and questions would follow, with students also teaching me about the ‘Gypsies in Africa’. Overall, my migrant background offered me ‘insider-by-proxy’ status (Carling et al., 2014).

Young people, young adults and parents alike were so warm and open, which made me feel like an insider. Following on from interviewing some of the young adults who participated in the current research I formed friendships with them potentially blurring the lines between ‘friend’ and ‘research’ participant (Fremlova, 2018) which may have impacted on how I

analysed and interpreted the data (Creswell, 1998). The employment of various methods of data collection and analysis, however, facilitated multiple vantage points on students' experiences, which may have served to mitigate the blurring of these boundaries. The use of focus groups, semi-structured interviews, observation and a rigorous approach to analysis (Braun and Clarke, 2006) allowed me to draw more trustworthy conclusions within the analysis than a single data source would have permitted.

It is also important to note, that a number of young Roma people (research participants and non-research participants) requested to follow me on Instagram and Twitter following the focus groups. While I was initially hesitant, some young people in England stated that they followed Flora the Roma Police Officer, while others in Wales followed their teachers. There was also the need for reciprocity as participants' had shared their lives with me. This pattern re-emerged again in the Scottish context with two young people requesting to follow me.

Moving some of the researcher-researched relationships online offered further unique insights into research participants' worlds (Marcus, 1995). Drawing on Goffman's (1964, p. 134) conceptualisation of a social situation as an 'environment of mutual monitoring possibilities, anywhere within which an individual will find himself accessible to the naked senses of all others who are present, and similarly find them accessible to him'. During these digital social situations, the researcher and the researched were able to monitor each other.

I had the opportunity to glimpse into their families, share in their birthdays, Christmas' and celebrate their milestones along with them. For example, when Nicki Minaj, a young Roma person living in England passed her driver's licence or the day that she finished school, I was able to celebrate with her and congratulate her. Similarly, students have celebrated with me every time I 'championed the cause'. For example, liking my posts that challenge the inequality Roma, Gypsy and Travellers face or when I represented their voices to the Advisory Council for the Education of Romani and Other Travellers Annual (ACERT) Conference in London.

Research participant and Showman Arthur Joskin invited me to speak at the ACERT conference which also allowed for further member checking (Creswell, 2012; Guba and Lincoln, 1989). In presenting my findings at the conference, it ultimately led to the recruitment of further participants such as Irish Traveller Kasey, perhaps because I demonstrated cultural competence and a sustained commitment to the cause thereby granting me access as an 'honorary insider' (Carling et al., 2014).

A further unintended consequence of the researcher-researched relationship moving online was that I was able to obtain additional data that I would not have had access to within focus group settings. Indeed, Hallett and Barber (2014, p. 307) were correct in pointing out that it is ‘no longer imaginable to conduct ethnography without considering online spaces’. As will be detailed within the subsequent chapter (see for e.g. Chapter five, p. 155) one of the Scottish Roma participants Alyssia was reluctant to speak during focus group settings but reached out to me following the focus group on Instagram. During this interaction, she shared her aspirations and requested further support, which she felt she was not receiving in school in order to achieve her dreams. The digital researcher-researched relationship also allowed me to conduct longitudinal research, as I could continue to have discussions with some of the young people on their progress toward achieving their stated goals (see for e.g. Chapter five, p. 145).

It is important to acknowledge, however, that online data gathering certainly brought up ethical concerns. With participants data being so easily accessible (Boyd and Crawford, 2012), I had to approach any data gathering reflexively and in a manner that I could be held accountable (Airoldi, 2018). First, it was important for me to ensure that parents knew that their children and I were ‘digitally connected’. I therefore requested that young people ask their parents for their consent and also invited parents to follow me on social media platforms in order that they knew who I was. Second, I decided early on that I would only use data that was particularly relevant to the thesis in order to challenge inequality. To this end I only used the aforementioned data from Alyssia and Nicki Minaj. Third, on both of these accounts I requested ethical consent from both young people and their parents. In the case of Alyssia, I also obtained her permission to discuss her request regarding hairdressing with one of her teachers (Charlotte), while keeping her name anonymous, which she agreed to, and I discussed the request with Charlotte (teacher within school D who participated in the current research).

Further online data gathering ethical considerations related to equity of internet access. The semi-structured interview with Irish Traveller Kasey took place over Skype, with Kasey in her trailer on-site. While the interview with Kasey yielded such rich and valuable data that touched on a number of key themes identified through analysis, data was lost due to internet connection issues. While we spoke for just over two and a half hours, the data presented here is a mere snapshot of the important issues she raised, some of which were not fully audible on the recording due to internet connectivity issues. Consistent with the literature, there were issues surrounding internet accessibility and quality on-sites (Article 12 in Scotland, 2018; Hay et al., 2020) that impacted on the data collection process.

At times throughout the research process, I was also confronted with the privilege I have taken for granted as a white migrant who can speak English fluently. The semi-structured interview with Roma mother Marianna in England as well as the focus groups with Roma students in Scotland required translation support. Translation support in England was provided by a member of the teaching staff team who is a Romanian migrant, while a self-ascribed Roma migrant who spoke both Romani and Romanian provided translation support to learners in Scotland. The employment of translators may have introduced language hierarchies and power differentials into the research process, while the participant's meaning may have been lost during the interpretation process (Temple and Young, 2004) ultimately impacting on the knowledge produced (Grace and Eng, 2019).

In further confronting my own privilege, another theme that emerged during the fieldwork process related to research participants' multiple identities. I overlooked my privilege associated with being a member of a nuclear family (Bengston, 2001). Two of the young people who participated in focus group interviews responded that they came from lone parent families within group settings which may have caused them distress. In response to my questions regarding who students spoke to at home regarding careers, one young person responded that he didn't have a father, while the other stated that it was only her and her Mom. These experiences served as a reminder of Stewart's (2010) call for Romani studies to transcend beyond the lens of ethnicity and encouraged me to be more reflective of the multiple social identities (Grimaldi et al., 2015) I occupy that influenced item construction.

My final thoughts on being confronted on the privilege I exercise during the doctoral research is paradoxical. As a migrant, I have listened to some family members, friends and wider community members comment on 'those foreigners coming here and taking all the jobs'. On the one hand, I have found myself feeling guilty for being a 'foreigner' and potentially taking a job from a Scottish born 'majority' community member over the last seven years. While on the other hand, I have also experienced significant guilt regarding the doctoral scholarship I have received. Ultimately, I have been given an opportunity that arguably should have gone to a Roma, Gypsy and Traveller scholar, and I have advanced my own career based on the knowledge produced with marginalised community members.

According to Fremlova (2018, p. 105), the paucity of Roma, Gypsy and Traveller scholars within the field as well as the lack of opportunity structures available to them is 'symptomatic of white-normativity' and is a structure of dominance that needs to be redressed. I acknowledge

that more needs to be done to address systemic racism, increase access and alter opportunity structures for Roma Gypsy and Traveller. To this end, I support positive action and call for further and higher education institutions to address their lack of diversity, whilst also calling on funding bodies to widen access for all Black and Ethnic minority students through positive action. On the micro level, I have attempted to address inequality by placing student voices at the centre of the process whilst aiming to embed social justice and impact throughout the research process.

First, I ensured to prioritise the data gathered from the focus group discussions with young people, providing ample room for their voices to be heard throughout the data analysis. I therefore worked to ensure that the narrative is based on Roma, Gypsy and Traveller knowledge production and expertise (see for e.g. Brooks, 2015; Grimaldi et al., 2015; Kóczé, 2011) in order to challenge majoritarian discourse (England, 1994) through presenting counter-stories (Solórzano and Yosso, 2002).

While this thesis presents counter-stories (Solórzano and Yosso, 2002) to challenge dominant discourses that serve to subjugate, I also felt that I could do more to challenge inequality. Grimaldi et al. (2015) conducted fieldwork in a Roma camp in Italy and illuminated an exchange wherein a Roma participant requested that the researchers asked the local council for a school bus to come to the camp. The researcher responded that they were merely there to map living conditions which could potentially improve the lives of Roma people. Exasperated the Roma participant responded ‘always the same story! Everyone listen, but nobody act’ (Grimaldi et al., 2015, p. 141). I wanted to do more than listen, I wanted to act. To this end, I took a number of steps to ensure that I wasn’t a ‘hit and run researcher’, merely ‘intrud[ing] into [my] subject’s privacy and giv[ing] little or nothing in return’ (Reinharz, 1983, p. 95) as detailed below:

- I lobbied the Scottish Parliament Equal Opportunities Committee to include Roma as an ethnic monitoring category and problematised the conflation of terminology within policy documents (Fulton MacGregor MSP, personal communications 3rd of August 2018; Monica Lennon MSP, personal communications 27th July, 2018).
- I submitted evidence to the National Records of Scotland consultation in December 2018 in addition to submitting a petition calling for the inclusion of Roma in Census 2021. The petition provided support from the following organisations: University of Dundee, University of Edinburgh, University of Glasgow, University of Strathclyde,

University of the West of Scotland, Glasgow Caledonian University, GMB Union, Unite the Union, Unison, Glasgow City Council Education Services, the SNP, the Scottish Greens, Glasgow City Council Social Work Services, and Friends of Romano Lav.

- I co-authored a journal article with colleagues and fellow activists (Hay et al., 2020) arguing that the omission of Roma as an ethnic category from data gathering processes renders entire populations invisible within policy interventions and restricts both the identification of needs and effective resource allocation.
- I was also invited to become an Honorary Education Committee Member for the Gypsy, Roma and Traveller Police Association (GRTPA) wherein I wrote briefings regarding educational exclusion and recommendations for best practice for the GRTPA. In this role, I also worked with GRTPA members as well as research participant James to co-develop educational content that they would deliver in educational settings.
- I have also delivered a number of educational workshops based on my research to various stakeholders such as Skills Development Scotland. One could, however, argue that these requests by SDS were ‘tokenistic’, as research demonstrates that one-off interventions are less effective than a programme of sustained education (Campbell and Hay, 2018, 2019). In support, this was evidenced by a member of SDS’ ‘Equalities Champions’ team approaching me after the presentation and stating that ‘Roma people are thieves and there is no changing them’.
- In my role as the Scottish Project Associate for the Career Development Institute of Scotland, I served as a member on Scottish Government’s Careers Strategy Steering Group providing policy responses pertaining to the equity of access work stream wherein I raised concerns related to equity of access for Roma, Gypsy and Traveller young people in the Scottish context.
- I raised similar concerns during a meeting with Skills Development Scotland and the Scottish Government’s Employer Engagement team focused on ‘employment and business outcomes for Gypsy/Travellers’ in preparation for a stakeholder meeting with Minister for Business, Fair Work and Skills Jamie Hepburn. These concerns and my calls for more targeted outreach work for these communities were, however, ignored.
- I also developed a range of intersectional lectures focusing on Roma, Gypsy and Traveller communities across Introducing Sociology, Gender Studies and Global Society modules in order to challenge conceptions within the public imaginary of who

these communities are. These lectures were well received by students and led to increased engagements and emails from students who wanted to explore further and engage in activism to support community members.

- I also facilitated discussions with teachers and teaching staff across schools A, C and D in order to provide further support for young Roma people and Charlotte in school D based on best practice. These discussions ultimately led to Charlotte travelling from Scotland to England in June 2019 to learn from the team within school C.

In addition to the aforementioned steps, I also applied for funding from Youth Link Scotland in January 2019, in partnership with Show Racism the Red Card Scotland to develop and deliver an after-school community programme based on the needs of young Roma people. Based on the findings from this thesis I drew up a 'dynamic template' to present to funders wherein the programme aimed to blend weekly career guidance, employer engagement, sport and poetry over an eight-week period. Students would also have the opportunity to turn their poetry into a 'Theatre of Oppression' (Fleming et al., 2003; Gadamer, 2004) following participating in culture circles (Freire, 1993), where they would work with stakeholders to problem pose the barriers they are facing and work to find solutions collectively. It was envisioned that the programme would culminate in young people showcasing their work in the Scottish Parliament on International Roma Day (8th of April 2020).

Once funding had been obtained from Youthlink Scotland, I conducted a number of focus groups with learners in school D as a volunteer for Show Racism the Red Card Scotland between March 2019 and September 2019. During these focus groups, students collectively constructed and designed the programme with me. Drawing on Freire (1993, p. 22) it was a programme 'forged with, not for the oppressed', for 'who are better prepared than the oppressed to understand the terrible significance of an oppressive society' (*ibid*, p. 45). When young people had designed the programme they wanted to participate in, I took the findings to Show Racism the Red Card and Community Renewal (a Roma led Employment support NGO) and worked with their Education and Youth Workers to finalise the programme. While we had formalised the structure, young people still had the option to set the agenda weekly and take us in the direction that they saw fit thereby making it a 'living programme'.

During this time, I also recruited former students, colleagues and activists to volunteer their time on the programme weekly with career guidance delivered by Working Rite and employer engagement opportunities from organisations such as Police Scotland, GMB Trade Union, the University of the West of Scotland, the University of Edinburgh and Dyslexia Scotland. The

programme ran every Friday afternoon after-school at Queens Park FC. Due to COVID-19, however, after-school sessions were cancelled from the end of February 2020 in order to safeguard young people and at the time of writing in July 2020, the programme has not yet been completed due to the ongoing pandemic.

Conclusion

Due to the paucity of literature on Roma, Gypsy and Traveller students' experiences of career education and guidance, this thesis set out to explore students' aspirations, how they access services and their experiences thereof. In order to meet the research aims I seek to address the following research questions:

1. What are young Roma, Gypsy and Traveller people's aspirations and what support do they feel they need in order to realise their aspirations?
2. Do young Roma, Gypsy and Traveller people have equitable access to career education and guidance provision. If they do, what have their experiences been? If they have not had access, do they believe that they would benefit from career guidance, and how do they think local services could best meet their needs?

The recruitment of research participants across the three home nations was facilitated through the support of organisations such as Article 12 in Scotland, the GRTPA and former colleagues known to the researcher who worked within local authority education departments. I also compiled 'recruitment videos' wherein I offered insights into my background, the research project and details on what I would be seeking from potential research participants that I shared with various groups and across multiple platforms, so that community members could get a sense for who I am.

Working within the emancipatory paradigm, I adopted an ethnographic approach to methodology, employing a mix of qualitative methods in order to explore and understand students' experiences. I conducted eight focus groups and four semi-structured interviews with 36 young Roma, Romani Gypsy, Scottish Travellers, Irish Travellers, and Showmen research participants across England, Wales and Scotland. While student voices were prioritised in the current research, their narratives were supplemented with data gathered from a focus group with eight stakeholders from Fife Council Education Services, Skills Development Scotland

and Fife Migrant's Forum in addition to 17 semi-structured interviews with six teachers, seven Career Advisers and four parents across England, Scotland and Wales.

The analytic process involved drawing on Braun and Clarke's (2006) six-phase guide to thematic analysis, to identify patterns (themes), interpret multiple aspects of these patterns, and provide a rich and detailed account of the qualitative data. The coded extract examples were then further analysed in relation to the research questions, literature and theoretical orientations. I drew on a number of theoretical orientations in a grounded practice approach to theory for the foregrounding of students' experiences. The work of Hodkinson and Sparkes (1997) was employed to examine the interface between structure and agency in learners' education and career decision-making; critical race theory (Solórzano and Yosso, 2002) in order to illuminate the high aspirations held by Roma, Gypsy and Traveller students and their parents and challenge dominant master narratives that suggest that these communities do not want a career or education; and theories of intersectionality (Crenshaw, 1991; Yuval-Davis, 2006; Hills Collins and Bilge, 2019) that allow for a more nuanced understanding of how complex and intersecting social inequalities within the educational field influence students' horizons for action. These theories are thread throughout the analysis and findings chapters and are useful in elucidating how young people's agency is constrained by structural forces within their field whilst exposing and challenging the discrimination within students' experiences.

I have been explicit in setting out my positionality remaining 'vigilant' (Spivak, 1984, p. 184) in my reflexivity, embedding considerations of social justice throughout the research process from interview guide item construction to the thematic analysis and interpretation of data. During this process, I was also mindful that my research participants were bringing me into their lives and sharing their stories and it was important that I 'gave back' by working to challenge the inequality that they faced. This chapter detailed the steps that I took and the impact I made to alter the structural barriers within young people's fields so as to ensure I was not complicit in being a 'hit and run' researcher (Grimaldi et al., 2015, p. 141). The significance and originality of this thesis will be set out in the subsequent chapters as the findings allow for more a nuanced understanding of how intersecting social inequalities within the educational field influence students' horizons for action across England, Scotland and Wales.

Chapter Five

Aspirations: ‘We are not all fortune tellers, beggars and scrap metal thieves’

The following chapter reflects and analyses the experiences and perceptions of young Roma, Gypsy and Traveller students and parents across England, Scotland and Wales. To date, there have been no studies that have attempted to explore these learners’ educational and career aspirations cross-nationally. This section attempts to address this gap and provides a space for student voices to be ‘represented’ (Spivak, 1988). Students’ aspirations will be presented as counter-stories in order to disrupt mainstream master narratives surrounding Roma, Gypsy and Traveller community members’ educational and career aspirations. The majority of young people who participated in my research indicated that they planned on completing secondary school and attending either further education or higher education institutions. Their narratives also suggest that they were making pragmatically rational decisions and taking steps in the present in order to achieve their future goals. The current chapter then, seeks to address my first research question: What are young Roma, Gypsy and Traveller people's aspirations and what support is available to them to realise their aspirations?

Educational Aspirations: ‘I am gonna do everything’

A large body of research perpetuates a prevailing master narrative that young Roma, Gypsy and Traveller people have low educational aspirations (Hutchinson et al., 2011; DfES, 2003; Ofsted, 2003). Similarly, research by Forster (2018, p. 119) found that those supporting community members perceived them as having a ‘lack of aspiration [...] and low levels of engagement in education’. As Arthur Joskin, a 27-year-old, Showmen, school psychologist and activist explains, the attitudes that he encounters are too often, ‘It’s not worth it because he will just claim benefits or do whatever basic labour his dad does or, as in my case, he’ll just do the fair’. The following section provides counter-stories to challenge pejorative master narratives, as told by young people, who demonstrate compelling agency in their aspirations for completing secondary school and enrolling in further and higher education, as a means to achieve their career goals.

The majority of students who participated in this research intended to ‘go all the way’, when we discussed their educational aspirations. Mrs H, a young Roma boy (13) attending an 11-18 school in Wales stated,

I am gonna do everything. I’ll go to sixth form and then uni, miss.

Mrs H’s words reveal that he had considered the educational ladder he would need to traverse in order to attend university. Indeed, a number of students had thought of the steps that they would need to take in order to achieve their educational aspirations. Where learners attended an 11-16 school, and regardless of their age or stage, they noted that they would have to attend college to complete sixth form. For example, Ana, (Roma girl, 14, England), stated ‘I’ll go to college then university in [...]’; while Poison Ivy (Romani Gypsy girl, 13, Wales), detailed the steps she planned to take in order to attend higher education as she stated, ‘I wanna go to college and uni, get my A-levels through the college’. Similarly Nicki Minaj, (Roma girl, 16, England) had planned her next steps ‘I’ll go college to [...] for sixth form’.

The majority of the boys also stated that they intended to complete secondary school, with only three Romani Gypsy boys in Wales suggesting that they did not intend to continue post-16. Learners who were attending the 11-16 school, which had no sixth form provision in Wales, often highlighted that they would need to go to college if they wanted to complete sixth form. While all students will experience what Hodkinson and Sparkes (1997) described as structural turning points¹⁹ upon leaving sixth form, students who attend 11-16 institutions will have a turning point imposed on them earlier, during their transition to sixth form college. Regardless of these imposed turning points, young people remained unwavering in their intentions to complete sixth form. Payne (2003) contends that this commitment may reflect their awareness of the increased risks of unemployment due to their ethnicity, relative to their white peers.

As can be see through the following exchange between Irish Travellers, Smooth Move (12), Big Man (14) and EE (Romani Gypsy, 13), during a discussion in Wales, young people had not only considered attending college to complete sixth form, but were drawing on family members’ careers in their own educational decision-making,

¹⁹ Hodkinson and Sparkes (1997, p. 39) define a structural turning point as one that is ‘determined by the external structures of the institution involved’ such as the ‘structural change that comes at the end of compulsory schooling’.

- Big Man: Go to college for sixth form, learn how to do it then get out working.
- EE: Yeah go to college. Maybe do construction, my brother went to college - he studied plumbing.
- Smooth Move: Comes in a load of work. You know my cousin is doing that yeah? He was doing plumbing.

Similarly, James (14) who was attending the 11-16 English academy school, had also noted the steps he would have to take in order to attend college before he could access higher education, citing a preference for physical proximity within his considerations,

I think after I finish school, I would like to go to [...] college, cause it's like, not far from here it's in [...]. Just where I live, so it's closer and after college I go university.

Consistent with the literature amongst minority and working-class populations, a number of students cited physical proximity as a barrier to further and higher education, preferring to attend educational institutions closer to home (Beremenyi, 2020; Ball et al., 2002b; Foskett et al., 2008; Reay et al., 2001; Smith, 1997). Similarly Pérez and McDonough's, (2008) sample of Latino secondary school students in Los Angeles, cited proximity to home and family as a factor associated with college selection. A further consideration in participant's decision-making process was the cost of travel, with students aiming to reduce costs by studying closer to home. Drawing on Hodkinson and Sparkes (1997), student narratives reflected that their geographical horizons for action were bound by the need to be closer to their families as well as consideration of the financial implications of studying further afield.

Although learners have demonstrated a compelling degree of agency in detailing the steps that they would need to take in order to achieve their dreams, structural barriers that exist within their educational field may constrain their continued engagement in post-school education. Learners in schools B and C (11-16 schools) with no sixth form option may be less likely to attain their desired goals of completing secondary school through sixth form college and transitioning to higher education. A number of authors contend that students continued engagement in post-16 education is contingent on them spending Year 11 in a school with a sixth form (Connor et al., 1999; Foskett and Hesketh, 1997; Payne, 1998). Foskett et al. (2008), however, suggest that students may be able to mitigate the effects of attending 11-16 schools,

if the school increases the quality and amount of educational and career guidance support available to them.

Throughout my research, many young people had not only considered the steps that they would need to take to complete sixth form before attending further and higher education – they had also made pragmatically rational decisions regarding the relevant subjects that would support their future careers. For example, when I asked young people what their favourite subjects were at school and why, Smooth Move (12) and Big Man (14) drew links between subject choices and their respective future worlds of work, as the exchange below reveals,

- Smooth Move: Maths, English, History, Welsh, French.
- Big Man: Science and Design technology.
- Nicola: Why those subjects?
- Smooth Move: Sometimes it's boring, and sometimes it's good. But you graft on top of it. I like Maths.
- Nicola: Why Maths?
- Smooth Move: Cause when I am older and I need to price a job.
- Big Man: How to add it all up!
- Smooth Move: So say now, if a woman wanted a drive done and I'd say it's £200, and she wanted a fence done. Then you would have to add something on top of that. It depends all on how much the materials are.
- Nicola: And you Big Man?
- Big Man: DT is important to me, I enjoy it and I can use it later on for a career.

As can be seen through these narratives, students provide career advice to their peers (Fabes et al., 2014), based on previous learning experiences with family members, but they have also retained that experiential knowledge and applied it to their own career considerations. Big Man and Smooth Move had centred their favourite subjects based on their respective utility for the

future, suggesting that subject choices are instrumental and pragmatically rational (Hodkinson, 1998). Similarly, Poison Ivy (13), had also drawn links between the subjects she enjoys at school and their applicability to her career aspirations of becoming a lawyer:

I like history, cause it's something I am really interested in and it's something that can benefit me in the future.

Young Roma migrants in England drew links between the opportunities available to them in the U.K and the steps that they would need to take in order to achieve their educational and career aspirations. The exchange below highlights that their migration to the U.K was a turning point (Hodkinson and Sparkes, 1997) broadening what they believed was possible for their education and career goals,

Nicola: What's the difference between schools here and in Romania?

Nicki Minaj: Oh there's a big difference. Everything is different!

James: Every school in the U.K. is better than Romania, because there's lots of things to do here.

Ariana: There's more possibilities!

Nicki Minaj: And opportunities!

Nicola: If you stayed at a school in Romania, what do you think you would have done at the end of school?

Nicki Minaj: I would still wanna learn and be a lawyer since six years old, but I don't think I will have the possibility to do it.

Nicola: Why?

Nicki Minaj: Because this is too hard to achieve, and you never get the opportunity to do all the steps you have to.

Nicola: And you get the opportunity to do all the steps here?

Nicki Minaj: Yeah.

As students' geographical horizons broadened, so too did their horizons for action (Hodkinson and Sparkes, 1997). A common theme that emerges from the transcripts is that students are

aware of the opportunity structures available to them within their new geographical field and are eager to take the necessary steps to achieve their aspirations, demonstrating purposiveness and pragmatism (Hodkinson, 1998). Indeed, Ana (Roma, 14, England) had noted the steps that she would need to take, despite the perceived difficulty of course work and attending university for her to achieve her career aspirations. As she explained,

Oh that's hard! Well I have thought of a few options, like being a Drama teacher. But I know I have to do a lot of course work and university. And I might as well do it but it's kind of hard.

The exchanges above provide a powerful counter-story to dominant narratives by demonstrating the steps students are planning to take to achieve their future aspirations. Within the health literature, Roma, Gypsy and Traveller communities are represented as being present-oriented (Lawrie, 1983; McCann, 1987; Feder et al., 1989; Jackson et al., 2016), living for the moment and not for the 'industrial clock'²⁰ (Forster, 2018, p. 170). Stakeholders within Forster's (2019, p. 170) research positioned Traveller identities as 'resistant to customs of time centred around employment', which impacted the design and delivery of health education workshops in the North of England. Young people in the current research, through the planning of their next steps in an educational context, demonstrated a future-oriented position centred on gaining employment.

It is important to note, however, that the young research participant's educational aspirations were not homogenous and not all students aspired to complete sixth form. For example, three out of the seven Romani Gypsy boys in Wales, who participated in the current research, advised that they only intended to complete their GCSEs in Year 11 (ages 15-16). Big Man Wayne, Pikey Bradley²¹ and Gypsy Tony, all stated that they did not intend to continue with further or higher education due to: the desire to follow more traditional paths; and concerns regarding the costs associated with continuing in further and higher education. This will be unpacked extensively in subsequent sections (see for e.g. 'Poverty and Class', p. 206).

Moreover, the data reveals that despite the compelling agency demonstrated by students in their desire to attend college, there were structural barriers within their educational field that served

²⁰ Health practitioner research participants in Forster's (2018, p. 52) research represented Gypsy/Travellers as not living in congruence with 'monochronic, linear notions of time which dominate the organisation of society'.

²¹ While the term 'Pikey' is considered pejorative (McCaffery, 2009) when used by gadjé, I have left the young person's name as 'Pikey Bradley', as students were instructed to select 'Super-hero' names and his choice of name may be indicative of him reclaiming the word with a sense of pride.

to narrow their horizons for action (Hodkinson and Sparkes, 1997). Due to the lack of support (both educational and language acquisition support [see Chapter seven, p. 247]) within school D, their decision to complete secondary school and attend college may be influenced by the perceived difficulty of such a transition along with limited institutional support,

Nicola: Do you plan on finishing your A-levels?

Magic Cat: Yeah and college, but hard.

Lenka: I don't know? I don't like this school.

Participant 1: Straight to college.

Nicola: What college?

Participant 1: (silence)

Super Cat: S6 and college. The school could help me more to do maths English.

Magic Woman: She²² doesn't want to finish school.

The excerpt above demonstrates the exclusionary dynamics within school D, characterised by unequal and limited access to education and career guidance. While a number of students aspired to complete sixth form and attend further education institutions, the forces in their field (low teacher expectations and limited support) determined this transition to be potentially beyond their horizons for action (Hodkinson, 2008). Despite perceived difficulty, a number of learners' continued to enact their agency within their means by highlighting that they felt in need but not in receipt of support. Moreover, none of the Scottish cohort could name college provision locally, they simply knew that they desired to attend 'college'. Student narratives appear to suggest that their educational field has taken insufficient account of their educational needs and aspirations resulting in the failure to provide sufficient and appropriate opportunities for students to explore 'what comes next'.

The data presented so far, supports the idea that Roma, Gypsy and Traveller students do indeed have educational and career aspirations. The degree to which young people can 'dream big' or even articulate their ambitions, however, is context dependent – those who have had the

²² Magic Woman's transcript narrative reads in the third person due to the translation process facilitated by Madalin. Within this focus group, Super Cat and Magic Cat could communicate in English, albeit with difficulty and support was needed at times.

opportunity to attend more supportive educational settings articulated higher aspirations (see for e.g. Chapter five, p. 154). This is in contrast to young people who were attending school environments characterised as less supportive. For a number of these young people, they were not only unable to articulate their dreams, but they were also unaware of the options available to them due to the paucity of support available to them within their school. While these participants knew that they wanted to complete school, the lack of support available to them was having a negative effect on their aspirations. London, (Roma, 15, Scotland), who was able to participate in the research without translation support, was considering dropping out of school to attend college for dance. While she desired to complete secondary school, she raised concerns regarding having to repeat third year and the perceived lack of support available to her in school D, as the exchange below demonstrates,

Nicola: Do you feel you need support from teachers to get to fourth year?

London: Yes, of course! Because I want to go to college and that as well. I just want to pass and leave third year. I want to go to sixth form. I want to finish S6, so I can get a good career. But I don't know if I am 18 and what class I am going to be in?

As can be seen from the exchange above, London valued education, as demonstrated through her desire to complete sixth form and college. She also showcased her agency in illuminating that she needed additional support in order to attain her educational aspirations. However, fear of potential failure and the lack of support within school D, may have compounded her sense of helplessness, and I worried that she may not be able to achieve her education and career aspirations due to the lack of an appropriate level of support. The absence of support within London's educational field may be limiting what she believes is possible and constraining her horizons for action (Foskett et al., 2008; Hodkinson and Sparkes 1997).

Career Aspirations: 'I wanna do human rights and sometimes people need help'

The preceding section demonstrated that the majority of young people who participated in focus group discussions valued education and planned on completing their A-levels, either through their 11-18 school or through the college route (where they attended an 11-16 school). A number of students also indicated that they planned on attending further and higher education institutions once they had attained their A-levels in order to pursue their career ambitions. Moreover, young people had drawn links between the utility of their current subjects and their

future careers, demonstrating that they had developed their own strategies and plans so that they may attain their goals. To this end, the findings presented here challenge the anecdote that *all* young Roma, Gypsy and Traveller people do not have educational aspirations (Lloyd and McCluskey, 2008; Peček and Munda, 2015).

Contrary to anecdotes in the public imaginary of ‘traditional’ Roma, Gypsy and Traveller employment patterns such as hawking and fortune-telling (Clark, 2001) or literature that represents these communities as not wanting a career (see for e.g. Marcus, 2016; McGarry, 2014), the current section demonstrates the broad range of career aspirations young people held for the future. The majority of participants’ expressed high aspirations for professional and managerial careers. Consistent with findings in both white and Ethnic minority populations (Croll, 2008) students did not demonstrate a ‘poverty of aspiration’ (Archer et al., 2014b, p. 66), but rather a poverty of opportunity (Roberts and Atherton, 2011). It is important to note, however, that learners within the current sample may not be considered to have high economic and cultural capital as was the case with Archer and colleagues (2014) sample due to the participants’ in this research descending from backgrounds that are marked by deprivation (see for e.g. ‘Poverty and Class’, p. 218).

James, a Romani Gypsy father and Police Officer in England who participated in the current research observes, community members ‘have to defend ourselves a lot more and be out there saying, “we are not all fortune tellers, beggars and scrap metal thieves”. We have got people who are highly educated teachers, nurses, doctors, lawyers - we want an education’. To this end, it is imperative that counter-stories are told so that Roma, Gypsy and Traveller community members receive equitable access to education and career services. In line with the first research question, (What are young Roma, Gypsy and Traveller people’s aspirations and what support do they feel they need in order to realise their aspirations?) I asked young people what they wanted to be when they grew into adulthood and what support they felt they needed. The following section discusses their choices, hopes and dreams for their future.

Table 4. Brief profile of Interviewed Participants and Aspirations

Interviewee	Age	Country	Aspirations
Cat Woman	13	Wales	Nursery teacher
Super Woman	13	Wales	Additional Support for Learning teacher

Poison Ivy	13	Wales	Lawyer
Gypsy Tony	13	Wales	Tree Surgeon
Pikey Bradley	14	Wales	Carpenter, mechanic or highway maintenance
Big Man Wayne	12	Wales	Brick layer, Carpenter, Rugby player
MC Allen	12	Wales	Landscaper
EE	13	Wales	Computer Game developer, YouTuber, Construction worker
Smooth Move	12	Wales	Boxer, Landscaping Self-employed
Big Man	14	Wales	Boxer, Landscaping Self-employed
Ana	14	Leeds, England	Drama teacher
Ariana	13	Leeds, England	Teacher
Nicki Minaj	16	Leeds, England	Lawyer
James	14	Leeds, England	Doctor or footballer or self-employed
Lauren	16	Wales	Hair and Beauty at college
Sonja	16	Wales	Hair and Beauty; Itec for sixth form
Jay	17	Wales	London King's College
Kooper	16	Wales	Sixth Form then University
MRSH	13	Wales	Police Officer; Army; Doctor Teacher
Katalina	14	Wales	Police Women, Doctor; Nurse
Ronaldo	11	Wales	Chef or doctor
Magic woman	13	Scotland	Singer or dancer
Super cat	12	Scotland	Veterinarian
Lenka	12	Scotland	Nail Technician
Magic Cat	12	Scotland	Dancer; Singer; Painter
Participant 1	12	Scotland	Make-up artist
Participant 2	12	Scotland	unknown
Spanja	13	Scotland	Hairdresser
Alyssia	15	Scotland	Hair and makeup
Participant 3	15	Scotland	Make-up artist

London	15	Scotland	Hairdresser/Flamenco dancing
Messi	13	Scotland	Footballer
Bernadette	23	Scotland	Currently: NGO Community Development Worker and further education students
Shera	27	Scotland	Currently: Volunteer and Activist
Kasey	26	London	Currently: Education Policy Officer, Masters Student, Activist
Arthur Joskin	27	London	Currently: School Psychotherapist, Volunteer and Activist, Honours Degree and post-graduate diploma

As the table above demonstrates, student aspirations were not homogenous reflecting both between-group and within-group differences and a diversity of aspirations (Crenshaw, 1991; Gutiérrez, 2004). A total of four young people aspired to be teachers. Students were quite specific about the type of teaching they wanted to do, with Cat Woman (Romani Gypsy, 13) indicating that she wanted to be a nursery teacher and Super Woman (Romani Gypsy, 13) aiming to be an Additional Support for Learning teacher. Ana (Roma, 14) expressed an interest in becoming a Drama teacher and Ariana (Roma, 13) aspired to be an Art teacher.

Cat Woman and Super Woman stated that they aspired to be teachers because they thought they would enjoy working with and helping children, however, I wondered if their decision had been influenced by a local Romani Gypsy community member who worked in school B as a teaching assistant. While not confirmed, the girls perhaps based what they wanted to be on what they could see within their field (Hodkinson and Sparkes, 1997). Ana, revealed that her decision to be a teacher was influenced by discussions with her Maths teachers which will be unpacked in subsequent sections (See for e.g. ‘Sources of Advice: Institutional Field’, p. 183)

Poison Ivy and Nicki Minaj aspired to be lawyers from a young age and both had been inspired by watching lawyers on television shows. Nicki Minaj (16) stated,

I wanna be a lawyer. I remember from when I was six years old, I was watching those movies about law, and those people that were lawyers and that helped people. I wanna do human rights and sometimes people need help.

During the focus group, Nicki Minaj seemed fixed on her aspirations to be a lawyer. Indeed, when I followed up with her in the September of 2019, she had started her A-levels at college with a focus on law and politics, aligned to her career aspirations discussed below:

Well now I'm gonna study law and politics and a bit of English language and I'm looking forward to getting my driving licence.

A few days after the exchange above, Nicki Minaj did indeed attain her driver's licence. A handful of scholars suggest that holding a drivers licence is very much within the domain of Gypsy and Traveller men (see for e.g. Okely, 1983; Levinson, 2008). Research by Allen (2000) suggests that Gypsy/Traveller men do not have drivers licenses as a result of not being able to read or write, or because they are unable to purchase insurance due to not having a fixed abode. Liégeois (1987) and Smith (1997), however, suggest that the desire to obtain a drivers licence amongst men serves as an incentive to learn to read and write. In considering Roma communities and specifically Roma women, Drydakis (2012) suggests that Roma women are less likely than gadje women to hold drivers licences. Nicki Minaj's success in obtaining her driver's licence, then contributes to the paucity of knowledge in relation to Roma women holding drivers licences and challenges a stereotyped narrative that purports that passing the driving test is only a concern for young men.

Poison Ivy appeared to be equally as determined as Nicki Minaj in her aspirations to be a lawyer:

When I am older, I *really* wanna be a lawyer. I have done for the last three to four years, but I don't just want to be one of those people who say they wanna do something. [Liani] is setting a meeting up for me. I am gonna shadow a lady lawyer. But that's always something I've wanted to do.

Her words demonstrate compelling agency and pragmatism as she had already begun researching the steps and processes related to achieving her aspirations. Like Nicki Minaj, Poison Ivy also recalled being inspired to become a lawyer through watching TV. A number of authors have noted that television serves as an early window into the range of occupational roles available to learners and may influence their aspirations (Archer et al., 2014b; Gehrau et al., 2016; McMahon et al., 2001).

Discussion with Poison Ivy further revealed that she had internalised stereotypical ideas and master narratives through her acknowledgment that a career as a lawyer went against the grain of ‘what people like her did’. She stated,

For Gypsies you don’t really see them with the law (laughs nervously). Usually they’re on the wrong side of the law. Gypsies are always meant to be on that side of the law, and then the police are meant to be on this side. *I really* wanna change that, and I wanna make it balanced. So we can’t be judged by what people have done in the past - we wanna move on from that stereotype.

According to critical race theory, ethnic minority community members often internalise and verbally perpetuate majoritarian and racist narratives (Solórzano, 1992; Solórzano and Yosso, 2002). For Poison Ivy, the goals of Gypsies have never centred on ‘being on the right side of the law’. Paradoxically, the racism she has internalised influenced her decision-making that centred on resistance - a catalyst for challenging perceptions of what her community does. Farris and de Jong’s (2014, p. 1513-1514) research on the intersectional experiences of second-generation migrant girls, argues that these girls often feel responsible to ‘cleanse the negative stereotypes’ surrounding their community group by ‘performing well and becoming a role model for the whole community’. Overall, Poison Ivy had clear ideas about what she wanted to do with her life and was actively pursuing her dreams by speaking to the Traveller Education Support Services (TESS) staff team regarding arranging a work placement for her to shadow a lawyer.

What struck me through the interactions that I had with a number of young people, was that they aspired to enter careers where there was a commitment towards helping others. Cat Woman, Super Woman, Ariana, and Ana, wanted to be teachers, echoing findings by Greenfields (2008) in her research with Romani Gypsy and Irish Traveller women who aspired to careers related to childcare. Contrary to findings by Greenfields however, students aspired to these professions regardless of whether or not they interfered with domestic responsibilities, which may, however, be a reflection of the age profile of the current sample.

Similarly, Poison Ivy and Nicki Minaj aspired to be lawyers so as to help others. As detailed within the table above, Mrs H (13), Katalina (14), Ronaldo (11), and James (14) also aspired to careers aligned towards helping others. Mrs H (young Roma boy), indicated that he aspired to a career in the army or the police force as it was important to him to be able to assist others:

I’ll see, maybe be in the army, or to be a police officer. To help people out.

Similarly, Katalina also expressed aspirations related to becoming a doctor, nurse or police officer:

When I grow up, I want to be a police woman, or a doctor, or a nurse. Take blood and stuff like that, it's my dream.

The participant's narratives echoed findings made by Milan-Tyner (2018) in her research exploring the impact of 'race', gender and class on African American women's career development. All research participants within her study suggested that their career decision-making was influenced by a commitment to helping others. This commitment to help people is posited to be due to early socialisation processes where Ethnic minority young people are taught to uplift their communities – a 'residual effect of the intersectionality experienced by African American women' (Milan-Tyner, 2018, p. 121). Similarly, early socialisation processes within Roma and Gypsy Traveller communities and the impact of class, 'race' and gender may influence their aspirations to help and uplift others. Student responses also embody what Freire would describe as gestures of love. For Shor and Freire (1987), the response of the oppressed to subjugation and the master narratives imposed on them by their oppressors, is that of a gesture of love which may be found either consciously or unconsciously.

Beyond a number of young people aspiring to careers aligned to helping others, their aspirations were also tied to consciously creating a better life for their families. Students were acutely aware of the challenging economic circumstances that their families were facing, and they understood their future achievements as a means to providing a better life for their families. Despite, being only 11 years old, an expression of love (Shor and Freire, 1987) emerged yet again through Ronaldo who stated that he wished to be a doctor so that he could help his family and brother live a better life, as he explains;

I want to be in sixth form. And after I want to I have car and to go to be doctor. And after, I want to do my family better and to do my brother big one.

While for Bernadette, a 23-year-old Scottish Traveller, her aspirations were tied to creating a better life not only for her family and her own community but for all disadvantaged groups. Bernadette dropped out of school at the age of 13 due to a culmination of factors. Bernadette's mother (a lone parent) suffered a stroke that rendered her disabled thereby resulting in increased caring responsibilities for Bernadette at the age of 13. During this time, Bernadette had also been experiencing persistent racist bullying at school, coupled with a perceived lack of support from teachers, resulting in her subsequent disengagement from education.

Bernadette now works as a Community Education Worker for Article 12 in Scotland (an NGO supporting Travellers in Scotland), while completing a SVQ²³ four Community Development Work at Level eight qualification. The exchange below between Bernadette and myself reveals that she managed to turn her childhood dreams of activism into employment in a manner that allows her to create social change through her role:

Bernadette: It's working for social change. I love my job.

Nicola: Can I ask why you choose to do the type of work you do?

Bernadette: I think about past experiences, and I want to change that for the future generation. I don't want anyone else to experience that and for them to actually have a chance. I want the world to be better for them. Plus, at that time there were loads of Travellers going downhill and were turning to maybe substances cause they not got anywhere in life. Or they got really bad social anxiety and they can't leave the house or a trailer, and they've got really bad depression.

Discussions with Bernadette further revealed that her aspirations were also partly influenced by her early experiences of being a victim of racist bullying (see Chapter seven, p. 221) thereby resulting in her choosing a career where she could work to ensure that others didn't experience what she had endured. Similarly, Shera a 26-year-old Scottish Traveller, felt that although she didn't know what she wanted to do, her volunteer work with Article 12 in Scotland and the Gypsy Traveller Youth Association²⁴ inspired her to believe that she could aspire to employment where she could create change. She explained:

I always wanted to do something, but I am old. I am in my twenties now. I cannae go to college. I don't want to be on the sick my whole life just cause I got depression and anxiety. That's not a life, that's no what I want. I didn't know I could do things to change things for Travellers. And then I found out that this is something I am really into. It's not just a hobby, cause you live enough life to be like let's change something about that!

²³ SVQ refers to Scottish Vocational Qualifications which are studied in the workplace, college and or with training providers and are based on the Scottish national standards, providing evidence that a learner can do a job.

²⁴ A youth forum established by Article 12 in Scotland wherein young Travellers represent and advocate for Human Rights issues that affect young people from the community.

Like Bernadette, Shera became a young carer at the age of 13 – for her sister, who was an infant at the time of her mother’s death. Shera had lost her mother to drug addiction and was left in the care of her stepfather, and then subsequently her aunt and uncle. Shera attended the first two years of secondary school, however, the death of her mother, increased caring responsibilities, and experiences of racism within school resulted in her dropping out of education without any qualifications. Now at the age of 26, she wanted to change things for her younger sister and community. Shera and Bernadette's experiences are consistent with the literature on care experienced young people, in that they left school without qualifications, eventually following a non-linear route to attain their educational and career goals (Brady and Gilligan, 2019).

During my interviews with both Shera and Bernadette, I felt that their involvement with Article 12 provided vital social capital (Hodkinson, 2008), broadening their horizons for action and what they believed was possible (Hodkinson and Sparkes, 1997). Collectively, their narratives suggest that their decisions were pragmatically rational, both cognitive and embodied, involving the ‘emotional and affective’ (Hodkinson, 2008, p. 7) drawing upon past experiences of marginalisation and oppression. Moreover, their career aspirations parallel findings reported by Ryder and Greenfields (2010) and Smith and Greenfields (2012), who identified that over one third of Gypsy and Traveller women worked in community outreach projects. The authors noted that participants valued working in this sector because they were able to support fellow community members, and it allowed for the opportunity to being gainfully employed despite having minimal qualifications.

The young Romani Gypsy boys I conducted focus groups with in Wales also drew links between future career aspirations and a desire to support their families, however, I felt that the boys were under a lot of pressure to conform to more traditional and heteronormative roles (Cheng, 1999). Consistent with the literature in other populations, career aspirations amongst Romani Gypsy boys in particular appeared to be deeply gendered (Ceci and Williams, 2010). As can be seen from the table above Big Man and Smooth Move aspired to be self-employed landscapers; Big Man Wayne aspired to a career in brickwork or carpentry; Pikey Bradley intends to be a carpenter, mechanic or work in highway maintenance; while Gypsy Tony hopes to be a tree surgeon. When I asked the young boys what inspired their decisions, there was an emphasis placed on the intergenerational transfer of tradition within Romani Gypsy communities. As Smooth Move explains,

Smooth Move: Because back in generations.

Nicola: So, is it because your dad does it and your grandad does it?

Smooth Move: Yeah!

Big Man: Yeah!

Smooth Move: It's just a routine. Isn't it?

Nicola: Have you ever thought about wanting to break out of that routine?

Smooth Move: No.

For Cossée (2005) and Clark (2001, p. 128), these aspirations are aligned to the 'economic niche that Gypsies so successfully inhabit' – 'the arena of ... multi-skilled family-based self-employment' in adapting to the changing world of work. The aspirations expressed are not, however, restricted to Roma, Gypsy and Traveller culture and traditions. For example, in their comprehensive mixed methods research, Fuller and colleagues (2005), found that within the construction and plumbing sectors, there are strong family traditions of self-employment between father and son - regardless of culture.

Two young Romani Gypsy boys attending school B in Wales added alternatives to the 'traditional' approach, when they spoke of their career aspirations. EE aspired to a career in the construction industry, but he also expressed an interest in becoming a YouTuber or a video games developer. Similarly, MC Allen aspired to a career in landscaping, but also mentioned that he had spoken to his mother about becoming a computer games developer. It is important to note that, the other research participants within MC Allen's focus group (Gypsy Tony, Pikey Bradley and Big Man Wayne), started laughing and chatting amongst themselves when MC Allen claimed that he had spoken to his mother about being a computer games developer, he quickly backtracked:

Nicola: Do you ever speak to your mom about careers?

MC Allen: Only once, she wants me to be a gamer (group chatters and laughs).

Nicola: A computer games developer?

MC Allen: Yeah (group chatters and laughs).

Nicola: That's really cool.

MC Allen: I am only joking. I wouldn't ask me mum for advice, I only ask me dad.

Nicola: But what if you get more money from gaming than landscaping?

MC Allen: Yeah but it's just what we do isn't it. Like do you know any Gypsies who do gaming? No because they call them a nerd, and give them slaps across the face. And our thing like, is cutting trees and boxing. That's our culture, that's what we do - we do bricklaying.

As can be seen from the interaction above, MC Allen dared to dream beyond the peer prescribed career horizons available to him, but backtracked when his peers began laughing and chattering amongst themselves. His words revealed conflict in his desire to break free from tradition. His departure from more traditional aspirations may be an attempt to articulate and practice a masculine identity that is in opposition to dominant masculinities (Greenfields, 2008; Bender, 2001; Haywood and Mac an Gaill, 2012). However, when his peers laughed at him, he conformed to the status quo by aligning his aspirations to the narratives shared by the other boys in the focus group and qualifying his decision by stating that 'cutting trees, bricklaying and boxing was [their] culture'.

Consistent with the literature, the exchange above reveals the influence that 'peer effect' may have on students' gendered aspirations (Crosnoe et al., 2008). The narrative directed toward MC Allen by his peers may be seen as a pattern of 'policing men' (Connell and Messerschmidt, 2005) in order to achieve hegemonic homeostasis. Teasing on the part of the young Romani Gypsy boys, serves to structure and maintain the hierarchy, as MC Allen may fear being exiled from the group, which may be socially devastating as group belonging may be a source of masculinity and self-worth for many young boys (McGuffey and Rich, 1999).

Later on in the focus group however, MC Allen again re-stated that he had aspirations beyond the traditional routes. As discussions continued, it became increasingly evident that his mother was a 'Chief Adviser' (Haynes et al., 2013) in his decision-making. When I asked if he planned on completing secondary school he stated, 'I have to - me Mam - you are more brainy when you stay in school'. It is important to note that MC Allen was the only Romani Gypsy boy to cite his mother as a source of guidance.

In coming to understand the educational and career aspirations that young people held for themselves, it is important to note that a significant number of participants placed responsibility for achieving their dreams solely at their own feet. Similarly, findings by Cassidy et al. (2006) amongst an ethnically representative sample of students across eight schools in Glasgow, demonstrated that an emphasis was placed on individual effort in attaining their stated aspirations. When I asked respondents in this research how they planned on achieving their aspirations, their responses alluded to individual effort, self-regulation and responsibility. MC Allen stated he would, 'go for [his] exams. Pass 'em all. Do [his] work. Be a good boy. Go to school. Learn'.

Mrs H (young Roma boy) believed that he would have to 'change [his] attitude to learning', however, he went on to state, 'I do have a good attitude but more high level, and to work harder and push myself in different higher levels, in different subjects. But it's hard; it's not easy.' It became clear that although both participants had already boasted a positive attendance record and demonstrated strong engagement with their respective schools, they believed that in order to achieve their career goals, each would have to self-regulate their behaviour more effectively.

In defining self-regulation, Porath and Bateman (2006, p. 185) contend that it is the 'processes that enable an individual to guide his or her goal-directed activities over time and across changing circumstances', which includes the regulation of 'thought, affect and behaviour'. While for Van der Heijde (2014) self-regulation is agentic in nature whereby motivational processes influence resource allocation to achieve goals. MC Allen and Mrs H's words demonstrate that they are motivated to regulate their thoughts and behaviour in order to attain their goals and overcome the barriers they perceive within their respective environments. A number of authors have suggested a high sense of self efficacy for self-regulated learning promotes academic aspirations (see for e.g. Bandura, et al., 1996; Zimmerman et al., 1992), as well as career decision self-efficacy and career exploration behaviours (Kim and Kim, 2014). Bandura et al. (2001) meanwhile, found a correlation between self-regulation, academic attainment and feeling responsibility for the welfare of others.

For Shor and Freire (1987), these young people are not merely waiting for their oppression to disappear, but are actively struggling to challenge and change the structure of their world through enacting self-regulation which is agentic in nature (Van der Heijde, 2014). Freire affirms that in dialectical thought, the world and action are inextricably linked, and in struggling for their humanization, the oppressed accept responsibility for their struggle.

However, it is also important to note, that by placing responsibility on themselves and their own behaviour, young people are adapting to the existing neoliberal social order, which fosters obedience and subordination (Vassallo, 2012), rather than questioning the mechanisms which have historically left children, such as themselves, at a distinct disadvantage from their peers.

The only participant in this study to have questioned the meritocratic paradigm is Kasey (Irish Traveller, London King's College Masters student), which will be unpacked in subsequent sections (see for e.g. 'Poverty and Class', p. 209). Contrary to previous findings by Smith (2007), students appeared to have subscribed to the concept of meritocracy - if you work hard and 'be good', you can be successful. However, while young people can regulate their own behaviour, they have little influence over their social environment.

A number of authors have previously written about Gypsy/Traveller girls' educational aspirations being aligned to the hair and beauty sector (see for e.g. Derrington and Kendall, 2004; Knipe et al., 2005; Marcus, 2015, 2016). Within the current research, however, only seven young girls out of 22 chose aspirations related to the hair and beauty sector, with none of the boys indicating an ambition to work in this sector. In Wales, two Roma girls stated that they aspired to a career in hair and beauty, while five Roma girls in the Scottish context aspired to careers within the hair and beauty sector. Lauren (16) and Sonja (16), who were attending the 11-18 school in Wales described hair and beauty as their passion. When I asked Lauren what influenced her decision she stated 'I am more into doing make-up and hair. So it's, like, my passion to do'. Natalie (15), Spanja (13), Alyssia (15), Lenka (12) and London (15) who were attending the 11-18 school in Scotland all also aspired to careers within the hair and beauty sector. For the Roma girls who aspired to careers within the hair and beauty sector, it appeared as though their aspirations were based on a 'realistic appraisal of the objective probability of [...] succeeding in a stratified education system, in which opportunities for social mobility are severely limited' (Gewirtz and Cribb, 2009, p. 48).

While many young people will feel passionate about a career in the hair and beauty sector, it struck me that the largest number of aspirations related this sector, came from students where there was a paucity of support within educational settings (see for e.g. Chapter six p. 189), with limited access to communities of interaction (Law, 1981). Their educational and career aspirations were then constructed within constrained horizons of action and determined by their institutional habitus (Hodkinson and Sparkes, 1997; Reay, 2001), characterised by subordination, where their voices had been muted (Freire, 1993).

The focus groups I conducted in the Scottish school appeared to have motivated Alyssia to reach out to me following the focus group. During the focus group, Alyssia was reluctant to speak, so I was surprised when she contacted me via Instagram to ask if I would speak to her teachers in order to arrange support so that she could achieve her hopes and dreams as detailed in the exchange below:

Alyssia: I want to hairs. See when I was six age old, I said to my mom ‘mom see when I grow up, can I do hairs?’ and she said ‘yes, why not if you like’.

Nicola: Once you become a hairdresser, I will come to you for my hair.

Alyssia: You can talk to one of the teachers, so they can become hairdresser?

Nicola: I will try. Would you want to learn hairdressing in school?

Alyssia: I want to be, but can you tell the teachers to give me some hours to learn? Believe me, that if you were not you, I was not telling anyone anything. You gave me the courage.

Nicola: I will try. These are great ideas you have.

Alyssia: Thanks, and I am very sorry to bother you.

Nicola: You are not bothering me.

As can be seen in the online exchange above, Alyssia was determined to be a hairdresser from the age of six, and had spoken to her mother about her dreams. Her silence within the focus group and the exchange above could potentially indicate that she does not feel that her school or focus group settings are a safe place to share her career aspirations. I feel that through reaching out to me, Alyssia was enacting agency over her aspirations, after she identified me as a trusted adult who could potentially help her. Drawing on Freire, (1993), despite how submerged an individual may be in a ‘culture of silence’, they still have agency to critically reflect on the world through dialogical encounters with others, therein allowing them to challenge the structural barriers within their educational field. My presence within Alyssia’s school allowed for a dialogical process to be initiated, wherein it encouraged Alyssia to critically reflect on what support she felt she needed – and this allowed her to ‘name her world’ (Freire, 1993) and push for the appropriate support that would enable her to progress towards her career ambitions. Similarly, Hart (2016) contends that there is a correlation between an

individual's ability to cultivate their aspirations, the freedom they have to give voice to those aspirations and their perceived support from others.

Parental aspirations: 'To be in a better situation than the family is in now'

My research participants also included parents, whose children did not participate in the current research. It is thought that this research may have been strengthened by recruiting parents whose children had participated in the study in order to determine if there was intergenerational congruence and a correlation between student and parental aspirations (Chavira, et al., 2016), however, research conditions and parental availability did not allow for this. Participants included parents who had recently migrated to the U.K: one Romanian Roma father (Remus), one Romanian Roma mother (Marianna) and one Slovakian Roma father (Mihael) living in Scotland. While one English Romani Gypsy father (James) in England agreed to participate.

Remus and Mihael had completed secondary school education in Romania and Slovakia respectively, while James attained his GCSEs in England but dropped out prior to completing his A-levels. Marianna attended neither primary nor secondary school. None had participated in further education, although at the time of data collection, Mihael was applying to college 'to be a good example' to his children. Remus worked in scrap metal, James was a Police Constable, Mihael was a Project Lead and Employment Advisor for a charity, and Marianna was a homemaker.

Unlike the male participants, Marianna, was not able to read or write and was unable to speak English. The research interview, therefore, required translation support from school C's community liaison worker Emanuel. To this end, it must be acknowledged the interpretation and translation process may have influenced the translation of meaning (Temple and Young, 2004). Moreover, the translation process introduced the potential for power relationships within interview settings (Benkert, 2002; Frow & Morris, 2000; Hendrickson, 2003).

A large body of literature suggests that Gypsy and Traveller parents only value the basic education available to young people at primary school (McKinney, 2001; Lloyd and McKluskey, 2008; Cemlyn et al., 2009). Beyond Bhopal (2004) Levinson's (2015) research, there is a paucity of literature pertaining to parents valuing education beyond primary school. Marcus (2016a, p. 206), suggests that Scottish Traveller mothers supported their daughters'

education aspirations towards ‘soft’ types of work, such as beauty courses, which could be utilised within their future roles as ‘homemakers’. The narratives espoused by parents in the current study are contrary to Marcus’ (2016a) emphasis on gendered and ‘soft types’ of work for Traveller girls.

Instead, this research concurs with findings by Levinson (2015), whose sample of Romani Gypsy parents were supportive of their children’s educational aspirations. Nuanced considerations are, however, needed as this data differs from Levinson’s (2015) findings in that the parents interviewed were not wary of their children finding employment within mainstream society. Research participants were invested in their children’s education and supported their career aspirations within their means and based on their individual circumstances. Their social, cultural and economic capital dictated the type of support each could offer, ranging from words of encouragement and supporting their children’s travel to and from school through to supporting them in filling out work-placement applications and providing financial support to enable their children to develop skills through extracurricular hobbies.

What follows illuminates the need for counter-stories to disrupt master narratives related to ‘cultural deficiency’ (Solórzano, 1992), as parental voices challenge stereotypical narratives of what ‘Roma, Gypsy and traveller people do’ in education and employment. Parents were able to express the aspirations they themselves held for their children as well as those their children had expressed during family discussions. The aspirations that parents held for their children generally reflect their unique ‘life histories’, marked by ‘unequal power relationships’ (Hodkinson and Sparkes, 1997, p. 437). Similarly, Langenkamp (2019, p. 232) contends that these aspirations are shaped by their own ‘educational and occupational struggles, their immigrant status’ and the opportunity structures available when attempting to support their children’s upward social mobility.

Roma, Gypsy and Traveller Fathers: Challenging Deficit Assumptions

Prior to exploring the aspirations that parents hold for their children, it is important to note the supporting role of fathers in their children’s education within this research. A number of authors have previously presented findings citing mothers’ disproportionate role and responsibility for child-rearing and schooling (Hamilton, 2016, 2017; Poole and Adamson, 2008; Sime et al., 2018; Marcus, 2016; Levinson, 2015; D’Arcy, 2017), however, the findings presented here provide a counter story to this oft overused narrative in order to redress common deficit assumptions about Roma, Gypsy and Traveller men. Similar to findings by Bhopal

(2004) regarding the role of fathers, the Roma and Romani Gypsy fathers who participated in this research were not only involved, but deeply invested in their children's education, working to support their educational and career aspirations through dialogue, homework monitoring, supporting school runs, providing work placement application guidance, drawing on support from external Career Advisers and purchasing equipment for their children to develop further skills on an extracurricular basis (laptops and keyboards).

Moreover, evidence of fathers supporting their children's education was presented by teaching staff in school B and C. For example, within my interview with teaching staff working with Romani Gypsy children in Wales, it was revealed that Big Man and Smooth Move's father gave children living on the local site a lift to school as Liani explained, '[their] dad is supportive too, brings them all to school'. Similarly, Remus, a self-employed Romanian Roma father of two living in England, also supported other community members' children in getting to school in the mornings as demonstrated through the exchange with Emanuel below:

Remus: When we come, we start with scrap metal and because of my family, I can't be employed full-time. So I choose to be self-employed. Sometimes, with too many kids sometimes in a moment, I have to come home, and that's the reason I choose to be self-employed. My wife is sometimes employed, but it's a bit difficult now because she's not speaking English.

Emanuel: And Remus is actually doing our school a massive favour, because how many of our pupils do you bring to school every morning in his mini bus?

Remus: Six students, and my two.

Nicola: What made you do that?

Remus: They are my friends and they are working, and if it's the same route then I pick them up.

Remus had completed secondary school in Romania and recognised the value in education – most evident through his choice to be self-employed in order to support his wife with child rearing and educational activities at home. Moreover, Remus offered support to his friends who had less flexible work schedules by ensuring that six children, in addition to his own two, had transport to and from school on a daily basis. Remus as well as Big Man and Smooth Move's

father both mobilised their ‘ethnic capital’ (Shah et al., 2010) based on community ties, by supporting their children and other community member’s children to access education (Bourdieu and Passeron, 1977).

Parental Hopes: ‘They need to graduate first then plan their next steps’

A number of authors contend that parental educational aspirations are key predictors of higher educational attainment, that serve as building blocks in establishing educational expectations (Bozick et al., 2010; Langenkamp, 2019), while others assert that parental involvement in their children’s schooling influences educational outcomes (Cheadle, 2008; Lareau, 1989). The paucity of literature available perpetuates master narratives, which indicate that Roma, Gypsy and Traveller families are extremely influential in shaping students’ choices – with parents often encouraging routes into family business for boys (see for e.g. Connexions Cornwall and Devon, 2005; Hutchinson et al., 2011; Wilkin et al., 2009) and homemaking for girls (Marcus, 2016). The following section details the aspirations parents have for their children, which may be conceptualised as the desire for their children to have a better life than they themselves have had. As three of the four parents interviewed migrated to the U.K, their hopes are tied to wanting their children to have opportunities that were not available to them in their respective countries of origin.

When I asked Marianna (Roma mother, England) what dreams she had for her daughters in the future, she responded that she wanted her children ‘to be better than they are now, so to be in a better situation than the family is in now’. Feliciano and Rumbaut (2005) argued that young girls in particular are seen as agents who can realise their families’ upward social mobility. In line with Feliciano and Rumbaut (2005), Marianna’s words indicated that her own aspirations for her children were for them to have a better life than they currently had. When I asked Marianna what support she felt her children needed, she described her aspirations for them along with the barriers she was facing in helping them attain their goals. She explained, with translation support from Emanuel:

She would be happy if they were nurses, so she would be happy if they got support in that area. That would be a good way, it’s difficult for Mom to support them because she is not very literate.

Marianna then discussed how despite her inability to read or write, she attempts to facilitate ‘career conversations’ with her children. She stated (again with translation support from Emanuel),

She says, most days when they come in from school, they get dressed and she prepares them some food. While they are eating, she asks them ‘what do you want to be in the future? How do you think you are going to get there?’ Children don’t know, because they are children. They have to be taught.

She then discussed the aspirations her own children have for their futures. Emmanuel translated:

Her daughter who is in year nine, was telling mom she wants to be a police officer, ‘we need police officers’, she says. She laughs a lot with them when they talk about all the crazy jobs they come up with. But they need to graduate first then plan their next steps. They need to learn a trade or a job or career. It’s very important.

Marianna’s responses indicate that she supports her children in achieving their stated aspirations – regardless of how much those aspirations may challenge the dominant narratives that she has internalised (Solórzano, 1992; Solórzano and Yosso, 2002), regarding what Roma, Gypsy and Traveller people do. I wondered if her children’s aspirations had been inspired by Flora, the Roma Police Constable who recently spoke to the children within school D, about becoming police officers. If this is the case, then orienting themselves towards this profession demonstrates the importance of visible community role models (Gonzalez et al., 2015) in broadening what learners see as possible within their horizons for action (Hodkinson and Sparkes, 1997).

While Remus claimed that his children could choose their ‘own way’, it was evident that as our discussion progressed, he was also steering them in the direction towards what he deemed to be a ‘good career’ I felt that due to Remus’ own limited opportunities and experiences related to what a ‘good job’ was, limited the potential horizons that he could present to his own children (Hodkinson and Sparkes, 1997) as evidenced in the excerpt below:

Remus: Your kids, they are your mirror. You know when I buy his keyboard, I spend 1500 pound and I tell him, ‘I spend a lot of money for your career, and you must think about that. Because, other kids may not even have a

computer, or laptop and they want to be like you and you must appreciate that. He can study what he decides.

Nicola: So you are encouraging him to have a music career?

Remus: Ah you know, first of all yes. Because if you are a musician, you have a lot of opportunities. You can play at the church weddings. They can make a band. It's a safe one.

Due to Remus' limited knowledge of the labour market landscape, he was making pragmatically rational decisions based on partial information within a field that was 'familiar' and 'known' to him (Hodkinson and Sparkes, 1997, p. 32-33) - the creative economy market. Indeed, a traditional occupation for Roma is music-making (Kovalcsik, 2003; Mikić, 2019) thereby reflecting that Remus' stated aspirations are pragmatically rational and based on 'safe options'. Remus' words indicated that while he had mobilised economic capital by purchasing computers and keyboards for his children to attain their goals, he was less able to mobilise cultural capital in order to navigate and provide guidance on educational transitions beyond what he had himself experienced (Shah et al., 2010).

During discussions with Remus, Emanuel interjected and stated Remus' son could consider a degree in music. While not a Career Adviser, Emanuel's words illustrate the importance of communities of interaction (Law, 1981) working closely with parents, who may have had limited opportunities, in order to broaden their horizons of what is possible. Emanuel stated:

I think Marek will be good enough to go on to sixth form. Do his A-levels, and he can specialise, and study that at university. I think Marek can do university, he is never excluded and he has a 100 percent attendance, and he could go to sixth form.

To this end, it is pivotal that schools involve children and their parents or guardians in the career guidance process. Lindblad and Lindahl (2020) argue that the family and their historical and contemporaneous situation is highly significant in their children's habitus and may influence their decisions. The authors suggest an interdependence between the child's horizon of action (Hodkinson and Sparkes, 1997) and the families horizons for action signalling the need to 'collectively enable' them (Lindblad and Lindahl, 2020, p. 90) in order for the student to progress towards their desired career.

Similar to Marianna and Remus, Mihael (Slovakian Roma father, Scotland), detailed how he was 'always talking more to [his] children and saying, "I would like them to have something

better than I have". These parents also drew on negative experiences from their countries of origin in perceiving the opportunities that their children have in the U.K to achieve their aspirations (Gonzalez et al., 2013). As Mihael noted the educational segregation of children in Slovakian schools is still rife, whereby Roma children are placed in 'special needs schools' because 'white parents don't like their kids sitting next to Roma kids'.

A joint report published by Amnesty International and the European Roma Rights Centre (2017), illuminated the discriminatory segregation that continues to take place in Slovakia with young people often being diagnosed as having mild mental disabilities and being placed in educational institutions offering inferior education. Mihael's narrative demonstrates the impact that racism has on narrowing Roma communities' educational opportunities and horizons for action in their countries of origin (Hodkinson, 1998).

The aspirations Mihael expressed for his children, were their dreams and hopes for the future that they shared with him. He noted how his eldest daughter 'always wanted to be a primary teacher', but health complications related to the development of cysts on her brain stem prevented her from doing her Highers, despite having achieved 'three Nat fives' in the previous academic year. Despite her health complications, Mihael had supported her in gaining an interview 'to do childcare early education' so she could 'maybe start in the nursery and then she can grow and develop'.

When discussing his son, Mihael noted that he was not sure what he wanted to do yet, but knew that he was 'skipping classes'. In contrast, he stated that his youngest daughter Timea was extremely sporty, played football and aspired to be a 'coach, trainer or PE teacher'. He also suggested that in order for her to attain her goals 'she needs higher education'. In addition to her interest in sport, Timea had also expressed to Mihael that she would be interested in physiotherapy but Mihael acknowledged that she doesn't do biology and therefore suggested 'that's probably not possible'. This reflected a realistic and pragmatic appraisal of what was probable due to the subjects that she selected constraining her future career trajectory (Gewirtz and Cribb, 2009; Hodkinson and Sparkes, 1997).

James, a Romani Gypsy Police Constable living in England, emphasised the importance of not 'pigeon-holing' community members as individuals need 'to carve [their] own paths'. He stated his son's expressed aspirations were to be a 'theme park ride designer and engineer', and though James, himself, was not 'engineering inclined', it was what his son wanted to do. His daughter wanted to be 'a zoo keeper and do conservation work'.

James, again emphasises the importance of carving out one's own path and stated that he was,

happy with both those choices that they want to make - it's their choices to make. I would never say to them 'you are going to be a police officer because that's what I do'. We can't follow in our parent's paths. My dad wanted me to be a solicitor, my mom wanted me to be a barrister. I wanted to be a copper. They would have had me do some mundane job that paid a wage.

The individual interview revealed that James was actively supporting his son in attaining his desired career goals by helping to arrange a work placement with a local theme park's engineering department and supporting him while he was writing his application. Only two parents within the current study demonstrated educational, social and cultural capital (Bourdieu, 1986) as reflected through their knowledge of the necessary steps their children would need to take in order to attain their aspirations. The parents who were more knowledgeable about these career steps either had experience within the U.K educational context, or worked in a field that afforded them that knowledge through experience. For example, James has experience with the U.K education system, while it appeared as though Mihael's employment support work through the charity provided him with the necessary skills and knowledge to guide his children on their journey and identify further mechanisms of support that they needed.

While James and Mihael demonstrated clarity on the next steps in supporting their children's career aspirations, discussions with Marianna and Remus demonstrated a lack of knowledge in how to traverse the labour market landscape. Participants largely exhibited limited educational, social and cultural capital (Bourdieu, 1986) as reflected through their knowledge about the steps that their children would need to take to transition to further or higher education, similar to research findings amongst Spanish-speaking immigrant families by Gonzalez et al. (2015).

Beyond welcoming any such opportunities for further and higher education, parents were unable to mention a specific institution. Further, parents' demonstrated limited knowledge related to the labour market and the relevance thereof to their children's aspirations. Harding (2010) posits that this may render parents less effective than parents who have access to and understand the further and higher education landscape and labour market when attempting to support their children in transitioning to higher education. To this end, it is of great significance that schools and Career Advisers engage in culturally-informed outreach work, especially

where parents have limited economic, educational, social and cultural capital (McDonough and Calderone, 2006) so that they more effectively support their children's transition to further and higher education.

Parental emphasis on Responsibility and Self-Regulation

The parental responses presented thus far serve as a powerful counter story to the anecdote that Roma, Gypsy and Traveller parents do not value education (Acton, 2004; Lloyd and McCluskey, 2008; Wilkin et al., 2010) or 'dream big' for their children's careers. Similar to young research participants' narratives, a common theme that emerged from discussions with parents was the emphasis that they place on the self-regulation of behaviour. As Marianna stated (with translation support from Emanuel),

Mom says she feels for them. So she says to them, 'make sure you don't get involved with anybody with a bad reputation. You should watch who you are hanging out with, and you should be studying more'.

The majority of parents who participated in the current research lacked the economic and cultural capital needed to fully support their children with the knowledge, education, advantages and resources needed to succeed in their desired professions (Bourdieu, 1986). As can be seen from the excerpt above, what Marianna has to offer, due to no fault of her own, are words of encouragement. Sadly, however, her lack of financial and cultural capital has a significant impact on the support she is able to provide her children. Her children's horizon for action will be influenced by the familial habitus (Hodkinson and Sparkes, 2006), characterised by limited cultural and economic capital and nested in a life history of unequal power relationships (McDonough and Calderone, 2006).

In addition to this, as Marianna does not have basic literacy skills in her own language or English, she is unable to help them with homework, and her children will consequently experience 'cultural and symbolic disempowerment' (Farris and de Jong, 2014, p. 1510). Despite Marianna's lack of capital, she supported her children's education by placing an emphasis on being responsible and self-regulating behaviour. This control of behaviour also permeated into what Marianna could control when explaining her children's 100 percent attendance rate as she had sent her children to school, 'even when they were poorly'.

Similarly, Remus motivated his children through placing an emphasis on self-regulation, based on his own early experiences. In response to the question ‘how important is education to you’, he responded,

Remus: Very important, because I know what I missed. Because even though I graduated, I missed some important things.

Nicola: Why do you think that was?

Remus: Because, when you are young you don’t think too much. It’s the same problem for everybody, but you try hard. My ones they’re studying by themselves in their room and I am happy with what they are doing, but I try to push them do *more, more, more...*

Remus placed the responsibility of what he missed at school at his own feet, as he had chosen to do sports instead of his homework, and he wanted to make sure his children did not repeat the same perceived mistakes. Similar to research by Langenkamp (2019) exploring Latino parental aspirations for their children, Remus has drawn on his own lived experiences in supporting and encouraging his children to self-regulate.

When I asked Remus if he ever spoke to his children about careers, I felt as though his response was partly attributed to internalised stereotypes regarding ‘bad examples’ related to what ‘Roma people do’. His words below also appear to suggest that he equated being educated with being a good person,

I speak with them because you know, there are bad examples as well. And in different cultures, you have bad examples, and every time I told them ‘if you don’t study, if you don’t try to be a good person, then you are gonna be like them’. And I encourage them to be good persons, and to try to give them a good education, and push them in that direction.

Self-regulation and being a ‘good person’ in relation to obtaining employment appeared yet again in the semi-structured interview with Remus. When I asked him what support he felt his children needed to achieve their career goals, he responded that his children didn’t need further support, and instead placed responsibility for their future achievements at both his and their feet. He stated,

If they study and continue to study in the future, after high school they can choose their way. And if you learn, if you do good ways, you can find a job. They just ask me for their laptop, and they do their homework and they are self-motivated.

Responsibility and role-modelling was again evidenced by James who stated that his children's 'career choices are only limited by their imagination' as they have seen him 'go out and do what [he] want[s] to do'. James went on to state that,

It doesn't matter how long it takes them', they just need to 'gain all the skills and courses you can - then go onto another thing that's what I did - gained the skills and started at the bottom of the ladder but with each change and growth in skills the pay got better'.

In describing how young people develop aspirations, Marek noted that when children see 'parents working entry level jobs they don't have aspirations', but if they witness 'their friends in school and they are talking then they will have dreams'. In support of Marek's perceptions, Seligman et al. (1991) contend that because children generally have a deeper understanding of their parent's occupations than those that they have had less exposure to, will influence their perceptions of their own career options and limit their 'capacity to aspire' (Appadurai, 2004). Peers and role models can, however, mitigate the impact of perceived limited mobility within communities marked by deprivation and poverty (Ray, 2006).

Marek went on to say that due to the presence of role models 'they will want to do something different to their parents, because if they hear my friends doing something architect, doctor because any job is better than nothing'. In addressing the perceived lack of role models within their immediate community, Marek adopted responsibility for facilitating and developing his children's career aspirations as he stated, 'I am trying to be a role model for my children that is why I am applying for college as well while I am working'. For Law (1981), the modelling that Marek is enacting provides his children with direct observations of educational and occupational habits that may positively influence their own education experience and career journey.

The emphasis that all parents within the current study placed on self-regulation may be in response to the non-linear nature of careers within a neo-liberal paradigm that places an emphasis on the need for increased individual responsibility (Pemberton, 2008). Parental narratives surrounding the need for individual responsibility and self-regulation are consistent with the emphasis that learners' in the current study place on moderating their own behaviour.

Both parents and students are adapting to the existing neoliberal social order, which fosters obedience and subordination (Freire, 1993; Vassallo, 2012), rather than questioning the mechanisms which work to oppress them. Overall, the majority of parents and young people involved in this research appear to have subscribed to the concept of meritocracy - if they just work hard enough, they might just be successful.

The Need for Further Support: ‘I still don’t know what I want, how can kids know?’

While all parents placed an emphasis on responsibility and self-regulation, two parents within the current research identified the need for further support so that their children may attain their educational and career aspirations. As mentioned previously, Marek’s son had been skipping classes, which was of concern to him. His son had also decided that he wanted to leave school at the end of fifth year. As a result of this, Marek identified that his son would require further support from a Career Adviser, but emphasised that the practitioner had to be external to school D.

Marek pointed out that he would be seeking support external to the provision offered within school D due to his children’s earlier experiences with SDS and he expressed scepticism regarding future engagements. Marek went on to say that SDS had engaged with his son but during the engagement, his son was told ‘you don’t know what you want - come back when you know what you want’. Marek noted that the Career Advisers ‘should help them explore and support them and talk about what is available and what they like - I still don’t know what I want, how can kids know?’ Contrary to SDS’ (2019a) Equality Outcomes publication, Marek’s words revealed that his children did not have equal ‘access to ongoing support from CIAG services’, so that ‘they may make informed choices’ (p. 9).

When discussing the employment support he offers to Roma community members, Marek noted that 90 percent of those coming through their charity doors were Roma, with a gender split of 60 percent males and 40 percent females, thereby further dispelling myths centred on female participation in the labour market. Due to these experiences, Marek drew parallels between the support offered in school and the support offered by the charity he worked for and stated the urgent need for further support as he stated, ‘we need more support for the Roma kids in school we even need more support here for the Roma looking for jobs and support’.

Similarly, Marianna placed an emphasis on the need for further support and opportunities for her children. She stated,

If there are jobs after school, or they could learn a trade, that's something they would be interested in. If that opportunity was there, they would take it. She would like them to go further once they graduate, to do something.

In moving away from the cultural deficit model in relation to Roma, Gypsy and Traveller families aspirations, this research points to high parental aspirations, the valuing of educational attainment, and calls for further support, so that their children can live better lives than they have. As both Mihael and Marianna's words reveal, there is a need for further support, so that their children can achieve their educational and occupational aspirations. Further in-school and post-school opportunities are needed, to provide vital education and career guidance provision in order to increase the social mobility of these communities based on the identified aspirations that young people and parents have (Solórzano, 1992).

Discussion

The first part of this chapter analysed the educational aspirations that Roma, Gypsy and Traveller students held for their educational careers. While Marcus (2016a, p. 180), purported that her findings challenged the 'anecdote that all Gypsy/Traveller girls do not attend school beyond the age of 12', her research recycled master narratives, as she asserted that 'most of the girls interviewed did not attach a high value to education and educational attainment' (*ibid*, p. 237). Contrary to Marcus' (2016) and Beremenyi's (2020) findings, the majority of learners who participated in this research were motivated and positively disposed toward education and expressed a range of educational aspirations as a means to achieving their future career ambitions. Young people had also thought about the steps that they would need to take in order to achieve their goals, thereby providing powerful counter-stories to dominant discourse regarding education and career trajectories (McGarry, 2014; Marcus, 2016). Student narratives also dispelled representations of Roma, Gypsy and Traveller people as being present-oriented (Lawrie, 1983; McCann, 1987; Feder et al., 1989; Jackson et al., 2016), living for the moment and not for the 'industrial clock' (Forster, 2018, p. 170).

The educational aspirations that participants have expressed thus far reflect what Hodkinson and Sparkes (1997) describe as pragmatically rational decision-making. Similar to findings

from Levinson (2015), the majority of young people who engaged in this research not only aspired to complete sixth form and attend further and higher education, but rather they planned on it as a means to achieving their goals. The data demonstrates multiple instances of young people enacting their agency, whereby they made active decisions regarding the subject choices that they believed would enable them to achieve their aspirations and their decisions to study closer to home due to the financial costs associated with travel.

Discussions also revealed that students' knowledge of higher and further education institutions and subject considerations reflected a form of cultural capital that varied across schools and geo-political contexts (Smyth and Banks, 2012). Although students in the Scottish context expressed a desire to complete secondary school, I worried whether they would achieve their educational aspirations due to the lack of support from teaching staff that served to narrow their horizons for action. The difference in expressed aspirations between geo-political contexts can be attributed to both the institutional habitus (Reay et al., 2001) and the pedagogical strategies (Shor and Freire, 1987) of the school's concerned and will be outlined in subsequent sections (see for e.g. 'Sources of Advice: Institutional field', p. 169; 'The Institutional Field: Stakeholder Perspectives', p. 179).

The second part of this chapter analysed the aspirations that students held for their future career paths. Students often expressed high career aspirations that did not fit 'existing social and occupational structures' whereby 'working class young people, leave school at 16, and follow working class careers' (Hodkinson, 2008, p. 4). The majority of learners who participated in this research have aspirations that transcend their objective reality and are contrary to patterns of working-class trajectories (Raffo and Reeves, 2000; Reay, 2006). Instead, student aspirations are consistent with data published by the OECD (2020) wherein the concentration of occupational expectations amongst 15-year old's across the world, include occupations such as doctors, lawyers, business managers, nurses and midwives, veterinarians, ICT professionals and police officers. Research participant narratives also appear to suggest that a large number of them aspired to careers aligned towards helping others (Milan-Tyner, 2018).

As expected, and in line with the intersectional framework student aspirations were not homogenous (Hancock, 2007; Levinson, 2015). The majority of Romani Gypsy boys in Wales planned to leave school at 16 and follow more 'traditional careers' centred on self-employment (Clark, 2001; Levinson and Sparkes, 2003). These entrepreneurship aspirations signal the need for teachers and career practitioners to provide more opportunities for these students to explore

entrepreneurship and develop the skills aligned with their stated aspirations (Henderson and Robertson, 2000).

Findings within the Scottish context indicate that learners' stated aspirations aligned to working class and gendered career trajectories (Hodkinson, 2008; Raffo and Reaves, 2000; Reay, 2006). It is thought that the observed differences in learners' career decision-making was influenced by what was familiar and known (Hodkinson and Sparkes, 1997). Consistent with findings in both white and Ethnic minority populations (Croll, 2008), students did not demonstrate a 'poverty of aspiration' (Archer et al., 2014b, p. 66) but rather a poverty of opportunity (Roberts and Atherton, 2011). The participants' stated career preferences then illuminate differences between institutional habituses (Reay et al., 2001).

The aspirations expressed by the large majority of young people are also contrary to findings by Clark (2001) and Lloyd and McKluskey (2008) that suggest that Roma, Gypsy and Traveller people rejected wage labour and overspecialisation. These shifting aspirations could be the result of evolving familial expectations, uncertain and rapidly changing labour markets and an increasingly digital world (OECD, 2020; Taylor, 2017; Nedelkoska and Quintini, 2018). Similar to findings by Levinson (2015) the data presented in this chapter demonstrates that young people expressed a broad range of career choices, highlighting the importance of providing to students opportunities to explore the careers landscape. While some young people will aspire to traditional careers like the young Romani Gypsy boys in Wales, others will carve their own paths based not only on their hopes and dreams, but on the range of learning opportunities that they have had access to within educational settings.

The third part of this chapter revealed the aspirations that Roma and Romani Gypsy parents have for their children. Contrary to findings by Sime et al. (2018, p. 325), claiming that parents suffered from a 'defeatist attitude in relation to their children's education' and a 'limited conviction that education could improve their children's social mobility', parents in this study, placed importance on educational attendance and attainment. Parents recognised the power of education in increasing social mobility so that their children could have a better life than they themselves have had. The data is also in contrast to research by Surdu and Surdu (2006), wherein Romani women encouraged higher levels of education amongst their sons, as they were traditionally seen as breadwinners. The parents who participated in this research promoted education and career aspirations for both their sons and daughters.

My analysis supports the use of critical race theory as a theoretical lens in order to illuminate counter-stories (Delgado and Stefancic, 2017; Solórzano and Yosso, 2002), to challenge the dominant discourse that suggests that Roma, Gypsy and Traveller people do not want an education or a career (Clark, 2001; McGarry, 2013; Marcus, 2016; Peček and Munda, 2015). While not generalisable due to the small sample size, parental narratives demonstrated overwhelming support for their children's educational and career aspirations, thereby challenging assumptions about Roma, Gypsy and Traveller parental involvement as deficient in comparison to majority populations. Moreover, the findings presented here provide a counter-story that redressed common deficit assumptions about Roma, Gypsy and Traveller fathers (see Hamilton, 2016, 2017; Poole and Adamson, 2008; Sime et al., 2018; Marcus, 2016; Levinson, 2015; D'Arcy, 2017). Similar to findings by Bhopal (2004) regarding the role of fathers, the Roma and Romani Gypsy fathers who participated in this research were not only involved, but deeply invested in their children's education, working to support their children's educational and career aspirations through dialogue, homework monitoring, supporting school runs, and providing work placement application guidance.

Findings suggest that the lived educational and career experiences of parents shape not only the aspirations that they hold for their children but how they can support them to achieve their dreams, often through placing an emphasis on the self-regulation of behaviour. Parental narratives related to the need for individual responsibility and self-regulation are consistent with the emphasis that learners in the current study place on moderating their own behaviour.

While parents may encourage their children's educational and occupational aspirations, they have little access to the structures of support necessary to foster those aspirations (Gonzalez et al., 2013). Finally, the parents who participated in this research demonstrated agency in their calls for further educational and career support for their children. Parental perspectives informed the need for improved engagement and support from schools linked to careers provision and employer engagement. It is therefore, of great significance that schools and Career Advisers engage in culturally-informed and relevant outreach work, especially where parents have limited economic, educational, social and cultural capital (McDonough and Calderone, 2006), so that they can more effectively support their children's transition to further and higher education.

In the chapter that follows, I will consider how young Roma, Gypsy and Traveller people approach for education and career guidance within their familial and institutional fields in order

to realise their aspirations. I then turn to consider the support available to students within educational settings from the perspective of stakeholders across the three home nations that either serve to broaden or constrain students' educational and career options.

Chapter Six

Who young Roma, Gypsy and Traveller people approach for education and career guidance

The previous chapter revealed the aspirations that Roma, Gypsy and Traveller students and parents held for the future therein working to dispel majoritarian narratives on what these communities do in relation to ‘education and careers’ (Lloyd and McCluskey, 2008; Peček and Munda, 2015). Young people had also thought about the steps that they would need to take in order to achieve their educational and career aspirations, thereby providing powerful counter-stories to dominant narratives within the public imaginary related to the educational and employment patterns of these communities (McCann, 1987; Clark, 2001; McGarry, 2014; Marcus, 2016; Forster, 2018). The current chapter will now explore who learners approach for education and career guidance within their familial and institutional fields and consider how these forces shape and influence their horizons for action (Hodkinson and Sparkes, 1997). This chapter then seeks to address my second research question: Do young Roma, Gypsy and Traveller people have equitable access to career education and guidance provision? If they do, what have their experiences been? If they have not had access, do they believe that they would benefit from career guidance, and how do they think local services could best meet their needs?

It is important to note, that no other studies have attempted to explore Roma, Gypsy and Traveller students’ aspirations cross-nationally; nor have any other studies explored who students from these backgrounds are talking to about their educational and career aspirations. This chapter therefore attempts to address this gap by providing a space to demonstrate how young people enact their agency through, for example, who they approach to gain support to achieve their education and career aspirations. It focuses on the significant others within learners’ lives and the individuals that they feel safe enough to approach when making career decisions. The data suggests that their decision-making processes regarding who to approach for guidance may be described as pragmatically rational (Hodkinson and Sparkes, 1997) and based on two factors: those who students trusted and felt comfortable with (the familiar and known) and those who were best placed to provide the advice in line with learners stated aspirations (expertise and knowledge based).

The following chapter highlights who young people approach within their familial fields, (which includes parents, siblings, aunts, as well as friends of the family); and then explores who students speak to within educational settings (which includes teachers, TESS staff and

Career Advisers). The caveat, however, is that who young people approach was dependent on the geographical context and institutional habitus of the relevant school – for example, young people in Scotland did not cite access to SDS Career Advisers as a source of support (see for e.g. ‘Sources of Advice: Institutional Field’, p. 175). These findings allow for the juxtaposition of inclusionary and exclusionary practices across the three home nations and are significant as they offer unique insights into how students’ education aspirations are facilitated and nurtured within safe spaces (Hart, 2012; Joyce, 2018).

Sources of Advice: Family Field

Consistent with relevant literature in other populations, the majority of young people in this study stated that their parents were important sources of career advice (Cassidy et al., 2006; Hutchinson et al., 2011). It is important to note, that six young people out of 36 did not approach their parents for career advice (Gypsy Tony, Romani Gypsy boy, Wales; Super Woman, Romani Gypsy girl; Wales; London, Roma girl, Scotland). Kasey explains that her parents didn’t give her career advice because ‘they couldn’t’ due to their own limited educational and cultural capital. In support, Haynes et al. (2013) argue that parents who have histories of unemployment or those who have had limited access to the labour market or careers information may not have the knowledge necessary for providing guidance to their children. Within the Scottish context, it was more difficult to discern whether ‘participant two’ and Messi spoke to their parents, due to the significant silences within focus groups and it remains unknown whether students approached their parents for career guidance.

Overall, discussions revealed that parents were generally supportive of their children’s educational and career aspirations (Greenfields, 2008), and encouraged them to ‘follow [their] dreams’ (Katalina, Roma girl, Wales; Ana, Roma girl, England). While the majority of parents were supportive of their children’s educational and career aspirations, it is important to note that parental education qualification levels were low, as often reported by participants. To this end, students’ access to economic and cultural capital (Lindblad and Lindahl, 2020) within their family field (Hodkinson and Sparkes, 1997) may be characterised as limited. Social capital in the form of support and encouragement was, however, abundant. The majority of students stated that they had spoken to their parents about their career aspirations and sought advice from them. As Katalina recalls,

I have spoken with my mum and dad. They have asked me what I want to be when I grow up, and they said, ‘do what you like’, they say ‘follow your dream’.

The guidance that Ronaldo (Roma boy, 11, Wales), received from his parents, centred on listening to his teachers in school, and working to develop his English language skills, revealing the uneven playing field that is shaping his horizons for action, as he is only learning to write in English in secondary school. He stated,

My mum and dad tell me to listen to my teacher and understand to writing. My mum tell me to 'be what I want to be. Doctor yeah and cooking. And to work, to listen to miss'.

Ana, (Roma girl, 14, England) had spoken to both of her parents, who were providing advice and guidance on subject choices. Her parents also encouraged her to seek guidance within educational settings in order to explore the range of options that she could study once she had completed secondary school as the excerpt below reveals,

So my dad told me that I should pick business and drama, and see which one I continue. So I did, and I have business and it works really well. He said, if I have business, I have more experience, when I wanna look at getting a job. I talk to my mom, and she said if you really want to do something, you need to follow your dreams. So if you are really confident, trust other people in school to talk to.

Although Ana aspired to be a Drama teacher, the guidance she received from her father has provided her with a number of potential career routes for later on in life – once again countering common deficit assumptions about Roma, Gypsy and Traveller men (see for e.g. Hamilton, 2016, 2017; Poole and Adamson, 2008; Sime et al., 2018). Her narrative also illuminates a common theme that emerged during discussions with students - the significance of developing trusting relationships with those within educational settings (Marcus, 2016). In the subsequent section (see for e.g. 'Sources of Advice: Institutional Field', p. 171), the reader will see how Ana's horizons for action were influenced by a teacher whom she trusted (Hodkinson and Sparkes, 1997).

While for James (Roma boy, 14, England), it was important for him to seek advice from both of his parents, as he felt that they were the people who knew him best and that he trusted. From this perspective, he approached those who were familiar and known (Hodkinson and Sparkes, 1997), 'hot sources' (Ball et al., 2000) as he explains below,

I would speak to my parents, because your parents grow up with you, and they learn you everything. So they will be the best person to speak with. They know all your mistakes, and they will learn you what's good, and what's wrong.

Kooper (Roma boy, 16, Wales), on the other hand, was undecided on his career aspirations, due to fear of making the wrong choice,

I'm thinking, I wanna take time cause I don't wanna make the wrong choice. I don't have lots of time to go back, so I wanna take it slow and make the right choices.

His careful approach and consideration of career routes appear to be shaped by advice he sought from his mother,

I always talk to my mom about it. Whenever I talk to her, she goes, 'you can make whatever choice you want, we can support you'. She said, 'you can go to a job, after you finish school but think about it. Is that really what you wanna do?' She said, 'if you wanna stay more in school, then that's good cause you know we'll support you'. They make it easier for me, they say, 'take it slow and take your time'.

Kooper's narrative reveals the classed aspects of his familial habitus, as his mother's encouragement and support for his continued engagement in education was presented as a choice and is in direct contrast to the expectations placed on middle class students. As Smyth and Banks (2012, p. 263), observe in their comparison of working class and middle-class student aspirations, when it comes to higher education for middle class students, 'there was never really any question of anything else'. As will be seen in the subsequent section, it was the advice from Kooper's mother, along with advice from his teacher and Career Adviser that resulted in his decision to complete sixth form. Experiences such as Kooper's demonstrate the importance of parents, teaching staff and Career Advisers working together to support students towards their goals, especially where young people have no family traditions of completing secondary school and pursuing further and higher education (Foskett et al., 2008).

Moreover, as Kooper's narrative reveals, a common theme that emerged was that while learners cited both parents as sources of career guidance, they were more likely to cite their mothers, consistent with the literature in other populations (Lundahl et al., 2017; McQuaid et al., 2004; Schultheiss et al., 2001; Smyth and Banks, 2012). Interestingly, this finding did not emerge from discussions with young Romani Gypsy boys in Wales.

Consistent with the literature, while parents play a significant role in providing career information and guidance, other family members, including siblings, aunts, and friends of the family were all cited as sources of career guidance (Schultheiss et al., 2002) and constituted students' communities of interaction (Law, 1981). For example, the chief adviser in Mrs H's (Roma boy, 13, Wales) life, was his brother, who worked in a factory, and volunteered for both the local church and at his brother's school supporting other Roma students. It is important to note here again, that the guidance Mrs H received also centred on a moral compass, self-regulation and responsibility (Van der Heijde, 2014). He stated,

My brother does job in factory and pastoral support. He helps the pastor to help people. He say, 'try your best and don't get in trouble'.

Sonja (Roma girl, 16, Wales) on the other hand relied on her aunts, sisters and brother for career guidance. She explained,

So, I would rather go to my aunties or older sisters and get advice. They told me that, if I have a proper job they are gonna help me with it, cause my brother has his own career. Car wash things. So he helps us with that. So if you wanna get a proper job, he can give some CV's to people around.

Drawing on Hodkinson and Sparkes (1997), Sonja's career decision-making has been influenced by the opportunities that can be seen within her field (familial habitus and the local labour market). While she was enacting her agency, Sonja's pragmatically rational decision-making demonstrated that she had to draw on her communities of interaction (Law, 1981) and rely on the social capital available within her field (Hodkinson, 2008) in order to find employment.

For the aspiring lawyer, Nicki Minaj (Roma girl, 16, England), the network of support she sought advice from was not only confined to her parents but also included her mother's friend Anna, who she had identified as successful, thereby demonstrating a logical, purposeful and context related approach to information gathering (Hodkinson and Sparkes, 1997). She explained,

Nicki Minaj: I would speak to my parents, obviously. And I would also speak to my mom's friend Anna. She actually helped me a lot with college and careers, and told me the benefits of the careers I can get.

Nicola: Why Anna in particular?

Nicki Minaj: Because she is a business woman.

Poison Ivy stated that she had spoken to her parents about careers. As our discussions progressed, it made more sense why Poison Ivy had stated that, 'I don't just want to be one of those people who say they wanna do something I actually wanna carry all the way through with it'. Poison Ivy had revealed that one of her sisters, who after completing secondary school, became an advocate for the Welsh Assembly and worked for Save the Children. Her sister, however, 'gave it all up' when she got married. The advice she received from her parents was based on wanting her to follow through with her career aspirations, as Poison Ivy explains,

Yeah my dad and my mum. They are *really, really* supportive, because they want me to go through with it, cause they don't want me to be like my sisters - get married young. She went all the way. From school, she went to college. She didn't go to uni, but she got married. My dad really really wants me to follow through with it.

It is important to note here, that while the vast majority of parents support their children's educational and career aspirations, a common theme emerges where guidance rests on narratives such as 'follow your dreams' and 'be good'. What appears to be absent from this guidance is specific and practical information and knowledge related to further and higher education pathways and the labour market (Smyth and Banks, 2012). As these students' come from homes where they are the first generation in their families who plan on completing secondary school and attending further and higher education, teaching staff and Career Advisers will be crucial sources of information on how to pursue such pathways (McDonough 1997; Foskett et al., 2008).

All Romani Gypsy in boys in Wales except for, Gypsy Tony, had approached family members for guidance regarding their future careers. The caveat here though, is that there appeared to be gendered approaches in who young people would speak to at home. Big Man Wayne (12), Smooth Move (12), Big Man (14), and Pikey Bradley (14), all stated that they had spoken to their fathers, about their career aspirations. Moreover, when I asked young people who they spoke to at home about their future careers, their responses also aligned to the practical advice of 'doing the job'. For example, Pikey Bradley revealed the advice that he received from his father was based on a particular set of skills,

Me dad. He told me to lay my angles in the carpentry.

At the age of 14, Pikey Bradley had been gaining experience as a trainee carpenter with his father after school. Irish Travellers Big Man and Smooth Move had also fleshed out the details for what would come next, as their discussion centred around their father purchasing them a van in order to support their aspirations. They explained,

Big Man: When I'm like 17 or 18, he's gonna buy me a van. So I can do all graft work, the home improvements.

Smooth Move: And get whatever we can get, have your own business and website.

As in D'Arcy's (2012, p. 105) research exploring the range of learning activities provided to young people within her elective home education sample, the advice that the Romani Gypsy boys received from their fathers within the current study, 'mirrored a vocational [...] apprentice-model' of guidance. The current findings however, paralleled D'Arcy's findings (2012) only in relation to the boys gendered career aspirations. A common theme that emerged from discussions with the Romani Gypsy boys was that their aspirations aligned to self-employment and entrepreneurship, illuminating the need for policy makers and teachers to provide increased opportunities for entrepreneurship education within the curriculum (Henderson and Robertson, 2000). These findings also highlight the role of Career Advisers and enterprise advisers in providing guidance tailored to Romani Gypsy boys so as to encourage their skill set development related to their stated aspirations.

During focus group discussions with these participants in Wales, I was acutely aware that the majority of them cited approaching their fathers for career advice, so I asked them whether they had also spoken to their mothers about careers. Only MC Allen indicated that he spoke to his Mom regarding educational and employment options. The response below from Gypsy Tony demonstrates gendered perceptions regarding women in relation to cooking, cleaning and shopping.

Nicola: So have any of you gotten advice from your moms on careers?

Gypsy Tony: Yeah all they do is clean up isn't it? They don't work, do they? They just let the men work, and they get all the money and provide for them isn't it?

Gypsy Tony's words here, appear to be framed as a question back to me, reflecting Stoudt's (2006) argument that there are spaces and moments of resistance where those who embody

hegemonic masculinities can in turn question them. More nuanced considerations pertaining to Romani Gypsies gendered perceptions will, however, be unpacked further in chapter seven (p. 210) due to the implications that these attitudes may have on attainment and progression.

Overall, the Romani Gypsy boys did not, however, cite their mother's as sources of guidance. One possible reason for this pattern is that women's domestic roles are generally valued less than waged labour (Kóczé, 2009). Another possible reason emerged in the subsequent section ('Sources of Advice: Institutional Field', p. 169) wherein students made pragmatically rational decisions in who they approached for advice based on those who were best placed to provide the advice in line with learners stated aspirations (context-related perceived experts). As their mothers were largely seen as exclusively homemakers, the boys may have decided that they were not best placed to provide guidance.

Roma students attending school D spoke freely and easily about the career discussions that they had with their parents. Spanja (Roma girl, 13, Scotland) stated that she came from a lone parent household, but that her mother aimed to help her with everything. She explained,

My mum says she's gonna help me. I don't have a dad. She said to me, when I said I want to do this and this, and she said, 'ok I am gonna help you with everything'.

Natalie's mother said, she could do whatever she wanted when she went to college, while Magic Woman's²⁵ parents told her that they would support her in her aspirations for a music career:

My mum says, 'you do what you like, when you go to college'. (Natalie, Roma, 15, Scotland)

Yes, they mentioned they will try to enrol her somewhere she can sing. (Magic Woman, 13, Scotland)

Overall, the current findings often suggest that young people's interpersonal transactions with parents, aunts, siblings, cousins and friends of the family - their localised community of interaction - serves to influence their educational and career aspirations (Law, 1981). For other young people, however, it was difficult for them to express themselves within the focus group setting. As mentioned in the preceding chapter, Alyssia (Roma girl, 15, Scotland) contacted me on Instagram following the focus group, stating that she did not feel brave enough to speak

²⁵ It is important to note that Magic Woman's excerpt reads in the third person due to translation support from Madalin during the focus group.

to anyone until I came in. If it weren't for this Instagram exchange, blurring the boundaries between public and private safe spaces, I would not have known that she spoke to her mother about her aspirations. Due to this interaction with Alyssia, I couldn't help but wonder, whether 'participant two' and Messi had spoken to their parents about their careers? I suspect that they had, but that I had not earned their trust yet.

Contrary to the support that her peers found from their parents, London felt that she could not approach her own parents for career guidance. During the focus group, London (Roma girl, 15, Scotland) appeared to get anxious, as she raised her voice and threw her hands up in the air, almost defeated when I asked her who she spoke to at home about her career aspirations. She explained,

No they are not gonna help me with anything! What can they do? Money, even money - I have money. I make money myself. My dad only working, no help and talks to nobody. I waiter at a restaurant. Some people say 'how can I wake up in the morning?'

Several young people within the current study worked whilst at school in order to contribute to familial income or to 'learn the family trade'. Consistent with the literature, (Mulcahy et al., 2017), familial 'economic realities meant an early start in the world of work' for these students (Smith, 2007, p. 432). London's words revealed that she was currently juggling work and school, which may be adversely affecting educational engagement (Lindblad and Lindahl, 2020).

Drawing on Ciuffetelli Parker (2013), it is necessary to understand the impact of poverty on families and the often contested decision between contributing toward household income and food for one's family or going to school tired from working late the night before. I worried about the impact that this would have on London's educational attainment, especially as she had stated that she felt she needed more support from the school in order to achieve her educational aspirations. To this end, Lindblad and Lindahl (2020, p. 94) suggest that teaching staff need to foster a deeper knowledge and understanding of students' 'social and historical context by working with parents, so that students may be empower[ed]'.

Sources of Advice: Institutional Field

The following section explores the school environment which Law (1981) identifies as one facet of the local community wherein students experience various interactions with others that serve to influence their career development. Learners' narratives demonstrate compelling

agency and their decision-making may be characterised as pragmatic rationality as evidenced by who they approach for guidance within institutional settings (Hodkinson and Sparkes, 1997).

Student accounts in England and Wales often indicated that while some young people in upper secondary school spoke with Career Advisers, students were more likely to speak to trusted teachers or members of the TESS team. This pattern is thought to reflect the younger age profile of the sample, where access to individual interviews with Career Advisers in early secondary school was limited due to various policy approaches wherein access to personal guidance only takes place during the final two years of secondary school (Careers Wales, 2017; Holman, 2014; DfE, 2018).

Hutchinson et al. (2011) argue that this lack of career related learning in the early years has a detrimental impact on aspirations. Young people in early secondary school in England and Wales did, however, have access to career related learning through teachers and the TESS team from their first year of secondary school. Teachers, TESS staff and Career Advisers across England and Wales appeared to influence students' motivation, their engagement with school and their horizons for action (Hodkinson and Sparkes, 1997).

As in the preceding section, I was again struck by the depth of thought Ana (Roma girl, 14, England) had given to her future career at such a young age. When I asked her who she spoke to at school for careers support, it emerged that she had already spoken to the school's Career Adviser and the community liaison worker – revealing a high degree of practical rationality. As Ana explains,

I would talk to [Zoe] or [Emanuel] or like my form teacher. They are really welcoming and support you really well. So there's people you can talk to. You are not alone in this school.

Although Ana's remarks demonstrate a pragmatically rational approach to guidance they also illuminate features of her educational field that appear to be a positive learning culture marked by openness and trust (Stoll, 1994). Her individual agency was again demonstrated in her revelation that she had applied for student parliament but was unsuccessful. Instead of accepting defeat though, Ana was proactive in finding where she belonged in the world, by speaking to Zoe, who was helping her access an after-school drama club. Ana explained,

Yeah so I have applied for student parliament, for business and finance. I tried to make myself more businessy, like work in offices and everything. But, I didn't get it so I talked to [Zoe] and she said she is gonna put me in an after school drama club. It made my life better.

Ana's words revealed that the guidance that she received from the school's Career Adviser, increased her self-confidence and life-satisfaction through opportunities for self-development and skills development (Hirschi, 2009). When I asked Ana, if she would re-apply for student parliament, she revealed the importance of finding a career that she derived meaning from over and above, potential earnings as detailed in the exchange below,

Ana: If I would have got it, and I wouldn't have [Zoe's] advice, I would probably be doing something I don't like. I would be doing something I don't want to, because I thought of it - I am gonna have money and everything, but then I thought that's not actually what I like.

Nicola: So you are looking at things that actually mean something to you?

Ana: So I have a maths teacher that used to work as an engineer. But, he got lots of money, but he didn't like it, and he moved to a maths teacher. Even though he gets less money, he says he enjoys teaching people. So it's better to enjoy something - something you like, then getting money for something you don't actually like.

Ana's words illuminate dimensions of the 'hidden curriculum' and the unintended learning that takes place within the student-teacher interaction unit (Valance, 1993). She had learned from her Maths teacher and integrated these experiences into her own career decision-making wherein she would seek a meaningful career over potential earnings. A number of researchers within the field of industrial-organisational psychology (see for e.g. Lips-Wiersma, 2002) have suggested that a sense of meaning and purpose are essential foundations in the career decision-making process, while others have highlighted the importance of values in relation to career decision-making (McCrorry and Thomsen, 2019). To this end, teachers and Career Advisers should work with students to explore the various reasons for choosing one occupation over another with reflections on student values and the derivation of meaning from potential occupations within the career guidance process (Dik et al., 2009; Seligman et al., 2006).

Nicki Minaj had indicated that she had already received guidance from the school's Career Adviser,

I would speak to [Zoe] cause she knows everything about careers, and she helps us with careers in school.

While James identified an adult in his life who he not only trusted and felt comfortable with (the familiar and known), but an adult who he perceived as having the expertise (knowledge based) aligned to his own aspirations (Hodkinson and Sparkes, 1997). He explained,

I would speak to Miss [...]. I would be a businessman and she teaches business. So she knows everything to do with jobs. How to apply for it, what to do with your money. So she'll be the most comfortable teacher to speak with.

Within Welsh school A, Roma students also indicated that they had spoken to both teachers and Career Advisers about what they wanted to be when they grew up. The significance of the relationship between young people in this school and their teacher, Mrs H (Big Boss) cannot be understated, as illustrated through student responses to my question, 'who do you speak to at school about careers?' They stated,

Lauren: Big Boss

Sonja: Yeah Big Boss!

Lauren: Yeah she helps us. She actually helps. She helps people who don't have house or something to wear. She actually goes and gives it to people.

Sonja and Lauren's words revealed that Mrs H – AKA 'Big Boss' - not only provided vital career guidance - but also went beyond the roles and responsibilities assigned to teachers as she actively worked to remove barriers related to poverty long after the school day had ended. Mrs H was altering the field, removing barriers and influencing learners' horizons for action (Hodkinson and Sparkes 1997). In addition to speaking to Mrs H about their futures, young people recalled speaking to form teachers and the school's Career Adviser. Lauren spoke of her interactions with the Career Adviser and the college taster days that she was going to attend,

Yeah we do. She said she's gonna help us, if we wanna go college she said she's gonna take us to college. She's a lovely person as well and shows us how it is and let us do some jobs in there as well.

As can be seen from the excerpts above, when considering who to approach for guidance, student decision-making may be described as pragmatically rational (Hodkinson and Sparkes, 1997) based on two factors: those who students trusted and felt comfortable with (the familiar and known) and those who were best placed to provide the advice in line with learners stated aspirations (knowledge based perceived experts).

The significance of a holistic approach between parents, education institutions and careers services in students' lives is pivotal to their development and has the potential to broaden what they see as possible within their fields. As mentioned previously, Kooper wanted to take his time in selecting a career as he was worried he would make the wrong decision. Although he had support and encouragement from his parents to remain in education, he was undecided as to whether he was going to complete sixth form. That is until he had a face-to-face interview with his form teacher and the school's Career Adviser, thereby illuminating the crucial role that personal interactions can have on learners continued engagement in education. The guidance interview that Kooper experienced, appeared to influence his decision to stay in school for sixth form. As he explains,

I spoke to the head of sixth form and the Career Adviser. I am coming back to sixth form cause I had the interview with Miss [...]. She convinced me of all the stuff I can do in sixth form. She said there's different options I can do.

Similar to Plank and colleagues (2005) longitudinal findings wherein career education and guidance alongside core academic learning reduced the risk of dropping out, the holistic support that Kooper received influenced his decision to continue in education and broadened his choices and life chances (Hodkinson and Sparkes, 1997). These findings suggest that institutional and familial habitus were working in tandem with both being pivotal in his decision-making process (Reay et al., 2001). According to Lindblad and Lindahl (2020) Kooper's decision to stay in school will determine his future career patterns and potentially reduce the length of time it will take for him to establish himself within the labour market and increase the potential opportunities available to him.

As demonstrated, support related to career guidance within school A in Wales and school C in England came from both teachers and Career Advisers. Provision for young Romani Gypsy people in Welsh school B, however, appeared to stem from discussions with the TESS staff team, who also delivered career education through personal, social, health and economic education (PSHE) lessons. Hutchinson et al. (2011) argue that access to career education within

PSHE provides students' a vital building block for their career decision-making skills, allowing students to explore the range of occupational possibilities within the labour market. These findings suggest that there is a benefit to a more broadly contextualised approach that involves a community (Law, 1981), beyond the Career Adviser and the need for more activity than the one-off personal guidance interview (Choi et al., 2015). Moreover, these findings illuminate the crucial work of the TESS team in ensuring students have equitable access to career education and raise concerns regarding the lack of such a body within the Scottish context.

Through focus group discussions with the Romani Gypsy girls in Wales, Poison Ivy had stated that she had already had discussions with Liani, who was setting up a work placement for her to shadow a lawyer. Similarly, Liani was the trusted adult that Cat Woman and Super Woman had discussed their career aspirations with. They explained,

Cat Woman: I told [Liani], but she said in year 11 I'll do a thing at [...]. It's a school for children with a disability, like children 13 to 16. First I was gonna go work with primary school, but then I changed my mind to work with children with disabilities.

Super Woman: Yeah I told her that I wanted to work in a school

Cat Woman's aspirations parallel those identified by Greenfields (2008) wherein a number of research participants aspired to work with and support young people who had a disability. Contrary to the experiences of the Romani Gypsy girls within the Welsh school, focus group discussions with the boys revealed that they did not have the same discussions pertaining to their future. When I asked the Romani Gypsy boys in Wales if they had spoken to anyone regarding support to achieve their career aspirations, they all unanimously responded 'no'. MC Allen went on to say that he had received some information regarding careers through PSHE lessons. Similar to findings by Hutchinson et al. (2011), these young people did not recognise that their enhanced knowledge developed within PSHE lessons was related to career education. I then prompted the boys further to ask if they had ever spoken to a Career Adviser and the exchange between MC Allen and myself revealed that he was not aware of what a Career Adviser was, nor was he aware of who the school's Career Adviser was:

MC Allen: What's that?

Nicola: The careers officer that works in the school.

MC Allen: I don't know who that is.

Nicola: Have you spoken to her?

MC Allen: Don't know. Don't even know her.

As evidenced across England, Scotland and Wales, a number of learners between ages of 11 and 14 expressed a broad range of educational and career aspirations. Students across England and Wales had also detailed the steps they would take to achieve their stated goals and recalled the career exploration discussions that they had already engaged in with trusted teachers. For example, Cat Woman and Super Woman both aged 13, had held discussions with the TESS team to start planning future work placements. These findings suggest that policy across the three home nations currently falls short (Scottish Government, 2020; Holman, 2014; DfE, 2018) as young people only have access to individual guidance interviews from the age of 16. To this end, it is vital Roma, Gypsy and Traveller students have earlier access to career education and personal guidance within educational settings (Hughes and Kashefpakdel (2018).

Across the English and Welsh geo-political contexts, the majority of students recalled support for accessing guidance, opportunities to explore their educational and career aspirations, lessons within the curriculum, discussions regarding employer engagement and work placement opportunities, access to further education and higher education open days and personal face-to-face career guidance interviews . Collectively, these strategies form the school habitus and broaden students' further education, higher education and career trajectories (Hodkinson and Sparkes, 1997; Smyth and Banks 2012). Consistent with the literature, the institutional habitus shapes students' educational and career decision-making, illuminating the opportunities available to them and the perceived accessibility of those opportunities (Foskett et al., 2008; Reay et al., 2005).

Within the Scottish context, and despite school D having a number²⁶ of SDS Career Advisers on campus, young Roma people did not have equitable access to career services due to structural dynamics (see for e.g. Chapter six, p. 189). Natalie (15) stated that she had only spoken to her teacher Charlotte about her career aspirations, London (15) said she had never spoken to anyone in school regarding careers, but that she sought further support. Similarly, Spanja (13) recalled never having spoken to a Career Adviser, but advised that she would like to speak to someone, as she stated, 'No but, I would want to speak to them'. These calls for

²⁶ The number of Career Advisers working in school D has not been disclosed due to concerns regarding anonymity.

further educational and careers support serve as a powerful counter-story to disrupt master narratives that espouse that Roma, Gypsy and Traveller people ‘don’t value’ education and careers (Solórzano and Yosso, 2002).

During focus group discussions, Super Cat revealed that she had spoken to her primary school teachers, regarding becoming a veterinarian. For Cahill and Furey (2017) children in primary school begin to explore possibilities for their present and future selves. In support of this, Poole and Low (1985) argue that career aspirations are formed early, with Hughes and Kashefpakdel (2018) emphasising the importance of career guidance in primary school. Although Super Cat had the opportunity to explore her future self as a veterinarian in primary school (Welde, 2016), such opportunities were largely absent in secondary school settings.

Contrary to the ease with which learners recalled sources of guidance within the home, Lenka and Magic Cat demonstrated significant silences regarding provision in educational settings, as can be seen from the exchange below:

Nicola: Have you spoken to anyone at school about college support getting to be a nail lady?

Lenka: (prolonged silence)

When the silence continued, I turned to Magic Cat and asked her the same question,

Nicola: Would you want to speak to teachers about what you would want to do as a career?

Magic Cat: (prolonged silence)

I did not dwell on the question, as my main priority within the focus group was to ensure that young people felt comfortable. Questions pertaining to the support they received in school, were the only questions that Lenka and Magic Cat chose to remain silent on. I wondered though, if like Alyssia, they did not have the courage to tell me that they did not receive equitable access to career guidance within their educational field. The theme of silence appears to suggest that students were conflicted between speaking up and remaining silent. Freire (1993, p. 72) would describe this silence as a ‘limit situation’, where young people are experiencing an ‘obstacle to their liberation’. He further argues that the ‘theme of silence suggests a structure of mutism in the face of the overwhelming force of the limit-situations’ (Freire, 1993, p. 79). It appears as though the lack of support as manifested through the

institutional habitus is constraining learners' horizons for action. These experiences increase learners' sense of helplessness and their silence may be construed as acknowledgement that their voices wouldn't be able to change how they are treated.

Similarly, Scottish Travellers, Bernadette and Shera, did not have access to career guidance when they were in school (Archer and Moote, 2016). Bernadette explains in the exchange below,

Nicola: So teachers never spoke to you about careers? Did anyone share careers websites with you, or did you ever watch videos about careers?

Bernadette: No not in primary school or high school. They don't learn you how to do your tax returns, or how to get a mortgage. You need money and you need to know how to get the money, and where to put it. Something they can go to learn more about careers and for advice I can't remember ever seeing anything like that.

Overall student narratives within the Scottish context are marked with subordination and powerlessness, revealing a clear lack of knowledge of the options available to them both within educational settings and for their further education options. Guidance provision from the perspective of learners within school D, as well as Bernadette and Shera's experiences highlight that access to institutional support appears to be largely absent for these young people (Smyth and Banks, 2012; Foskett et al., 2008).

While for Irish Traveller Kasey, the multiple intersecting barriers she endured during secondary school became too overwhelming and ultimately led to her disengagement from education. As she explained, her home life was in disarray, having lost two cousins and a grandmother in a short space of time, and then her father went to prison. In addition to her Traveller identity, she was grappling with her sexual identity which was also impacting on her mental health. Although the school's Career Adviser attempted to engage her, Kasey however, felt that the Career Adviser could not understand her experiences and that she would never be able to use career guidance as she explained in the exchange below,

Kasey: There was a lot going on, over a two-year period, so I became disengaged. I couldn't see the point, I am never going to use this. That's how I felt about the careers lady. I felt like she didn't get it. She wasn't

able to address the points of life I was facing. She didn't answer those questions. Or she couldn't.

Nicola: What kinds of questions?

Kasey: My question for me, was Travellers don't do this, so why are you following me? I didn't know how to get past it and she couldn't get me past that. So it felt pointless. It was difficult. I remember they took us LSE and I remember thinking why did you pick me? I distinctly remember sitting there and being 'I will never go somewhere like here, so why bring me here, what's the point, because you are showing me something I can never have.

Nicola: Why did you think you could never have it?

Kasey: Because Travellers don't go to uni – that was my perception. That higher education wasn't a place for us. I looked around and I didn't see anyone go to uni, I didn't know anyone that went to uni, so it felt like something I couldn't do. It played heavily into why I didn't do A-levels.

Kasey's words capture the essence of what Holman (2014) meant when he stated that young people often internalise ideas pertaining to what 'people like them do'. Here, Kasey indicates that she believed that Travellers didn't go to university and despite a school trip to the London School of Economics, she still could not envision herself attending. Higher education was something she could never have. Consistent with the literature, Kasey's habitus (first generation, working class, ethnic minority community member) informed her perceptions of higher education as being beyond her horizons for action (Hodkinson and Sparkes, 1997; Reay et al., 2005; Redmond, 2006). To this end, Hodkinson (2008) observes that young people will often dismiss interventions that appear to be too far beyond their frame of reference, thereby illuminating the need to build interventions from the perspective of young people (Freire, 1993).

Although Kasey dropped out of secondary school, she enrolled in college when life felt more manageable and because she 'wanted more'. The importance of access to communities of interactions as well as opportunities for critical consciousness development (Freire, 1993) in broadening students' career horizons, may be evidenced through Kasey's experiences with her tutor in college. Bron had worked for over a year to build up trust with Kasey so that she would

engage with him. Bron and Kasey slowly formed a professional relationship and would have weekly discussions. She recalled that he worked to increase her confidence and skills and continually encouraged her to consider higher education. Once she had agreed, he liaised with his contacts at King's College London and continued to support her through the application process. During their initial discussions, Kasey had expressed that she aspired to be a physical education teacher, but Bron had offered her another perspective. She explained,

In college I wanted to be a PE teacher, but Bron said most people wanna be a PE teacher because they know what one looks like and they think they can do that job. That always stuck with me it makes so much sense.

Kasey's chance encounter with Bron parallel's Bernadette and Shera's serendipitous meeting with Article 12 in Scotland, suggesting that positive relationships with trusted others resulted in turning points for all, highlighting what opportunities each could see within their respective fields (Colley, 2003; Hodkinson, 2008). In the same way that Shera 'didn't know [she] could do things to change things for Travellers' until she came into contact with Article 12, Kasey didn't see the broad and various routes available to her, initially basing her decision on the familiar and known, because she knew what a PE teacher looked like (Hodkinson and Sparkes, 1997). Finally, although these chance encounters increased Kasey, Bernadette and Shera's horizons for action, they demonstrated their own agency by reacting to these serendipitous events thus confirming that individuals do exert a significant influence over their own careers (Hodkinson, 2008). The following section will now consider the support available to young people across England, Scotland and Wales from the perspective of stakeholders.

The Institutional Field: Stakeholder Perspectives

As the preceding sections demonstrate, young people from across the studied age range, are actively demonstrating agency through seeking advice and guidance from a number of trusted adults in their lives. A significant number of students also demonstrated help-seeking behaviours in relation to identifying the support that they felt they needed, not only when accessing education, but in order to achieve their wider aspirations. When young people received appropriate levels of support within their educational setting, higher learning and career aspirations were voiced. The following section discusses the support available to young people across the four schools from the perspective of stakeholders. Provision differed

depending on the school. Findings highlight the inclusionary and exclusionary practices that serve to either broaden or dampen students' horizons for action. The institutional habitus of the schools that are successfully supporting students may be characterised by the following features:

- School leadership and culture
- Focussed and targeted staff support
- High expectations from teachers, teaching staff and Career Advisers
- Strong links with communities of interaction (further and higher education institutions; local employers; NGO's and parents)
- Flexible curriculum and student-centred orientation
- Strong relationships
- Addressing structural barriers

In school's A-C young people had access to a range of opportunities enabling them to develop their educational and career aspirations. The curriculum in school A, offered students the opportunity to engage in future motivation goal setting activities and to create an action plan for how they are going to achieve their aspirations. These sessions were delivered by Mrs H. In addition to this, young people learned about employability and business development by setting up their own in-school business. Mrs H discussed how young people had established a sweets business where they would plan their finances, make their own sweets and work through the 5 P's²⁷ of marketing in order to sell their sweets.

Although Mrs H provided career advice to young people, she also emotionally supported them when they didn't know what they wanted to do once they reached adulthood. She held high expectations of her students and placed a strong emphasis on them obtaining their GCSEs and A-levels whilst still in school. As stated previously, Kooper was unsure of his career aspirations and sought advice from Mrs H. Her response to Kooper was to continue his sixth form education, as he could decide on his career once he had obtained his A-levels. Mrs H encouraged all students to be 'present' focused with the aim of attaining qualifications that would broaden the opportunities available to them. All young people in school A had access to personal guidance from Year 10 and each student had one face-to-face guidance interview with

²⁷ The 5 Ps of marketing: product; price; promotion; place; people (Judd, 1987).

both their form teacher and the Career Adviser to discuss their aspirations and to identify possible steps towards achieving their goals.

Young people within school A were also supported by staff to attend open days at the college and university where they could sample different careers. Moreover, school A had formed links with London King's College via their 'RomBelong' widening access programme – drawing on local charity Travelling Ahead to further support students (Beremenyi, 2020; Law, 1981). Seb, who participated in the current research was being supported by Mrs H and Travelling Ahead²⁸ to fill out his application forms for the programme, as Mrs H explains,

Well, Seb has got an opportunity for London King's College. With another boy they will have a taster with five different subjects like war studies, business...

As Harrison (2018) contends, widening access programmes serve to disrupt historical inequality by providing opportunities for those from marginalised backgrounds to overcome the barriers that they face. It is important to note, that within school A, Mrs H has fostered relationships to form communities of interaction (Law, 1981) with stakeholders such as Travelling Ahead and King's College London in order to provide opportunities for students to explore the broad range of possibilities available to them.

Overall, I felt that it was Mrs H's nurturing and supportive nature that was making all the difference in these learners' lives. Her belief in them, as well as the high expectations she held of them, aided their own self-belief in what they could achieve. As Pantaleo (2016) recently noted, high teacher expectations serve a vital role in increasing student engagement and achievement, while others have observed a significant correlation between high teacher expectations and student attainment (see for e.g. McKown and Weinstein, 2008; Timperley and Phillips, 2003). Similarly, Mrs H's holistic approach coupled with high expectations served to keep young people engaged.

It was not only Mrs H who was supporting young people with their career development journey in school A but the Career Adviser too. The role of the Career Adviser, extended beyond providing career guidance and involved working with young people to overcome structural barriers within their field (Hodkinson and Sparkes, 1997). By way of illustration, Mrs H, recalled how the Career Adviser helped learners by taking them 'to open bank accounts if they

²⁸ Travelling Ahead is an NGO in Cardiff Wales that works with children and young people from Roma, Gypsy and Traveller backgrounds.

struggled with language'. Although there is a paucity of literature to suggest Career Advisers should go beyond providing career guidance (Thomsen et al., 2013), the educational literature emphasises the importance of teachers going beyond merely teaching the curriculum and enacting community mindedness (Ladson-Billings, 2009). In the same way, Career Advisers could embody and enact community mindedness to enable learners' to overcome structural barriers.

Individual interviews within school B revealed a more flexible curriculum available to young people alongside career guidance support. The Welsh education system allows greater flexibility within the curriculum, giving learners the opportunity to gain the necessary qualifications to pursue their career aspirations. A number of authors emphasise the importance of a culturally relevant and flexible curriculum to ensure continued engagement in education (see for e.g. Padfield, 2005; Jordan, 2001; Bhopal, 2000; Hamilton, 2017).

Consistent with the literature the TESS team demonstrated that they had a significantly positive impact in increasing engagement and retention of students within educational settings (Estyn 2019; Fremlova et al., 2009). Discussions further revealed that they had engaged in critical thought relating to how young people accessed education and ensuring that provision was based on the families' stated desires or needs (e.g. students were separated for lessons in order to respect gender norms within their community). In the same way, Hamilton (2017), found that the Gypsy/Traveller parents who participated in her study advised that young people would have to be separated for sex-education classes.

Further adaptations were observed that aimed to increase engagement and retention. These adaptations were especially important for a number of young Romani Gypsy boys, who worked with their fathers for a few days each week – serving as a form of work placement - while simultaneously attending school. Counterintuitively, the flexible approach appeared to facilitate increased attendance for some young people who were working with their fathers, as Stephanie recounted,

I've got some of the boys on a flexible curriculum. In Wales we can use a flexible curriculum so they go home a little bit to work then with fathers but now a mum's just rung me saying she wants to extend her sons week!

Stephanie's words revealed that devolved powers (Reynolds, 2008) meant that the TESS team could modify the curriculum so that students were not only able to learn from their fathers but could also continue to access education. The excerpt also suggested that the approach resulted

in one parent wanting to extend her child's school week. These results lend support to Bridgeland and colleagues (2006) research that demonstrated that opportunities to engage in real-world and work-related learning increased their participant's engagement and retention in the school system.

Moreover, findings revealed that the TESS team adopted a student-centred orientation in their approach to education and career guidance (Foskett et al., 2008). The student-centred orientation was demonstrated through the TESS teams' adaptation of provision to suit students' needs by offering a package that included maths, English, and Design, Construction & Technology qualifications. The programme designed by the TESS team is based on the young boys' stated interests, in line with Freire's (1993) call for designing education programmes with the oppressed as opposed to for them. Consistent with findings by Lanskey et al. (2015, p. 579) in illuminating successful interventions by youth justice and educational professionals, the approach taken by the TESS team may be described as 'education by design rather than default' as they developed the curriculum activities monthly and tried to ensure that the programme was aligned to students stated interests where possible.

During my individual interview with Stephanie, it struck me that there were stark gender differences between students. Discussions revealed the importance of adapting provision for young Romani boys in particular, with Stephanie once again emphasising that the offer would have to be flexible or young people wouldn't attend. She explained,

Stephanie: Girls do better than boys. Girls tend to stay until Year 11. The boys tend to drop off from Year 10 onward but we do try to keep them to do their GCSEs. We'll put them in early so they are not leaving with nothing, so they will leave with some qualifications.

Nicola: So you bring them forward a bit so they can get those qualifications?

Stephanie: Yes, they need to leave with something, and when they go off we still have input into them. We still meet them and we make sure they are ok. And they do a more work based thing cause they go out working with their families, they need to learn the trade from their fathers.

The excerpt above reveals that Romani Gypsy boys are more susceptible to dropping out than Romani Gypsy girls (Levinson and Sparkes, 2003) due to the emphasis placed on learning a trade from their fathers (Clark, 2001; D'Arcy, 2012). The discussion also illuminates the

importance of school B's flexible approach and the cultural considerations taken by the TESS team in their attempts to support students. The discussion with the TESS team also revealed that students were able to undertake their qualifications earlier, citing educational opportunities as a basic human right, as Liani stated, 'yeah, we have brought it back. We bank as much as we can. They got a right to education'. Drawing on Bourdieu and Passeron (1977), the TESS team were gatekeepers who played a key role in the dissemination of educational capital through supporting learners in attaining their qualifications. By banking as much as they could, TESS staff were altering the structure of the field by creating opportunities for qualifications in order to broaden learners' potential horizons for action (Hodkinson and Sparkes, 1997).

School B also provided face-to-face personal career guidance from Year 10, helping explain why the younger Romani Gypsy boys who participated in this research, did not yet know who the Career Adviser within the school was. As can be seen from discussions with students in preceding sections, many were already thinking about their educational and career aspirations from the first year of secondary school, highlighting the importance of earlier access (Hughes, and Kashefpakdel, 2019). While young people did not have access to the Career Adviser until Year 10, the TESS team led by supporting them from their first year of secondary school, guiding them on their careers timeline, making referrals to training providers, organising work placements and 'holding their hands' along their journey to college.

As with school A, Romani Gypsy students in school B also accessed careers education through the curriculum - particularly through PSHE lessons that provided young people with opportunities to build CV's and engage in enterprise activities, all under the support and guidance of the TESS team. Stephanie indicated that the curriculum activities offered to students were 'all relevant to what they need to know in their life, for later on and [that] they love[d] doing it as well'. In addition to this, Shareen facilitated the college application process by taking young people to the local college's open evening where they could explore the options available to them.

Focus group discussions with Emanuel and Zoe, within school C in England, revealed the level of hands-on support available to students, which appeared to be making a discernible difference in their lives. Both the principal and vice principal were undertaking Masters degrees focused on Roma students, demonstrating an awareness of student backgrounds within the school's leadership and culture (Foskett et al., 2008). Subject teachers and the school's Career Adviser

provided guidance to the students. As with schools A and B, young people within school C, only had access to personal guidance from Year 10. The school also held an annual careers day where Year 10 and Year 11 students would do mock interviews and meet with local businesses to explore potential career opportunities. Similar to school B, opportunities for work placements were also available to young people.

The wrap-around care that young people had access to within school C was further demonstrated through the approach that Zoe took to arrange work placements for her students. The excerpt below demonstrates the importance of nurturing relationships for young Roma people, as Zoe explains,

Sam was one of the students who hadn't enrolled come September and when we got hold of him he was kind of waiting for someone to collect him and go and enrol. He was quiet, sort of reserved and he needed that almost hand holding to take him to enrol and even when he was signing the form he was quiet... He was shaking he was a bit nervous, but he's still there which is great.

Zoe's words revealed that she took the time to get to know the young people she was working with on an individual basis. Her words also indicate that Sam was eager to participate on the work placement programme despite being nervous, and that he is still working at the donkey sanctuary with support from the school. Discussions further illuminated the importance of the interpersonal relationships that Zoe and Emanuel had built with young people and their families, and their role in promoting continued engagement in education where young people were at risk of dropping out (Mittendorff, 2010). The staff team also worked to highlight the long term benefits of continued education to parents. Zoe explained,

Bogdan and Atahac got jobs over the summer and when we did the home visit it was the parents, they told us they got jobs. But we said that they need to be in education so then we went back and collected them and took them in the minibus to enrol at [...] they both wanted to do a football coaching programme so we took them, and after three days of attending that they thought this is too far to travel so then we got them on to the ESOL programme but they are still attending that and with the ESOL programme then they have got more options available to them.

Zoe's words revealed that while Bogdan and Atahac had dropped out of school in order to take up employment and earn money (Mulcahy et al., 2017), the intervention by the school staff, however, resulted in them re-enrolling on a football coaching programme, therefore ensuring

the former students still had access to education that provided opportunities for them to attain a formal qualification. The excerpt also demonstrated that Zoe embodies what Sultana (2014, p. 319) describes as career guidance for social justice, by actively creating outreach interventions on the micro- and meso- levels to ‘reach out to dropouts’.

The excerpt also revealed that Bogdan and Atahac had dropped out of the football coaching programme due to the distance that they needed to travel to the college. Zoe’s words confirm a number of young participants’ earlier stated preference for physical proximity to educational institutions out of economic necessity (Beremenyi, 2020; Pérez and McDonough, 2008; Reay et al., 2001; Smith, 1997). The wrap around care offered by school C, was again demonstrated by the staff team facilitating young people to attend college closer to home, in line with their stated needs.

Discussions with Zoe also illuminated the advocacy role she played on the meso or institutional levels on behalf of Roma students, lobbying for the restructuring of social structures (Sultana, 2014). By way of illustration, Zoe recalled that the current apprenticeship framework was reproducing injustice as the offer was inaccessible to Roma students but was also adding to the current skills shortage manufacturing firms were facing. She noted that at a recent ‘meet the manufacturers event’ concerns were raised regarding the ageing workforce with no young people coming through to ‘backfill’ these positions. Zoe then described how she problematised the current framework to manufacturers in that it excludes learners’ who do not meet the level two apprenticeship requirements.

Following this event, Zoe had arranged to meet with a large, multinational company²⁹ in order to address the current framework and discuss lower entry options. Zoe felt as though the organisation could get around the framework by offering students a ‘level one in customer services’, even though they wouldn’t necessarily ‘be doing customer services’. From this perspective the transformation of current entry requirements would be giving young people a ‘foot in the door that will then enable them to progress, whilst studying their Maths and English’. According to Sultana (2014, p. 319), Zoe’s actions indicate that she is lobbying hard to change organisational practices and working around exclusionary frameworks to ensure that her Roma students are not on the ‘receiving end of social injustice’.

²⁹ The name of the company has been removed due to anonymity and confidentiality reasons as the firm may be softening apprenticeship entry requirements.

More than Education and Career Guidance: ‘Opening Doors’

A common theme that emerged from discussions with teachers, teaching staff and Career Advisers across school’s A-C was that the staff teams often went beyond their job description. The approach taken by the aforementioned staff members embodied what Ladson-Billings (2009) would describe as ‘community mindedness’ which encouraged increased student and parental engagement. There was also an emphasis placed on holistic support to increase attendance through the removal of structural barriers present within families’ fields. As Liani explained,

We do everything from finding dentists, doctors, supporting parents in court and supporting social services. It’s gotta be holistic for the parent to buy into education, into the support. Otherwise it wouldn’t have worked.

Mrs H emphasised that students thrive when barriers are ameliorated and opportunities are presented as she stated,

Students are more than happy to walk through doors - if their obstacles to their learning are eliminated or reduced and if they are aware of the opportunities around them.

As mentioned previously, a corner of Mrs H’s classroom is filled with furniture items, educational material and clothing she had personally collected from charity shops after school hours, often delivering items to families and storing other items for ‘future need’. Mrs H, also worked to help students challenge discrimination. She explained,

We need to be flexible. People don’t understand GRT issues and the challenges they face, the educational gap and the prejudice - it’s a vicious circle. You need to attack it from all angles, all the time and chip away at it. You can’t just look at one aspect, it’s all related.

Mrs H achieves this by inadvertently employing Freirean pedagogy (Freire, 1993). For Freire dialogue provides a means for participants to problem solve through constructing and deconstructing knowledge, in culture circles. Culture circles are designed as a medium for problem posing, dialoguing and problem solving thereby raising awareness of an individual or groups reality, so that they may address inequalities. Freire’s culture circles employ problem-posing methodology and include three general phases: 1. To identify and name the social barrier; 2. Analyse the cause of the barrier; 3. Work to find solutions to overcome the barrier (Freire, 1993).

As can be seen from Mrs H's excerpt below, students are supported in naming their world, by participating in culture circles with teaching staff, community organisations and the Welsh Government to collectively problem solve. She stated,

This is what the children made for the Welsh Government, looking at barriers and solutions to obstacles. So if money was the issue and the obstacle to learning, where would you get the money from for your learning? If bullying was an issue, where could you go to get help? So if people are sexist, what can we do about it?

For Watts et al. (1999), critical consciousness is theorised to be a tool to tackle oppression. Mrs H's problem posing approach with young people facilitates their critical consciousness development, which they can draw on in dealing with oppression in order to overcome socio-political barriers. Moreover, as she includes stakeholders who have power within the exercise, this may increase a learner's belief that they have influence and agency over the oppression that they face. The problem posing approach adopted by Mrs H, emphasises the consideration of education and future career orientations within the social, cultural and political conditions that serve as a barrier to opportunity amongst these marginalised young people (Blustein et al., 2005).

Moreover, Mrs H's problem posing approach is intersectional in nature, as it takes into account multiple interlocking barriers (Clark, 2015) as identified by young people through dialogue, that serve to limit their educational and future career opportunities. In support of the current findings, the literature suggests that through supporting students to challenge intersectional barriers such as racism, sexism and poverty influences their critical consciousness development (see for e.g. Balcazar et al., 2001; Campbell and MacPhail, 2002). Similarly, research by Diemer and Hsieh (2005) and Diemer and Blustein (2005) demonstrated that facilitating and nurturing critical consciousness development in young people serves to empower them to transcend socio-political barriers along their career journey.

Applied to the career guidance context, Career Advisers would do well to learn from Mrs H's approach as it emphasises the importance of championing equality and diversity through an empowered 'frame of reference' (Field and Baker, 2004, p. 57). From this perspective, Career Advisers should not only advocate for young people but also teach them self-advocacy skills using pedagogical experiences (Freire, 1993) to foster an empowered worldview which students can use to bridge intersectional barriers (Field and Baker, 2004).

The accounts from teachers and the TESS team across school's A-C serve to confirm the experiences of students within the current study. A common strategy identified across schools in England and Wales was focussed staff support to promote inclusion and continued engagement and retention in education. The role of Careers Advisers, teachers, teaching staff and the TESS staff team has been crucial in not only broadening learners' horizons for action but also addressing the structural barriers within their educational field.

While Career Advisers play a significant role in guiding learners, findings reveal the importance of teachers and teaching staff in shaping student perceptions (Foskett et al., 2008). They have served as guides, supporting young people with a range of educational and guidance activities, informing them of and providing experiences of local further and higher education provision and employer engagement opportunities. Smyth and Banks (2012) argue for the effectiveness of these strategies as they normalise attending further and higher education, and encourage students to explore a range of options by providing information which broadens their horizons for action (Hodkinson and Sparkes, 1997).

The Picture in Scotland: 'We are a wee bit away from an open Careers Field'

The career conversation tone in Scotland was starkly different to the discussions I had with those supporting young people in England and Wales. Scottish teachers and Career Advisers often placed a greater emphasis on process and how provision works rather than on wrap-around care or developing relationships. Alison (teacher) explained careers provision in school D by stating,

There are workshops and groups they can join and that tends to start September time. I am quite shaky on that but there is definitely support available and we go to them because these are pupils who require additional support. If we left them to self-refer a lot of pupils wouldn't do it.

It is important to remind the reader that students within school D recalled no such access to support. Moreover, career education within the curriculum as identified within the Welsh and English contexts, did not emerge through discussions within the Scottish context. There was also no allusion to career education in the Scottish curriculum or guidance on how young people could access such education without language support, which is in direct contrast to the entitlements as set out by the Career Education Standard (Scottish Government, 2015). In an

attempt to rectify the structural language barriers impeding Roma students participation in education, Charlotte (teacher, school D) noted that she had reached out to the Scottish Government's 'Scottish Traveller Education Programme' (STEP) for language support but that no one had responded to her pleas.

Common themes that permeated interviews within the Scottish context include low expectations amongst teachers and Careers Advisers and the tendency for both to pathologise students' culture (Derrington and Kendall 2004, 2008; Derrington, 2007). Similarly, research by Wilkin et al. (2010) demonstrated that teachers attributed low attainment outcomes to parental and community attitudes. The individual interview with Alison provides one of the first examples within the transcripts of the low expectations held for Roma students. She stated,

I think we are a wee bit away from an open careers field but, definitely, they would be able to hold down a full time job. I would hope.

The implications of her words is that she is narrowly framing students' horizons for action and enforcing limited options on them (Lundahl, et al., 2017). Individual interviews with Careers Advisers within the Scottish context also revealed low expectations with staff tending to pathologise culture while simultaneously using community members' mistrust of authorities to justify the lack of provision. As Sarah explains,

I mean, anecdotally there's that community thing where they are a bit more suspicious of authority and outsiders in general, and I think advisers on the ground would anecdotally reflect that back. We've not got hard evidence. The school might say 'don't come in and see them' so employability and jobs are not on the agenda. We take the lead from schools.

While Sarah acknowledges that her observations are merely anecdotal, her words suggest that because communities 'mistrust' authorities, employability and jobs are taken off the agenda, with no consideration of how stakeholders could build relationships of trust with community members. Majoritarian master narratives wherein community members' mistrust of authority are therefore adopted to explain the lack of engagement and ultimately serve as a barrier to young people accessing career guidance (Schaffer, 1985; Solórzano and Yosso, 2002).

Overall staff narratives within the Scottish context denoted that they expected very little of the students both within educational settings and post-school, consistent with the literature pertaining to Gypsy Travellers (Foster and Norton, 2012; Wilkin et al., 2010) and other

minority populations (McDonough and Calderone, 2006; Smyth and Banks, 2012). George and Aronson (2002) argue that the low expectations expressed by teachers and Career Advisers sheds light on their implicit beliefs about 'race' and ethnicity. The implications of these beliefs is that they will influence all subsequent support offered to learners.

In an individual interview with Carina, an SDS Career Adviser supporting students within school D, it was revealed that her responses aligned to master narratives (Solórzano and Yosso, 2002). When I asked if she provided careers support to Roma students, she responded that,

Well we should, but we can't because a lot of them don't come to school or if they do, they can't speak English that well and it's hard for us to communicate with them, and we don't have our own translators. Most of them don't want to engage with careers. We don't know where they are. So we change their risk to not ready to access the support because we just can't find them, or they just don't attend.

Carina's comment is one of many examples within the Scottish transcripts that illustrate the degree to which institutional habitus, is shaped by the multiple habituses of teaching staff that serve to constrain and limit Roma students career choices and life chances (Reay et al., 2001). Carina's words suggest that students are not interested in careers and she never questions whether factors such as language barriers or poverty might affect their ability to engage. The theme of truancy from education and career guidance was prevalent in the majority of the Scottish interviews. For example, discussions with Alison also tended to err on the side of pathologising culture to explain non-attendance amongst Roma students.

A more plausible explanation for learners' lack of engagement may be demonstrated by Charlotte as she explains that within school D, a lack of resources mean that 'good teachers' were failing to 'receive the necessary support required to teach all the pupils in their classes'. She also went on to discuss that teachers were feeling burnt out. From this perspective Charlotte explains her colleagues' attitudes and actions to be the result of austerity and inadequate resources to support mainstreaming efforts (Glasgow City Council, 2011; Ryder and Cemlyn, 2014).

These findings support the use Hodkinson and Sparkes (2017) careership theory as they demonstrate the extensive influences of social structure as manifest through policy that is preventing students from receiving the support that they need and subsequently shaping their perceptions about what is probable within their field. However, this is only part of the picture. The current data has demonstrated multiple instances of low teacher expectations and racist

attitudes that are operating to keep Roma students on an uneven playing field. To this end, the exclusionary practices of teachers and Career Advisers make up the field or institutional habitus through which students experience education and career guidance, thereby restricting the development of their aspirations (Lanskey, 2015).

It is important to remind the reader that school's A and C, both supported Roma pupils and boasted 95 percent attendance rates (see 'School Environments in England, Wales and Scotland', p. 94). These attendance rates provide a powerful counter-story to challenge the narratives put forward by research participants in Scotland. Discussions with teaching staff in Wales and England demonstrated that where young people are supported in school settings, they engage consistently with education and career guidance services. By way of illustration, discussions with Mrs H in Wales revealed that non-attendance had previously been an issue, but by working with parents and supporting young people to foster a more inclusive learning environment, the school was able to overcome non-attendance.

In order to further counter majoritarian narratives related to non-attendance that emerged during interviews with Scottish stakeholders, I would also like to draw the reader's attention to the 'Roma Broadening Horizons' programme that I designed and established as an after-school project for Roma students. The programme was developed with young people, support from NGO's Show Racism the Red Card Scotland, Community Renewal and Charlotte (teacher from school D). This programme ran over eight³⁰ weeks every Friday afternoon and saw over 15 Roma students voluntarily give up their free time each week. The workshops included career guidance, employer engagement and Freirean culture circle sessions blended with football, dance and art. Young people arrived at Queen's Park FC every Friday afternoon after school without fail. It is thought that the programme was successful in maintaining continued engagement with young people due to the design of the weekly workshops being built from their perspective of students stated needs (Freire, 1993).

As the interview with Carina progressed, she again pathologised Roma students' culture by explaining that the lack of career provision was a result of them falling pregnant, their limited English, and family mobility. She explained,

A lot of them will get pregnant at such a young age but that's expected, so we don't have a lot of dealings with them. If we get through to a phone number, the person

³⁰ While the 'Roma Broadening Horizons' project ran for six consecutive weeks, the programme had to be halted due to COVID-19.

doesn't speak English and most of the time the school says they have moved out of Scotland as well [laughs] and most of its done through letters, phonecalls, emails...

Further discussions with other SDS Career Advisers (Falon and Richard) confirmed the 'off-rolling' of students, but their narratives suggested that this practice is not only restricted to Roma young people and occurs across various community groups due to staff having to 'tick boxes and meet targets'. Carina's words also revealed a tendency to pathologise culture when explaining lack of engagement. Echoing Solórzano and Yosso (2002) this excerpt demonstrates a majoritarian narrative to explain student engagement through a cultural deficit model. The use of a master narrative by Carina, may be seen as an abdication of responsibility for Roma students career guidance needs, thereby playing a significant role in their exclusion (D'Arcy, 2012). Carina's words demonstrated an exercise of power, in that they reflected, 'what can be said and thought [...] who can speak [...] and with what authority' (Hall, 1992, p. 290).

Drawing on Cunliffe's (2004) work based on Freire (1993) and critically reflexive practice amongst career practitioners, it is evident that Carina does not employ a critical stance, as she does not question how her words and ethics inform practice and how they may impact on her relations with students. Cunliffe (2004, p. 414), asserts that 'critically reflexive practitioners [...] question the ways in which they act and develop knowledge about their actions [by] highlighting ideologies and tacit assumptions – exploring how our own actions, conversational practices, and ways of making sense create our reality', together with participants. Moreover, within critically reflexive practice, there exists a moral requirement to provide opportunities for others voices to be heard. To this end, Carina's words indicate that her assumptions reinforce pejorative and racist stereotypes, where she provides limited opportunities for young people to communicate and share their reality.

Research participants (Carina, Richard and Terrence) also revealed that prejudicial attitudes are present amongst SDS Career Advisers preventing them from conducting home-visits. This revelation is problematic as Humphris (2016), contends that home-visits are often the primary and only contact that Roma communities make with state actors. Carina explained this reluctance to conduct home visits to be due to fear,

Sometimes the post-school team do house visits but see now a lot of them are refusing to go to the [...] area. They feel unsafe. They feel quite intimidated in that area. I wouldn't want to be marching around [...] myself chapping on doors. Scotland's never had to deal with those kinda issues in the past.

As the reader will recall, the individual interviews with Emanuel and Zoe in England demonstrated the difference home visits by careers staff and teachers were making in reducing drop-out rates. Carina's words revealed that SDS staff were refusing to do home visits due to fears around personal safety. Drawing on Solórzano and Yosso (2002, p. 29), Carina's words are indicative of a majoritarian master narrative, in that 'darker skin and poverty correlate with bad neighbourhoods'. Terrence (Career Adviser) on the other hand, thought that his colleagues' refusals to do home visits may be attributed to the negative media representations surrounding Roma communities living in Scotland (Stewart, 2019; McKenna, 2017; Mullen, 2018).

Nevertheless, staff members' reluctance to conduct home-visits means that they are missing an opportunity to create communities of practice with those furthest from the labour market. As Roma, Gypsy and Traveller people place an emphasis on community and collectivism (Greenfields, 2006), Thomsen and colleagues (2013) model of career guidance in communities is highly relevant to the current analysis. The authors draw on Freire (1985, p. xxiii), in that theory creates a space in order to 'mediate and critically comprehend the type of praxis needed within a specific setting at a particular time in history'. The model consists of several elements such as:

1. Creating opportunity structures and access
2. Entering a community and increasing visibility
3. Providing guidance in communities
4. Exploring potentials in guidance situations
5. Deciding on guidance activities
6. Developing, planning and implementing
7. Documenting and evaluating

The authors observe that the model is not linear and encourage practitioners to reflect on the elements simultaneously. For the purposes of the current analysis, however, I will focus on the first three elements of the model. In terms of creating opportunity structures and access, both Cunliffe (2004) and Thomsen et al. (2013) emphasise the moral requirement to provide opportunities for participants' voices to be heard in order to create meaningfully relevant career guidance activities. Career Advisers reluctance in conducting home-visits suggests that they are failing to provide opportunities for student voices to be heard. Engaging in home-visits and involving parents and community organisations will give practitioners insight into the

challenges community members face in order to create relevant guidance activities (Thomsen, 2017).

The second element entails entering a community and increasing visibility (Thomsen et al., 2016). Increased visibility will create opportunities to develop trust (Messing, 2014; Hamilton, 2018) with Roma, Gypsy, Traveller students and parents simultaneously, a crucial factor in relationship building (Marcus, 2016). Dialogue is an important tenet within the third element of the model – providing guidance in communities. Drawing on the work of Rogers (1971), Amundson (2006) and Westergaard (2010), Thomsen (2017, p. 12) asserts that the ‘standard virtues of professional career guidance [require] active listening, unconditioned positive attention, congruence and empathy’.

The words elicited by Carina above, indicate that she has failed to exercise the standard virtues of professional practice and reveal a deep lack of empathy for students’ histories and the challenges that they currently face. Career Advisers’ refusal to conduct home visits prevents community-based dialogue. This dialogue serves not only to increase visibility in order to access and mobilise resources based on the challenges that community members face collectively but also to increase the relevancy of career guidance practice to all (Thomsen et al., 2016).

By engaging in community-based dialogue and identifying the problems that community members (as demonstrated in the ‘Roma Broadening Horizons’ programme I developed with young people), are facing in accessing adequate support, the career practitioner could work with members of the Roma community to create a context for action (Thomsen, 2012). Moreover, Career Advisers could also exercise advocacy by highlighting the issues to various stakeholders who have influence in order to tackle the intersectional barriers community members are facing (Niles and Harris-Bowlby, 2009). For Law (1981), various community stakeholders should be ‘interwoven into the experience of the client with a wide range of sources of help and influence’.

Overall, school D appears to have failed in several respects, ranging from the lack of career guidance provision within the curriculum, a clear lack of engagement with parents and students, generally low teacher and Career Adviser expectations and the tendency to pathologise Roma culture. The low expectations that institutional stakeholders often held for Roma students appeared to influence the support that they provided to students. Similarly, research by Bryan et al. (2009) demonstrated a correlation between Career Advisers’ expectations for pupils and

the amount of contact with the student. Moreover, a common theme that emerged from the Scottish context indicated that relationships between students and staff were marked by negativity (Bhopal, 2011; Jordan, 2001; Lee and Burkam, 2013), which has the potential to place learners at increased risk for dropping out (Lundahl et al., 2017).

Career guidance appeared to be demarcated to SDS by teaching staff, with only Charlotte (teacher, school D) being cited as a source of advice by students themselves indicating that provision of such support was not a high priority for Roma students (Foskett et al., 2008). The implication of this demarcation is that career guidance appears to be removed from Roma students' day-to-day learning and suggests piecemeal provision from SDS. Drawing on Shor and Freire (1987, p. 4), staff in the Scottish context dehumanised learners as the focus of change was placed on the 'consciousness of the oppressed, and not the social order that oppresses them'.

A worrying theme that emerged from discussions with Career Advisers in one local authority area in Scotland is that when a child fails to attend school or if they haven't been seen in a while, their status is changed to having 'moved out of Scotland'. Further discussions revealed that this practice occurs not only in relation to young Roma people but all community groups that Career Practitioners work with due to the pressures associated with number-crunching and targets. Consistent with the literature, the most commonly cited reason for Roma learners non-attendance or disengagement from education is that 'they travel all the time' (Lauritzen, 2018, p. 60). A master narrative that is used by practitioners to shift responsibility and justify Roma, Gypsy and Travellers exclusion from education thereby sustaining 'key tropes of antigypsyist discourses' (*ibid*; 59).

Staff narratives suggest that when a student disengages from services or when they 'can't be found', their disengagement is not followed up with a home visit, consistent with Scottish Traveller Bernadette's experiences and contrary to best practice as identified in schools A-C that successfully encouraged students' re-engagement in education. School D may then be described as failing in their duty to detect early warning signs and provide additional support for vulnerable learners (Elffers, 2012; Lamote et al., 2013). These factors need to be addressed as they impede students' educational and career trajectories (Hodkinson and Sparkes, 1997).

The data sheds light on gaps within SDS' (2012) guidance provision based on the 'Career Management Skills Framework. In line with the neo-liberal and meritocratic paradigm (Smith, 2007; Vassallo, 2012), the framework purports that learners can be successful in the world of

work if they develop certain key competencies. Skills development and management is envisaged as being primarily the responsibility of the individual but the framework fails to address the structural patterns of inequality within a learner's field, which can limit social mobility.

Staff narratives also appear to be contrary to SDS' (2019a) Equality Outcomes as learners do not have 'access to and ongoing support from CIAG services', so that 'they may make informed choices' (p. 9). These findings suggest that SDS needs to adopt racist reporting and monitoring mechanisms where students can report acts of racism perpetrated by Career Advisers. In addition there is a need for Career Advisers to participate in a sustained programme of anti-racism training instead of one-off diversity workshops, that research demonstrates to be less effective in addressing prejudicial attitudes (Campbell and Hay, 2018, 2019).

The discussions related to the Scottish context thus far have raised worrying concerns regarding practice within educational institutions. There were, however, examples of 'good practice' that emerged with some stakeholders in Scotland and the efforts of these individuals cannot be overlooked. For example, Clinton the SDS Career Adviser based in Fife arranged the stakeholder focus group in order to share knowledge and best practice with community groups in the local area. Throughout the fieldwork process Clinton remained engaged, and shared job opportunities for Roma community group members with me, which I shared with the various organisations and Roma community group members I know.

Sherrie (Irish/French Traveller), a retired Community Development Worker who recently attained her PhD, continues to volunteer for Article 12 in Scotland also participated in the current research and emulated pedagogical educational practices (Freire, 1993) blended with Thomsen and colleagues (2013) model of career guidance in communities. Sherrie, also fostered a student-centred approach and altered the field within which young people found themselves by actively creating and promoting opportunities for their further development. In discussing Bernadette she stated,

Bernadette knew she needed a qualification, and she knew she wanted to be a community development officer. But she didn't wanna go straight into further education it would just be a step too much. So then we said you can do it as work training and that's what fitted for her.

As can be seen from the excerpt above, Sherrie entered into dialogue with Bernadette, providing a space for her needs to be expressed thereby basing provision on her identified

needs. Through Article 12 in Scotland, Bernadette was able to attain a £10,000 per year training allowance wherein she works two and a half days a week as a community development officer for Article 12 and then studies for the rest of the week. Sherrie noted that this approach was imperative as Bernadette ‘hadn’t done any formal learning since leaving school’ so the ‘tailored training blended within studying was helpful’ as she used the ‘training to better understand the theoretical side’.

As discussions progressed, Sherrie suggested that it is imperative that opportunities are visible to young community members and that they have equal access to them, echoing the words of Mrs H, Sherrie stated that, ‘a door just needs to be opened’ for them to walk through. These findings illuminate the need for access to flexible adult education and further post-school opportunity structures built with and from the perspective of students (Hodkinson, 2008; Freire, 1993; Thomsen et al., 2013) so that young people do not become trapped in low-status jobs or cycles of unemployment.

Discussion

The first section of this chapter demonstrates the range of individuals within students’ familial networks that they approach for education and career guidance. Learner narratives indicate agency in that they draw on parents, siblings, extended family and adults who they consider to be ‘successful’ as sources of career support. They then utilise this guidance to make pragmatically rational decisions for their futures (Hodkinson and Sparkes, 1997). These findings challenge majoritarian narratives relating to Roma, Gypsy and Traveller families education and career aspirations and illuminate the value that they place on familial support as a means of attaining social mobility (Solórzano and Yosso, 2002). Indeed, as Romani scholar Ethel Brooks (2015, p. 60) contends Romani ‘success stories’ do not happen in isolation but always with the family and wider community. She further argues that the ‘narrative of the (deracinated) exception as heroic individual struggling against community is, at the core, an impossibility that simply serves to reinforce liberal, capitalist, and fundamentally classist and racist, conceptions of expertise, knowledge production and class mobility’ (Brooks, 2015, p. 60).

While I agree with Brooks, there are still structural constraints within the educational field that may impede students’ social mobility. The evidence presented here demonstrates overwhelming support emanating from familial networks, however, these families often lack

the cultural capital necessary to provide information on further and higher education (Smyth and Banks, 2012). As the majority of these students will be the first generation in their families who plan on completing secondary school and attending further and higher education, knowledge in traversing this unknown landscape will therefore not be readily available at home. This analysis therefore illuminates the need for access to support within educational institutions and the equitable dissemination of information that will enable students to navigate further and higher education and the labour market (Reay et al., 2005; Smyth and Banks, 2012).

The second part of this chapter analysed who young people approached for education and career guidance within institutional settings. Students' decision-making processes regarding who to approach for support may be described as pragmatically rational and based on two factors: those who students trusted and felt comfortable with (the familiar and known); and those who were best placed to provide guidance in line with learners stated aspirations (knowledge based experts) (Hodkinson and Sparkes, 1997). Contrary to findings by Marcus (2016a), who asserted that young Scottish Traveller's only cited role models were their parents and relatives, the current research suggests that students also identified a range of actors within educational institutions who inspired student career choices.

Across the English and Welsh geo-political contexts, the majority of students recalled support for accessing guidance, opportunities to explore their educational and career aspirations, lessons within the curriculum, discussions regarding employer engagement and work placement opportunities, access to further education and higher education open days and personal face-to-face career guidance interviews. Collectively these strategies form the school habitus and broaden students' further education, higher education and career trajectories (Hodkinson and Sparkes, 1997; Smyth and Banks 2012). Consistent with the literature amongst settled populations, the institutional habitus shapes students' educational and career decision-making, illuminating the opportunities available to them and the perceived accessibility of those opportunities (Foskett et al., 2008; Reay et al., 2005). Collectively, these findings indicate that when institutional and familial habitus work in harmony with each other, they have the power to influence a range of decisions such as continued engagement in education and broadening learners' perceptions in 'what people like them do' (Reay et al., 2001; Bourdieu, 1990; Smyth and Banks, 2012).

Contrary to the support identified for students in England and Wales, student narratives within the Scottish context are marked by subordination and powerlessness, revealing a clear lack of

knowledge regarding the options available to them. Equitable access to education, guidance provision and careers exploration appears to be largely absent for these young people (Smyth and Banks, 2012; Foskett et al., 2008) thereby demonstrating a systemic failure on the part of education and career institutions to effectively and appropriately support students from these backgrounds.

The third part of this chapter revealed that the provision of education and career guidance support varied markedly across geo-political context and institutional habitus or 'school affect', as reflected in teachers attitudes towards learners (McCoy et al., 2006) and the provision of services available to young people. The evidence presented here, demonstrates the tremendous influence that teaching staff and Career Advisers have on Roma, Gypsy and Traveller students. The data points to the pivotal role played by staff across school's A-C in broadening learners' worldview whilst simultaneously addressing the structural barriers within their respective educational fields. There was consensus amongst participants that suggested that students would often walk through doors of opportunity – but that these doors had to be opened by those with the power to do so.

The education and career staff across England and Wales provided access to information and guidance, access to further and higher education open days, opportunities to engage with employers and undertake work placements - strategies that are suggested to broaden students' horizons for action (Hodkinson and Sparkes, 1997; Smyth and Banks, 2012). While school's A-C can be characterised as having a student-centred orientation embedded within school culture, the Welsh schools offered students access to a flexible curriculum to further support their social mobility. Teaching staff and Career Advisers in England and Wales were also found to provide support that extended beyond educational and career-related tasks, removing barriers for students so that they could engage in education and think about their futures which may be described as a form of social capital (McDonough, 2005; Plank and Jordan, 2001; Bryan et al., 2010).

In contrast, provision in Scotland echoed findings by Diemer and Blustein (2006) wherein structural oppression and limited access to education and career-related support may be acting as a barrier to limit social mobility. Overall staff narratives often denoted that they expected very little of the students both within educational settings and post-school (McDonough and Calderone, 2006; Smyth and Banks, 2012). It is thought that these expectations reflect their

beliefs about ‘race’ and ethnicity (George and Aronson, 2002) and ultimately influence the support that they were willing to offer to learners.

The data in Scotland revealed negative relationships between students and staff (Bhopal, 2011; Jordan, 2001; Lee and Burkam, 2013), which may place learners at increased risk for dropping out of education (Lundahl et al., 2017). The exclusionary practices of teachers and Career Advisers make up the institutional habitus of school D, through which students experience education and career guidance, that may constrain their educational and career trajectories (Lanskey, 2015). Moreover, findings demonstrate the influence of social structure as manifest through mainstreaming policies and austerity (Glasgow City Council, 2011; Ryder and Cemlyn 2016) that are preventing students from receiving the support that they need.

Worryingly, there appeared to be an agreement between teaching staff and Career Advisers in Scotland whereby a child’s failure to attend school would result in their status being changed to having ‘moved out of Scotland’. A further revelation that emerged during discussions indicated that SDS staff refused to conduct home visits, which meant that Career Advisers were not actually following up on learners to see if they had indeed ‘moved out of Scotland’. Consistent with the literature, the most commonly purported reason used by adult stakeholders in Scotland to explain learners non-attendance or their disengagement from education is that ‘they travel all the time’ (Lauritzen, 2018, p. 60). Staff often relied on this majoritarian narrative to abdicate responsibility and justify exclusions (Solórzano and Yosso, 2002).

Findings also revealed disparities between policy and practice in the Scottish context. Although SDS’ (2012) ‘Career Management Skills Framework’ suggests learners can be successful in the world of work if they develop certain key competencies, it fails to address the structural patterns of inequality within a student’s field that limits social mobility. Staff narratives also appear to be contrary to SDS’ (2019a, p. 9) Equality Outcomes guidance as learners do not have ‘access to and ongoing support from CIAG services’, so that ‘they may make informed choices’.

Finally, as evidenced through the work of staff in England and Wales as well as Article 12 in Scotland, successful engagement with students is often aligned to critical pedagogy (Freire, 1993). Blustein et al. (2005) assert that career interventions with marginalised communities should aim to develop participants’ critical consciousness so as to transform structures of inequality. For Diemer (2009), engaging in dialogue about inequality facilitates critical

consciousness development which significantly impacts on young ethnic minority students' career development and occupational attainment.

It must however be noted, that this critical consciousness development is not fostered by one individual, but by multiple individuals such as teachers, Career Advisers and community organisations in a holistic manner. The way that school staff respond to young people based on their culture (Hargreaves, 1967), the interpersonal contexts (Rutter et al., 1979) and the personal exchanges of 'community interaction' (Law, 1981) between family, peer group, ethnic group, teaching staff and Career Advisers are of great significance in career development.

Overall, the pedagogical experiences that young people access across a variety of contexts, with staff personnel from the school and community organisations foster their aspirations, enable them to identify opportunities and empower them to make choices. Equitable access to pedagogical experiences that reflect students' multiple identities are therefore increasingly important in order to address the simultaneity of oppression within their experiences. The subsequent chapter addresses the intersectional barriers that serve to constrain learners' educational choices and career trajectories.

Chapter Seven

Intersectional Barriers

A large body of literature has demonstrated that young people perceive multiple barriers to career development such as ethnic and gender discrimination and poverty (Creed et al., 2007; McWhirter, 1997; Swanson et al., 1996). Drawing on Lorde (2007, p. 138), who asserts that ‘there is no such thing as a single-issue struggle’ as ‘we do not live single-issue lives’, this chapter presents findings to demonstrate the multiple, intersecting issues experienced by young Roma, Gypsy and Traveller people. Their experiences reflect that they are caught between institutional, structural, political and cultural tensions intersecting with ethnicity, ‘race’, gender, class and poverty to exert power over and influence their lives.

Observing these inequalities is important in order to demonstrate the matrix of barriers that impact on students’ experiences of education and career advice and guidance. As Mama (1997, p. 40) contends, ‘what is bad for women is worse for Black women’. Yuval Davis (2006, p. 201) raises the question ‘how many social divisions are involved and/or which ones should be incorporated into the analysis of the intersectional process’? Based on the data, we see that Roma, Gypsy and Traveller students face a matrix of interlocking barriers such as ‘race’, ethnicity, gender and poverty, which intersect with both structural and political inequality that compound and constrain their agency and horizons for action (Hodkinson and Sparkes, 1997).

Poverty and Class: ‘Who can afford to want? Who can afford to do?’

Relative poverty and deprivation is regarded as a paramount barrier to accessing secondary, further and higher education. This view was shared by all learners, teaching staff in Wales and England and the majority of parents. Young Roma people discussed the implications that poverty had on their aspirations. As Lauren (Roma girl, 16, Wales) explains below, achieving her aspirations will be determined by finances,

Lauren: Yeah I was thinking but I will have to see how the money goes. Now that’s the big problem.

Nicola: In terms of barriers for what you wanna do next, would money be one of them?

Lauren: Yeah cause with money you can actually do something.

Lauren's words appear to indicate that money is a 'big problem' within her horizons and she can't pursue her goals due to her lack of economic capital (Hodkinson, 2008). Similarly, Scottish Traveller Bernadette (23), was deterred from attending drama school in Glasgow after she dropped out of secondary school. Despite being offered a place at the drama school, she was unable to attend due to financial constraints. She recalled, 'I wanted to go to drama school and I got into one in Glasgow but I couldn't afford it cause they are so expensive. So I just kinda dropped out'. As Kasey (Irish Traveller, 26, England) eloquently explains, realising one's aspirations is dependent on economic capital,

Who can afford to want? Who can afford to do? Not if you are poor. I worked because I had to. You don't have that luxury of having parental financial support, so sometimes it's more important to get into a job.

Relative poverty was not only impeding students achieving their future aspirations but it was also serving as a barrier for their continued engagement within secondary school. Roma learners' described barriers relating to housing, school uniform and the welcomed support they received from Mrs H (teacher, school A, Wales). Lauren stated,

She helps us, she actually helps people who don't have house or something to wear. She actually goes and gives it to people.

Indeed, discussions with Mrs H, revealed the levels of deprivation students were living in, as many of the pastoral issues the school was dealing with related to accommodation, overcrowding, sourcing mattresses for young people to sleep on as well as utilities support for the provision of heating and water. Mrs H spent a significant amount of time doing clothing collections through various charity shops with support from the wider community. I spent the evening before the focus groups with Mrs H and was given further insight into the levels of deprivation young people were facing and the lengths she went to support students, long after the school day had ended.

Mrs H, had been collecting household goods, furniture and clothes to distribute to families that were piled up in a corner of her classroom. Although Mrs H is an extremely committed individual who goes above and beyond the remit of her job, policymakers cannot assume that all teachers will have the drive or capacity to do this and future policy developments must consider the structural barriers impacting on student's development. During the focus group in

Wales, when young people were discussing the financial implications of staying on in sixth form, Mrs H attempted to reassure them that finances should not be an obstacle to education as they would be supported³¹ by the school. Mrs H explained,

In sixth form you are eligible and we can help to apply for funding and the team helps them apply for funding. So it covers your travels, it covers your food. So it shouldn't be an obstacle. So they don't think, 'I am not going to stay cause I can't afford this and that'.

Mrs H in Wales and Emanuel (community liaison worker, school C) in England were acutely aware of the impact that poverty was having on young people accessing and engaging in education. During discussions, it was revealed that if families could not afford transport to get to school or if they could not afford school uniforms, then attendance would be affected. Both Mrs H and Emanuel worked to remove the financial barriers young people were facing, by providing food, uniforms and transport so that all students 'had to do was learn'. Emanuel had recently been dealing with a case that illustrates the levels of poverty families are living in. He explained,

Mum says they're in a very difficult situation, they don't have money for buses so we went and collected them but they didn't have trousers or shoes. So we clothed them and put shoes on their feet. Sometimes food in their bellies so all they have to do is learn, so we need to take care of everything else.

As can be seen from Emmanuel's words, he believes that his role is to remove all of the barriers by 'tak[ing] care of everything else' so that all young people need to do is learn. The implications of learners disengaging from education due to not having the economic capital to get to and from school or to be able to afford a school uniform is that by dropping out, they will be severely constrained in what they will be able to do next (Lundahl et al., 2017). These barriers will serve to limit their future potential, keeping them in a cycle of poverty, low pay and precarious work conditions (Martin et al., 2017; Foster and Norton, 2012). The staff teams across England and Wales were, however, actively working to remove the barriers within students' educational fields in order to broaden the range of possibilities available to them.

Individual interviews with Emanuel and Zoe in England also revealed the push and pull factors facing young people in their decision to continue with education or leave school to earn money

³¹ The financial support includes the Education Maintenance Allowance; supporting students 16 and above with benefits and housing applications; free school meal applications; as well as bus passes.

to provide support for their families. Zoe problematized the £17 in child benefits³² for the eldest child. She recounted that learners' are often conflicted in their decision to continue in education when considering the potential earnings in factories with parents, aunts and uncles that could contribute to the household. To this end, while child benefits were seen to incentivise continued engagement in secondary school and further education, the amount of money was not seen as a strong enough pull to ensure retention.

Indeed, when discussing career aspirations, a number of student narratives alluded to helping their families financially and the responsibility that they felt to contribute to familial income. Faced with continued deprivation or the option of being able to contribute to their familial households impacted on young people's decisions (Mulcahy et al., 2017). These concrete constraints give lie to the assumption within Career Management Skills (CMS) frameworks (Skills Development Scotland, 2012, 2019b; Careers Wales 2017; Scottish Government, 2020) that suggest that students can act freely and achieve social mobility thereby illuminating the need for structural solutions (Simon et al., 1991; Sultana, 2012). While parents are supportive, they too may be motivated by a need for immediate income due to high levels of poverty and deprivation. Emanuel explained,

Because these boys were 16, they were already considered men. So parents were on board with school but then if the boys found a job and went to work somewhere part-time, or with their parents, they would encourage that instead.

It is important to note, that while Roma, Gypsy and Traveller people are the most deprived communities across all indicators (Equality and Human Rights Commission, 2015), there are many young people across different ethnicities and cultures who suffer from poverty and deprivation and face stark choices. Elffers (2012) notes that immigrant and Ethnic minority students are more likely to drop out of school due to socio-economic constraints, while Forsyth and Furlong (2014) found similar results within their gadjé Scottish sample, where financial deprivation and the need to support their families served as a barrier to full-time education. Drawing on McDonough and Calderone (2006, p. 1713), the push and pull factors associated with continued engagement in education need to be 'reconceptualised as affecting not only the child but also the family as a whole'.

³² As of the 2019/2020 tax year, parents could claim £20.70 per week for their first child and £13.70 per week for their second child (The Money Advice Service, 2019).

The following discussion between myself and Romani Gypsy boys in Wales captures the conundrum that they are facing when considering further and higher education,

Pikey Bradley: Why would you do that? Stay in school for more time in your life when you could just be out. Think about it all these days I am coming to school I could be going to work yeah. Imagine how much money I could have now.

Nicola: If you think about the higher salary you would get for an extra four years of studying

MC Allen: You wouldn't be minimum wage. I would go if it was free.

That's why I want university to be free.

Consistent with Hodkinson and Sparkes (1997, p. 31) notion of 'economic rationalism', student narratives reflect an externalised calculation of the imminent costs of attending higher education versus benefits and the 'net utility' of receiving higher education qualifications. The excerpt above also appears to suggest that learners are making pragmatically rational decisions in that they consider the economic, cultural and social capital gains or losses that each decision carries.

A number of authors (see for e.g. Bowers-Brown, 2006; Connor et al., 2001) have found that amongst students from lower socio-economic backgrounds, the cost of entering higher education influences their decisions to disengage from education. A significant causal factor within this decision-making is the lack of information on the costs associated with further and higher education and financial support (McDonough and Calderone, 2006; Perna, 2000). Similarly, Greenfields (2008) found that her English Romani Gypsy and Irish Traveller research participants demonstrated limited knowledge regarding training bursary eligibility in order to enter Health and Social Care careers. In a recent blog post by the Travellers Times (2019), some of the most frequently asked questions by young people include: how to obtain a student loan; how and when to pay it back; and how to cover the living costs associated with attending university. Learner narratives signal a need for Career Advisers to provide financial advice so that the perceived costs of further and higher education do not deter young people from attending.

For those students who have managed to overcome the barriers and broadened their horizons making university enrolment possible, the effects of poverty and class persist. As Kasey explains,

I remember my second week of uni thinking this is not a place for me. Bron had told me that university was full of white middle class kids who didn't have many issues. When I went to college kids didn't have money for lunch every day and these uni kids were insanely privileged kids. It was a different world.

Despite Kasey's history being marked by intersectional deprivation and oppression, hers is a story where her own agency along with a happenstance³³ encounter (Krumboltz, 2009) with Bron broadened her horizons for actions and enabled her to transcend her background, becoming the first generation in her family to attend university. During her first few months in the wholly unfamiliar habitus of university, she felt like a 'fish out of water' (Bourdieu, 1999, p. 495), in comparison to her middle class peers who were 'fish in water: unable to feel the weight of the water, taking the world about them for granted' (Bourdieu and Wacquant, 1992, p. 127). Consistent with the literature, students from non-traditional backgrounds experience higher education as an alienating and marginalising experience (Ball et al., 2002a; Redmond, 2006) increasing the need to familiarise learners with higher education culture (James, 2000).

In order to overcome the alienating experience of higher education, Kasey had to rely on her communities of interaction (Law, 1981). The significance of trusted others in imparting cultural and social capital may be demonstrated through Kasey's on-going professional relationship with Bron. She explained,

That's why I created those relationships and sat with Bron because he told me these conversations are of value and they were. It led to more opportunities. They don't tell you to do this stuff though - to have these conversations. The conversations with Bron were so important because I didn't know.

In order to successfully traverse the higher education landscape, Kasey relied on the transfer of cultural capital from her former college tutor Bron, who continued to mentor her. As suggested by Krumboltz (2009) and Hodkinson and Sparkes (1997), her decision-making reflects an opportunistic dependence on serendipitous encounters with others. Through the knowledge disseminated by Bron, Kasey was able to learn how to 'embody the culture and

³³ Happenstance Learning Theory holds that behaviour is the result of 'planned and unplanned situations', which yield learning outcomes such as 'skills, interests, knowledge and future actions' (Krumboltz, 2009, p. 135).

traditions of higher education' (Redmond, 2006, p. 122). She detailed the realisation that her grades were not all that mattered (Bourdieu and Passeron, 1977). Kasey had also become acutely aware of her language and pronunciation (Goffman, 1953) and that she would have to attend social events and create relationships in order to broaden her choices and life chances (Hodkinson and Sparkes, 1997). Drawing on Redmond (2006, p. 127), Kasey had learned to transcend being a 'Wash 'n' Go' student, no longer simply attending lectures and heading home immediately after. She became engaged in the broader social and cultural aspects of university life and developed 'soft currencies' by amending her language and accent (Brown and Hesketh, 2004), a form of institutionalised cultural capital necessary to navigate higher education (Naidoo, 2004).

Although Kasey had increased her social and cultural capital and appeared to be embodying the culture and traditions of higher education to broaden the range of opportunities available to her, she wasn't entirely convinced that her actions would free her from a lifetime of poverty. As she explains,

That's what you are told, they tell you, the neoliberal argument – if you work hard and you do all these things then that is enough but I don't think it is enough. You are still on an unlevel playing field. They don't tell you when you are going to uni, you think it's gonna be the route of you getting out of poverty but equally it might not be. What you do is a very small part of it.

Kasey's words illustrate her tragic, but vital awareness, that despite her own agency and the chance event of meeting Bron, her future may still be partly determined and constrained by the opportunity structures within her field. While it appears that she may have been successful in increasing her own social mobility by drawing on others within her community (Law, 1989), her actions do not 'dismantle the structural patterns of inequality' (Kóczé, 2009, p. 37). As Reay et al. (2001, p. 872) observes, higher education is not likely to 'offer the same rewards for all'. Nevertheless, her experiences may serve as a guide for teachers and Career Advisers, illuminating the need for dialogue with learners, particularly those from deprived backgrounds so that they may develop 'soft currencies' (Brown and Hesketh, 2004). This dialogue will enable students to learn about the cultural capital necessary to navigate higher education (Naidoo, 2004) and the importance of relationship building and networking in broadening the scope of opportunities available to them.

Gender: ‘A man should have his career and a woman should have hers’

A number of authors contend that gender role socialisation and cultural expectations may place a gendered ceiling on Roma, Gypsy and Traveller girls’ career prospects (Hamilton, 2017, Kiddle, 1999, Marcus, 2016, Okely, 1983). Contrary to previous findings, the current data demonstrates a shift in gendered cultural norms amongst the girls who participated in this research. Domestic aspirations for their own futures were not mentioned by the girls.

Some of the Romani Gypsy research participants expressed that they felt pressure to conform to heteropatriarchal expectations from the wider community living on their site, but the girls demonstrated resistance. Further resistance was demonstrated by Roma girls in England who not only expressed aspirations aligned to ‘gender atypical’ occupational fields, but were entering further education in order to achieve these aspirations. It is, however, important to note that while the theme of resistance emerged from discussions with the girls, these narratives were geographically bound. For example, Romani Gypsy girls’ in Wales demonstrated tension towards wider community expectations for them, while Roma girls’ in Scotland appeared to passively accept that they would one day do ‘girl jobs’.

Comparatively, fewer authors have explored the perspectives and experiences of Roma, Gypsy and Traveller men (see for example Okely, 1983; O’Boyle 1990; Greenfields, 2008; Levinson, 2015; Levinson and Sparkes, 2003). Okely (1983) and O’Boyle (1990) provided summaries relating to the attributes of Gypsy/Traveller men, while Sparkes and Levinson (2003) explored the performative nature of masculine Gypsy identities through business skills, dealing, fighting and sex talk. In the following section, I provide extracts and commentary from interviews with young Romani Gypsy and Irish Traveller boys in Wales that relate to issues of gender performance and the impact that gendered expectations have on young people.

‘Men is for work and women is for cleaning’

As mentioned previously, Romani Gypsy students in Wales were separated within educational settings, and provision differed depending on gender. Okely’s (1983) social anthropological fieldwork contends that Gypsy/Traveller girls cannot be seen to be alone with boys unsupervised, even within school settings, as it may pose a threat to her reputation and honour – bringing shame on the family. Indeed, within this educational context, boys and girls were

not to be alone with each other in class without adult supervision, as the school based provision on families stated needs. These findings concur with Marcus' (2016, p. 194) research with Scottish Traveller girls, where 'girls are with girls' and 'boys are with boys' due to the emphasis placed on morality and decency. Contrary to Marcus' finding that secondary school was only considered a place for Scottish Traveller boys (*ibid*), secondary school was a place for both genders within the current research, albeit in separate classes with girls tending to stay on in secondary school longer than boys (Derrington and Kendall, 2003).

What struck me most, speaking to a number of Romani Gypsy and Irish Traveller boys and girls in Wales, was when I asked them what their mother's and sister's did as an occupation. The most common response offered by students was that they did 'nothing'. In describing her sister's occupation, Poison Ivy (Romani Gypsy girl, 13) stated that she 'is nothing. No job. She's a fulltime mother'. The tendency for young people to equate homemaking with 'nothing' offers a deeper understanding to the way in which homemaking and housework activities are perceived and defined by students across genders and the role that household labour plays within the family. Kóczé (2009) contends that, just as in the case of gadje women, Roma, Gypsy and Traveller women's domestic roles are valued less than waged labour. It is important to note however, Roma, Gypsy and Traveller women tend to be overrepresented in the role of domestic work, in comparison to other ethnic identities (*ibid*).

Comparatively, there is a paucity of literature on the perceptions and experiences of Gypsy/Traveller men and boys in relation to the gendered division of labour. A common theme that emerged from focus group discussions with Romani Gypsy and Irish Traveller boys in Wales was that the majority of them (except for MC Allen) cited that they did not approach their mothers as sources of career guidance. It is not only that mothers are not seen as a source of valuable information but the notion that they could be is overtly ridiculed. For instance, as mentioned in the preceding section entitled 'Career Aspirations' (p. 140), MC Allen (Romani Gypsy boy, 13) was teased by the other boys in the focus group when he stated that he had spoken to his mother about his future plans.

Such negative sanctioning can be seen as a clear illustration of what Connell and Messerschmidt (2005) have described as a pattern of 'policing men' who deviate from the established norm in order to achieve hegemonic homeostasis. Teasing, a form of passive aggression by the more high status boys, serves to structure and maintain the hegemonically masculine hierarchy through subordinating alternative positions (McGuffey and Rich, 1999).

MC Allen's subsequent denial of speaking to his mother as a source of career guidance may be due to fear surrounding being exiled from the group, which may be devastating as group-belonging is a source of masculinity and self-worth for many young boys across various community and ethnic groups (McGuffey and Rich, 1999).

This internal group regulatory practice may be further evidenced by Gypsy Tony's response to my question regarding whether he spoke to his mother about careers which clearly denotes a belittling of his mother's roles and activities:

All they do is clean up isn't it. They don't work do they? They just let the men work and they get all the money and provide for them isn't it?

Such gendered perceptions of what defines 'real' work are so embedded in these young men and can be seen as an attempt to further regulate and 'police' men into a particular behavioural pattern, re-establishing the masculine gender hierarchy and relegating women to the inferior role on non-wage earning homemaker (Walkerdine et al., 2001). Such practice clearly illustrates what Connell and Messerschmidt (2005) describe as a pattern of hegemonic masculinity which must include a simultaneous lowering of the value of the work of women. It is, however, important to note the subtleties and nuances within Gypsy Tony's words as they appear to be framed as a question back to me, which may reflect Stoudt's (2006) argument that there are spaces and moments of resistance where those who embody hegemonic masculinities can in turn question them.

In discussing shared domestic responsibilities around the house, Smooth Move (Irish Traveller boy, 12, Wales) stated that domestic responsibilities would fall on his sisters when they got older (Derrington, 2016; Cudworth 2019), while his brother, Big Man (Irish Traveller, 14, Wales) reinforced that 'men is for work and women is for cleaning'. These patterns of practice appear to be 'common-sense' and thus becoming somewhat 'naturalised' (Bourdieu, 1984, 2001) as neither of the boys questioned the demarcated gendered divisions of labour within the family structure.

This lack of gendered self-awareness is further evidenced in the responses I received when I then asked the boys within the focus group if they felt pressure to be the main breadwinner and their perceptions on gender equality. In response, Pikey Bradley (Romani Gypsy, 14, Wales) and Gypsy Tony (Romani Gypsy, 13, Wales), asked what gender equality was. The excerpt below demonstrates the entrenched heteropatriarchal views that the boys have internalised, when I explained what I meant by gender equality:

Nicola: When both people are contributing to the household, do you think it's a lot of pressure on the guy that he has to bring in all the money?

Gypsy Tony: No Gypsies just go out to work every day. Men do anyway and women they clean the flat, what's that thing when you can't stop cleaning and you see every piece of dirt?

Nicola: Obsessive Compulsive Disorder

Gypsy Tony: Yeah that's what women do all day, they clean the furniture and men go and earn the money then give it women and they go to shop.

Okely (1983) affirms that it is the role of the Gypsy/Traveller mother to govern, maintain and care for their home and children, with Cemlyn et al. (2009) suggesting that the primary role of men is to support their families financially. Family structures are based on the intergenerational transfer of traditional patterns of the gendered division of labour, and Romani Gypsy women play a vital role in the preservation of cultural practices (Acton and Mundy, 1997; Hamilton, 2016). Although these practices may be perceived to be oppressive by mainstream society, they are a source of great pride for Romani Gypsy women (Casey, 2014).

According to Tichenor (2005), such traditional gendered division of labour reinforces the patriarchal gender hierarchy as men's traditional role as breadwinner across various populations confers on him greater power and privilege. There are nuanced considerations necessary here, however, as Gypsy Tony advises that while men earn the money, they hand it over to the women to control the household budgets. Indeed, Greenfields et al. (2012, p. 108) contend that Gypsy and Traveller economic relations are 'embedded through systems of redistribution and reciprocity' reflective of the 'hierarchy of the kin group'.

'We do girl jobs'

Roma, Gypsy, and Traveller girls who come from backgrounds marked by deprivation and poverty 'constitutes a "triple burden" of gender, class and race' (Casey, 2014, p. 5), which shapes their worldview in relation to education and career options. Focus group discussion with young Romani Gypsy girls in Wales revealed that the role of marriage coupled with wider community expectations worked to influence the options available to them. When I asked Poison Ivy, if she thought her sister would return to studying following marriage, she stated,

Not now that she is married. You stop all that when you are married. It depends what kinda work it is, and if you are making more than a man then yeah you stop working. If you are like a hairdresser or something then it's fine cause it's girly.

Echoing findings by Okely (1983) and Greenfields (2008), Poison Ivy's words reveal that there were restrictions on the types of activities that Romani Gypsy girls could pursue. Similarly, Helleiner (2003) found that Irish Traveller women were more likely to engage with the labour market prior to marriage. For Kóczé (2009, p. 24), however, this 'gender-typified socialisation' wherein 'Romani women are expected to be the main care providers for their children' occur in 'most societies around the world'. Indeed Gaskell (1992) contends that women generally base career decisions on domestic circumstances. The girls' narratives revealed that marriage and careers were seen as mutually exclusive by their wider community, and a career could only be pursued, if it were not of a higher status to their husband's career.

Tichenor (2005) argues that the conventional marriage contract demarcates men as the breadwinner and women as the homemaker. When the wife, however, enters the labour market and earns more than her husband, this 'gender disruption' results in a shift in the balance of power within the traditional marital contract (Risman, 1998). Learners' educational and career options are then partly determined by wider community expectations that are influenced by gender roles and the need to maintain gender harmony within the traditional marriage contract. Nevertheless, despite the pressure the girls felt to conform to gender specific roles, they demonstrated resistance and challenged these expectations for their own futures (Cudworth, 2019).

Pertaining to the young Roma girls living in Scotland, the majority of them expressed career interests in art, music, dance and the beauty sector, with two young Roma girls living in Wales expressing career aspirations related to the hair and beauty sector. Farris and de Jong (2014) argue that these professional directions are inherently characterised as feminine and are perceived to be 'safe options' (Marcus, 2016) in that they are familiar and known (Hodkinson and Sparkes, 1997). When I asked the Roma girls in Scotland, if they thought their gender would be a barrier to achieving their career aspirations, London (Roma, 15) replied, 'no, because we do girl jobs'. While London felt that her gender would not prevent her from gaining employment, her words reveal that her career options are constrained along gendered lines (Hodkinson and Sparkes, 1997).

What is important to note, is that contrary to the strict cultural expectations placed on Romani Gypsy girls in Wales, the Roma girls in Scotland did not cite cultural expectations as a barrier to employment – employment was very much on their agenda. Their employment options were, however, aligned to sectors where women are over-represented. Farris and de Jong (2014) cite Severiens et al. (2007) to explain that these safe decisions are the result of receiving limited guidance and support from educational institutions and families. As evidenced in the preceding chapter (p. 162) students within the Scottish context reported familial support for their aspirations. The support available from their familial habitus was however, marked by limited economic, social and cultural capital thereby illuminating the need for career guidance that enables them to challenge stereotypical assumptions regarding gender. It is questionable whether these students will, however, gain access to such support as participants often cited limited exposure to career guidance within educational settings.

Viva La Resistance

Romani Gypsy research participants, Poison Ivy (13, Wales) and Cat Woman (13, Wales) demonstrated resistance towards traditional attitudes regarding women in the labour market. They advised that they felt as though the pressure to conform from their wider community on site was ‘intense’. When I asked them how it made them feel, the girls responded:

Poison Ivy: We got no choice, but to be ok with it. I am not ok with it personally. I think a man should have his career and a woman should have hers.

Cat Woman: Travelling boys treat us like slaves. This is why I don’t want to have a boyfriend.

Poison Ivy: Yeah we don’t go anywhere unless we are allowed to. We are not allowed to leave unless we are told we can. We are not allowed to wear what we want. Like if we had a pair of shorts on and they told us to take them off we would take them off. We have to.

Cat Woman: I wanna punch them in the face!

Poison Ivy: A man will always overpower a woman. No matter what you do, a man will always have power over a woman. They are stronger and taller, they are always bigger built. I find this serious.

The girls experiences illuminate the power of patriarchal control and the pressure they feel to conform to dominant power structures (Walkerdine et al., 2001). Poison Ivy and Cat Woman's words demonstrate limited choice, relating to hegemonic community values and a woman's decision between marriage and a career, echoing hooks (2015) definition of oppression in that it is the absence of choice. Poison Ivy also alluded to the perceived power of men over women due to their size and strength that appears to govern the choices available to girls. Poison Ivy is, however, not alone in her perception, as across many cultures, men are seen as inherently stronger, rendering women as dependent and vulnerable (Nieto-Gomez, 1997).

These exchanges also illustrate the regulation, surveillance and policing of the girls bodies by male community members. Research by Casey (2014) and Hamilton (2016), suggested that Gypsy Traveller mothers and female community members policed girls and young women as a means of cultural maintenance. Conversely, the girls who participated in this research perceived that the control and restrictions placed over their bodies stemmed from male community members (Greenfields, 2008; Cudworth, 2019).

Both girls however, demonstrate critical reflection of these expectations and resist against the patriarchal discourses imposed on them by their wider community, suggesting that culture is neither static nor impervious to wider societal change. The excerpt above reveals the girls resistance in the grey spaces, and challenges the master narrative that positions 'Gypsy-Traveller women as passive and docile subjects of male subordination' (Casey, 2014, p. 10). Indeed Connell and Messerschmidt (2005), argue that patterns of hegemonic masculinity are open to challenge, when tensions exist such as those identified within the current data.

The role of institutional habitus in undoing gender

In considering the gendered aspects of support available to learners, it is important to highlight the approach taken by the TESS team and Mrs H in developing students' critical consciousness to challenge sexism. During individual interviews, all TESS team members in Wales recalled the dialogue that they engaged in with young Romani Gypsy girls and the impact that this dialogue was having on retention. TESS team member, Shareen revealed that when they first started the transitions programme (2007 - 2008), the girls' in their care expressed an overwhelming ambition to get married at 16, but through a process of dialogue these aspirations were beginning to change.

The TESS team also engaged in dialogue with parents in order to provide sexual and reproductive health education opportunities from local midwives to the girls. This required negotiation and adaptation of the delivery on the part of TESS staff and local midwives before parents would agree to let their children participate. By way of illustration, only Romani Gypsy Traveller girls and their mothers were allowed to be present and the blinds in the classroom had to be drawn for the delivery of the workshop. Liani recalled, that the presentation had to run from 'birth to backwards' which allowed 'the parents to buy into it'. While adapting the sexual health education workshop based on the needs of families, TESS staff also drew on their communities of interaction to facilitate the dialogue (Law, 1981) through the local midwifery team.

Discussions with TESS staff also suggested that they were spending a significant amount of time with the girls to promote engagement with career exploration whilst simultaneously challenging traditional gender roles. Liani recounted the ongoing conversations she has with students in the excerpt below,

We keep talking to them and reminding them that you can have a job, or you can have your children and go to college when you are older. There's a whole world out there.

Drawing on Freire (1993), the dialogue that is taking place between the TESS staff team and Romani Gypsy girls are providing an opportunity for dialogue and conscientisation to occur. The development of critical consciousness, enables them to understand the forms of 'power that they [can] exercise and the awareness of choice' (hooks, 2015. p. 94). Discussions with Liani highlighted, that while some girls do leave school at 16, she had noticed changes, in that, they were increasingly approaching her seeking guidance to increase their choices in life, which may be seen as an exercise of power. Liani stated,

It gives the girls a choice, if they got qualifications. But the girls - it's changing and it's encouraging for them to say to me, 'what do I need for me to do this job?'

According to Cudworth (2019) schools may provide a different spatial environment that fosters girls' aspirations and enables them to challenge the socio-spatial expectations of their communities. The support given to young people by the TESS team in challenging sexism within the educational field, may be influencing the development of critical consciousness in these students through opportunities for problem-posing and working to find solutions within their socio-political worlds (Diemer, et al., 2006). Similarly, an intervention conducted by

Bryant (2000) utilised challenging sexism as a means to foster and develop critical consciousness amongst young Black girls, through dialogue.

The evidence suggests, however, that Romani Gypsy girls are more likely to be provided opportunities to engage in such dialogue for challenging sexism and critical consciousness development due to support from the TESS staff team. In the same way, research by Diemer et al. (2006) revealed that gadje adolescent girls perceived more support for challenging sexism than boys did. The conversations with both TESS staff and the Romani Gypsy boys in this study did not reveal evidence to demonstrate dialogue or education interventions that would support them to confront gender inequality and reflect on their own potential participation in it. The community liaison worker in England Emanuel did, however, emphasise the need for provision to target support toward Roma boys. Discussions with Emanuel revealed that an increasing amount of Roma boys are raising the flags and challenging traditional models of gender, but that boys wait longer than the girls to raise issues. Emanuel thought that the boys in his care waited longer to raise concerns due to a perceived lack of support.

Emanuel's concerns may be correct as the data suggests that Mrs H was the only teacher across the three home nations who had been providing support to both genders. Mrs H provided sexual health education opportunities to both Roma girls and boys. By way of illustration, Mrs H explained the 'C-card' which was available every Friday, where students, whether they were sexually active or not, could obtain condoms and relationship advice from her. These open spaces appeared to be one factor amongst others in mitigating the occurrence of early marriage (Oprea, 2005; Council of Europe, 2013). This dialogue often included Mrs H, speaking with students about protecting themselves and their rights. She recalled that the school had previously experienced a few cases when Roma students first arrived, but that these practices no longer occurred. Young people were present for this part of the interview with Mrs H, due to her open door policy, and Kooper commented that 'it's changed a lot'.

These findings indicate that it is necessary to consider the 'gender burden' as it relates to both Roma, Gypsy, Traveller, girls and boys. To this end, teachers and Career Advisers should engage students in critical consciousness development (Freire, 1993) across genders to challenge norms related to 'how we do gender' in order to broaden what students believe to be possible. Drawing on Bimrose (2008), the guidance sessions could utilise images that challenge common gendered stereotypes and provide work placement opportunities for young Romani

Gypsy boys with self-employed female role models in industries where women are generally under-represented.

Finally, within the English context, there appeared to be a shift in how communities do gender. Discussion with the Career Adviser Zoe also revealed that Roma girls are increasingly seeking career guidance in fields where women are traditionally under-represented,

There are a lot of females, coming through and talking about engineering. A few of our female students, have gone to Leeds City College Building. They are looking at architecture, and instead of doing the traditional A-level route, they are looking at College Building. Which is a great qualification within construction and the building environment.

These findings appear to suggest that the range of work placement and open day opportunities available to Roma girls within their education field may be influencing their career decision. Institutional habitus, along with their new geographical habitus has increased what they see as possible (Hodkinson, 2008) and may be playing a role in these Roma girls demonstrating resistance to cultural expectations of acceptable gender roles. This analysis indicates that there are a number of girls who are not only expressing aspirations toward ‘gender atypical’ occupational fields, but they are entering further education in order to achieve these aspirations. It is therefore imperative that Career Advisers and employment support services reflect on the intersectional barriers that these girls will face due to the compounding effects of their multiple identities (Solórzano and Yosso, 2002; Hill Collins and Bilge, 2016) and advocate on their behalf to alter the structural barriers within their field (Field and Baker, 2004).

‘Race’ and Ethnicity: ‘They treat you different because of your colour and we have a different culture, but we are still humans’

The findings presented so far reveal that young people are oppressed by multiple political, structural, institutional, class and gender inequities (Crenshaw, 1991). The following section demonstrates that virulent racism homogeneously experienced by all students across the three home nations. Drawing on Bhopal (2020, p. 508), ‘racism predominates as central to these experiences’. In support, Cemlyn, et al. (2009) and others (see for e.g. Bhopal, 2004; Deuchar and Bhopal, 2013; Foster and Norton, 2012; D’Arcy, 2017) argue that the most common theme identified as a barrier to inclusion amongst Roma, Gypsy and Traveller students is racism.

Learners' detailed the racist bullying they have experienced and continue to encounter in educational settings from both their peers and staff. What emerges through the focus group discussions with participants, is that they are negatively affected and disadvantaged because of their 'race' and ethnicity.

Students in England recalled their encounters of racism in both primary and secondary school. For Ana (14, England), these experiences were tied to her identity when peers were surprised to learn that she is Roma. She explained,

I am not naming everybody, but like the Romanians are not as behaved, but like not only Romanians the other people are racist to Roma's. Sometimes I feel bad, when I am asked, 'are you Roma?' and I say, 'yes' and they say, 'oh are you actually?' Because they are amazed, like how come? And I feel bad, but I will always be proud of where I come from.

James (Roma, 14, England) recounted that he has experienced racism based on his skin colour and culture in both his community and in his school, as revealed through the excerpt below,

Many times this happened to me. Like whenever we go to the parks and even in school they go, they can't play with us. They treat you different because of your colour and we are a different culture, but we are still humans.

Hearing students' experiences within focus group discussions was difficult. What struck me, however, was the sense of hopelessness, in that students had accepted this treatment as part of life within their accounts. A common theme that emerged from conversations with a number of students, was their seemingly passive acceptance of racism as part of life, a common coping response amongst victims of racism (Feagin, 1990). By way of illustration, during a focus group in England, I said to learners, 'I am sorry you had to go through those experiences because you are Roma', to which Nicki Minaj (Roma, 16, England) responded, 'well you don't have a choice'. Nicki Minaj's words reflect the absence of choice in how she is treated due to her identity (hooks, 2015).

Bernadette (Scottish Traveller, 23), recalled that her experiences of racism included both verbal and physical violence due to her Traveller identity. Bernadette stated that she was initially excited when entering secondary school, but soon became the target of vicious attacks after revealing her identity. She explained,

I had people smashing my windows. They even put fireworks through our door once. Then you got people in school, whose beating you up in the corners, and calling you names, and online abuse. So you get enough and I left just before I turned 14. I just left one day after, in the cafeteria, 10 boys came up behind me and started pushing me across the tables and stuff, and started calling me names and laughing. So straight away, I went to the pastoral care teacher and I told him what happened, and he said there was nothing he could do.

Bernadette's words revealed how her experiences of racism and lack of support from staff in her school resulted in her decision to disengage from education as she felt that school was no longer a safe space. Drawing on Hodkinson and Sparkes (1997), experiences of racist bullying may serve as a turning point in that they serve to push young people from educational institutions thereby constraining their educational and career trajectories.

In sharing her experiences of racism within Scottish educational institutions, Shera (Scottish Traveller, 27), noted that she had initially tried to hide her identity and 'pass' (see for e.g. Foster and Norton, 2012; Hancock, 1997; The Traveller Movement, 2017). When her mother, however, shared her Traveller identity with teaching staff, this resulted in Shera being moved to different classes and teachers demonstrating lower expectations of her. She also felt that the revelation resulted in her being infantilized by teachers due to her identity as the exchange below reveals,

Shera: So I hid who I was, and didn't tell them I was a Traveller. But my mum told the teachers in the schools, so they knew but they never spoke about it. But because I was a Traveller, they put me in enable classes, as if I never had enough schooling. So giving me really childish work. The work the other students were doing, I said I could do that work but they would nae take me seriously.

Nicola: How did that make you feel?

Shera: Like really dumb, and like I was being treated differently, because, 'oh she's a Traveller'; 'she does nae know anything', and they wouldn't take me seriously when I spoke to them about it. I just had to accept it, this is life. It's just life, it's what you are brought up to know. It's as normal

as having a cup of tea and coffee, it's just life. So just accept it and move on.

Consistent with the literature, Shera's Traveller identity resulted in her subsequent placement on a 'levelled down' curriculum (Lloyd, 1999, 2005; Marcus, 2016). Shera's words, alluding to racism as being as 'normal' as 'having a cup of tea and coffee' echoes one of the basic tenets of critical race theory, in that racism is an 'ordinary' and a 'common everyday experience' for Ethnic minority community members (Delgado and Stefancic, 2017, p. 8). In her ordinary experience of racism, Shera, had stoically accepted the mistreatment she received based on her identity.

Experiences of racism again permeated across geographical boundaries into Wales, where both Roma and Romani Gypsy students detailed their encounters. Much of the literature points to primary schools being 'safe places' for young people (Foster and Norton, 2012), however, student narratives echo findings by Bhopal (2011) in that primary schools are also sites of oppression. As Sonja (Roma, 16, Wales) explained,

In primary here I have been bullied a lot. They called me names, saying we smell, that we are black, and we have a different skin colour. They weren't doing anything about them, and they just kept bullying me. I wanted to drop school but then I spoke to my parents, and they said what they are doing is against the law. They saw them doing stuff to me, and they wouldn't do anything and that's what I don't understand.

Similar to Bernadette's experiences within the Scottish context, Sonja felt that school staff failed in their duty to support her when they had themselves witnessed the racist bullying she had been experiencing, consistent with the literature (Bhopal, 2011; Law and Swann, 2011; Wilkin et al., 2010). The awareness that Sonja's parents had of their rights may be considered a form of cultural and social capital (Bourdieu, 1986) that allowed them to intervene and question the school's handling of a racist incident by drawing on Equalities legislation (Equality Act, 2010).

Left unchecked, these experiences of racist bullying could have resulted in a turning point with Sonja dropping out of school (Hodkinson and Sparkes, 1997). These experiences, however, raise concerns for parents who may not have the language, social or cultural capital to understand their basic rights. The excerpt above also reveals Sonja's difficulty in understanding why those who were meant to support and protect her within educational settings simply stood by and allowed it to happen.

During the focus group with Romani Gypsy girls in Wales, I asked what support they would find useful in order to achieve their educational and career aspirations. The students' responses alluded to wanting to not be treated differently by teaching staff as the exchange below reveals,

- Nicola: What other support do you think would be helpful?
- Super Woman: Um, I know some teachers in our school treat us different to what they treat the others.
- Nicola: Different how?
- Super Woman: Like because we are Travellers, they treat us like, they are more strict on us, than what they are to others.
- Nicola: And you notice it?
- Super Woman: Yeah you can notice it.
- Cat Woman: We get chucked out, but they don't.
- Super Woman: But if we had a support teacher with us, they wouldn't say anything. They just do it, when they are not there.
- Nicola: That's not fair.
- Poison Ivy: No one sees what they are actually like, because they can't witness it for themselves.

The exchange with the girls reveals that they believed that they were treated differently than their mainstream peers by teaching staff. Moreover, these experiences appeared to occur when students did not have the protection of support staff and that they would not be believed unless the TESS team could witness it for themselves. These findings echo Becker's (1967, p. 241), notion of hierarchies of credibility, in that members of the 'highest group' (teachers) 'have the right to determine the way things really are', often overlooking the experiences of the lowest group (students).

In the same way, findings reported by Lloyd and Stead (2001) suggested that teachers did not believe Gypsy and Traveller students when they reported incidents of racism, while Bhopal (2011) demonstrated that Gypsy and Traveller students' experiences of racism were not viewed in the same light as other Ethnic minority students, due to their white ethnic identity. The girls

narratives illustrate that systemic, institutional racial inequality is still rife as defined by the MacPherson report (1999, p. 6):

‘The collective failure of an organisation to provide an appropriate and professional service to people because of their colour, culture or ethnic origin. It can be seen or detected in processes, attitudes and behaviour which amount to discrimination through unwitting prejudice, ignorance, thoughtlessness and racist stereotyping which disadvantage minority ethnic people.’

As mentioned previously, a number of research participants across different community groups and geographical locations demonstrated responses of passivity in accepting experiences of racism as a way of life. This was, however, community group dependent as Roma learners’ were more likely to demonstrate passive acceptance than their Romani Gypsy counterparts. The Romani Gypsy cohort in Wales, exhibited acts of resistance in response to experiences of racism by retaliating (Law and Swann, 2011). By way of illustration, Gypsy Tony’s (13) stated, that when he experienced racism along with his Romani Gypsy peers, they gave the perpetrators ‘a smack and they shut up’. Poison Ivy (13), explained the reason for this retaliation,

We do retaliate. But when they do say it to us, they don’t understand that, when we retaliate it’s because it does dig deep. It’s not just like with you say now, I called you a gorjio, it’s just a name, but for us, it’s who we are. We can’t change that. I think with Travellers and non-Travellers, I think we all need to start getting along because for the future - if we do leave the EU, it’s gonna get worse and its gonna get tougher.

Despite being only 13, Poison Ivy’s critical reflection struck me in that she understood the implications of Brexit on race relations within the U.K and the importance of working together to traverse this uncertain landscape. For MC Allen, he was acutely aware that anti-Gypsyism was indeed, one of the last forms of acceptable racism (Balogh and Clark, 2018), as revealed through his response to dealing with racist bullying,

Just laugh. This is what I think - if someone’s a different colour yeah, and you say whatever the word is yeah, you can get locked up for it, you can get in trouble. When someone is being racist to you or like a Gypsy, they’ll do nothing.

Consistent with the literature, Richardson and Ryder (2012, p. 5), observe that when a racially motivated verbal attack is perpetuated against Roma, Gypsy and Traveller communities, if you

had to replace the word ‘Traveller with any other race or ethnicity [...] there would be outrage’. MC Allen was not alone in his perceptions. Similar observations pertaining to anti-Gypsyism being the last acceptable form of racism was also observed by Scottish teacher Alison as she stated,

This is the last community it’s ok to be racist about. I think it’s pretty negative I am afraid. I think it’s terrible, and there are people who are so politically correct, and they will hit out with something and I think you would never say that about any other group.

Students in Scotland anticipated that the last acceptable form of racism would permeate future employment settings due to their identity (Greenfields, 2008). For example, when I asked London (Roma, 15) if she thought being Roma would stop her from getting jobs, she responded with translation support from Madalin by stating, ‘yes some people are racists, she mentioned English speakers are racist with the Roma, they call us dirty bastards’. After Madalin had listened to students concerns for their respective future worlds of work, he noted that all young people within the Scottish focus groups had experienced racism and that they perceived their identities to be a barrier to future employment opportunities.

Perceptions of racism as a barrier to employment were not only reserved to young people, as the staff supporting them provided accounts that suggested learners’ identities did indeed impede their progression within the labour market. The exchange below with TESS staff member Shareen, demonstrates the difficulties she experienced when attempting to support students into employment in Wales,

Shareen: Trying to get them jobs because, as soon as they put [...], where they live, they don’t get a job because people know that’s the Gypsy site.

Nicola: So is putting their address on their CV a barrier?

Shareen: Yeah there’s a factory in [...], a biscuit factory, and two of ours applied and they were told there weren't any jobs going. And my daughter was about to go to uni and thought she’d see if she could get into the factory for the summer, and she got a job straight away. And I mean she was only going for a few weeks, where they would have gone forever.

The current findings indicate that while school personnel may facilitate students’ critical consciousness development in order to help them challenge intersectional barriers related to their identity, structural barriers persist, as evidenced through an employer’s decision to hire

being influenced by the applicants address. In support of the current findings, ground-breaking research on labour market discrimination by Bertrand and Mullainathan (2003), revealed that an African sounding name or a physical address associated with deprivation on a CV significantly decreased an applicant's chances of securing an interview. Similarly, Greenfield's (2008) research demonstrated that her research participants anticipated problems in obtaining employment and training if they could not place a permanent address on their CV. While research conducted by Casey (2014) demonstrated that Gypsy Traveller women lied about their site address on employment applications in order to gain employment.

Racism perpetuated by employers reared its head again within the Scottish context. Terrence, a Career Adviser in Scotland, detailed the racism experienced by students he had been supporting on the Modern Apprenticeships programme (Scottish Government, 2014). He noted, that a number of young people experienced racism perpetuated by employers engaging with the programme and that in one particular incident the 'provider was extremely nasty'. He also observed that, 'indigenous, white groups receive more support from employers than Roma groups'. As the interview progressed, Terrence pointed to the tendency for employers to put Roma apprentices into the lowest paid positions (Beremenyi, 2020) and then 'dispose of them when they no longer need them'. Terrence acknowledged that the implications of these racist experiences is that 'young people reach a breaking point, tell their community and they shut down' thereby making future engagement difficult.

Language Barriers: Scotland

The preceding sections have demonstrated the multiple and interlocking barriers that serve to marginalise Roma, Gypsy and Traveller students – 'race', ethnicity, gender, and class. In what follows, I highlight the social processes and structures that intersect with these social identities that further place Roma young people in particular on the margins and perpetuate systemic inequalities. These systemic inequalities have longer term implications on students' entry into the labour market and their social mobility. Research suggests that migrants' English proficiency and fluency within a host country is strongly correlated to their chances of obtaining and retaining employment and increased earning potential (Dustmann and Fabbri, 2003; Syed and Murray, 2009; Clark, 2018). This section also contributes to the paucity of knowledge related to the importance of language within an intersectional analysis in understanding barriers to employment.

The barriers that young people faced were not homogenous (Hancock, 2007) and experiences varied by geographical context. The Roma students I interviewed in England and Wales did not present with the same language barriers that the young people in Scotland did. It is thought that this difference was due to the support that they received within their respective educational institutions. The lack of language support in the Scottish context serves as a barrier to equity of educational access and leads to decreased engagement in school. The findings suggest that this decreased engagement has negative implications for students' careers aspirations and occupational outcomes (Creed et al., 2007). It is important to note, however, that not all young Roma people in England and Wales have access to adequate language acquisition support. By way of illustration, Ana (Roma, 14, England) felt that she did not receive adequate support to learn English in her primary school, but that changed when she started attending school C in England.

Young Roma people in Scotland were not receiving the same level of support that Ana had found. I argue that current policy and practice is preventing the resources necessary within school D, to support students to access the curriculum and career services. Neoliberal policies, localism, structural and institutional discrimination, socio-economic status and ethnicity intersected to prevent these students from accessing the curriculum and career guidance (Kisby, 2010; Ryder and Cemlyn, 2016).

Mainstreaming approaches implemented under austerity, were evident within Fife and Glasgow, both of which are home to large Roma communities (Fremlova, 2009; Hay et al., 2020). Policy and practice in Glasgow changed in 2011 when Maureen McKenna, the then Executive Director of Glasgow City Council's Education Department, published a report to the Children and Families Policy Development Committee (2011). The report suggests that the best way for students to acquire English as a language is for them to have 'role model' peers, who have recently acquired the language. The report subsequently resulted in the closure of the bilingual support unit in the local area that served schools and instead moved to mainstreaming support through 'peer education' in individual schools. As revealed through the individual interview with Charlotte (teacher, school D), provision remains largely the same in Glasgow since the publication of the Children and Families Policy Development Committee (2011) report. She explained,

The model we used to have in Glasgow, was the language support unit. Newly arrived pupils across the city would spend some time there, develop their language across the

curriculum, and then they would be sent back to their own school, where an EAL teacher would work with them there. But that was closed down.

Overall, current policy and practice in Glasgow reflects a ‘one size fits all’ policy approach and a lack of targeted services for those communities facing multiple deprivations. Kisby (2010) argues that localism disguises the reality of cutbacks and reflects neoliberal ideals that are at odds with the principles of the EU Roma Inclusion Framework (Ryder and Cemlyn, 2016). It is thought that Roma communities will further shoulder the burden associated with the outcome of the EU Referendum (Clark, 2018) and the ‘potential loss of EU funding for integration and support services’ (Morris, 2016, p. 28).

This analysis has revealed that bilingual support was offered to young Roma people in schools in two local authority areas in Scotland for a limited amount of hours sporadically each week. The support was delivered by a Roma home link worker in Glasgow and a Romanian speaking volunteer in Fife. The implication of the lack of sustained language support within schools is that students are unable to access the curriculum.

As mentioned previously, young people in school D, only had access to language acquisition support for three hours on a Friday morning – and only if Madilyn (translator, school D) was not busy supporting parents with filling in forms. Charlotte explained the impact that local authority policies were having on Roma students in the lengthy excerpt below,

So our policy of inclusion that Glasgow City Council supports is for newly arrived pupils with no English language, and in a lot of cases no literacy - was for them to go and be in their local school. But in actual fact the case here, is that we have a number of kids that are geographically included as much as they are in a classroom. But they are unable to access and learn because they can’t access through reading, writing their own first language. They can’t access what’s happening in the classroom, so to my mind that is not effective inclusion at all

As can be seen through the excerpt above, the implication of current policy and funding cuts, is that students are unable to learn due to a lack of language acquisition support within their school. Lyons and Little (2009) and Asenova et al. (2015), argue that such funding cuts place significant pressure on schools and teachers and impact heavily on provision. Charlotte’s narrative illuminates the negative impact that current policy and austerity measures post-2008 onwards are having on students’ ability to access the curriculum.

These exclusionary practices within the education field could potentially prevent learners' from gaining qualifications, which will severely constrain their educational and career options (Hodkinson and Sparkes, 1997). English language proficiency also fosters and facilitates social interaction and networking which will be necessary within further and higher education settings as well as future workplaces (Syed and Murray, 2009). Inequitable access to the curriculum will therefore have significantly negative implications for students' career progression. According to Farris and de Jong (2014, p. 1508), these practices may be characterised as 'institutional intersectional discrimination' in that they 'produce discriminatory treatment' that is 'nurtured by structural discrimination' in the form of policies that are enacted by institutions that affect learners'.

Language barriers were also brought up by Alison (teacher, school D), where she raised concerns related to difficulties associated with engagement by stating:

A lot of it all comes back to the language barrier. We've got real issues with, how do you properly engage when discussion is so difficult?

When I asked Alison what resources she used to support her work with young Roma people, I was shocked by her response. I had expected Alison to cite literature or training that she had received, instead, she stated that students were utilised as a resource. She explained,

In the first instance, we know the pupils in the school who speak the relevant languages. So if there was an emergency, you could take one of the pupils. One of the older kids could translate. We can use google translate with the speaker. It's not perfect. The pupils are very good at helping each other and as I say we have kids who help. For more official things, we have Madilyn who can come in.

In line with Glasgow City Council's (2011) 'policy of inclusion', Alison's words suggest that young people were being utilised as unpaid resources to support teachers in carrying out their duties. Appropriate additional resources and further support should be available to all students within Scottish educational settings whose first language is not English, on a daily basis throughout the school term – good practice that this research identified within the Welsh and English contexts. When the focus of the interview turned to students accessing SDS career services, or apprenticeship schemes, Alison was not aware of any language support for learners:

There's foundation apprenticeships. So I don't know if there is any specific arrangements for EAL pupils, but there's people whose sole remit is to take that forward.

When I followed up with the Carina (Career Adviser, school D) regarding EAL support, I was disappointed to learn that similar to the inequitable education provision identified within school settings, there was inequitable career guidance for learners who were new to English as SDS did not have translation support. Carina explained,

Well, we should. But, we can't because a lot of them don't come to school or if they do, they can't speak English. We don't have our own translators, there's very few organisations we can refer them to.

In response to Carina, I suggested that the issue may be a structural one. I explained the lack of language support that I had witnessed in the school was rendering students unable to access the curriculum. I also suggested that this may be a reason for their perceived disengagement. In response, however, Carina pathologised Roma students' culture as she stated,

Yeah I totally agree, but I also think it's a cultural thing because there is lots of other types of ethnicities that come into [...] that can't speak English. But they still come every day, they have to from their parents side of things but with the Roma community - it's to do with their family background. I don't think they have the support of their parents to go to school. A lot of them will get pregnant at such a young age, but that's expected.

Farris and de Jong (2014, p. 1508) describe discursive intersectional discrimination, as discrimination that serves to '(re)produce images of inferiority'. Carina uses a script regarding language and cultural difference to abdicate responsibility for providing these students with career guidance. Consequently these scripts or master narratives play a significant role in Roma students' exclusion from educational settings. Carina's words place the students inability to speak English at the feet of their family background, failing to consider the literacy barriers and additional language support that students need to access education and the careers service. As Alison explains,

So a lot of them are first level English, but the problem is they can't read or write in their own language. So if we are trying to do things like google translate, they wouldn't necessarily be able to read it.

Sarah, (Career Adviser, Scotland) suggested the difficulty in presenting apprenticeship opportunities to parents as she explained,

It was also hard to get across to parents who couldn't speak English, what modern apprenticeships are.

The need for additional language support was not only identified within Glasgow, but also in Fife - home to over '2000 Portuguese and Romanian Roma families' according to focus group stakeholders, which brings into question current Scottish Government population estimates for Roma communities living in Scotland (Hay et al., 2020). Despite these large numbers, evidence suggested that provision in Fife was limited and provided by a Romanian volunteer Michelle, as she explained,

What I am doing also, is I am translating for them, so they can learn more easy. And we have some special small books, where we have Romanian, English, Portuguese. So they work in all languages.

Unlike Carina, Michelle was more reflective of literacy issues amongst community members. She noted that while she often sends parents text messages and letters in Romanian, she problematized the approach by stating, 'some of them won't know how to read so it's very difficult'. Within the focus group, Clinton a Career Adviser who worked for SDS, also problematized the organisation's approach to supporting Roma communities as he stated 'we are very much a leaflet driven organisation so if they can't read, they are stuck if they are not literate', therefore raising further concerns regarding how young people access career provision if they are new to English.

The focus group in Fife revealed that additional support was required within schools. Vicky (local authority education department official) whose remit was to work with pupils who have English as an additional language stated,

What we are finding from feedback from schools, is our Roma learners, what schools are asking for support with, and it is about how we meet the need. And our support for different communities, and different cultures is different. And we have realised, we need to think of something new to support our Roma learners.

In order to address these barriers to support Vicky advised that the council was trialling a phone application developed by the Scottish Traveller Education Programme (STEP) to support Roma students and their parents. She explained,

One of the things we are trialling so Fife, is to do a link, I guess it would be for use on smart phones - which is sort of key information about the school voiced by a Roma pupil. So we are tackling the literacy issue that way, for just sharing information: when the school day is, how you get free school meals, that sort of thing. Because lots of things, like in-service days or dress up days get completely lost. So we are trying to do it that way, but we don't know if it will be successful yet.

A recent study conducted by STEP (2016) entitled 'Mobile Children, Young People and Technology Project', explored students use of technology, the researchers recruited 19 young people in primary schools who identified as Slovakian Roma in Glasgow and Gypsy/Traveller in Edinburgh, the Highlands and Ayrshire. The authors explicitly acknowledged within their research design that the methodologies employed 'reflected anticipated low written literacy and communication levels and placed emphasis on oral and visual forms of participation and expression' (STEP, 2016, p. 15).

While all 19 young people in their sample utilised digital technology, the authors noted, that there may be variability in access to the internet. However, the lack of data related to digital poverty and digital literacy rates raise concerns. Moreover, while the application may support information sharing practices, the solution largely overlooks more pressing accessibility and language support needs within the classroom. For example, in considerations of addressing interrupted learning, Vicky stated that, '100 percent attendance was an unrealistic target' for Roma students, and that their previous model was not working as EAL support would be provided on Thursday mornings but young people wouldn't attend. For young people to attend, however, language support would need to be available daily. Considering these findings, it may be questionable that Roma students are being supported effectively within secondary school education settings in Scotland.

Disparities between Policy and Practice within the Scottish context

Ager and Strang's (2008) work entitled 'Understanding integration: A conceptual framework' demonstrated elements that were pivotal to successful integration based on research with Refugees and migrants in Islington and Glasgow. Their report serves as a benchmark for current Refugee and migration policy across the U.K. The authors argue that successful integration depends on provision that allows new migrants to foster language skills. Moreover, in support of the current findings within the Scottish context, Ager and Strang found

insufficient language support to negatively impact Refugee students' education and integration. The authors also observed that where specialised language units were available to young people, their needs were met.

The Home Office report 'Indicators of Integration' (2004) employed Ager and Strang's (2008) framework wherein integration was divided into 10 distinct but interrelated domains against which progress could be measured. Similarly, Ager and Strang's (2008) report also serves as a benchmark for the Scottish Government's 'New Scots' policies (2013, 2018). Following devolution, the protection of borders, immigration and asylum remain reserved matters, while education, interpreting and translation are areas of social policy that are devolved to the Scottish Government.

The New Scot's 2018-2022 (2018) policy suggests that English language proficiency is linked to Refugee and migrant communities' ability to gain employment and pursue education. Across Europe, the language gap is cited as the most influential factor in accounting for young migrants' poor achievements (Andriessen and Phalet, 2002). Similarly, the data presented here suggests that the lack of adequate support for young people in Scottish schools is further entrenching the language gap and negatively influencing students' attainment. Cemlyn and colleagues (2009, p. 101) affirm that there are 'contradictions in public policy' wherein there is 'an emphasis on equality and inclusion alongside market-oriented reforms' that serve to exclude. Overall, current provision identified in Scotland fails to measure up to policy benchmarks for successful integration (Ager and Strang, 2008).

Turning to SDS' (2012, 2019b) 'Career Management Skills' (CMS) Framework, it is worrying that none of the Career Advisers who participated in this research questioned the lack of language acquisition support available to learners' despite the emphasis that current policy places on networking. The CMS Framework identifies four pillars: 'self', 'strengths', 'horizons' and 'networks' (Skills Development Scotland, 2012). The subsection 'networks', states that it is key for individuals to 'Know how to manage relationships, use information and [their] range of networks to support [their] career journey'.

The framework also states that SDS will help deliver the support and development of CMS to 'all of Scotland's people', so that they can 'interact confidently and effectively with others to build relationships; 'use information and relationships to secure, create and maintain work'; and to 'develop and maintain a range of relationships that are important for [their] career journey' (Skills Development Scotland, 2012, p. 4). This analysis suggests that current policy

and practice is too generic, based on a ‘one size fits all’ approach that fails to question how individuals are meant to ‘network’ if they do not have the English proficiency skills necessary to socially interact.

Collectively, these findings raise grave concerns as a number of authors have illuminated the role that English language proficiency plays in successfully navigating education systems and the labour market (see for e.g. Asenova et al., 2015; Darmody et al., 2014; Lyons and Little, 2009; Phillipson, 1992; Syed and Murray 2009; Tietze, 2004). The lack of English proficiency is one of the most commonly cited barriers to accessing quality education (Darmody et al., 2014), the labour market and increasing social mobility for migrants (Syed, 2008). To this end, equitable access to English language support for Roma students is vital as it will not only shape their educational career but their life trajectories.

Language Support in England and Wales: ‘When I came to this school and I found so much help and joy, I learned English better’

As the preceding section demonstrated, educational institutions that did not permit equitable access to language acquisition support, negatively impacted on students ability to engage with both the curriculum and career guidance services. The following section outlines and analyses best practice as identified in England and Wales and the positive impact that access to language acquisition support was having on students. School’s A and C both provided students’ access to specialist language units within their respective schools. The provision identified in these schools paralleled the provision identified by Ager and Strang (2008) that positively impacted on young people’s engagement and retention and was considered a benchmark for successful integration. However, contrary to the authors findings, that suggested that specialist language units ‘limited opportunities for mixing with local children’ (Ager and Strang, 2008. p. 172), the specialist language units within the current research promoted integration as students could communicate with their diverse peers and teachers.

Young people in both Wales and England often recalled the struggles they initially experienced when attempting to learn English when they first arrived in the U.K. As mentioned previously, Ana had failed to acquire support within primary school settings but she managed to increase her English proficiency rapidly upon attending her current secondary school due to the support mechanisms in place. She recalled, ‘when I came to this school and I found so much help and joy I learned English better’. Sonja (Roma girl, 16, Wales) stated that ‘it was hard the first time,

cause you don't really know the language but now its ok'. Similarly, Kooper (Roma boy, 16, Wales) expressed that 'we struggled at the start and then we got used to it'. Sonja, Kooper, and Ana were able to acquire English as an additional language due to the mechanisms of support available to them within their respective educational institutions.

School C's language support provision involved a week-long induction course; bespoke teaching and in class support; a 'trained Buddy' system; and homework support for students who were new to English. Following induction, young people entered into mainstream classes with the exception of English classes. In lieu of entering into mainstream English classes, students instead received six hours of specialised language support from the EAL department with the staff team consisting of individuals who spoke multiple languages. Emanuel explained, that once 'they reach a certain level, they move into mainstream English lessons [and that] there is an EAL class for each year group'. Students and parents also had access to Emanuel who spoke Romanian and was able to offer both pastoral and translation support on a full-time basis. Finally, school C's website offered translation support with three language options for students and parents - Romanian, Italian and Polish.

School A offered similar provision to the offer in school C, with students being able to access dedicated language units to support their educational careers. School C's approach was largely successful with the majority of students progressing through two phases of language acquisition support before entering mainstream classes. Mrs H explained,

So these children are in mainstream classes, so they are taught with everyone else. Same curriculum for everyone. So 80 children in mainstream classes out of the 91, so at that point we only had 11 children in language acquisition classes post sixteen...so they went from group one to group two, into mainstream.

Of the 91 young Roma people attending school A, 80 had progressed through two stages of language acquisition classes into mainstream classes, therein demonstrating the level of specialised support. In order to further facilitate students' language development, Mrs H felt that it was important to identify topics that were interesting to young people. She acknowledged the difficulties associated with breaking the language down for students to understand and emphasised the need to 'scaffold sentence building'³⁴ with the use of sentence starter examples.

³⁴ It is thought that Mrs H is drawing on the Vygotskian metaphor of 'scaffolding' here, which holds that 'what children can do with the assistance of others' demonstrates the development of capabilities that cannot be explained when focusing on what a child can do alone (Vygotsky, 1978, p. 85).

Mrs H felt that learners' language acquisition success was dependant on a supportive approach. She stated,

Show them an example of good work, and then they will be able to do the work - but they need lots of support with it. So this GCSE is not designed for children with EAL, it's designed for everyone. So it doesn't differentiate in language, but they have to finish sentences like 'I am happy when'; 'my favourite places'; 'I am good at'. So you can see the language is not perfect always, and the student who's this is (points to course work), she came from a special school. So when she arrived I asked her, she said, 'copy miss, copy', and I say, 'no we don't copy'. She used to just copy all day from book and I said that's not learning. We discuss things and now she is happy to talk to get involved.

According to Lloyd and McCluskey (2008) and the ERRC (2017), Roma, Gypsy and Traveller young people are more likely than any other group to be placed in Additional Support for Learning schools or classes. Mrs H's words reveal that the student she was supporting had come from an ASL school where she had largely been left to copy material. Mrs H challenged this practice and instead encouraged discussion and engagement that actively promoted inclusion. The young person's experiences prior to her involvement with Mrs H, are characteristic of a narrative teacher-student relationship where the teacher leads the student to mechanistically memorise the narrated content (Freire, 1993). Mrs H on the other hand, employs what Freire (1993) would describe as a humanising pedagogy, by establishing a relationship of dialogue and moving beyond instruction in order to co-construct knowledge.

These findings suggest that equitable access to language acquisition support broadens students' horizons for action (Hodkinson and Sparkes, 1997). The provision available with school's A and C has the potential to support students to complete secondary school and attain qualifications which will determine their future career patterns (Lindblad and Lindahl, 2020). English language proficiency will increase their social capital and facilitate social interactions and the networking necessary to successfully manage their careers (Syed and Murray, 2009).

Discussion

This chapter opened by critically analysing intersectional barriers related to poverty and class that disadvantage young Roma, Gypsy and Traveller people. Student and staff narratives collectively suggest that the extent to which learners can influence their own career trajectories was significantly affected by their position within the education and employment field and their

access to economic, cultural and social capital (Hodkinson, 2008). Consistent with Hodkinson and Sparkes (1997, p. 31) notion of 'economic rationalism', student narratives reflect an externalised calculation of the imminent costs of remaining in secondary school or attending further and higher education versus the benefits and the 'net utility' of receiving an education.

Faced with the often conflicted options of continued deprivation or being able to contribute to their familial households impacted on students' decision-making (Mulcahy et al., 2017) thereby problematizing the assumption within Career Management Skills (CMS) frameworks (Skills Development Scotland, 2012, 2019; Careers Wales 2017; Scottish Government, 2020) that suggests that students can act freely and achieve social mobility (Simon et al., 1991; Sultana, 2012). Current policy therefore fails to consider structural patterns of inequality that need structural solutions.

The analysis also demonstrated that for those students who have managed to overcome their intersectional barriers and enrol in university, the effects of poverty and class persist. Findings suggest that students from non-traditional backgrounds experience higher education as an alienating and marginalising experience (Ball et al., 2002a; Redmond, 2006) increasing the need to familiarise learners with institutionalised cultural capital (James, 2000; Naidoo, 2004).

These findings also highlight the utility in blending careership theory with an intersectional framework. The focus on class and poverty within careership theory addresses the gaps within the Romani studies intersectional literature. As Kóczé (2009) observes, intersectional policy and research often focus on combatting racism and sexism, but do not integrate solutions to problems of social exclusion related to poverty, which intersect with 'race', ethnicity and gender. Indeed, intersectional research by Marcus (2016a) failed to consider the impact of poverty and class on Scottish Traveller girls educational experiences, which is an oversight as Kóczé (2009) asserts that it will intensify the level of discrimination experienced Roma, Gypsy and Traveller people.

As Croll (2008, p. 255) contends, young people with high aspirations and disadvantaged backgrounds are 'less likely to be educationally equipped to realise their ambitions'. The findings presented here, indicate that an intersectional approach needs to be embedded within policy and practice in order to address the multiple and interlocking barriers that students face. Moreover, teaching staff and Career Advisers need to be more aware of how racism, sexism and classism intersect to create an uneven playing field for students, and the need to design

specific interventions to address these intersectional barriers that young people are grappling with and actively work to remove these barriers.

The second part of this chapter examined the theme of gender and the impact of gender role socialisation on education and career options. The majority of girls and boys who participated in this research had parents who supported their career aspirations. Contrary to previous findings (see for e.g. Marcus, 2016a; Hamilton, 2017), this thesis demonstrates a shift in gendered cultural norms amongst the girls who did not express domestic aspirations for their own futures.

Nuanced considerations are needed relating to the experiences of various community groups' across the three home nations. Romani Gypsy girls appeared to experience heteropatriarchal attitudes from the wider community living on-site (particularly from men and boys). The girls' narratives revealed that marriage and careers were seen as mutually exclusive by their wider community, reflective of 'gender-typified socialisation' (Kóczé, 2009, p. 24). The girls also suggested that they could pursue a career, but only if it were not of a higher status to their future husband's career. Despite wider cultural expectations, the Romani Gypsy girls who participated in this research demonstrated critical reflection of and resistance against the patriarchal discourses imposed on them, thereby suggesting that culture is neither static nor impervious to wider societal change.

For the Roma girls living in Scotland, their intended professional directions may be characterised as feminine and 'safe options' (Marcus, 2016), with participants often reporting that they will 'do girl jobs'. It is thought that the aspirations expressed by the girls in Scotland are a result of limited exposure to career exploration opportunities within their institutional habitus and the girls therefore gravitate toward what is 'familiar and known' (Hodkinson and Sparkes, 1997).

In contrast, the data indicated that Roma girls in England are increasingly seeking career guidance in fields where women are traditionally under-represented such as engineering, construction and architecture. It is thought that the aspirations expressed are due to the range of work placement and open day opportunities available within their education field. Institutional habitus, along with their new geographical habitus has broadened what they see as possible (Hodkinson, 2008). This analysis indicates that there are a number of girls who are not only expressing aspirations toward 'gender atypical' occupational fields, but they are entering further education in order to achieve these aspirations.

The Romani Gypsy boys who participated in this research appeared to have internalised heteropatriarchal attitudes related to the division of labour. The boys did not question the demarcated gendered divisions of labour within the family structure and such patterns of practice appeared to be ‘common-sense’ having become somewhat ‘naturalised’ (Bourdieu, 1984, 2001). As many of the Romani Gypsy boys in this study aspired to self-employment, guidance sessions could utilise images that challenge common gendered stereotypes and provide work placement opportunities for them with self-employed female role models in industries where women are generally under-represented (Bimrose, 2008).

Overall, discussions with stakeholders, Roma and Romani Gypsy boys revealed that they had fewer opportunities to engage in dialogue or education interventions that would support them to confront gender inequality and reflect on their own potential participation in it (Diemer et al., 2006). As evidenced in Wales, Roma boys are increasingly raising concerns and challenging traditional models of gender, but that they were waiting longer than the girls to raise issues. It is vital that students across genders have opportunities to engage in such dialogue so that they may raise their concerns and garner support in a safe place.

The students' responses indicate that their choices are bounded along gendered and racialized lines, which may limit their educational and career options (Hodkinson and Sparkes, 1997). The findings also suggest the role that the institutional habitus plays in supporting students to challenge gendered norms that may serve to constrain educational and career options. The development of critical consciousness is facilitated through dialogue (Freire, 1993; Diemer et al., 2006) with trusted others and a range of experiences available to learners within educational settings. Work placement and open day opportunities at further and higher education providers may be influencing student decision-making. The findings presented here also help address my research questions and demonstrate the intersections of ‘race’ with gender (Solórzano and Yosso, 2002; Hill Collins and Bilge, 2016).

The third part of this chapter explored the virulent racism students experienced due to their ‘race’ and ethnicity. Consistent with the literature, the most commonly cited theme that emerged from learners narratives across the three home nations was their experiences of racism and discrimination in both educational and community settings (Bhopal, 2004, 2011; Cemlyn, et al. 2009; Deuchar and Bhopal, 2013; D’Arcy, 2017). These experiences of racism were as ‘ordinary’ (Delgado and Stefancic, 2017, p. 8) as ‘having a cup of tea and coffee’ (Shera, Scotland). The majority of Roma and Scottish Traveller participants often passively accepted

this oppression, as though they had no other choice (hooks, 2015), whereas the Romani Gypsy students were more likely to retaliate to acts of racism perpetuated against them (Lloyd et al., 1999; Derrington and Kendall, 2004; Law and Swann, 2011).

What emerges through the analysis is that students are negatively affected and disadvantaged because of their 'race' and ethnicity. Contrary to findings amongst gadjé Ethnic minority populations by Hodkinson and Bloomer (2000) and Smith (2007) suggesting that experiences of racism did not constrain learners' horizons for action, experiences of racism and discrimination limited the educational and career opportunities available to students within the current study. This analysis indicates that experiences of racist bullying may serve as a turning point that pushes young people to disengage from education. The implications of dropping out of secondary school are thought to result in exclusion from further and higher education (Clark, 2004), the labour market in adulthood (Kóczé, 2009) as well as having a lower economic status (Drydakis, 2012), and fewer opportunities overall (Geraghty, Erbstein, and Greenfield, 2010).

Stakeholder narratives mirrored student accounts detailing the pervasive racism perpetrated against young people. TESS staff in Wales recalled that learners' identities did impede their progression within the labour market as they were denied employment opportunities if their site address was used on employment applications (Greenfields, 2008; Bertrand and Mullainathan, 2003; Casey, 2014). While discussions in Scotland revealed the structural racism young people experience on Modern Apprenticeship programmes wherein they are pushed into the lowest positions and 'disposed of' when they are no longer needed. The resultant consequence is that young people share their experiences of racism with the wider community which then prevents future engagements due to fears of racism.

While intersectionality is vital to understand the multiplicities of identity and how they intersect (Crenshaw, 1991; Hill Collins and Bilge, 2019), the accounts presented here demonstrate the primacy of racism within and across community groups' experiences (Bhopal, 2020). My analysis also supports the use of critical race theory as a theoretical lens to demonstrate both the personal experiences of students as well as the structural and hegemonic mechanisms that operate within institutions that impede students' development. Student experiences within school, modern apprenticeship programmes, further and higher education and the labour market indicate that their life chances are heavily influenced by exclusionary and discriminatory practices perpetuated by others within their field due to their 'race' and ethnicity.

The fourth part of this chapter offers a critical analysis of the intersectional barriers related to migration and English language fluency that serve to disadvantage students who are new to English. The analysis illuminates that the agency demonstrated by students is not completely open and free but instead bound by unequal and intersectional forces within the field that constrain their educational and career options (Hodkinson and Sparkes, 1997). The findings in Scotland suggest that learners' do not have equitable access to language acquisition support and are at increased risk for adverse educational and employment outcomes (Lyons and Little, 2009). Conversely, the specialist language units within school A in Wales and school C in England appeared to facilitate students' language development and qualification attainment potential which will broaden their career trajectories (Darmody et al., 2014; Syed and Murray, 2009).

An implication inherent within these findings is that Scottish education policy needs to include language provision for students who are new to English. Good practice as identified in exemplar models in Wales and England suggests that specialist language units in school's A and C are positively impacting on students' engagement and retention in education. The creation of such specialist language units in Scotland will support the educational integration of young people who are new to English and allow them to access the curriculum. Similarly, SDS' provision needs to include translation support services in order to effectively and appropriately engage with EAL students. Moreover, promotional leaflets need to be disseminated in multiple languages and be supplemented with community outreach supported by translation services in order to ensure that those furthest from the labour market may access vital services. This provision will also enable SDS to meet the foundational pillars of the CMS framework (Skills Development Scotland, 2012).

Finally, my analysis supports the use of an intersectional framework which yields great utility in allowing researchers, educators and career guidance practitioners to think holistically about how learners' multiple identities impact on their career decision-making and social mobility. Findings demonstrate 'race', ethnicity, gender, class and English language proficiency combine to structure and limit opportunities for students (Archer et al., 2014b). Interventions that deal solely with one axes of inequality without considering the matrix of marginalisation and structural inequality that young people endure, will have limited success in reducing disparities and promoting social mobility.

Chapter Eight

Concluding Discussion

In this doctoral research, I have examined and ‘represented’ (Spivak, 1988) the narratives of 36 Roma, Romani Gypsy, Scottish Traveller, Irish Traveller and Showmen young people across England, Scotland and Wales in order to address the following research questions:

1. What are young Roma, Gypsy and Traveller people’s aspirations and what support do they feel they need in order to realise their aspirations?
2. Do young Roma, Gypsy and Traveller people have equitable access to career education and guidance provision. If they do, what have their experiences been? If they have not had access, do they think believe that they would benefit from career guidance, and how do they think local services could best meet their needs?

Student voices from these heterogeneous community groups are often absent from the scholarly literature and policy documents cross-nationally. This chapter reflects on and distils the implications of the key findings of my work in order to make recommendations for school-based career guidance practice and inform future research. I have demonstrated and evidenced these students’ broad and high reaching aspirations, their experiences of education and career guidance and the intersectional barriers within their respective fields that serve to constrain their life choices and chances. Findings revealed that students do not suffer from a ‘poverty of aspiration’, but instead face a ‘poverty of opportunity’ (Roberts and Atherton, 2001).

The data illuminates the subordination and exclusion many young Roma, Gypsy and Traveller people face due to their ‘race’, ethnicity, gender and English proficiency. This study further illustrates discriminatory practices embedded within institutional structures that impede Roma, Gypsy and Traveller learners’ horizons for action (Hodkinson and Sparkes, 1997). Due to the rapidly changing nature of the world of work, the impact of Brexit (McCrorry and Thomsen, 2019; Clark, 2020) and COVID 19 (Blustein et al., 2020) on the labour market and the pervasive structural barriers that Roma, Gypsy and Traveller people face, equitable access to career related learning for these communities has never been more vital.

The Aspirations expressed by Roma, Gypsy and Traveller Community members'

Findings reveal that the majority of students were positively disposed to education echoing findings by Levinson (2015). Young people often expressed high educational and career aspirations similar to those identified within gadjé populations (OECD, 2020), thereby providing powerful counter-stories that challenge dominant narratives that have historically served to subjugate (Solórzano and Yosso, 2002). As mentioned previously however, the OECD (2020), suggests that the aforementioned occupations are problematic as they are outdated and fail to take into consideration the rapid acceleration of automation, thereby further illustrating the need for the equitable provision of career education and guidance.

Although the majority of students in this study expressed aspirations aligned to recent OECD (2020) findings, their stated aspirations were not homogenous in line with the intersectional framework adopted in this research (Hancock, 2007). A significant number of young people expressed an interest in careers aligned to helping others similar to findings by Milan-Tyner (2018) in her sample of African American women. Consistent with the literature, some of the Romani Gypsy boys in Wales expressed aspirations related to self-employment and entrepreneurship (Clark, 2001; Lloyd and McCluskey, 2008).

In support of the 'careership' theoretical framework (Hodkinson and Sparkes, 1997; Hodkinson 2008) and consistent with findings amongst gadjé populations, young Roma people living in Scotland often expressed aspirations aligned to working class and gendered career trajectories (Raffo and Reaves, 2000; Reay, 2006). It is thought that the observed differences in learners' career decision-making was influenced by what was familiar and known (Hodkinson and Sparkes, 1997) and a poverty of opportunity (Archer et al., 2014; Croll, 2008; Roberts and Atherton, 2011) to engage in career exploration. The participants' stated career preferences therefore illuminate differences between institutional habituses (Reay et al., 2001).

Overall, the data demonstrates multiple instances of young people enacting their agency and making pragmatically rational decisions in order to achieve their goals (Hodkinson and Sparkes, 1997). By way of illustration, students often made active decisions regarding the subject choices that they believed would enable them to achieve their aspirations and their decisions to study closer to home due to the financial costs associated with travel. Moreover, a number of young people also placed an emphasis on the moderation and regulation of their own behaviour and actions as a means to achieve their goals.

Parents in the current study, placed importance on their children's educational attendance and viewed educational attainment as a means of increasing social mobility (Acton, 2004; Myers et al., 2010; D'Arcy, 2017). Both parent and student narratives suggest that parents were largely supportive of their children's education and career aspirations (Greenfields, 2008), contrary to findings by Sime et al. (2018) and Surdu and Surdu (2006). The current research also challenges deficit assumptions about Roma, Gypsy and Traveller men (see for e.g. Hamilton, 2016, 2017; Poole and Adamson, 2008; Sime et al., 2018; Marcus, 2016; Levinson, 2015; D'Arcy, 2017). Similar to findings by Bhopal (2004) regarding the role of fathers, the Roma and Romani Gypsy fathers who participated in this research were not only involved, but deeply invested in their children's education in order to nurture their aspirations. Research participants often worked to support their children's educational and career aspirations through dialogue, homework monitoring, supporting school runs, and providing work placement application guidance.

Factors influencing Students' decision-making and Career progression

Student educational and career decisions were found to reflect the interaction between the following processes: individual habitus; agency; family habitus; and the institutional habitus or 'school affect' in shaping learners horizons for action, consistent with the wider literature amongst gadjé populations (Smyth and Banks, 2012; Lanskey, 2015). Learner narratives indicate agency in that they draw on parents, siblings, extended family, teachers, teaching staff and Career Advisers for both educational and career guidance, contrary to findings by Marcus (2016a).

Who young people approach for guidance was based on two factors: trusted individuals that students felt comfortable with (the familiar and known); and those who the student believed were best placed to provide the advice in line with learners' stated aspirations (expertise and knowledge based) (Hodkinson and Sparkes, 1997). Student and parental accounts indicated that the vast majority of parents were supportive of their children's stated educational and career aspirations, but young people were often constrained by their family habitus (Smyth and Banks, 2012) due to limited economic, educational and cultural capital.

Although their familial networks may provide words of encouragement and support for 'what comes next', parents often lack the cultural capital necessary to provide information on further and higher education. For the overwhelming majority of research participants, they are the first

generation in their families who intend on completing secondary school and attending further and higher education. To this end, knowledge of how to navigate this unfamiliar landscape is often not readily available at home and it is therefore essential that access to such knowledge within educational institutions is equitably disseminated.

Although both familial and institutional habitus play a crucial role in students' decision-making, this research has determined that institutional habitus exerts a greater influence. While parents, siblings and familial networks often play a supportive role in encouraging and nurturing participants dreams, evidence demonstrates that this support may be negatively impacted by experiences within the institutional field, consistent with findings by Smyth and Banks (2012).

Student aspirations and their expectations for the future were established over time and in relation to teachers, teaching staff and Career Advisers. The findings from this study illustrate how 'school affect' or the institutional habitus, not only shaped students' horizons for action but either reinforced or removed the structural barriers within their respective educational fields. Learners across England, Scotland and Wales had differential access to economic, cultural and social capital through their institutional habitus. The institutional habitus of the schools that were successfully supporting students across schools A-C in England and Wales may be characterised by the following features:

- School leadership and culture
- High expectations from teachers, Career Advisers and school personnel
- Strong links with communities of interaction (further and higher education institutions; local employers; NGO's and parents)
- Flexible curriculum and student-centred orientation
- Strong relationships
- Addressing structural barriers

Echoing findings by Reay et al. (2001) the institutional habitus was also reflected in the quantity and quality of guidance and support available to students. Structural conditions, such as a flexible curriculum, equal access to education and career guidance and opportunities for further and higher education exploration were found to play a role in increasing students' agency and broadening their worldviews (Hodkinson and Sparkes, 1997). Significantly, it was the concerted and sustained efforts by teaching staff and Career Advisers who fostered and

encouraged students' engagement in a programme of both educational and career related activity.

Collectively teachers, teaching staff and Career Advisers played a pivotal role in guiding and shaping student perceptions (Foskett et al., 2008). They served as guides, supporting young people with a range of educational and career guidance activities, informing them of and providing experiences of local further and higher education provision and employer engagement opportunities and normalising that Roma, Gypsy and Traveller identities are not incompatible with educational aspirations (Smyth and Bank, 2012). Importantly, these staff members often went beyond the role specification of what their job description entailed, working in a pan-sectoral manner, long after the school day had ended. There was consensus amongst a number of institutional stakeholders that suggested that most students would walk through doors of opportunity – but that these doors had to be opened by those with the power to do so.

Across the English and Welsh geo-political contexts, the majority of students recalled in-school support from teachers, teaching staff and Career Advisers for accessing guidance, opportunities to explore their educational and career aspirations, lessons within the curriculum, discussions regarding employer engagement and work placement opportunities, access to further education and higher education open days and personal face-to-face career guidance interviews. Collectively these strategies form the school habitus and serve to broaden students' further education, higher education and career choices (Hodkinson and Sparkes, 1997; Smyth and Banks 2012). Consistent with the literature, the institutional habitus shaped students' educational and career decision-making, illuminating the opportunities available to them and the perceived accessibility of those opportunities (Foskett et al., 2008; Reay et al., 2005).

These findings were, however, not replicated across all studied geo-political contexts. For students in school D in Scotland, their sense of self and their horizons for action were limited by their educational field, which, at times, imposed a narrow range of options that staff deemed as possible for these young people. There was an over-reliance on majoritarian master narratives by a number of Scottish teaching staff and Career Advisers who drew on community members' 'mistrust' of authority, their culture, and their 'inherently mobile' lifestyle in order to justify their exclusion. Consistent with the literature, the majority of staff from Scotland demonstrated deficit assumptions towards the education of Roma students (see Hamilton,

2016, 2017; Poole and Adamson, 2008; Sime et al., 2018; Marcus, 2016a; Levinson, 2015; D'Arcy, 2017).

The narratives adopted to explain the lack of engagement, ultimately serve as a barrier to young people accessing education and career guidance (Solórzano and Yosso, 2002). While the impact of localised austerity measures over the last decade were cited as a barrier to the effective implementation of mainstreaming efforts in Scotland (Glasgow City Council, 2011; Ryder and Cemlyn, 2014), there were also multiple instances of low expectations from teachers and racist attitudes that were operating to keep young Roma people participating on an uneven playing field. Overall staff narratives often denoted that they expected very little of the students both within educational settings and post-school (McDonough and Calderone, 2006; Smyth and Banks, 2012). It is thought that these expectations reflect staff beliefs about 'race' and ethnicity (George and Aronson, 2002) and ultimately influence the support and guidance that they were willing to offer to learners.

Moreover, there appeared to be a juxtaposition between stereotypical perceptions espoused by some teachers and Career Advisers in school D, and students' consistent calls for further educational and career guidance support within their respective school. Despite young people constructively detailing the education and careers support they felt they would need in order to make successful transitions, some staff within the Scottish context described them and their families as 'problematic truants', thereby adopting a deficit approach towards the education of Roma students and illuminating that education is not neutral (Bourdieu, 1990). These findings therefore illustrate the need for practitioners not to operate from a deficit informed approach that purports these community members to be 'disengaged' or disinterested in education or career guidance.

My findings revealed that students in Scotland demonstrated a distinct lack of knowledge regarding the options available to them both within educational settings and for their further education options. Guidance provision from the perspective of research participants across Scotland highlighted that access to support appears to be largely absent for these young people, with staff narratives often reinforcing that education and careers are not for 'people like them'. The experiences of learners in Scotland are consistent with wider research detailing experiences of exclusion from education (Bhopal and Myers, 2009; Devarakonda, 2013; Warrington, 2007).

The data that emerged from stakeholder and student accounts in Scotland further revealed negative relationships between students and staff akin to findings from Bhopal (2011), Jordan (2001) and Lee and Burkam (2013), which as suggested by Lundahl et al. (2017) may place learners at increased risk for dropping out. Structural oppression and limited access to education and career-related support may therefore be acting as a barrier to limit social mobility (Diemer and Blustein, 2005). Worryingly, there appeared to be an agreement between teaching staff and Career Advisers whereby a child's failure to attend school would result in their status being changed to having 'moved out of Scotland' with staff often refusing to conduct home visits in order to encourage re-engagement. This revelation also raises safeguarding concerns. Basit (1996) emphasises the significant role that home-school liaison may play in encouraging continued educational engagement amongst Ethnic minority community members, with Humphris (2016) arguing that home-visits are often the primary and only contact that Roma communities make with state actors.

Intersectional Barriers

While the majority of young people exhibited a compellingly high degree of agency, intersectional themes emerged to suggest that they were not entirely the architects of their lives that they believed themselves to be. Gender differences, poverty and class, 'race' and ethnicity and English language proficiency intersected with institutional and structural tensions to determine their horizons of action (Hodkinson and Sparkes, 1997; Smith, 2007) as reflected in their stated educational and career aspirations (Hodkinson and Bloomer, 2000; Raffo and Reeves, 2000).

Poverty and class. Student accounts demonstrated the pervasive impact of poverty and class on their decision-making. My research findings demonstrated that the extent to which learners can influence their own career trajectories was constrained by their position within the education and employment field and their access to economic, cultural and social capital (Hodkinson, 2008). Consistent with Hodkinson and Sparkes' (1997, p. 31) notion of 'economic rationalism', student narratives reflect an externalised calculation of the imminent costs of remaining in secondary school or attending further and higher education versus the benefits and the 'net utility' of receiving an education.

Learners were often faced with the limited options of continued deprivation or contributing financially to their familial households (Mulcahy et al., 2017), thereby rendering further and

higher education attendance a distant dream. Students across England and Wales stated that they would go to university if it was free but that finances served as a barrier. The findings also revealed that for those students attending higher education, the effects of poverty and class persist. Students from non-traditional backgrounds experience higher education as an alienating and marginalising experience (Ball et al., 2002a; Redmond, 2006) illuminating the need for educators and Career Advisers to familiarise learners with institutionalised cultural capital (James, 2000; Naidoo, 2004).

Gender. The analysis revealed the need for nuanced considerations relating to the gendered experiences of various community groups involved in this study across the three home nations. None of the girls who participated in this research expressed domestic aspirations for their futures. Romani Gypsy girls in Wales appeared to experience heteropatriarchal attitudes from the wider community living on-site (particularly from men and boys) (Greenfields, 2008). Marriage and careers were seen as mutually exclusive by their wider community, reflective of ‘gender-typified socialisation’ (Kóczé, 2009, p. 24). The girls also revealed that while they could pursue a career, it had to be of a lesser status to their future husband’s career in order to avoid subverting these patriarchal norms. Despite these expectations to conform, the Romani Gypsy girls who participated in this research demonstrated critical reflection of and resistance against the patriarchal discourses imposed on them, thereby suggesting that culture is neither static nor impervious to wider societal change.

For the Roma girls living in Scotland, their intended professional directions may be characterised as feminine and ‘safe options’ (Marcus, 2016), with the girls often reporting that they will ‘do girl jobs’. It is thought that the aspirations expressed by the girls in Scotland are a result of limited exposure to career exploration opportunities within their institutional habitus, and they therefore gravitate toward what is ‘familiar and known’ (Hodkinson and Sparkes, 1997). In contrast, data emerging from England indicated that Roma girls are increasingly seeking career guidance in fields where women are traditionally under-represented such as engineering, construction and architecture. It is thought that the aspirations expressed are due to the range of work placement and open day opportunities available to Roma students within their education field.

Overall, discussions with stakeholders, Roma and Romani Gypsy boys revealed that they had fewer opportunities to engage in dialogue or education interventions that would support them to confront gender inequality and reflect on their own potential participation in it (Diemer et

al., 2006). As evidenced in Wales, Romani Gypsy boys appear to have internalised heteropatriarchal attitudes towards the gendered division of labour. Staff narratives in England appear to indicate that Roma boys are increasingly raising concerns and challenging traditional models of gender, however, they are were waiting longer than Roma girls to raise issues due to a perceived lack of support.

The students' responses indicate that their choices are bounded along gendered and racialized lines, which may limit their educational and career options (Hodkinson and Sparkes, 1997). The findings also illuminate the role that the institutional habitus plays in supporting students to challenge gendered norms that may serve to constrain educational and career options. Therefore, students should have access to opportunities that aim to facilitate the development of critical consciousness through dialogue (Freire, 1993; Diemer et al., 2006) with trusted others in addition to a range of experiences within educational settings in order that young people may question how we do gender.

'Race' and Ethnicity. Consistent with the literature, the most commonly cited theme that emerged from learners narratives across the three home nations involved in this study was participants' experiences of racism and discrimination in both educational and community settings (Bhopal, 2004, 2011; Cemlyn, et al. 2009; Deuchar and Bhopal, 2013; D'Arcy, 2017). These experiences of racism were as 'ordinary' (Delgado and Stefancic, 2017, p. 8) and common everyday occurrences. However, various community groups demonstrated different coping responses. By way of illustration, Roma and Scottish Traveller participants often passively accepted these racist experiences as part of life, whereas the Romani Gypsy students were more likely to retaliate to acts of racism perpetuated against them (Lloyd et al., 1999; Derrington and Kendall, 2004; Law and Swann, 2011).

My research findings reveal that students are negatively affected and disadvantaged because of their 'race' and ethnicity. Contrary to findings by Hodkinson and Bloomer (2000) and Smith (2007) that suggested that experiences of racism did not constrain their gadjé Ethnic minority learners' horizons for action, this thesis has demonstrated that sustained experiences of racism do indeed shape students' worldviews and limit the educational and career opportunities available to them. This analysis indicates that experiences of racist bullying may serve as a turning point that pushes students to disengage from education.

These systemic inequalities have longer term implications on students' entry into the labour market and their social mobility as the majority of students anticipated that the 'last acceptable

form of racism' would permeate future employment settings due to their identity. Indeed, stakeholder narratives in Wales revealed that learners' identities did impede their career progression within the labour market as they were denied employment opportunities when a known Traveller site address was used as the home address on employment applications (Greenfields, 2008; Bertrand and Mullainathan, 2003; Casey, 2014). My research findings also demonstrate the institutional and structural racism young people experience from employers whilst on the Modern Apprenticeship programme run by Skills Development Scotland (SDS). The implications of these racist experiences is that for many young Roma people, they simply reach a breaking point and choose to disengage from future interactions with the careers service. Moreover, these experiences are likely to make future engagement with the wider community more difficult as these experiences are shared through the grapevine.

Language. The utility in adopting an intersectional framework within the current thesis is that it demonstrated that students' experiences are not homogeneous and vary across the home nations. Due to the lack of English language acquisition support in schools, Scottish students faced increased barriers to accessing the curriculum and career guidance services. While young people were included within educational institutions 'geographically' they were excluded from accessing education within those locations. This exclusion is likely to impact on their life trajectories in terms of gaining qualifications and progressing to further and higher education. Moreover, findings suggest that this exclusion leads to decreased engagement and subsequent negative implications for students' career aspirations and occupational outcomes (Creed et al., 2007).

From this perspective, neoliberal policies, localism, structural and institutional discrimination, socio-economic status, English language proficiency and ethnicity intersected to prevent young people from accessing the curriculum and career guidance in Scotland. In contrast to the provision available to young people in Scotland, are the specialist language units within school's A and C in England and Wales that facilitate students' language development and qualification attainment potential with wider implications for their occupational outcomes (Ager and Strang, 2008; Darmody et al., 2014; Syed and Murray, 2009). To this end, equitable access to English language support for Roma students is vital as it will not only shape their educational career but their life trajectories.

Original Contribution to Knowledge

This doctoral research is the first of its kind to explore young Roma, Gypsy and Traveller aspirations and their experiences of career education and guidance cross-nationally and provides a vital contribution to developing knowledge. This thesis challenges deficit assumptions that purport that Roma, Gypsy and Traveller communities are present-oriented (Lawrie, 1983; McCann, 1987; Feder et al., 1989; Jackson et al., 2016), living for the moment and not for the ‘industrial clock’ (Forster, 2018, p. 170). Young people in the current research, through the planning of their next steps in an educational context, demonstrated a future-oriented position centred on gaining employment.

I have also evidenced important correlations between the institutional habitus or ‘school affect’ and students’ aspiration formation and their continued engagement in education. My research has illuminated the intersectional barriers that impede students’ life choices and chances. The findings presented in this thesis also reveal that equitable access to education and career guidance is geo-political and resource dependant, illustrating the need for further work in order to appropriately and effectively support these marginalised students. Accordingly, this research allows for new understandings and it is hoped that these findings will help inform policy and practice across the U.K regarding Roma, Gypsy and Traveller educational and career aspirations and decision-making processes.

Theoretical and methodological contributions to knowledge

Hodkinson and Sparkes (1997), ‘careership’ theory yielded great utility in examining the interface between structure and agency in learners’ education and career decision-making. Building on the work of Hodkinson and Sparkes, in addition to student decision-making being ‘pragmatically rational’, these decisions were based on ‘values’ (McCrary and Thomsen, 2019) with young people often expressing a desire for a career that they derived meaning from (Lips-Wiersma, 2002). Moreover, student narratives also revealed that it was important that their future career had the potential to uplift their family and wider community.

This thesis has also extended the scope of ‘careership’ theory by moving the focus beyond social class. As mentioned previously, careership literature is largely class focused and there is a paucity of research detailing how factors such as gender (Allin and Humberstone, 2006; Fejes and Haake, 2012; Lang, 2012), ‘race’ and ethnicity (Hodkinson and Bloomer, 2000; Smith, 2007) migration (Lindblad and Lundahl, 2020) and language impact on learners’ education

development and career-related decision-making. Nor does careership theory take into consideration the intersecting and compounding effect of 'race', ethnicity, citizenship status, gender, and class. This thesis has therefore addressed calls by Morrison (2012) and Webb et al. (2017) in the need to expand on Bourdieusian theory by incorporating critical 'race' and intersectional frameworks within the structural analysis. This approach allowed for more nuanced understandings of how students experience intersectional barriers on inequality and how these influence their horizons for action.

The use of critical 'race' theory as a theoretical lens has helped illuminate the primacy of 'race' and racism in the lives of young Roma, Gypsy and Traveller people that ultimately influences their worldview and impedes their social mobility (Delgado and Stefancic, 2017; Solórzano and Yosso, 2002). The use of counter-story telling illustrates the high educational and career aspirations that these communities' hold and challenges dominant narratives in the public imaginary regarding what Roma, Gypsy and Traveller people do in relation to education and careers (Clark, 2001; Lloyd and McCluskey, 2008; McGarry, 2014; Marcus, 2016; Peček and Munda, 2015).

Despite the centrality of 'race' and racism in students' lives, this doctoral research addresses calls by Stewart (2010) to move beyond the ethnic lens in Romani studies and confirms that examining students' interlocking intersections of oppression allows for a more complex and dynamic understanding than a focus on 'race' and ethnicity alone. The results of the study show that the agency demonstrated by students is not completely open and free. It is bound by unequal and intersectional forces within the field that serve as barriers to their place in education, the labour market, and their positioning in mainstream society (Syed and Murray 2009). Overall structural conditions, intersectional identities and learner agency determined the range of what participants believed was possible within their field.

In further contributing to original knowledge, this thesis addresses gaps as identified by Kóczé (2011) who called for intersectional approaches within Romani studies to include identity markers related to poverty. To date there has been a dearth of research focusing on the intersectional experiences of Roma, Gypsy and Traveller communities in the U.K (see for e.g. Marcus, 2016). While Marcus (2016a) considers the intersectional barriers facing Scottish Travellers, her focus is primarily on gender and ethnicity and her data did not include an analysis of the compounding and intersecting effects of class and poverty. The current research addresses this gap.

Implications for Policy

My research findings illustrate that Roma, Gypsy and Traveller students experience inequality due to their intersectional social belongings. Consequently, there is a need to acknowledge the implications of their multiple identities in order to address their educational and career guidance needs. Education, Skills and Employment policy must confront the gaps inherent within policy and practice that marginalise and Roma, Gypsy and Traveller communities.

Despite the Equality Act (2010), my research demonstrated that students continued to experience overt and covert racism within both educational and community settings across the three home nations. While intersectional policy is necessary to address the multiple barriers of exclusion young people face, racist bullying remains pervasive and needs to be addressed. Gillborn et al. (2012), however, argues that ‘race’ inequity discussions have ultimately left the policy agenda table. A commitment to challenge and address racism must be prioritised and embedded within all policy and guidance documents in order to improve Roma, Gypsy and Traveller students’ life choices and chances.

Across the home nations, there is a need for various Government administrations to revise their respective Career Management Skills Frameworks (see for e.g. Scottish Government, 2020; Careers Wales, 2017), as they currently fail to take into account structural factors that marginalise young Roma, Gypsy and Traveller people. Accordingly, it is critical then that CMS policy approaches recognise the interplay between structure and agency as an individual’s success within the labour market is dependent on the economic environment and structural solutions are often needed in order to ameliorate multiple and interlocking barriers impacting on marginalised community groups (Simon et al., 1991; Sultana, 2012).

My findings also revealed that there is a need for the various administrations to provide adequate resourcing of education and career guidance services in order to effectively support students. Sufficient and sustained resources are needed in order to fund dedicated teams to support learners and effectively nurture their capacity to aspire (Hart, 2012). Moreover, in support of Bhopal’s (House of Commons, 2018) calls for ring-fenced funding for these communities, this thesis recommends ring-fenced education funding for initiatives such as TESS in order to appropriately support young Roma, Gypsy and Traveller people throughout their educational careers. In regard to the Scottish context, it is recommended that a similar

model to TESS is established in Scotland, as the Scottish Traveller Education Project (STEP) is failing to effectively support teachers.

The intersectional analysis also revealed the implications of poverty on students' decision-making processes. Student narratives illuminated the impact that financial constraints were having on their life choices, particularly regarding attending higher education. These findings suggest that there is scope for the de-marketisation of higher education in England and Wales and the adoption of the Scottish model where access to education is not based on a student's ability to pay (Riddell et al., 2013).

In Scotland, there is a need to include Roma populations in school census data in order to address issues of invisibility, monitor attendance, and identify needs for the effective targeting of resources (Hay et al., 2020). Moreover, this thesis recommends that Scottish education and skills policy needs to include language provision for students who are new to English in the form of a specialist unit as witnessed within school's A and C in England and Wales. The creation of these specialist language units will support the educational integration of young people who have recently arrived in Scotland and allow them to access the curriculum and engage more effectively in education. Similarly, SDS provision needs to include translation support services, leaflets disseminated in multiple languages and community outreach work with language assistance to ensure that those furthest from the labour market may access vital services. This provision will also enable SDS to meet the foundational pillars as outlined in their CMS framework (Skills Development Scotland, 2020).

Finally, my research has also illuminated the longer term implications of intersectional barriers within educational institutions as revealed through the non-linear educational and career journeys of the young adults who participated in this current research. Their experiences illustrate the need for policy makers to increase access to flexible adult education and further post-school opportunity structures are therefore essential so that community members do not become trapped in low-pay jobs or cycles of unemployment.

Implications for Practice

In order to ameliorate the barriers related to poverty affecting Roma, Gypsy and Traveller young people, there is still a vital need for teachers and Career Advisers to provide further support and guidance on: the costs associated with further and higher education; and

information on the financial support available to students. Teachers and Career Advisers should also include pragmatic considerations in discussions with learners regarding how they could potentially contribute financially to their families while engaging further and higher education, consistent with the literature amongst working-class, gadjé research participants (McDonough and Calderone, 2006).

Moreover, when sign-posting and presenting further and higher education options to students, teachers and Career Advisers must acknowledge students' stated preferences for physical proximity out of economic necessity and familial obligations (Beremenyi, 2020; Pérez and McDonough, 2008; Reay et al., 2001; Smith, 1997). Student accounts during this doctoral research also demonstrate the need for teachers and Career Advisers to facilitate the development of 'soft currencies' (Brown and Hesketh, 2004) and cultural and social capital in learners from deprived backgrounds so that they may successfully navigate further and higher education and the labour market

In relation to gender barriers, teachers and Career Advisers should work with young people across genders to challenge norms related to 'how we do gender' through critical consciousness development (Freire, 1993). This research also demonstrates the need for teachers and Career Advisers to provide increased opportunities for a broad range of careers exploration across genders. By way of illustration, many of the Romani Gypsy boys in this study aspired to self-employment, guidance sessions could utilise images that challenge frequently gendered professions and facilitate work placement opportunities for them with self-employed female role models in industries where women are generally under-represented therein challenging these stereotypes (Bimrose, 2008). Moreover, findings illuminate that there is further scope for including entrepreneurship education within the curriculum (Henderson and Robertson, 2000).

The findings presented here demonstrate that learners' decisions are not made in a vacuum and that the nature of school in the form of trusted and supportive teachers, teaching staff and Career Advisers and effective pedagogical practice (Freire, 1993) can operate to reinforce or mitigate the impact of multiple intersectional barriers. Colley (2003, p. 95) contends that sharing students' 'collective social location' may mitigate the potential for 'self-blame when the labour market is not easy to enter' due to structural barriers. In order to facilitate a student-centred approach and offer young people a diversity of experiences, communities of interaction (Law, 1981) should be established with an emphasis on pan-sectoral support. From this perspective, local schools, further education colleges, higher education institutions, NGO's and

employers should commit to equitable participation, especially where parents have limited economic and cultural capital.

The data has demonstrated that holistic guidance from a range of significant others can make a tangible difference in students' lives, encouraging their continued engagement in education and nurturing their future aspirations. The findings suggest that students should have increased opportunities to access a programme of sustained blended group and personal guidance meetings (Bryan et al., 2010; McDonough and Calderone, 2006) from their first year of secondary school (Archer et al., 2014b; Hughes, & Kashefpakdel, 2019). Such a programme should also ensure that parents, learners, teachers and Career Advisers work together to facilitate their educational and career development (McDonough and Calderone, 2006).

Findings evidenced that a learner's habitus (i.e. first generation, female, working class, ethnic minority community member) influences their perceptions of what is possible (Hodkinson and Sparkes, 1997; Redmond, 2006). To this end, career education and guidance programmes should also be built with and from the perspective of students (Hodkinson, 2008; Freire, 1993; Thomsen et al., 2013), recognising the intersectional and structural barriers that will influence learners' social mobility. Failing to do so runs the risk of creating well-meaning programmes that inadvertently have a negative and alienating impact on students due to being insufficiently connected to their lived experience.

Limitations

Although the methodological approach adopted within the current doctoral research has yielded great utility in exploring, understanding and foregrounding student aspirations and experiences, it is important to observe the limitations of the research. The relatively small sample size of Roma, Romani Gypsy, Scottish Traveller, Irish Traveller and Showmen young people recruited (N = 36) for the current research, limits the generalisability of the findings (Vasileiou et al., 2018). Similarly, while parental narratives may not be generalisable due to the small sample size (N = 4) and class differentials between participants, they nonetheless demonstrated overwhelming support for their children's educational and career aspirations, thereby challenging assumptions about Roma, Gypsy and Traveller parental involvement as deficient in comparison to majority populations. A further limitation of this study is that the young adults (N = 4) who participated in this research have strong activist links and their experiences may not be reflective of the wider community and may have impacted on findings. To this end, it is

important to acknowledge that there may be many other experiences of Roma, Gypsy and Traveller parents and young people that may not be captured here. The heterogeneous sample of Roma, Gypsy and Traveller community members involved in the research cross-nationally may, however, serve to mitigate the identified weaknesses. The diverse and cross-national sample broadened our current understanding of community members' various needs in order to develop appropriate interventions and for the effective targeting of resources. Moreover, based on my deep immersion and engagement with Roma, Gypsy and Traveller community groups more broadly, during conferences, events and telephone calls, the narratives espoused in the current research are echoed by those beyond the boundaries of this study.

Recommendations for future research

Due to the lacuna of scholarly research on Roma, Gypsy and Traveller communities' experiences of education, career guidance and the labour market there are numerous possibilities for future research that aims to illuminate and challenge the barriers that these communities face. As this is the first study of its kind, future research has the potential to draw on and build on the current findings. Further studies exploring how young people enact their agency and the types of structural racism they contend with across services within their educational settings that impact on their well-being are necessary. Such research would provide further insights from the perspective of students on how to address barriers. In building on the current research, a longitudinal study on the students' experiences of education and career guidance in further and higher education could address a striking gap within the field. Future research could also look to develop, design and test the effectiveness of culture circle dialogic programmes designed with community members (Freire, 1993; Szira 2015; Fernandez, 2016) across the U.K. From this perspective, research could engage community members in conversations and activities intended to assist them in career development and upward social mobility. Finally, research into Roma, Gypsy and Traveller students' experiences of apprenticeships and their employment prospects would also be relevant to any such study with the aim of examining how their multiple social belongings affect their career trajectories.

Concluding Statement

The findings indicate that schools across the three nations involved in this study need to rethink how they engage with Roma, Gypsy and Traveller young people in order to identify and meet

student needs. Consistent with the broader educational literature, the evidence presented here demonstrates that where young people are supported effectively in developing their educational and career goals, they thrive (D'Arcy, 2017; Joyce, 2018). I propose that the information within this qualitative study can inform education, career education and guidance and community work practice. The recommendations outlined above will, however, require time and adequate resourcing to fully and effectively implement. There will also be a need for policy and practice to move away from a number crunching and performance outcomes approach and to a more relationship and community-centred approach. Programmes also need to level the playing field and include an equitable distribution of opportunities so that young people can 'walk through doors'. In the words of Butler (2016, p. 14), 'freedom can only be exercised if there is enough support for the exercise of freedom'.

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Appendices

APPENDIX A: Terminology

There are a number of key terms employed within this thesis that need to be clarified: ‘Roma, Gypsy and Traveller’, ‘career education’, ‘career guidance’, ‘aspirations’ and ‘career’. The descriptions stem from the literature, young people’s voices and experiences within the field.

Roma, Gypsy and Traveller identities. Roma, Gypsy and Traveller identities are often clustered homogeneously within data sets and policy (see for e.g. Scottish Government, 2018) rendering distinctions between various communities invisible (Richardson and Ryder, 2012). For example, in a House of Commons Library (2017) briefing paper the terms ‘Gypsy and Travellers’ were used to capture Roma, Romani Gypsies, Irish Travellers, Scottish Gypsies/Travellers, and Welsh Gypsies/Travellers. Whereas in a recent Scottish Government consultation the term ‘Traveller’ is used to describe Gypsy/Travellers, Roma and Showpeople (Scottish Government, 2017).

The current thesis employs the umbrella term ‘Roma, Gypsy and Travellers’ (Bhopal and Myers, 2009) except in instances where I am referring to specific community members who participated in the study (i.e. Showman³⁵ Arthur Joskin) or where the original author of a paper has used alternative terminology that does not include Roma populations. For example, Bhopal (2004) uses the term ‘Gypsy Travellers’; while Deuchar and Bhopal (2013) employ the term ‘Traveller’ to capture Fairground Traveller identities.

Career Education and Guidance. A critical issue across the career guidance literature and policy contexts is the need to define a set of terms that may be used by policy makers, researchers and practitioners. Hooley et al. (2011) observe that the terms ‘career education’, ‘career development’, ‘career learning’ and ‘career guidance’ are largely synonymous and are used interchangeably. However, there are practical differences between the activities, and they are often not synonymous. For example, the European Lifelong Guidance Policy Network (ELGPN, 2014) developed a glossary in order to facilitate dialogue and peer learning processes between countries. According to the ELGPN (2014, p. 14) the term career guidance describes a range of activities that individuals may draw on in order to ‘identify their capacities,

³⁵ Research participant Arthur Joskin identified using the self-ascribed term ‘Showman’ as opposed to ‘Showpeople’ as he felt that terminology was changed by various administrations without consulting community members.

competences and interests' across the life-span in order to make 'meaningful educational, training and occupational decisions'. The term career education refers to programmes of learning to help individuals 'develop the skills necessary to manage their career and life pathway' which includes opportunities to access career information and guidance (ELGPN, 2014, p. 14). Across England, Wales and Scotland, career education refers to programmes of career learning that are embedded within the curriculum (Sultana, 2012; Scottish Government, 2011; Careers Wales, 2017).

For the purposes of this thesis, the terminology 'career advice' and 'career guidance' will be used interchangeably to describe the range of services available to individuals in order to facilitate informed decision-making related to education, training and other opportunities relevant to their identified aspirations. The terms 'career education' and 'career learning' will be used to refer to programmes of activity linked to the curriculum and delivered primarily by teaching staff to groups of students within educational settings. The programme of activities available to learners' within educational settings can also include opportunities to access personal career guidance, employer engagement, work placements and attending open days at further and higher education institutions.

Aspirations. Within the literature, there is no single definition of aspirations (Best, 2017) and there are many interpretations of the notion of aspiration (see for e.g. Watts and Bridges, 2004; Hart, 2012). Archer et al. (2010, p. 78), define aspirations as ranging from 'intensely held goals and desires to looser, more nebulous interests; from 'high' or lofty ambitions to more prosaic mundane or realistic expectations'. While for Hart (2016, p. 326) aspirations are 'future-oriented, driven by conscious and unconscious motivations' that represent an individual's 'commitments towards a particular trajectory'. Aspirations are relationally bound (Hart, 2016) and they may vary depending on interactions, support, guidance and opportunities from teachers, Career Advisers, parents, siblings, peers and community organisations.

Drawing on Archer's (2014, p. 24) conceptualisation of aspirations being 'cultural and social products', and Hart's (2016) conceptualisation of aspirations being relationally bound the current thesis argues that young people's aspiration formation is facilitated by their historical and socially-situated experiences. Quaglia and Cobb (1996) argue that aspirations are two-dimensional, where learners have to simultaneously look to the future while working in the present to attain their goals. As will be evidenced within the subsequent chapters, however, young people often embody three-dimensional aspirations. Although participants' aspirations

are future-oriented, and while many engage in self-regulatory behaviours (Bandura et al., 1996; Porath and Bateman, 2006) in the present to achieve their goals, they also draw on their own lived pasts and their community-wide histories of oppression (Acton, 1974; Brown et al., 2013; Acton and Ryder, 2012; Hancock, 2002; James, 2014), which shape and influence their motivation, aspirations and intentions in relation to their educational and career goals. To this end, the majority of learners' aspirations are not merely individualistic but are often centred on a commitment to uplift their families and communities (Milan-Tyner, 2018).

Career. Within the literature, there is no single definition of the word career. Barnes et al. (2010, p. 11) describe the concept of career as the lifelong roles that a person plays in participating and contributing to society. Similarly, Hooley et al. (2011, p. 1) contend that 'careers are something that [individuals] build incrementally over their life'. Student conceptualisations of the term career, however, often conformed to a more rigid description put forward by Armstrong (1987, p. 9) who suggests the concept of 'career' to be a 'fixed and inevitable process', that is linear, entailing upward progression due to rationally made decisions.

APPENDIX B: Letter sent to Head Teachers

Dear xxxxxxxxxxxxxx

I am a PhD student at the University of the West of Scotland. I am seeking your consent to approach Teaching Staff working within your school about a research project I am undertaking.

Roma, Gypsy and Traveller young people face significant disadvantage across a number of indicators. Research on education attainment demonstrates that young Roma, Gypsy and Traveller people fare less well than their peers at every age and stage despite policies and interventions to bridge the attainment gap. One such intervention that has been overlooked within research literature for these marginalised communities is that of career information, advice and guidance in raising aspirations and bridging the attainment gap. To this end, there is limited research on school staff and Career Practitioners views on the role of careers information, advice and guidance in raising aspirations and reducing the attainment gap amongst young Roma, Gypsy and Traveller people.

I am interested in the views of school staff on their work in relation to career related learning and guidance with Roma, Gypsy and Traveller young people. In particular, I am interested in considering the following questions:

1. How do school staff perceive the relationship between career information, advice and guidance and Roma, Gypsy and Traveller young people in relation to: aspirations and attainment?
2. What support do teachers access to enable them to work with Roma, Gypsy and Traveller young people

I will be asking school staff to complete a questionnaire as well as carrying out interviews with a range of teaching staff (class/subject teachers; teaching assistants; head teachers; pastoral staff) who have worked with young Roma, Gypsy and Traveller people. The questionnaire will be provided through an online platform for Teaching Staff to complete at a time that is convenient for them. Interviews will also be conducted at a time and place convenient to participants. Interviews will be held on an individual basis and last a maximum of one hour.

Data will be confidential, participants and the school in which they work will remain anonymous.

I have enclosed a copy of the letter which would be sent to staff working within your school should you consent to me contacting them.

If you would like any further information or have any questions you can contact me on Nicola.Hay@uws.ac.uk, my Director of Studies, Prof. Colin Clark on Colin.Clark@uws.ac.uk or alternatively The School of Media, Culture and Society Ethics Committee If you have any questions or concerns: Dr Christopher O'Donnell (Tel: 0141 848 3798, e-mail: christopher.odonnell@uws.ac.uk).

I would be grateful if you could complete and return the attached consent slip by to Nicola.Hay@uws.ac.uk

Warm Regards

Nicola Hay (PhD Candidate)

Name of School:

I, the Head Teacher, do/do not give my consent for staff within my school to be asked if they would like to take part in the research project.

Signed:

APPENDIX C: Letter sent to Career Service Managers

Dear

I am a PhD student at the University of the West of Scotland. I am seeking your consent to approach Career Practitioners working within your office about a research project I am undertaking.

Roma, Gypsy and Traveller young people face significant disadvantage across a number of indicators. Research on education attainment demonstrates that young Roma, Gypsy and Traveller people fare less well than their peers at every age and stage despite policies and interventions to bridge the attainment gap. One such intervention that has been overlooked within research literature for these marginalised communities is that of career information, advice and guidance in raising aspirations and bridging the attainment gap. To this end, there is limited research on school staff and Career Practitioners views on the role of careers information, advice and guidance in raising aspirations and reducing the attainment gap amongst young Roma, Gypsy and Traveller people.

I am interested in the views of Career Practitioners on their work in relation to career related learning and guidance with Roma, Gypsy and Traveller young people. In particular, I am interested in considering the following questions:

1. How do practitioners perceive the relationship between career information, advice and guidance and Roma, Gypsy and Traveller young people in relation to: aspirations and attainment
2. What support do practitioners access to enable them to work with Roma, Gypsy and Traveller young people

I will be asking Career Practitioners to complete a questionnaire as well as carrying out interviews with those who have worked with young Roma, Gypsy and Traveller people. Following the interviews, the questionnaire will be provided through an online platform for Career Practitioners to complete at a time that is convenient for them. Interviews will also be conducted at a time and place convenient to participants. Interviews will be held on an individual basis and last a maximum of one hour.

Data will be confidential, participants and the school in which they work will remain anonymous.

I have enclosed a copy of the letter which would be sent to staff working within your office should you consent to me contacting them.

If you would like any further information or have any questions you can contact me on Nicola.Hay@uws.ac.uk, my Director of Studies, Prof. Colin Clark on Colin.Clark@uws.ac.uk or alternatively The School of Media, Culture and Society Ethics Committee If you have any questions or concerns: Dr Christopher O'Donnell (Tel: 0141 848 3798, e-mail: christopher.odonnell@uws.ac.uk).

I would be grateful if you could complete and return the attached consent slip by to Nicola.Hay@uws.ac.uk

Warm Regards

Nicola Hay (PhD Candidate)

Name of School:

I, _____, do/do not give my consent for staff within my office to be asked if they would like to take part in the research project.

Signed:

Dr Christopher O'Donnell,
School of Media, Culture and Society
University of West of Scotland,
Paisley Campus,
High Street,
Paisley.
PA1 2BE

APPENDIX E: Participant Information Sheet for Teaching Staff

Understanding Teaching Staff's subjective experiences of working with young Roma, Gypsy and Traveller people, career related learning and sources of support.

The study

Roma, Gypsy and Traveller (RGT) people are heterogeneous communities who share the common experience of suffering from significant disadvantage across education, employment, health, accommodation and prejudice. Education is the best way to tackle these multiple inequalities. Yet, RGT students school experiences are synonymous with absenteeism, underachievement and high drop-out rates between the ages of 13 and 14. RGT students are more likely to be excluded from school, be identified as having additional support needs and leave school without formal qualifications. Further, rapid technological advancements are drastically transforming the labour market, which RGT people have historically been excluded from. Careers education may prepare and equip young people with the skills needed to successfully negotiate this complex terrain. Research also suggests that careers education leads to positive outcomes such as promoting motivation, positive attitudes to learning, social equity and social mobility. For instance, young people broaden their aspirations for what is possible if they have had access to careers education from a young age. Few studies however, have explored young people's experiences of careers education and young RGT people were not included this research. Therefore, I will explore RGT student's perceptions and experiences of careers education in their first two years of secondary school as well as careers and teaching staff working with young people.

Who are we?

The principal researcher who will facilitate the interviews is Nicola Hay, a PhD student within the School of Media, Culture and Society at the University of the West of Scotland. The study is sponsored by a University of the West of Scotland PhD studentship.

Why have I been asked to take part?

This study aims to gain a detailed understanding of your views and opinions of your experiences of working with young Roma, Gypsy and Traveller people and the role school and career related learning in raising aspirations and reducing the attainment gap, as well as your sources of support.

What will I have to do if I take part?

We would like you to take part in an interview regarding your experience of working with young Roma, Gypsy and Traveller people, career related learning, as well as your sources of support. If you agree to participate, you will be asked to participate in one semi-structured interview which will take place in a room within your school.

The interview will last for approximately 60 minutes and you will be asked to answer a range of questions about your experiences of working with young Roma, Gypsy and Traveller people, career related learning, as well as sources of support.

The interviews will be audio-recorded, however, your name will not be included on the write-up of the focus groups or any subsequent research reports. The audio-recordings will be transferred from the audio-recording device to a password protected hard-drive, while all information sheets and transcripts will be kept in a locked drawer, within a locked room. All information collected from you will be stored, analysed and reported in compliance with the Data Protection Act (1998) and General Data Protection Regulation (2018). No personal details about yourself will be required. The data will be kept for 10 years following the completion of the study, after which it will be destroyed.

Do I have to take part?

No. Participation in this study is voluntary. We would be grateful for your help, but the choice is entirely your own. If you choose to take part in the study you can withdraw at any time up until the completion of interview. If you do withdraw prior to the completion of the interview in which you participated, your data and all other records will be destroyed.

What are the possible disadvantages of taking part?

There are no possible risks or disadvantages of taking part in this study.

What are the benefits of taking part?

The research will add to the limited literature regarding the role of career information, advice and guidance in addressing the attainment gap amongst Roma, Gypsy and Traveller young people and in order to identify best practice so as to tailor services to be more inclusive of Roma, Gypsy and Traveller young people.

Confidentiality

The data recorded is entirely confidential, although subject to normal legal requirements. Your name will not be identifiable from the interview transcripts or the audio-recordings. It is important that you do not share the experiences, views/opinions and thoughts and feelings of others who participate in the focus groups. The anonymised transcripts will be analysed by the primary researcher and one other researcher to identify important themes and to inform future research (e.g. the construction of a survey tool).

What will happen to the results of the research study?

The data from the interviews will form part of an exploratory study which will inform subsequent research on the role of career information, advice and guidance in reducing the attainment gap amongst young Roma, Gypsy and Traveller people. The data will highlight future aspects of the school environment, career information, advice and guidance provision, inclusive practice and educational outcomes which are important to young people and their parents. In addition, this data will be written up as part of a University of the West of Scotland PhD thesis, and may be presented (with names anonymised) at academic conferences or submitted to peer review journals.

What if I want to find out more or have a complaint about the research?

If you want to find out more about this research or have a complaint about this research, please contact myself (principal investigator) or the Chair of the Ethics Committee:

Principal Investigator:

Nicola Hay,
University of the West of Scotland,
High Street,
Paisley,
Renfrewshire, Scotland.

PA1 2BE,
School of Media, Culture and Society,
Division of Psychology,
E-mail: nicola.hay@uws.ac.uk

Dr Christopher O'Donnell,
Senior Lecturer in Psychology
Chair of the MCS Ethics Committee
School of Media, Culture and Society
University of West of Scotland,
Paisley Campus,
High Street,
Paisley.
PA1 2BE
Email: Christopher.ODonnell@uws.ac.uk

THANK YOU FOR YOUR HELP

APPENDIX F: Participant Information Sheet for Career Practitioners

Understanding Career Practitioners subjective experiences of working with young Roma, Gypsy and Traveller people, career information, advice and guidance as well as sources of support.

The study

Roma, Gypsy and Traveller (RGT) people are heterogeneous communities who share the common experience of suffering from significant disadvantage across education, employment, health, accommodation and prejudice. Education is the best way to tackle these multiple inequalities. Yet, RGT student's school experiences are synonymous with absenteeism, underachievement and high drop-out rates between the ages of 13 and 14. RGT students are more likely to be excluded from school, be identified as having additional support needs and leave school without formal qualifications. Further, rapid technological advancements are drastically transforming the labour market, which RGT people have historically been excluded from. Careers education may prepare and equip young people with the skills needed to successfully negotiate this complex terrain. Research also suggests that careers education leads to positive outcomes such as promoting motivation, positive attitudes to learning, social equity and social mobility. For instance, young people broaden their aspirations for what is possible if they have had access to careers education from a young age. Few studies however, have explored young people's experiences of careers education and young RGT people were not included in this research. Therefore, I will explore RGT student's perceptions and experiences of careers education in their first two years of secondary school as well as careers and teaching staff working with young people.

Who are we?

The principal researcher who will facilitate the interviews is Nicola Hay, a PhD student within the School of Media, Culture and Society at the University of the West of Scotland. The study is sponsored by a University of the West of Scotland PhD studentship.

Why have I been asked to take part?

This study aims to gain a detailed understanding of your views and opinions of your experiences of working with young Roma, Gypsy and Traveller people and the role school and career information, advice and guidance in raising aspirations and reducing the attainment gap, as well as your sources of support.

What will I have to do if I take part?

We would like you to take part in an interview regarding your experiences of working with young Roma, Gypsy and Traveller people, career information, advice and guidance, as well as your sources of support. If you agree to participate, you will be asked to participate in one semi-structured interview which will take place in a room within your school.

The interview will last for approximately 60 minutes and you will be asked to answer a range of questions about your experiences of working with young Roma, Gypsy and Traveller people, career information, advice and guidance, as well as sources of support.

The interviews will be audio-recorded, however, your name will not be included on the write-up of the focus groups or any subsequent research reports. The audio-recordings will be transferred from the audio-recording device to a password protected hard-drive, while all information sheets and transcripts will be kept in a locked drawer, within a locked room. All information collected from you will be stored, analysed and reported in compliance with the Data Protection Act (1998) and General Data Protection Regulation (2018). No personal details about yourself will be required. The data will be kept for 10 years following the completion of the study, after which it will be destroyed.

Do I have to take part?

No. Participation in this study is voluntary. We would be grateful for your help, but the choice is entirely your own. If you choose to take part in the study you can withdraw at any time up until the completion of interview. If you do withdraw prior to the completion of the interview in which you participated, your data and all other records will be destroyed.

What are the possible disadvantages of taking part?

There are no possible risks or disadvantages of taking part in this study.

What are the benefits of taking part?

The research will add to the limited literature regarding the role of career information, advice and guidance in addressing the attainment gap amongst Roma, Gypsy and Traveller young people and in order to identify best practice so as to tailor services to be more inclusive of Roma, Gypsy and Traveller young people.

Confidentiality

The data recorded is entirely confidential, although subject to normal legal requirements. Your name will not be identifiable from the interview transcripts or the audio-recordings. It is important that you do not share the experiences, views/opinions and thoughts and feelings of others who participate in the focus groups. The anonymised transcripts will be analysed by the primary researcher and one other researcher to identify important themes and to inform future research (e.g. the construction of a survey tool).

What will happen to the results of the research study?

The data from the interviews will form part of an exploratory study which will inform subsequent research on the role of career information, advice and guidance in reducing the attainment gap amongst young Roma, Gypsy and Traveller people. The data will highlight future aspects of the school environment, career information, advice and guidance provision, inclusive practice and educational outcomes which are important to young people and their parents. In addition, this data will be written up as part of a University of the West of Scotland PhD thesis, and may be presented (with names anonymised) at academic conferences or submitted to peer review journals.

What if I want to find out more or have a complaint about the research?

If you want to find out more about this research or have a complaint about this research, please contact myself (principal investigator) or the Chair of the Ethics Committee:

Principal Investigator:

Nicola Hay,
University of the West of Scotland,
High Street,
Paisley,
Renfrewshire, Scotland.

PA1 2BE,
School of Media, Culture and Society,
Division of Psychology,
E-mail: nicola.hay@uws.ac.uk

Dr Christopher O'Donnell,
Senior Lecturer in Psychology
Chair of the MCS Ethics Committee
School of Media, Culture and Society
University of West of Scotland,
Paisley Campus,
High Street,
Paisley.
PA1 2BE
Email: Christopher.ODonnell@uws.ac.uk

THANK YOU FOR YOUR HELP

APPENDIX G: Consent Form for Young People and Parents

Understanding Roma, Gypsy and Traveller young people and their parents' experiences of school, career related learning, career information, advice and guidance, sources of support and aspirations.

Name of Researcher: Nicola Hay

Please initial box

1. I confirm that I have read and understand the information sheet dated _____/2018 for the above study and have had the opportunity to ask questions.
2. I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time, without giving any reason.
3. I understand that my data from this study will be securely stored by the researchers, will not be identifiable.
4. I understand that this focus group will be recorded and subsequently transcribed.
5. I agree to take part in the above study.
6. I agree that this form that bears my name and signature.

Name of participant Date Signature

Name of Researcher Date Signature

APPENDIX H: Consent Form for Teaching Staff

Consent Form

Understanding Teaching Staff's experiences of working with young Roma, Gypsy and Traveller people, career related learning, as well as sources of support.

Name of Researcher: Nicola Hay

Please initial box

1. I confirm that I have read and understand the information sheet dated _____/2018 for the above study and have had the opportunity to ask questions.
2. I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time, without giving any reason.
3. I understand that my data from this study will be securely stored by the researchers, will not be identifiable.
4. I understand that this interview will be recorded and subsequently transcribed.
5. I agree to take part in the above study.
6. I agree that this form that bears my name and signature.

Name of participant

Date

Signature

Name of Researcher

Date

Signature

If you have any complaints, concerns or questions about this research, please feel free to contact the Chair of the School of Media, Culture and Society Ethics Committee, Dr Christopher O'Donnell (Tel: 0141 848 3798, e-mail: christopher.odonnell@uws.ac.uk).

APPENDIX I: Debriefing Sheet

The relationship between Careers Guidance and Social Mobility amongst Roma, Gypsy and Traveller young people in English and Scottish Secondary Schools.

Thank you very much for participating in this study. Little is known about how young Roma, Gypsy and Traveller young people access and experience careers education and guidance services within English and Scottish Secondary schools and the implications for policy. To date, there is a dearth of research pertaining to young Roma, Gypsy and Traveller people's experiences of accessing sources of careers education (Wilkin, 2010; Mulcahy et al., 2017). Further research is needed in order to understand how young Roma, Gypsy and Traveller people experience careers education provision, how they access services, the information available to their parents and the impact that careers education has on breaking down internalised stereotypes and on their engagement and retention within the formal education system and their future participation within the labour market.

If you have any complaints, concerns or questions about this research, please feel free to contact the Chair of the School of Media, Culture and Society Ethics Committee, Dr Christopher O'Donnell (Tel: 0141 848 3798, e-mail: christopher.odonnell@uws.ac.uk).

APPENDIX J: Semi-structured focus group schedule

Sample: RGT Young People and Parents

Thank you for offering to take part in this focus group. I would like to assure you that your participation will remain anonymous and no records of the interview will be kept with your name on it. You can choose to withdraw from the current study at any point. Your identification number is.....

Icebreaker task:

The researcher will develop an ice breaker task relevant to Roma, Gypsy and Traveller culture and history such as 'Would you rather'. For example, Show Racism the Red Card Scotland utilises the 'would you rather' ice breaker but has aligned it to football culture. The researcher will ask members of Roma, Gypsy and Traveller communities to provide insight in to the relevant questions that they would like to see within the ice-breaker task.

Focus Group Procedure:

The intention here is for the participants (young people and parents) to guide the researcher through their experiences and perceptions of the school system, career related learning, sources of information and support and aspirations.

Age:

Gender:

School Year:

How do you choose to identify?

For Parents: 1. Can you tell me how you perceive the relationship you have experienced with the school system?

For Parents: 2. What support and information do you get from the school about career related learning?

Prompts

For example: teacher and career practitioners sharing information on careers and the labour market; signposting to career websites; watched videos about careers

For Parents: 3. For Parents: How would you describe your occupation?

For Parents 4: What aspirations do you hold for your children in the future?

For Young People: 1. Can you tell me what you want to be in the future?

Prompts

For example earn lots of money; to be your own boss; to be famous; to have time for a family; to make a difference in the world; to work outdoors; to work with people rather than things; to build or work with your hands (Dewitt, Osborne, Archer, Dillon, Willis and Wong, 2013)

For Young People: 2. Can I ask why you would choose that kind of work? (open ended) (Bloom et al., 2008)

For Young People: 3. Can you tell me about your experiences at school?

For Young People: 4. What do you think you will most likely be doing in the year after you leave school? (open ended)

For Young People: 4. Can you tell me about any experiences you have had with career information, advice and guidance at school?

Prompts

For example, career websites; library; learning about different careers in subject classes; group work with your peers on thinking about careers; personal guidance interviews with a career counsellor?

For Young People: 4. What type of information did you receive? (open ended) (Haynes et al., 2013)

For Young People: 5. Can you tell me about any experiences you have had with career information, advice and guidance at home?

For Young People: 6. What discourages you when you think about your career? (open ended) (Code, Bernes, Gunn and Bardick; Magnusson and Bernes, 2002).

For Young People: 7. Who would make you feel most comfortable to approach for help with career planning? (Magnusson and Bernes, 2002).

Prompts

For example, from teachers, career counsellors, parents, siblings, friends

For Young People: 8. What help would you like to feel supported during your career planning process? (Bardick et al., 2004; Magnuson and Bernes, 2008).

For Young People: 9 Do you think having career information, advice and guidance makes you think of your future aspirations?

For Young People: 10 How do you feel about Science, Technology, Engineering and Maths?

For Young People: 11 What about careers related to those subjects?

Appendix D: Semi-Structured Interview Schedule for Teaching Staff

Thank you for offering to take part in this interview. I would like to assure you that your participation will remain anonymous and no records of the interview will be kept with your name on it. You can choose to withdraw from the current study at any point. Your identification number is.....

1. What does Career Information, Advice and Guidance mean to you? (adapted from Lam and Hui, 2010)
2. What role do you think teachers should play in career related learning? (adapted from Lam and Hui, 2010)
3. What have you been doing that you consider as a part of career related learning for students? (adapted from Lam and Hui, 2010)
4. What kinds of formal and informal training have you received about career related learning and guidance? (adapted from Lam and Hui, 2010)
5. Can I ask you to tell me about your experience of working with young people from Roma, Gypsy and Traveller communities?
6. How do you view the aspirations and attainment of young Roma, Gypsy and Traveller people that you have worked with?
7. How do you perceive the relationship between young Roma, Gypsy and Traveller people's engagement with career information, advice and guidance and their aspirations?
8. What resources do you use to support you in your work with young Roma, Gypsy and Traveller people?

Prompts

For example, colleagues, CPD training, good practice guidelines?
How could you better be supported?

9. Can you tell me about any career related learning training you have received and do you feel comfortable embedding career related learning in to your subject within the Curriculum?
10. Could you identify barriers to accessing career information, advice and guidance for Roma, Gypsy and Traveller young people?
11. How are you preparing learners for careers related to STEM?

APPENDIX K: Semi-Structured Interview Schedule for Career Advisers

Thank you for offering to take part in this interview. I would like to assure you that your participation will remain anonymous and no records of the interview will be kept with your name on it. You can choose to withdraw from the current study at any point. Your identification number is.....

1. What does Career Information, Advice and Guidance mean to you? (adapted from Lam and Hui, 2010)
2. What role do you think Career Practitioners should play in career information, advice and guidance? (adapted from Lam and Hui, 2010)
3. Can I ask you to tell me about your experience of working with young people from Roma, Gypsy and Traveller communities?
4. How do you view the aspirations and attainment of young Roma, Gypsy and Traveller people that you have worked with?
5. How do you perceive the relationship between young Roma, Gypsy and Traveller people's engagement with career information, advice and guidance and their aspirations?
6. What resources do you use to support you in your work with young Roma, Gypsy and Traveller people?

Prompts

For example, colleagues, CPD training, good practice guidelines?
How could you better be supported?

7. Can you tell me about any Equalities related training you have received?
8. Do you feel the training you have received has given you the necessary skills to confidently work with young Roma, Gypsy and Traveller young people?
9. Could you identify barriers to accessing career information, advice and guidance for Roma, Gypsy and Traveller young people?
10. Do you think self-referral to Career Information, Advice and Guidance may serve as a barrier to young people accessing services?

Prompts

For example confidence and self-esteem; mistrust of institutions.

APPENDIX L: Field Notes Excerpt School A in Wales

22 January 2019. School: [REDACTED]
89 Roma students.

Di picked me up from the train station @ 6:30 @ night to give me an initial run through of the service offer.

I was struck by how warm she was & she invited me to have dinner @ her house with her & her family → SO GRATEFUL WAS STARVING!!!

After dinner he suggested to their rooms & we went to the sitting room. She talked me through the school's provision & then ended up waking through emails until 11:36pm which was so late. As she was waking she shared me excerpts of students work & spoke so passionately about what they were achieving.

She then invited me to sleep over instead of having to make the hours journey to my hotel. At first I thought this was really weird that a complete stranger would take you into their home but she just has such a big heart. I was so tired & so glad I didn't have to write the memo into a call.

I left Di's @ 7 in the morning as she wanted to get into school early to sort through me of the charity furniture she got the night before. THIS WOMAN HAS SO MUCH ENERGY & PASSION!!

The EAC office was buzzing & Di runs an open car policy providing an area for students to chill. Not one of the students knocked - they just opened the door, sat down & made themselves comfortable.

↳ THIS ALSO OCCURRED DURING FOCUS GROUPS & ALLOWED FOR A UNEQUALLY COMFORTABLE ATMOSPHERE.

was struck by how close the students were to Di & a number of them just topped in the wheelbarrow & walked into her.

→ 1 → N = 4 → 2 Romanian Roma F
Senja, Lauran, Kasper & Seb → 1 Romanian Roma M
1 Croatian Roma M

APPENDIX M: Field Notes Excerpt School B in Wales

8th January 2019. School: [redacted]
 33 RQ/IT studies community (commute)
 TAXI DRIVER → IRON + COAL DECLINE HAVE TO WORK WITH THE ARC (commute)
 Had to get taxi in from hotel - last night was a nightmare arrived @ the train station @ West Wymath Parkway, I tried to walk from the station to my hotel @ 8:30pm only to realise I was in the middle of a motorway. Talk ages for a taxi to come, I nearly froze. Luckily had just enough battery. Everything is so far apart, I along a motorway so got a taxi in this morning too.
 Arrived @ the school for 9am, I sat in the reception for 25 minutes before the TES team came to get me.
 There were flyers for careers guidance sessions, I support from careers Wales with info for drop in sessions for students in the flyers/magazines section (Tony table!).
 TES team showed me around parts about

that they first go 10 years ago for young RQ students & they still use them

NB These cabins are separate from the under school, I away from the main building

Lynne said they got funding for the beauty room 6 years ago because that's what the girls wanted to do but they no longer have funding to keep it running + GIRLS ASPIRATIONS HAVE CHANGED!!
 a function of the times?

APPENDIX N: Young Romani Gypsy students' artwork and poetry in School B in Wales

APPENDIX O: A corner of Mrs H's classroom filled with furniture and charity goods for those in need

APPENDIX P: Field notes excerpt from focus group interview with Romani Gypsy boys in school B in Wales

FG 2: → N=4 RG Males

check with Colin I can use this term? pejorative?

Pikey Bradley Gypsy Tony McAllen Big man Wayne

↳ The boys were accompanied by a male chaplain who sat in on the FG

I got young people to choose their super hero pseudonyms & noticed that the boys in this group tried to 'one up' each other on the masculine names except McAllen.

I inadvertently used the term 'gadjis' & the boys asked me what it meant & I said 'flatties' / mainstream ppl.

↳ I let the boys correct me!
RIGHT TERM

Used this term throughout FG to refer to non-Romani Gypsies. → CORJAS

with Big Man / Smooth Move

↳ SUPER MACHO VIBES !!

COMMON THEME !!

There was a heavy focus on gender roles & what it takes to be a 'MAN'.

I worried for the boys - isn't it a lot of pressure that they believe from such a young age that they need to be the macho breadwinner? When I asked them about it and expressed EQUALITY it seemed the idea of dual male archetypes was at the heart of their frame of reference.

↳ Boys just shrugged!!

MENTAL HEALTH IMPLICATIONS.

APPENDIX Q: Table 2. Brief Profile of Interviewed Participants

Participant	Ethnic Identity	Gender	Age	Grade	Country
Cat Woman	Romani Gypsy	F	13	Year 8	Wales
Super Woman	Romani Gypsy	F	13	Year 8	Wales
Poison Ivy	Romani Gypsy	F	13	Year 8	Wales
Gypsy Tony	Romani Gypsy	M	13	Year 9	Wales
Pikey Bradley	Romani Gypsy	M	14	Year 10	Wales
Big Man Wayne	Romani Gypsy	M	12	Year 8	Wales
MC Allen	Romani Gypsy	M	12	Year 8	Wales
EE	Romani Gypsy	M	13	Year 9	Wales
Smooth Move	Irish Traveller	M	12	Year 8	Wales
Big Man	Irish Traveller	M	14	Year 10	Wales
Ana	Roma	F	14	Year 10	England
Ariana	Roma	F	13	Year 9	England
Nicki Minaj	Roma	F	16	Year 11	England
James	Roma	M	14	Year 9	England
Lauren	Romanian Roma	F	16	Year 11	Wales
Sonja	Romanian Roma	F	16	Year 11	Wales
Seb	Croatian Roma	M	17	Year 12	Wales
Kooper	Romanian Roma	M	16	Year 11	Wales
Mrs H	Slovakian Roma	M	13	Year 8	Wales
Katalina	Romanian Roma	F	14	Year 9	Wales

Ronaldo	Romanian Roma	M	11	Year 7	Wales
Magic woman	Italian Roma	F	13	2 nd year	Scotland
Super cat	Romanian Roma	F	12	2 nd year	Scotland
Lenka	Romanian Roma	F	12	2 nd year	Scotland
Magic Cat	Romanian Roma	F	12	2 nd year	Scotland
Participant 1	Roma	F	12	2 nd year	Scotland
Participant 2	Roma	F	12	2 nd year	Scotland
Spanja	Romanian Roma	F	13	2 nd year	Scotland
Alyssia	Romanian Roma	F	15	3 rd year	Scotland
Participant	Romanian Roma	F	15	4 th year	Scotland
London	Romanian Roma	F	15	3 rd year	Scotland
Messi	Romanian Roma	M	13	2 nd year	Scotland
Bernadette	Scottish Traveller	F	23	Final year of further education	Scotland
Shera	Scottish Traveller	F	27	No qualifications	Scotland
Kasey	Irish Traveller	F	26	Honours degree	England
Arthur Joskin	Showman ³⁶	M	27	Honours Degree and postgraduate	England

				diploma in Counselling and Psychotherapy	
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APPENDIX R: Table 3. Profile of Stakeholders and Parents

Research Participant	Role	Country	Interview type
Wonder woman	Teacher	Wales	Semi-structured interview
Sheila	Teacher	Wales	Semi-structured interview
Lisa	Teacher	Wales	Semi-structured interview
Zoe	Career Adviser	England	Focus Group
Emi	Roma support teaching staff	England	Focus Group
Marianna	Roma Mother	England	Semi structured interview with translator present
James	Romani Gypsy Father	England	Semi-Structured interview
Mihael	Roma Father	Scotland	Semi-structured interview
Remus	Roma Father	England	Semi structured interview

Terrence	SDS Career Adviser	Scotland	Semi-structured interview
Alison	Teacher	Scotland	Semi structured interview
Anna	SDS Career Adviser	Scotland	Semi structured interview
Chris	Fife Migrants Forum	Scotland	Focus Group
Billy	Fife Migrants Forum	Scotland	Focus Group
Suzanna	Case worker	Scotland	Focus Group
Vicky	Education department EAL support	Scotland	Focus Group
Clinton	SDS Career Practitioner	Scotland	Focus Group
Gary	Manager Fife Migrants forum	Scotland	Focus Group
Sylvia	Volunteer	Scotland	Focus Group
Michaela	Volunteer	Scotland	Focus Group
Mrs H	Teacher	Wales	Focus Group and Semi-structured interview
Sarah	SDS Scotland	Scotland	Semi-structured interview

Charlotte	Teacher	Scotland	Semi-structured interview
Falon	SDS Career Adviser	Scotland	Semi-structured interview

APPENDIX S: Example of analysis coding into themes and subthemes

Q1: so I want to ask about your careers and your future aspirations what are your dreams

Poison Ivy

when I am older I really wanna be a lawyer I have done for the last three to four years but I don't just want to be one of those people who say they wanna do something I actually wanna carry all the way through with it [redacted] is setting a meeting up for me I am gonna shadow a lady a lawyer but that's always something I've wanted to do cause for Gypsy's you don't really see them with the law (laughs nervously) and things cause usually they're on the wrong side of the law because I was really really interested in the murder investigations on tv but Gypsy's are always meant to be on that side of the law and then the police are meant to be on this side I really wanna change that and I wanna make it balanced so we can't be judged by what people have done in the past we wanna move on from that stereotype

Superwoman

I would like to work with disability children I think I would like it

Nicola

I used to work with young people with ASL

Superwoman

Is it hard to work with them

Nicola

It's hard because you want them to have the same opportunities but also very rewarding they are very loving and people don't always treat them so good

Catwoman

I wanna work with little children

Q2. have you spoken to your parents about careers

Catwomen

yeah

Poison Ivy

Yeah my dad and my mum they are really really supportive because they want me to go through with it cause they don't want me to be like my sisters get married young well my sisters not young for us she's twenty but that's not young for us she went all the way from school she went to college she didn't go to uni but she got married my dad really really wants me to follow through with it cause I have wanted to do it from such a young age

Nicola

and you were saying [redacted] was helping you to do a placement so you are speaking to the school about what you wanna do when you are older

Handwritten notes and codes:

- ASPIRATIONS → career
- LONGEVITY?
- SUPPORT
- @school
- PLANNING
- steps
- CHALLENGING
- PERCEPTIONS
- TV AS AN INFLUENCE
- CHALLENGING REASON → resistance?
- BARRIERS
- nurturing
- helping
- internalised racism
- Societal perspectives
- See Himan/Wang 'people like us'
- PLANNING → information gathering
- someone who has experience
- ASPIRATIONS → career
- helping
- ASPIRATIONS → career
- helping
- SUPPORT → @parental support
- BARRIERS → gender
- marriage?
- SUPPORT
- SUPPORT → parents listen to their children's aspirations
- @ father
- Perceptions of age → young vs old came up in the interview with Bernadette → explore further → very interesting!